

CARMEN: Center for Automated Vehicle Research with Multimodal Assured Navigation

A USDOT Tier-1 University Transportation Center

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Analysis and Simulation of PNT Threats and Risks to HATS

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Highly automated vehicles (HAV), whether ground, aerial, or maritime, rely on a steady stream of signals and information from external sources: signals that localize the vehicle and provide information about the road network, other nearby vehicles, larger-scale traffic, and state of the infrastructure and the environment. Currently, many deployed systems either trust the information implicitly, or at best perform basic sanity and consistency checks leading to little more than enabling or disabling the entire system. This includes a heavy reliance on PNT as location and timing information is central to many HAV operations. The potential impacts of radio frequency (RF) jamming and spoofing, interference with PNT sensor data, or interference with PNT augmentation or correction communications, on HAV functions are not thoroughly investigated, but they could wreak havoc in HAVs or result in passenger fatalities.

In this project, thorough risk identification, threat assessment, and risk analysis studies will be conducted at the component, subsystem, and system level to understand the impact of interference on HAVs using risk and failure analysis methodologies and modeling and simulation tools. Approaches such as Attack Trees and Failure Modes and Effects Analysis are utilized for qualitative analysis of different PNT threats for HAV operations. The safety and functional impacts of intentional and unintentional PNT issues are explored. The quantification of threats and risks is accomplished by integrating the simulation models of PNT features with HAV functionalities through modeling and simulation. These functionalities include maneuvers limited to individual or multiple HAVs where V2X may play an important role. Academically available simulation tools were used to evaluate the PNT concerns in HAV operation.

Several PNT threat scenarios were selected for initial analysis: (i) GNSS sensor spoofing, (ii) multi-sensor fusion, (iii) sensor based obstacle localization, and (iv) faulty PNT information from other connected HAVs. We have studied these scenarios, performing a risk and threat analysis to HAV functions for each threat, including simulation results and analysis of the level of risk and the effectiveness of identified HAV mitigation strategies.

We also selected several HAV operational scenarios for initial analysis: (i) passing behavior on rural highways; (ii) intersection safety; and (iii) multi unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) takeoff, formation flying, and landing. We have outlined the identified PNT threats, risk methodology and threat assessment, and simulation analysis and results of the level of risk and the effectiveness of identified HAV mitigation strategies.

After a literature review conducted in another project, additional threat scenarios were identified and studied, including spoofing of other HAV sensor modalities such as radar, image processing. Several additional operational scenarios were also identified and studied, including lane lateral position detection and lane keeping control, data spoofing in infrastructure and traffic con-

trol, pedestrian and vulnerable road user sensing, and intersection behavior planning, safety, and cooperative navigation.

Finally, we also initiated studies of potential cyber attacks and cybersecurity issues in HAV systems involving PNT components, including a novel potential approach to improving authentication and localization of cooperative information sources and the security and potential vulnerability of multi-sensor fusion models to parameter extraction and reverse engineering.

This report details each of these activities, describing the specific problem addressed, providing a survey of relevant literature and current best practices, exploring the proposed solution and its implementation, and presenting the results and outcomes of each study. We have organized these studies into six groups:

- Specific On-Vehicle Sensor Threat Analysis
- Sensor Threat Mitigation
- Multisensor Fusion Threat Analysis
- Scenario and Cooperative Systems Threat Analysis and Mitigation
- Infrastructure Sensing Threat Analysis
- Cybersecurity

This chapter will provide an introduction and overview of each of the specific problems explored in this project, and future chapters will individually describe each activity in detail.

1.1 Specific On-Vehicle Sensor Threat Analysis

1.1.1 Chapter 2: Threat Analysis of Position, Navigation, and Timing for Highly Automated Vehicles

This chapter focuses on threat and vulnerability analysis for position, navigation, and timing (PNT) sensors and modules, and the subsystems that rely on this information, in a highly automated vehicles including connected vehicle operations. We present the attack trees of the sensors used in automotive industries to calculate PNT solutions. It also presents systems Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) to see the hazards related to the attack on the sensor, its effect on the subsystems, and the PNT solutions outcome. Threats and vulnerabilities are further validated by the design and test of the cooperative navigation algorithm and their quantitative results in a later chapter of this report.

A literature survey was conducted to generate the relationship between the sensors and the subsystems. Further analyses were done to develop the link between vulnerabilities and threats associated with sensors. Attack Trees analyzing the risks of threats and vulnerabilities of cooperative automated driving systems, which define the sensors' vulnerabilities that lead to threats, were developed based on the literature review. FMEA analysis of HAVs establish the link between sensors with the subsystem. Since errors generated in each subsystem will lead to errors in PNT solutions, we also study the link between the affected PNT solution with threats associated with the faulty solution.

This activity was originally reported in [1].

1.1.2 Chapter 3: Signal Identification and Entrainment for Practical FMCW Radar Spoofing Attacks

This chapter proposes a method of passively estimating the parameters of frequency-modulated-continuous-wave (FMCW) radar signals with a wide range of structural parameter values and analyzes how a malicious actor could employ such estimates to track and spoof a target radar. When radars are implemented to support automated driver assistance systems, an intelligent spoofer has the potential to substantially disrupt safe navigation by inducing its target to perceive false objects. Such a spoofer must acquire highly accurate estimates of the target radar’s chirp sweep, timing, and frequency parameters while additionally tracking and compensating for time and Doppler shifts due to clock errors and relative movement. This is a difficult task for millimeter-wave radars due to severe Doppler shifts and fast sweep rates, especially when the spoofer uses off-the-shelf FMCW equipment. Algorithms and techniques for acquiring and tracking an FMCW radar are proposed and verified through simulation, which will help guide future decisions on appropriate radar spoofing countermeasures.

This activity was originally reported in [2].

1.1.3 Chapter 4: Fooling Perception via Location: A Case of Region-of-Interest Attacks on Traffic Light Detection in Autonomous Driving

The perception module is the key to the security of Autonomous Driving systems. It perceives the environment through sensors to help make safe and correct driving decisions on the road. The localization module is usually considered to be independent of the perception module. However, we discover that the correctness of perception output highly depends on localization due to the widely used Region-of-Interest design adopted in perception. Leveraging this insight, we propose an ROI attack and perform a case study in the traffic light detection in Autonomous Driving systems. We evaluate the ROI attack on a production-grade Autonomous Driving system, named Baidu Apollo, under end-to-end simulation environments. We found our attack is able to make the victim a red light runner or cause denial-of-service with a 100% success rate.

This activity was originally reported in [3].

1.2 Sensor Threat Mitigation

1.2.1 Chapter 5: Calibrating the Extrinsic and Intrinsic Parameters of the Inertial and Radar Sensors of a Vehicular Perception System

This chapter documents techniques developed for calibrating inertial sensors and radar units in a ground vehicle sensor suite. Together with the estimate of the center of rotation of a ground vehicle, this calibration enables long-term navigation in GNSS-denied conditions based solely on radar and inertial sensors. We demonstrate as much in real-world tests with a ground vehicle experiencing various levels of GNSS denial in downtown Austin, TX. It is shown that when operating with an industrial-grade MEMS IMU, the proposed system maintains 95th-percentile horizontal position errors below 6 m after 60 s and below 15 m after 300 s of GNSS outages.

This activity was originally reported in [4].

1.2.2 Chapter 6: Low-Cost Inertial Aiding for Deep-Urban Tightly-Coupled Multi-Antenna Precise GNSS

A vehicular position and attitude estimation technique is presented that tightly couples multi-antenna carrier-phase differential GNSS (CDGNSS) with a low-cost MEMS inertial sensor and vehicle dynamics constraints. This chapter describes our effort that is the first to explore the use of consumer-grade inertial sensors for tightly-coupled urban CDGNSS, and first to explore the tightly-coupled combination of multi-antenna CDGNSS and inertial sensing (of any quality) for urban navigation. The multi-antenna CDGNSS measurement update is linearized via an unscented transform, allowing all baselines' integer ambiguities to be resolved using traditional integer least squares while both implicitly enforcing known-baseline-length constraints and optimally exploiting the correlations inherent to the multi-baseline problem. State propagation is driven by inertial measurements, with vehicle dynamics constraints applied as pseudo-measurements. A novel false fix detection and recovery technique is developed to mitigate the effect of conditioning the filter state on incorrect integer fixes. When evaluated on the publicly-available TEX-CUP urban positioning dataset, the proposed technique achieves, with consumer- and industrial-grade inertial sensors, respectively, a 96.6% and 97.5% integer fix availability, and 12.0 cm and 10.1 cm overall (fix and float) 95th percentile horizontal positioning error over more than 2 hours of driving in the urban core of Austin, Texas.

This activity was originally reported in [5].

1.2.3 Chapter 7: End-to-end Analysis and Uncertainty-based Mitigation of Adversarial Attacks to Automated Lane Centering Systems

In the development of advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) and autonomous vehicles, machine learning techniques that are based on deep neural networks (DNNs) have been widely used for vehicle perception. These techniques offer significant improvement on average perception accuracy over traditional methods, however they have been shown to be susceptible to adversarial attacks, where small perturbations in the input may cause significant errors in the perception results and lead to system failure. Most prior works addressing such adversarial attacks focus only on the sensing and perception modules. In this chapter, we propose an end-to-end approach that addresses the impact of adversarial attacks throughout the perception, planning, and control modules. In particular, we choose a target ADAS application, the automated lane centering system in OpenPilot, quantify the perception uncertainty under adversarial attacks, and design a robust planning and control module accordingly based on the uncertainty analysis. We evaluate our proposed approach using both a public dataset and production-grade autonomous driving simulator. The experiment results demonstrate that our approach can effectively mitigate the impact of adversarial attack and can achieve 55% ~ 90% improvement over the original OpenPilot.

This activity was originally reported in [6, 7].

1.3 Multisensor Fusion Threat Analysis

1.3.1 Chapter 8: Drift with Devil: Security of Multi-Sensor Fusion based Localization in High-Level Autonomous Driving under GPS Spoofing

For high-level Autonomous Vehicles (AV), localization is highly security and safety critical. One direct threat to it is GPS spoofing, but fortunately, AV systems today predominantly use Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) algorithms that are generally believed to have the potential to practically

defeat GPS spoofing. However, no prior work has studied whether today’s MSF algorithms are indeed sufficiently secure under GPS spoofing, especially in AV settings. In this chapter, we perform the first study to fill this critical gap. As the first study, we focus on a production-grade MSF with both design and implementation level representativeness, and identify two AV-specific attack goals, off-road and wrong-way attacks.

To systematically understand the security property, we first analyze the upper-bound attack effectiveness, and discover a take-over effect that can fundamentally defeat the MSF design principle. We perform a cause analysis and find that such vulnerability only appears dynamically and non-deterministically. Leveraging this insight, we design FusionRipper, a novel and general attack that opportunistically captures and exploits take-over vulnerabilities. We evaluate it on 6 real-world sensor traces, and find that FusionRipper can achieve at least 97% and 91.3% success rates in all traces for off-road and wrong-way attacks respectively. We also find that it is highly robust to practical factors such as spoofing inaccuracies. To improve the practicality, we further design an offline method that can effectively identify attack parameters with over 80% average success rates for both attack goals, with the cost of at most half a day. We also discuss promising defense directions.

This activity was originally reported in [8].

1.3.2 Chapter 9: Anomaly Detection Against GPS Spoofing Attacks on Connected and Autonomous Vehicles Using Learning from Demonstration

GPS spoofing attacks pose great challenges to connected vehicle (CVs) safety applications and localization of autonomous vehicles (AVs). In this chapter, we propose to utilize transportation and vehicle engineering domain knowledge to detect GPS spoofing attacks towards CVs and AVs. A novel detection method using learning from demonstration is developed, which can be implemented in both vehicles and at the transportation infrastructure. A computational-efficient driving model, which can be learned from historical trajectories of the vehicles, is constructed to predict normal driving behaviors. Then a statistical method is developed to measure the dissimilarities between the observed trajectory and the predicted normal trajectory for anomaly detection. We validate the proposed method using two threat models (i.e., attacks targeting the multi-sensor fusion system of AVs and attacks targeting the intersection movement assist application of CVs) on two real-world datasets (i.e., KAIST and Michigan roundabout dataset). Results show that the proposed model is able to detect almost all of the attacks in time with low false positive and false negative rates.

This activity was originally reported in [9].

1.4 Scenario and Cooperative Systems Threat Analysis and Mitigation

1.4.1 Chapter 10: Methodology for Hazard Identification and Mitigation Strategies Applied to an Overtaking Assistant ADAS

In this chapter we propose a methodology for analyzing the hazards and potential mitigation of faults and failures in an Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS) which is applicable to individual systems and subsystems of a larger automated vehicle implementation. To illustrate the methodology, we outline the structure of a notional overtaking assistant. An overtaking assistant for automated vehicles is considered a type of Advanced Driver Assistant System (ADAS) that assists a partially or fully automated vehicle with an overtaking maneuver consisting of acceleration and steering control during a double lane change. Crash data indicates that although only 19% of

the US population inhabits rural zones, 54% of the vehicular crashes happen on rural roads, with a high number of those events occurring during an overtaking maneuver on two-lane rural roads. While such an overtaking assistant would help to minimize these collision events, no commercial product is yet available due in part to the challenge of defining what constitutes *safe* navigation in these systems.

The structure of the overtaking assistant system includes not only internal sensors such as global navigation satellite system (GNSS) receivers, map data, and other motion and localization sensors and external sensors such as radars, lidars, and vision systems but also access to cooperative positioning information through a wireless connected vehicular network in order to identify the location of oncoming traffic.

We perform the hazard analysis of this subsystem utilizing a combination of methods. For the vehicle level hazard analysis we use Hazard Operability Study (HAZOP) and the first step of System Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA), and for the overall safety analysis we use Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) and the second step of STPA. The analysis performed on the system is presented and is proposed for use as a general methodology to analyze hazards in any ADAS system or subsystem. The summary of the analysis results provided here include a list of hazards and mitigation strategies for the proposed two-lane rural road scenario.

This activity was originally reported in [10].

1.4.2 Chapter 11: On the Validation of Adversarial Threats to Cooperative Unmanned Aerial Systems for Search and Rescue Missions

This chapter studies the effects of adversarial threats on the localization stack of cooperative Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) that perform cooperative search and rescue missions (CooSAR). We propose a methodology for incorporating different types of attacks in the localization stack of the UAS to spoof the sensors and actuators of the vehicles with two goals: fail the mission (not locate the target) and fly off path. For this purpose, we resort to a progressive-spiral-in (PSI) search path with theoretical success guarantees to cover the search area in finite time given at least a certain minimum number of aerial vehicles. Then, we formulate a control strategy for each UAS and implement two types of spoofing attacks: i) attack to the sensors and actuators, and ii) attack to the residuals of the GNSS localization measurements. We evaluate the effects of the attacks by measuring the decrease in effectiveness in finding the target and the reduction in area coverage when the UAS are subject to the attack. The attack is applied to one UAS at a time (the one closest to the target), and we find that even with this simple approach, the probability of finding the target is greatly reduced up to 36%.

This activity was originally reported in [11].

1.4.3 Chapter 12: Cooperative Navigation Strategy for Connected Autonomous Vehicle Operating at Smart Intersection

This chapter focuses on the cooperative navigation strategy for connected autonomous vehicles operating at smart intersections. The goal of this work is a cooperative navigation system to achieve cooperative collision avoidance for enhancing the safety and capacity of the intersection. This work considers cooperative connected autonomous vehicles operating simultaneously with non-cooperative autonomous vehicles, and uses beyond-visual range scenarios to reduce vulnerable situations. The safety of Vulnerable road users and the framework of Cooperative navigation is accomplished by using the data from the Road-Side Units (RSU) and On-board Units (OBU). Signalized intersection scenario uses information from the RSU, OBU, Autonomous Intersection

Management (AIM) system, and Smart Traffic Lights (STL). Jamming of infrastructure devices and interference into the OBU is enforced to evaluate the cooperative navigation framework in vulnerable situations occurring at the intersection. Threats and vulnerabilities are identified and validated by the design and test of the cooperative navigation algorithm and their quantitative results. Multiple threat scenarios were simulated and results of separation between ego vehicle and actor vehicles were presented, showing the separation time within the set upper and lower bounds. That ensures that the ego vehicle does not collide with others at the intersection. Safety results are also used to generate the Threat Assessment and Risk Analysis (TARA) matrix for quantities analysis.

The cooperative collision avoidance algorithm guides the ego vehicle as soon as the ego vehicle comes in the range of the intersection service area, which increases the safety and capacity of the intersection. This strategy is comfortably used for both an unsignalized and signalized intersection. In an unsignalized intersection scenario, the ego vehicle uses an onboard unit. In signalized intersection scenario, the ego vehicle uses a roadside unit, onboard unit, autonomous intersection management system, and smart traffic lights. The proposed framework is the near-future requirement where the connected autonomous vehicle utilizes the information from smart infrastructure devices.

This activity was originally reported in [12].

1.4.4 Chapter 13: Ensuring the Safety of Highly Automated Vehicles through Cooperative Navigation Methodology

The work described in this chapter quantifies the development of a methodological framework and scenario generation for the safety testing and validation of Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) by using cooperative navigation at smart intersections. The focus of the work is to enhance the safety of the intersection. The purposed methodology allows HAVs to safely navigate through intersections while operating with non-cooperative vehicles. One of the main challenges in this context is that city intersections are often complex environments where onboard sensors may not be able to detect all relevant information, such as vehicles or pedestrians behind obstructions. To address this issue, the proposed approach uses beyond-visual range information from vehicles that are transmitted via an everything communication network. This allows HAVs to perceive their surroundings and make safer navigation decisions.

The cooperative navigation of HAVs is achieved through the use of data from various sources, including Roadside Units (RSU), Onboard units (OBU), Autonomous Intersection Management (AIM) systems, and Smart Traffic Lights (STL). The proposed framework includes several key features, including cooperative collision avoidance (CCA), cooperative cruise control (CCC), and cooperative adaptive lane-keeping (CALK). In addition, HAVs can follow predefined paths using model predictive control. In the proposed framework each vehicle is an independent agent, makes its own decision based on the information available from the vehicle to the everything communication network, and uses a mathematical model to predict future behavior for optimized navigation solutions. To test the performance of the cooperative navigation framework, the authors have generated a scenario in which HAVs operate at a smart intersection. Results show that safety is ensured in a dynamic scenario. Hence the new proposed work is contributing to enhancing the safety of the intersection and development of a new methodological framework.

This activity was originally reported in [13].

1.4.5 Chapter 14: Entropy Based Metric to Assess the Accuracy of PNT Information

Entropy measures uncertainty present within the data. Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) can navigate safely and efficiently if location information of occluded dynamic objects is available. It is assumed that dynamic objects have GPS receivers, and location information can be acquired through a fast communication link. However, GPS info can be easily modified or suffers from high error because the transmission link is not secure or due to Non Line of Sight (NLOS) between transmitter and receiver. To solve this problem, an entropy metric is introduced to ascertain the value of the supplied information and reject information with a high amount of error present within the data. This chapter focuses on pedestrians as dynamic objects and uses Finite State Machine (FSM) based hierarchical control to navigate HAVs. It is shown that the entropy metric can improve the efficiency of the control of HAVs.

This activity was originally reported in [14].

1.5 Infrastructure Sensing Threat Analysis

1.5.1 Chapter 15: Infrastructure-Aided Defense for Autonomous Driving Systems: Opportunities and Challenges

With the growing interest and investment in leveraging intelligent infrastructure support for practical AD, AD system may have new opportunities to defend against existing AD attacks. In this chapter, we are the first to systematically explore such a new AD security design space leveraging emerging infrastructure-side support, which we call Infrastructure-Aided Autonomos Driving Defense (I-A2D2). We first taxonomize existing AD attacks based on infrastructure-side capabilities, and then analyze potential I-A2D2 design opportunities and requirements. We further discuss the potential design challenges for these I-A2D2 design directions to be effective in practice.

This activity was originally reported in [15].

1.5.2 Chapter 16: Detecting Data Spoofing in Connected Vehicle based Intelligent Traffic Signal Control using Infrastructure-Side Sensors and Traffic Invariants

Connected Vehicle (CV) technologies are under rapid deployment across the globe and will soon reshape our transportation systems, bringing benefits to mobility, safety, environment, etc. Meanwhile, such technologies also attract attention from cyberattacks. Recent work shows that CV-based Intelligent Traffic Signal Control Systems are vulnerable to data spoofing attacks, which can cause severe congestion effects in intersections. In this chapter, we explore a general detection strategy for infrastructure-side CV applications by estimating the trustworthiness of CVs based on readily-available infrastructure-side sensors. We implement our detector for the CV-based traffic signal control and evaluate it against two representative congestion attacks. Our evaluation in the industrial-grade traffic simulator shows that the detector can detect attacks with at least 95% true positive rates while keeping false positive rate below 7% and is robust to sensor noises.

This activity was originally reported in [16].

1.5.3 Chapter 17: Risk Analysis for Vehicle-Pedestrian Interaction with Extended Sensing

In this chapter, we introduce the concept of Extended Sensing (ES) and provide a comparison tool that evaluates the risk for vehicle-pedestrian interaction (VPI) scenarios by performing statistical analysis of the number of hazardous situations encountered when there is occlusion (without communication) versus using a sensing technology that informs the vehicle of the presence of a potentially occluded pedestrian.

The Extended Sensor can be a camera on a pole or a pedestrian self sending a warning signal. We propose a collision-avoidance planner for the vehicle based on a finite state machine (FSM). The risk analysis is performed using the Backtracking Process Algorithm (BPA), which has been used in previous works, as a way to provide sufficient coverage of the Operational Design Domain (ODD). Qualitative and quantitative simulation results show the benefits of having ES (in this case, an external pedestrian alert system) to decrease the possibility of collision. The proposed method also proves to be useful to evaluate the risk for VPI scenarios in general.

This activity was originally reported in [17].

1.6 Cybersecurity

1.6.1 Chapter 18: Vision-Based Two-Factor Authentication & Localization Scheme for Autonomous Vehicles

In autonomous vehicle systems – whether ground or aerial – vehicles and infrastructure-level units communicate among each other continually to ensure safe and efficient autonomous operations. However, different attack scenarios might arise in such environments when a device in the network cannot physically pinpoint the actual transmitter of a certain message. For example, a compromised or a malicious vehicle could send a message with a fabricated location to appear as if it is in the location of another legitimate vehicle, or fabricate multiple messages with fake identities to alter the behavior of other vehicles/infrastructure units and cause traffic congestion or accidents.

In this chapter, we propose a Vision-Based Two-Factor Authentication and Localization Scheme for Autonomous Vehicles. The scheme leverages the vehicles’ light sources and cameras to establish an “Optical Camera Communication (OCC)” channel providing an auxiliary channel between vehicles to visually authenticate and localize the transmitter of messages that are sent over Radio Frequency (RF) channels. Additionally, we identify possible attacks against the proposed scheme as well as mitigation strategies.

This activity was originally reported in [18].

1.6.2 Chapter 19: Play the Imitation Game: Model Extraction Attack against Autonomous Driving Localization

The security of the Autonomous Driving (AD) system has been gaining researchers’ and public’s attention recently. Given that AD companies have invested a huge amount of resources in developing their AD models, e.g., localization models, these models, especially their parameters, are important intellectual property and deserve strong protection.

In this chapter, we examine whether the confidentiality of production-grade Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) models, in particular, Error-State Kalman Filter (ESKF), can be stolen from an outside adversary. We propose a new model extraction attack called TASKMASTER that can infer the secret ESKF parameters under black-box assumption. In essence, TASKMASTER trains a substitutional

ESKF model to recover the parameters, by observing the input and output to the targeted AD system. To precisely recover the parameters, we combine a set of techniques, like gradient-based optimization, search-space reduction and multi-stage optimization. The evaluation result on real-world vehicle sensor dataset shows that TASKMASTER is practical. For example, with 25 seconds AD sensor data for training, the substitutional ESKF model reaches centimeter-level accuracy, comparing with the ground-truth model. The evaluation shows that TASKMASTER can recover the ESKF with high fidelity. The error rate of the recovered parameters can be below 1%.

This activity was originally reported in [19].

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Chapter 2

Threat Analysis of Position, Navigation, and Timing for Highly Automated Vehicles

This chapter focuses on threat and vulnerability analysis for position, navigation, and timing (PNT) sensors and modules, and the subsystems that rely on this information, in a highly automated vehicles including connected vehicle operations. We present the attack trees of the sensors used in automotive industries to calculate PNT solutions. It also presents systems Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) to see the hazards related to the attack on the sensor, its effect on the subsystems, and the PNT solutions outcome. Threats and vulnerabilities are further validated by the design and test of the cooperative navigation algorithm and their quantitative results in a later chapter of this report.

A literature survey was conducted to generate the relationship between the sensors and the subsystems. Further analyses were done to develop the link between vulnerabilities and threats associated with sensors. Attack Trees analyzing the risks of threats and vulnerabilities of cooperative automated driving systems, which define the sensors' vulnerabilities that lead to threats, were developed based on the literature review. FMEA analysis of HAVs establish the link between sensors with the subsystem. Since errors generated in each subsystem will lead to errors in PNT solutions, we also study the link between the affected PNT solution with threats associated with the faulty solution.

This activity was originally reported in [1].

2.1 Introduction

PNT solution refers to a technology that provides the precise location, speed, and direction of an object in real time. PNT systems are often based on satellite-based technologies, such as the Global Positioning System (GPS), which is a network of satellites orbiting the earth that transmit signals to GPS receivers on the ground. The importance of PNT solutions for Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) is significant, as these vehicles rely on accurate and reliable information about their location, speed, and direction to perform autonomous driving functions, such as navigation and obstacle avoidance. In order for HAVs to operate safely and efficiently, it is critical that they have access to high-precision PNT information at all times. This information is used by the vehicle's onboard control systems to make decisions about vehicle speed, direction, and other aspects of vehicle operation.

Recent advancements in the automotive industry are centered on autonomous vehicles. These vehicles operate in an environment where they receive information to ensure safe and secure operations. Innovations in technology such as Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V), Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I), Vehicle to Cloud (V2C), and Vehicle to Pedestrian (V2P) communication, guidance, navigation, and control systems continue to be developed to create a safe environment for autonomous vehicles and all road users. Government agencies are investing in the automotive industry, technology companies, and research institutions to create better prospects for the future [20]. One example of this is the "Smart Columbus" project, which is supported by the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT) to make Columbus a model smart city for autonomous vehicles, improving quality of life, economic growth, sustainability, and safety [21]. Researchers and scientists are making great efforts to develop a secure and highly reliable autonomous system for smart cities. These systems can be divided into two main categories: centralized and distributed approaches for autonomous vehicles.

Technological developments in the automotive infrastructure are focused on roadside computing and communication devices such as Road Side Units (RSU), STL, Smart Traffic signs (STS), AIM systems, cloud storage and connectivity, and Automated Traffic Management (ATM) systems. RSUs are edge computing devices that establish communication between vehicles and infrastructure. They use the Dedicated Short Range Communication (DSRC) channel to exchange information. The Onboard Unit (OBU) is the second technological development that assists HAV by utilizing distributed approach. Hence safe transit operation in different scenarios such as lane change scenarios, lane merging, lane bi-parting, non-signalized intersections, and roundabout and signalized intersections would be accomplished.

This study aims to fill a gap in the existing literature by analyzing the attack trees and system-level failure mode and effect analysis (FMEA) of the PNT sensor in HAVs. By understanding the sources of threats and challenges facing HAVs, scientists can develop more effective strategies for protecting these vehicles. In previous research, such as [22], the focus has been on attack and defense strategies for HAVs operating in intelligent and smart infrastructure environments, with a particular emphasis on GPS jamming and spoofing. However, there has been less attention paid to other PNT solutions, such as lidar, radar, and cameras. This study aims to address this gap by examining the attack surfaces of HAVs and providing a comprehensive analysis of the PNT sensor.

The more concise summary of the contributions outlined in the purposed work is:

- Quantifies the various ways to deceive HAVs when they are operating at smart intersections.
- Displays the attack trees targeting PNT sensors and sources.
- Shows the system-level FMEA of PNT solutions for HAVs.

This chapter consists of six sections. Section II presents the systems and subsystems in relation to its PNT sensors and sources required by HAVs to operate in any vulnerable situation. Section III presents PNT sensors HAVs used for cooperative driving and threats and vulnerabilities associated with these sensors. Section III also presents the threats and vulnerability chart of sensors and the attack tree of these sensors. Section IV presents the system-level FMEA of the PNT solution available for HAVs. Section V is used to validate the results shown in Sections II, III, and IV. The cooperative navigation framework [23] is used for the validation of attack trees and system-level FMEA.

Figure 2.1: The framework of sensors and subsystems used in a Highly Automated vehicles' navigation system to operate independently at the smart intersection.

2.2 Position, Navigation, and Timing systems and subsystems

Technology is accelerating and evolving rapidly. Scientists, researchers, and innovators use multiple sensing elements and techniques to fulfill the requirements of their needs. Automotive industries working toward shaping the future of humankind with connected autonomous vehicles and smart infrastructure. According to the standards of SAE, autonomous vehicles have five levels of autonomy. To achieve these levels of autonomy, and to transform a vehicle into a connected autonomous vehicle the automotive industry depends on PNT sensors. These sensors are available from different vendors and Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) with diverse levels of accurate measurements. The framework of the HAVs sensors and PNT computing systems is shown in Fig. 2.1. Fig. 2.1 also elaborates on the attack surfaces of each sensor of the PNT subsystem. The subsystem is divided into two categories to focus on the need for vulnerable situations present at smart intersections. Near space, navigation shows the PNT subsystem that is important while an HAV operates at a smart intersection and the Far space navigation subsystem that is important in strategic planning and guidance. A red box and arrow show the attack surface of sensors and communication channels. Connected autonomous vehicles have different subsystems to achieve different autonomy objectives with the use of different PNT sensors. The subsystems and sensors relationship matrix is developed to analyze the types of effects on PNT solutions and related hazards. Fig. 2.2 shows the subsystem in the left-hand side column and sensors and sources shown on the top row of the matrix. The color cell in the matrix shows that the specific sensors can be available for a specific set of subsystems. The blue color shows that the sensor and the related subsystem can be utilized in both sets of scenarios (i.e. urban and rural).

2.3 Position, Navigation and Timing sensors and their attack trees

PNT sensors and sources are associated with various vulnerabilities and threats. A different class of sensors has different vulnerabilities and threats. The presented work has an analysis of the vulnerabilities and threats associated with the sensors and sources available for PNT solutions. Nowadays, there are a few basic sensors and sources available such as radar, lidar, camera, GPS, INS, LTE, and DSRC for V2V and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication. A literature survey has been done to analyze the vulnerabilities of sensors shown in Fig. 2.3. The red color

		Sensors/Sources									
		RADAR	GPS	INS	Doppler	LTE	Camera	Sonar	Lidar	WIFI	Legacy maps
HATS-PNT Sub-System	Waypoint Positioning System										
	Attitude Determination System										
	Path Planning System										
	Collision Avoidance System										
	Lane keeping and Centering system										
	Lane Departure Warning System										
	Adaptive Cruise Control System										
	Lane Change Assist System										
	Adaptive Front Lighting System										
	Traffic Sign Recognition System										
	Night Vision System										
	Emergency Braking System										
	Pedestrian Detection										
	Blind Spot Detection										
	Collision Warning System										
	Parking assist system										
	Free Space Detection										
	Valet parking system										
	Auto Summon system										
	Autonomous Control system										
Cooperative Navigation System											

Figure 2.2: Matrix shows the sensors available for HAVs and subsystems necessary to conduct the autonomous operation. it shows the link of subsystems with the sensors of HAVs for rural and urban environment operation.

		PNT Sensors/Sources							
		GPS	LTE	WIFI	IMU	Camera	Radar	Lidar	3D map v2v/v2c
Possible Threats	Eavesdropping		█	█					█
	Denial of Service		█	█					█
	Sybil	█	█	█					█
	Black Hole		█	█					█
	Reply Attack	█	█	█			█		█
	Timing	█	█	█					█
	Malware								█
	Spoofing	█	█	█		█	█		█
	Jamming	█	█	█			█	█	█
	Man in the Middle	█	█	█		█			█
	Physical Integrity					█	█	█	
	Injection Attack								█
	Impersonation Attack								█
	Illusion Attack					█	█	█	
	Possible Vulnerabilities	Bogus Information Attack					█	█	█
Random Walk					█				
Calibration Error					█				
Bias Instability					█				
line of Sight		█				█	█	█	
Multi Path Reflection		█	█	█		█	█	█	
Atmospheric layer Refraction		█							
Weather		█	█			█	█	█	
Cloud		█							

Figure 2.3: Threats and vulnerabilities matrix present the associated sensors used in the automotive industry.

Figure 2.4: Threats due to vulnerabilities of RADAR presents in the form of an attack tree.

cell in Fig. 2.3 illustrates the relationship between sensors and threats associated with the PNT solution of the HAVs. Such as spoofing attacks can happen on GPS, LTE, Wi-Fi, Camera, Radar, and V2X communication channels.

2.3.1 Radar

Radar is the sensing device that transmits the electromagnetic radio signal and received the echo returns from objects to determine the position and velocity. Vulnerabilities and threat challenges associated with radar are related to challenges of electromagnetic radio waves and the physical appearance of the object in a detection space. Threats take advantage of vulnerabilities in cyber-physical systems, which can lead to potential hazards and risks. These threats and vulnerabilities are presented in the attack tree of the radar in Fig. 2.4. This chapter discusses the specific threats and vulnerabilities associated with radar systems, and how they are interconnected in order to evaluate the overall risk. Since radar position and velocity-solution depend on radio waves therefore they have similar vulnerabilities that are multi-path reflection [24], the reflection of the energy by flat objects, and absorption of electromagnetic wave energy by stealth material and color [25].

Eq. 2.1 represents the power reflected from a target and received by the radar and is used to evaluate the position of the target object or vehicle.

$$P_r = \frac{P_t G \sigma A_e}{(4\pi)^2 R^4} \quad (2.1)$$

where, P_r represents the power received by the radar P_t, G, σ, A_e are power transmitted, the directive gain of the radar antenna, target cross-section, and receiving antennas effective aperture respectively. Power received (P_r) is directly proportional to $P_t, G, \sigma,$ and A_e while its inversely proportional to $(4\pi)^2 R^4$, where the only limitation is the range of the target vehicle. Eq. 2.1 explains the vulnerabilities associated with radar and how malicious actors can get the advantages of low power receiving echo returns [26]. Such low-power signals are easily jammed [27] or spoofed [28] by attackers if they somehow guess the carrier frequency of the radar. Since energy is transmitted and the returned echo is used to evaluate the position and velocity of the target object. Hence, maintaining line of sight [29] with the target vehicle is also necessary to determine accurate position and velocity. Fig. 2.4 illustrates how the vulnerabilities of radar lead to false detection and thus create a critical situation that may lead to fatal crashes. Such as energy from other sources having the same frequency as automotive radar may spoof the original radar signal which will result in false detection and a PNT solution.

2.3.2 Global Positioning System (GPS)

The global positioning system (GPS) is a satellite-based navigation system. The satellite transmits radio signals from medium earth orbit to the user segment over the surface of the earth. Due to the long-distance transmission, the user segment receives very low power signals [30] which is the main vulnerability of the global navigation satellite system. As GPS transmits a high-frequency carrier wave therefore another major issue is the line of sight [31]. Most of the threats on the GPS receiver are associated with these two issues, line of sight and low power signal. These two vulnerabilities play a critical role in jamming [32] and spoofing [33] attacks. We present the attack tree of GPS to analyze the effect of these two vulnerabilities on the PNT system. GPS is also used for time synchronization therefore it is more vulnerable for autonomous vehicles. The pseudo-range equation is a fundamental equation used in GPS positioning as given in 2.2.

$$R_{GPS} = c * (t_r - t_t) + t_e \quad (2.2)$$

where R_{GPS} is the distance between the GPS receiver and the satellite, c is the speed of light, t_r is the time the signal was received by the GPS receiver, t_t is the time the signal was transmitted by the satellite, and t_e is the error of the clock in the GPS receiver. This equation describes the line of sight distance between the GPS receiver and the satellite. But since it doesn't take into account the errors due to the ionosphere and the troposphere, it is called a pseudo-range. Fig. 2.5 shows how low power signals of GPS transmitters due to long distances will lead to jamming, Spoofing, Timing, Sybil, injection, and reply attack.

2.3.3 Inertial Navigation System (INS)

An inertial navigation system is a self-defined PNT solution provider that depends on onboard accelerometers and gyroscopes. Therefore it is not affected by threats associated with malicious actors, hackers, and cyber attackers. Although its internal electronics are very sensitive to electromagnetic signals that create interference and degrade the position and velocity estimation [34]. We present the attack tree for INS to analyze the effect on the PNT solution. Fig. 2.6 shows that the INS system is prone to external threats but INS devices are very sensitive and their results will be affected by internal electromagnetic interference and surrounding temperature.

Figure 2.5: Attack tree of GPS to illustrate the Threats and vulnerabilities in the system.

Figure 2.6: Attack tree of INS to illustrate the Threats and vulnerabilities in the inertial system.

Figure 2.7: Attack tree of LTE to illustrate the Threats and vulnerabilities in the PNT system.

2.3.4 Long-Term Evolution (LTE)

LTE is a cellular communication network used for bi-directional data transfer for wirelessly connected devices. LTE used radio waves to transmit and receive 3G and 4G communication signals. In recent years LTE is used for providing alternate PNT solutions with the method of trilateration and triangulation techniques. LTE positioning system is a location-based service that uses the LTE network to determine the location of a device. Like any other positioning system, the LTE positioning system also has some vulnerabilities. Some of the main vulnerabilities of the LTE positioning system include: spoofing [35], denial of service [36], eavesdropping [37], unauthorized access [38], jamming [35], and interference [39]. Since it works on radio waves, therefore malicious actors can disturb LTE positioning and communication in multiple ways. In Fig. 2.7, we analyze most of the attacks that happened after exploiting the authentication of LTE communication. Denial of service can also be performed due to a jamming attack. Jamming can be done in two ways either penetrate into the device through authentication or block the carrier frequency of the LTE communication channel. As attackers can have user information in multiple ways to impose any kind of attack. These vulnerabilities can be mitigated by using encryption, authentication, and other security measures. Additionally, some of the vulnerabilities can also be addressed by using multiple positioning methods, such as combining GPS, Wi-Fi, and cellular positioning to provide more accurate location information.

2.3.5 Camera

A camera is used in autonomous industries to detect and identify objects. The camera provides 2D images for object detection and identification. Object detection and identification such as the status of the traffic light are important in autonomous operation. The camera is also used for relative positioning. Camera positioning systems, also known as visual odometry systems, are used to determine the position and orientation of a camera in relation to its surroundings. These systems typically use computer vision techniques to analyze images captured by the camera and can be vulnerable to a number of issues including weather conditions [40], line of sight [41], sensor

Figure 2.8: Attack tree of vision sensor to illustrate the Threats and vulnerabilities in the system uses vision sensor.

noise, feature matching errors [42], spoofing [43], jamming, and interference. The camera has vulnerabilities that lead to opportunities for attackers to generate threats. The attack tree presents the threats for HAVs that affect the PNT solutions and leads to undesired situations. Fig. 2.8 shows that similar images of road signs can lead to illusion attacks. Since illusion can also be done through mirrors and other light-reflecting objects. Therefore, all illusion attack falls into multi-path reflection.

2.3.6 Lidar

Lidar (Light Detection and Ranging) is a technology that uses laser beams to scan the environment and create a 3D map of the surroundings. Lidar technology determines position by measuring the distance to surrounding objects. The sensor emits laser beams, which then bounce back and is measured to calculate the distance to the objects in the environment and generate a 3D map of the surrounding area. This map can then be used to pinpoint the exact location of the Lidar sensor in relation to the objects around it. Lidar positioning can be used in a variety of applications, including self-driving cars, drones, and robots. It is a relatively robust and accurate method of positioning, especially in environments with a high degree of reflectivity, such as urban areas or industrial environments. Lidar plays a vital role to provide resilient PNT solutions. However, Lidar positioning also has some vulnerabilities and these vulnerabilities are similar to radar as the working principle of radar is identical to lidar. Some of the vulnerabilities of lidar are adverse weather conditions [44], line of sight [45], limited range, spoofing, jamming, and interference [46]. Threats associated with the lidar are presented in the attack tree that shows how the PNT solution

Figure 2.9: Attack tree of Lidar to illustrate the Threats and vulnerabilities in the PNT system.

is affected by the attacks. Fig. 2.9 shows how spoofing will affect the lidar solution due to energy received by another source thus it falls in the vulnerability of energy diverted, lost, or received from another source.

2.4 PNT System level FMEA

System Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) is the highest-level analysis of an entire system, made up of various subsystems. The focus is on system-related deficiencies, including system safety, system integration, interfaces or interactions between subsystems or with other systems, interactions with the surrounding environment, human interaction, and service. It also includes the issues that could cause the overall system not to work as intended. It includes failure modes associated with interfaces and interactions [47]. The sensor and subsystem association tree shows how the imposed threat on one of the sensors leads to the PNT solution. Threats and vulnerabilities of sensors affect the PNT solution which leads to hazards. Dedicated Short-Range Communication (DSRC) is used by the HAVs for V2V and V2I correspondence. DSRC shares vehicle parameters and current state via the V2V communication channel and environmental parameters via the V2I communication channel. Hence DSRC is one of the large attack surfaces for PNT systems that have the same vulnerabilities and threats similar to radio communication devices.

The system level FMEA shows the hazard of threats and vulnerabilities with the PNT solution. HAVs are controlled by C-ADS to operate in a smart environment. The C-ADS generates steering, brake, and acceleration command to guide the HAVs while crossing the smart intersection. The effect caused by the mode of failure is shown in Fig. 2.10. Fig. 2.10 illustrates that if the GPS

Figure 2.10: FMEA analysis to illustrate the risk and threats for HAVs due to faulty PNT solution with respect to sensors and subsystem.

solution is affected due to any reason mentioned in Fig. 2.5 will disturb the PNT solution of the waypoint positioning system. The faulty output of the waypoint positioning system will affect the result of the Path planning system and so on. It will create hazardous PNT solutions by the path of the following system. All of these systems are directly effected by faulty GPS solutions, on the other hand, there is also an indirect impact on other navigation systems. Integrated results of these sub-systems will generate faulty steering, braking, and acceleration commands. these faulty commands will leads to fatal crashes and vulnerable situations as mentioned in Fig. 2.10. System level FMEA in Fig. 2.10 shows that if any of the fault or threat occurs as mentioned in Figs. 2.4, 2.8, and 2.9 will affect static and dynamic object detection systems and this will affect the collision avoidance system. therefore collision avoidance system generates faulty PNT solutions and will result in crashes, traffic jams, and lane changes and may hit the object or pedestrians.

2.5 Conclusion

We have conducted a threat and vulnerability analysis of HAVs operating at a smart intersection. A literature survey is done to identify the sensors and sources used in the automotive industry. Further analysis is performed to identify the vulnerabilities and threats related to sensors and sources. The system level FMEA presented shows the effect on the related sub-system and system of cooperative navigation of HAVs and further leads to a hazardous situation with the faulty PNT solution.

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Chapter 3

Signal Identification and Entrainment for Practical FMCW Radar Spoofing Attacks

This chapter proposes a method of passively estimating the parameters of frequency-modulated-continuous-wave (FMCW) radar signals with a wide range of structural parameter values and analyzes how a malicious actor could employ such estimates to track and spoof a target radar. When radars are implemented to support automated driver assistance systems, an intelligent spoofer has the potential to substantially disrupt safe navigation by inducing its target to perceive false objects. Such a spoofer must acquire highly accurate estimates of the target radar’s chirp sweep, timing, and frequency parameters while additionally tracking and compensating for time and Doppler shifts due to clock errors and relative movement. This is a difficult task for millimeter-wave radars due to severe Doppler shifts and fast sweep rates, especially when the spoofer uses off-the-shelf FMCW equipment. Algorithms and techniques for acquiring and tracking an FMCW radar are proposed and verified through simulation, which will help guide future decisions on appropriate radar spoofing countermeasures.

This activity was originally reported in [2].

3.1 Introduction

Frequency-modulated continuous-wave (FMCW) radars operate by transmitting a sequence of multiple linear chirps called a frame. After reflecting off an object, the received signal is mixed with a replica of the transmitted chirp sequence, resulting in a sinusoid whose frequency indicates the range to the reflecting object. By examining the phase shifts of this sinusoid across multiple chirps, a radar can estimate the object’s relative velocity. Furthermore, an FMCW radar can estimate an object’s direction by examining the phase shifts across elements in its antenna array.

Millimeter-wave (mmWave) radars have significantly improved radar precision [48], providing benefits over alternative sensors for use in automated driver assistance systems (ADAS) and autonomous vehicle (AV) platforms [49, 50]. Radars are currently deployed in ADAS for adaptive cruise control, forward collision avoidance, and lane-change assist, among others [51]. In more advanced systems, these radars may be used for imaging by providing point cloud data to computer vision systems within AVs [49]. Beyond the automotive industry, these radars can provide precise sensing for urban air mobility applications [52]. With an ever increasing number of automated systems relying on mmWave FMCW radar, it is crucial that these sensors remain secure against

potential threats.

Since typical fast-chirp mmWave FMCW radars use an intermediate frequency (IF) bandwidth in the 10s of MHz and chirp slopes in the 10s of MHz/ μ s, these radars only sample a thin sliver of the time-frequency spectrum at any instant, making it unlikely that persistent interference will appear in the band of sensitivity and manifest as a false reflecting object [53,54]. However, existing fast-chirp processing is susceptible to deliberate spoofing. By controlling the time-of-arrival and frequency offset of the spoofing signal, an attacker can induce the target receiver to perceive fake objects at any arbitrary range and velocity. Since FMCW radars are the most widely used radars in automotive vehicles [55], such spoofing could have widespread ramifications.

Previous studies on radar spoofing have focused directly on the mechanics of a spoofing attack, demonstrating FMCW spoofing attacks with commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) devices [28, 56, 57], with custom boards [58], and with an AV testbed [59]. However, this work assumes that the spoofer already knows the target radar’s waveform, which is unlikely in a real-world scenario. Furthermore, the advanced spoofing attack in [59] was carried out using high-end test equipment, which may not be representative of the most common radar spoofing threats. Separate from spoofing literature, the related problem of FMCW parameter estimation and synchronization has been examined. Gardill et al. proposed a method of finding an unknown FMCW signal by analyzing the time-frequency spectrum of interference when mixed with a local fast-sweep-rate FMCW signal [60]. Their study was then extended to demonstrate how such a tactic could be used to first estimate signal parameters, switch the local mixer to a CW signal to obtain precise timing, and then switch the local mixer to a time-aligned replica of the transmitted signal [61]. While these studies did not directly address FMCW spoofing, they show that synchronization schemes are practical and that issues such as timing jitter can be accounted for. However, the papers do not propose a rigorous method of chirp parameter estimation and tracking. Other work has focused purely on synchronizing FMCW systems when the signal shape is known [62,63]. Work on counter-adversarial tracking has also analyzed the estimation and countering of cognitive radars [64].

Prior work has studied passive FMCW parameter estimation and FMCW spoofing attacks but falls short of detailing a comprehensive attack that can be carried out using COTS radars without prior signal knowledge. This work addresses these gaps so future work can evaluate effective countermeasures.

3.2 System Model

Consider an environment where there is a set of radars \mathcal{I} , all with standard FMCW architectures, and each having one or more transmit and receive antennas. Each radar has a signal generator that creates linear frequency chirps. A sequence of these chirps, called a frame, is generated and processed coherently. The number of chirps depends on the desired Doppler resolution and can range between tens and hundreds of chirps per frame. Each chirp signal is sent to one or more transmit antennas and to a mixer that takes its other input from the receive antennas. Let the transmitted signal of the k th chirp in the i th radar’s frame be denoted as $s_{ik}(t)$, where $i \in \mathcal{I}$ and $k \in K_i$, with K_i being the set of chirps in one frame from radar i . The k th chirp has a start frequency f_{ik} , a chirp slope β_{ik} , a phase offset ϕ_{ik} , and a duration T_{ik} . A baseband model of the i th radar’s k th chirp is

$$c_{ik}(t) = \begin{cases} \exp\left(j2\pi\left(f_{ik}t + \frac{\beta_{ik}t^2}{2}\right) + j\phi_{ik}\right) & t \in [0, T_{ik}) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} . \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

This chirp signal is sent to one or more transmit antennas with some complex weighting. Assume that radar i has $N_{\text{TX},i}$ transmit antennas and $N_{\text{RX},i}$ receive antennas. Let the vector of transmit antenna weights for chirp k on radar i be $\mathbf{w}_{ik} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{TX},i} \times 1}$. For this work, \mathbf{w}_{ik} is assumed to be one-hot, meaning that it contains only one nonzero element. However, MIMO radars may use orthogonal codes such as Hadamard codes across multiple antennas, in which case every element of \mathbf{w}_{ik} would contain ± 1 in accordance with the code. Additionally, \mathbf{w}_{ik} may apply a binary phase-shift keying (BPSK) or quadrature phase-shift keying (QPSK) phase code across each chirp k . Each chirp signal is delayed Δt_{ik} seconds after the beginning of the frame and weighted by the vector \mathbf{w}_{ik} , creating the transmitted signal

$$\mathbf{s}_i(t) = \sum_{k \in K} \mathbf{w}_{ik} c_{ik}(t - \Delta t_{ik}), \quad (3.2)$$

which propagates along several paths to the receive antennas. Let \mathcal{R}_i^l be a set of paths from radar l to radar i . In the case of monostatic radar, the transmit and receive radars are the same, and this set can be written as \mathcal{R}_i^i . Focusing on the monostatic case, the signal in each path $r \in \mathcal{R}_i^i$ experiences a propagation delay Δt_r and arrives with a receive magnitude α_{ir} . Due to the antenna array manifold, relative phase shifts are imparted on the signal depending upon the angles of departure and arrival of each path. The transmitter array phase shift is given by $\mathbf{a}_{\text{TX},ir} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{TX},i} \times 1}$ and the receiver array phase shift is given by $\mathbf{a}_{\text{RX},ir} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RX},i} \times 1}$ for the r th path. Lastly, the signal propagating along the r th path experiences a Doppler shift $f_{D,r}$ arising from the motion of the radar and the reflecting object. This shift is modeled as a multiplication of the signal by $\nu_r(t) = \exp(j2\pi f_{D,r}t)$. The received signal across all receive antennas is then given by the vector

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t) = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_i^i} \alpha_{ir} \mathbf{a}_{\text{RX},ir} \mathbf{a}_{\text{TX},ir}^\top \mathbf{s}_i(t - \Delta t_r) \nu_r(t). \quad (3.3)$$

In addition to this monostatic signal, radar i will receive interference from other radars in the environment. The interference signal received at radar i is

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i(t) = \sum_{l \in \mathcal{I} \setminus \{i\}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_i^l} \alpha_{ir} \mathbf{a}_{\text{RX},ir} \mathbf{a}_{\text{TX},lr}^\top \mathbf{s}_l(t - \Delta t_r) \nu_r(t). \quad (3.4)$$

The sum $\mathbf{x}_i(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i(t)$ is mixed with the conjugate transpose of radar i 's local signal given in (3.2), passed through a lowpass anti-aliasing filter with impulse response $h(t)$, and sampled with period T_s , creating the $N_{\text{RX},i} \times N_{\text{TX},i}$ matrix $\mathbf{Y}_i[n]$:

$$\mathbf{Y}_i(t) = (\mathbf{x}_i(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i(t)) \mathbf{s}_i^H(t). \quad (3.5)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_i[n] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(nT_s - \tau) \mathbf{Y}_i(\tau) d\tau. \quad (3.6)$$

Consider the mixed signals originating from a different radar. Let $m_{l\bar{k}}^{ikr}(t)$ be the resulting signal when the \bar{k} th transmitted chirp from radar l is received along path r by radar i and mixed with its k th chirp:

$$\begin{aligned} m_{l\bar{k}}^{ikr}(t) &= c_{l\bar{k}}(t - \Delta t_r) c_{ik}^*(t) \nu_r(t) \\ &= \exp \left(j2\pi \left((f_{l\bar{k}} - f_{ik})t - \beta_{l\bar{k}} \Delta t_r t + f_{D,r}t - f_{l\bar{k}} \Delta t_r \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_{l\bar{k}} - \beta_{ik})t^2 + \frac{1}{2}\beta_{l,\bar{k}} \Delta t_r^2 \right) + j(\phi_{l\bar{k}} - \phi_{ik}) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

Table 3.1: Required Signal Parameters

T_{frame}	Frame interval
Δt_{frame}	Frame timing offset
T_k	Duration of the k th chirp in the frame
Δt_k	Start time of the k th chirp after the frame start
Δf_k	Start frequency of the k th chirp
β_k	Slope of the k th chirp
K	Number of chirps in a frame
ϕ_k	Phase shift applied to the k th chirp

This is a linear chirp with a slope of $\beta_{l\bar{k}} - \beta_{ik}$, a start frequency of $f_{l\bar{k}} - f_{ik} - \beta_{l\bar{k}}\Delta t_r + f_{D,r}$, and a phase shift of $-2\pi f_{l\bar{k}}\Delta t_r + \pi\beta_{l\bar{k}}\Delta t_r^2 + \phi_{l\bar{k}} - \phi_{ik}$.

Real-world radar systems are prone to clock errors, and the system model must account for their effects, especially in the case of bistatic propagation where the two radars are unsynchronized. Therefore, the clock frequency and phase drifts are modeled with the two-state model described in [65, Chapter 9.3]. This model is parameterized by two Allan variance parameters, h_0 and h_{-2} . Consider two white-noise processes, $F_i(t)$ and $G_i(t)$, with spectral densities $S_{f,i} \approx \frac{h_0}{2}$ and $S_{g,i} \approx 2\pi^2 h_{-2}$, respectively. The time perceived at radar i is $\tilde{t}_i(t)$, a function of the true time t :

$$\tilde{t}_i(t) = t + \int_0^t F_i(\tau_f) + \int_0^{\tau_f} G_i(\tau_g) d\tau_g d\tau_f. \quad (3.8)$$

Considering only the azimuth dimension, propagation path r has an angle of arrival $\theta_{\text{AOA},r}$ and an angle of departure $\theta_{\text{AOD},r}$. Each radar's antennas have a gain as a function of angle, $G_{\text{RX},i}(\theta)$ and $G_{\text{TX},i}(\theta)$. The signal experiences a path loss of $L_{\text{prop},r}$, which may be one-way for a direct path, or two-way for a reflected path. The reflection in the path has a radar cross section of $\sigma_{\text{RCS},r}$. The total received power is $P_{\text{RX},ir} = P_{\text{TX},l} G_{\text{RX},i}(\theta_{\text{AOA},r}) G_{\text{TX},l}(\theta_{\text{AOD},r}) L_{\text{prop},r}^{-1} \sigma_{\text{RCS}}$; the received magnitude is $\alpha_{ir} = \sqrt{P_{\text{RX},ir}}$.

3.3 FMCW Entrainment

Consider an instance of the signal model where the set of radars includes one target radar l and one spoofer radar i . The spoofer aims to transmit a false replica of the target's signal, causing the target radar to perceive a fake object. However, the spoofer is assumed to have no prior knowledge of the target's signal structure other than it taking the form of a mmWave FMCW signal with repeating frames. To recreate the target signal accurately for spoofing, the spoofer must have an estimate of the parameters in Table 3.1. These are the parameters as perceived by the spoofer which may be different from the true target parameters due to ambiguities caused by the clocks, timing, Doppler, and chirp phase shifts. Furthermore, the spoofer is assumed to use COTS FMCW radar equipment. While a wideband mmWave receiver may be capable of easily estimating these parameters after capturing the entire chirp sequence, the small IF bandwidth of COTS FMCW radars complicates this task. Instead, the spoofer must strategically design its mixing signal to collect information about the spectrum and the target signal, only receiving useful samples when the target and mixing signals are close in frequency. The spoofing scheme proposed here offers one possible strategy for estimating the target signal's parameter under these constraints.

The proposed FMCW spoofing attack can be divided into three stages: (1) an identification stage where the spoofer samples the spectrum to discover a target radar signal and coarsely esti-

Figure 3.1: Complex samples of the signal modeled in (3.7) during an interval in which the mixing signal crosses the received signal in time and frequency, $f_{ik} = f_{\text{tone}}$, and $\beta_{ik} = 0$.

mates the target’s parameters, (2) a tracking stage where the spoofer refines its parameter estimates and tracks the signal with greater precision, and (3) a spoofing stage where the spoofer transmits a signal with the intent of appearing as a fake object to the target radar. This chapter focuses on the first two stages, which will collectively be called signal entrainment.

3.3.1 Identification

During the identification stage, the spoofer operates passively and attempts to find an FMCW radar to target. Throughout this stage, the spoofer restricts its signal to a constant frequency tone with frequency f_{tone} . First, the spoofer attempts to detect the presence of an FMCW signal. From (3.7), the mixed output of a chirp with a constant frequency tone (i.e., $f_{ik} = f_{\text{tone}}$ and $\beta_{ik} = 0$) is a chirp whose instantaneous frequency is $\beta_{l\tilde{k}}(t - \Delta t_r) + f_{l\tilde{k}} - f_{\text{tone}} + f_{D,r}$. Due to the anti-aliasing filter, this signal will be filtered out except for the short time-span when the instantaneous frequency is near zero. Fig. 3.1 visualizes one instance of such a signal. Due to the one-way path loss of the target-spoofing system and beamforming, this signal is easily detectable above the noise floor without any pulse integration. Recall that \mathbf{w}_{ik} and, consequently, $\mathbf{s}_i(t)$ are assumed to be one-hot. From (3.5), this assumption means $\mathbf{Y}_i[n]$ has only one non-zero column. Let this column be written as $\mathbf{y}_i[n]$ with shape $N_{\text{RX},i} \times 1$ in this specific case. Beamforming is performed with an FFT [50, 66] of $\mathbf{y}_i[n]$ across the receive antenna dimension, creating the beamformed vector $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_i[n]$, whose b th element corresponds to the b th beamforming bin. Assuming an oversampling factor of N_{os} , $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_i[n]$ has the shape $N_{\text{os}}N_{\text{RX},i} \times 1$.

First, the spoofer determines which sample index n and beamforming bin b contain the maximum power: $\{\hat{n}_{\text{max}}, \hat{b}_{\text{max}}\} = \text{argmax}_{n,b} |(\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_i[n])_b|^2$. The spoofer then uses a constant false alarm rate (CFAR) detector [67, Chapter 6.5] on the power-maximizing beamformed signal $(\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_i[n])_{\hat{b}_{\text{max}}}$ to create a set of detections $\mathcal{D}_{\text{sample}}$ containing sample indices and frequencies (\hat{n}, \hat{f}) . The frequencies come from the known frequency of the spoofer’s mixer, f_{tone} . The set of detections $\mathcal{D}_{\text{sample}}$ is consolidated by replacing groups of neighboring sample indices \hat{n} with a single detection at the center sample of each group. Lastly, a new set \mathcal{D} is created where $\mathcal{D} = \{(nT_s, f) : (n, f) \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{sample}}\}$, converting the sample indices to times.

Now, the spoofer estimates the frame interval T_{frame} and frame timing offset Δt_{frame} , which are

Figure 3.2: A visualization of the detections obtained during the two captures in the identification stage when mixing with a 76.25 GHz tone. The target signal’s frame interval T_{frame} and frame timing offset Δt_{frame} are highlighted.

defined graphically as shown in Fig. 3.2. The spoofer collects two captures of samples while mixing the received signal with a constant frequency tone for T_{capture} seconds each. T_{capture} is chosen to be long enough to contain at least two repetitions of the target radar’s frame, whose interval T_{frame} is unknown to the spoofer but can be reasonably bounded. The samples from both captures are passed through the same CFAR detector, creating two sets of detections: \mathcal{D}_1 and \mathcal{D}_2 . Note that $f_1 = f_2 = f_{\text{tone}}$ since the mixing frequency has not changed. These detections are visualized in relation to the frame parameters in Fig. 3.2 and to the chirp parameters in Fig. 3.3. Since the spoofer currently has no reference of the target’s frame timing, the spoofer does not yet know which frame each detection belongs to. To estimate the frame timing under this ambiguity, the spoofer analyzes the periodicity of the detections. This is done by evaluating how well these two sets match over shifts in time using a Gaussian kernel likelihood function $k(t_1, t_2, \sigma) = \exp\left(\frac{-|t_1 - t_2|^2}{\sigma^2}\right)$. This approach is inspired by kernel correlation techniques used in point-set registration [68]. The sum kernel likelihood between the sets for a lag l is

$$d(l) = \sum_{(t_1, f_1) \in \mathcal{D}_1} \sum_{(t_2, f_2) \in \mathcal{D}_2} k(t_1, t_2 - l, \sigma). \quad (3.9)$$

The kernel standard deviation σ is chosen to be greater than the longest possible chirp interval and less than the shortest possible frame interval, causing the function $d(l)$ to smooth over small time differences between the two sets. The result is a function that exhibits multiple peaks with an inter-peak distance approximately equal to the frame interval, from which one may obtain an estimate \hat{T}_{frame} . Fig. 3.4a shows an example of this sum kernel likelihood function.

The spoofer then estimates the frame timing offset Δt_{frame} . Since there is an inherent ambiguity between the frame timing offset and the chirp timing offsets relative to the frame start, the spoofer has flexibility in selecting this value. However, it is important that the chosen offset does not cause the estimated frames to contain detections from two of the target’s frames. To minimize this

Figure 3.3: A visualization of the detections obtained during a capture in the identification stage when mixing with a 76.25 GHz tone. The target signal’s chirps are shown, highlighting each chirp’s start time Δt_k , start frequency Δf_k , duration T_k , and slope β_k .

possibility, Δt_{frame} is chosen as the time that minimizes the mean squared distance between the detection times and the center of the nearest frame. The two sets of detections are combined to form $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{D}_1 \cup \mathcal{D}_2$, and the frame offset Δt_{frame} is estimated as

$$\Delta \hat{t}_{\text{frame}} = \underset{\Delta t_{\text{frame}} \in [0, \hat{T}_{\text{frame}}]}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{(t, f) \in \mathcal{D}} \left| ((t - \Delta t_{\text{frame}}) \bmod \hat{T}_{\text{frame}}) - \frac{\hat{T}_{\text{frame}}}{2} \right|^2. \quad (3.10)$$

With an estimate of the frame interval and a frame time offset that centers the chirp sequence in the frame, the spoofer can now partition its detections into each frame and further refine its frame interval estimate. Similar to the first frame interval estimation, a kernel likelihood measure is used. First, define a function $g(t, l) = (t - \Delta \hat{t}_{\text{frame}}) \bmod (\hat{T}_{\text{frame}} - l)$, and let σ_{ref} be a refined kernel standard deviation, which is chosen to be less than the minimum chirp duration but larger than the spoofer’s desired time resolution. Then the sum kernel likelihood using the refined kernel is

$$d_{\text{ref}}(l) = \sum_{(t_1, f_1) \in \mathcal{D}} \sum_{(t_2, f_2) \in \mathcal{D}} k(g(t_1, l), g(t_2, l), \sigma_{\text{ref}}). \quad (3.11)$$

The frame interval estimate error is given by the value l that maximizes the refined kernel likelihood: $\hat{l}_{\text{max}} = \text{argmax}_l d_{\text{ref}}(l)$. This likelihood function is visualized in Fig. 3.4b. Using this error, the spoofer creates a new set of detections that accounts for the refined frame timing estimate:

$$\mathcal{D}_{\text{frame}} = \{(g(t, \hat{l}_{\text{max}}), f) : (t, f) \in \mathcal{D}\}. \quad (3.12)$$

Finally, the frame interval estimate \hat{T}_{frame} is adjusted by \hat{l}_{max} seconds for future captures. Frame timing estimation is complete now that the spoofer has estimates \hat{T}_{frame} and $\Delta \hat{t}_{\text{frame}}$.

Next, the spoofer identifies each chirp in the frame. Chirps from different frames are matched by their proximity in time in the new set $\mathcal{D}_{\text{frame}}$. The matching criterion for $(t_1, f_1) \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{frame}}$ and

Figure 3.4: (a) The sum kernel likelihood between \mathcal{D}_1 and \mathcal{D}_2 for different lag times. The distance between each peak provides an estimate of the frame interval. (b) The refined kernel likelihood used for estimating the error in the initial frame interval estimate.

$(t_2, f_2) \in \mathcal{D}_{\text{frame}}$ is $(t_1 - t_2)^2 < \sigma_{\text{chirp}}^2$. Each unique set of matching detection times is considered a detected chirp, creating an initial estimate of the set of chirps \hat{K} . Each chirp's time offset is set equal to the average of the detection times matched to that chirp. The chirp timing threshold σ_{chirp} is chosen to be larger than the worst-case timing jitter and less than the minimum inter-chirp time.

Now that the spoofer has a sense of the target radar's frame timing and chirp locations, the spoofer can begin sampling frequencies to determine each chirp's duration T_k , start time Δt_k , start frequency Δf_k , and slope β_k . The spoofer captures samples for M_{search} frames, mixing with a different constant frequency tone f_m , $\forall m \in \{1, \dots, M_{\text{search}}\}$ in the m th frame. In this work, f_m were linearly spaced in frequency, but other strategies are possible. As before, the spoofer creates a set of detections D_{search} , from which it estimates each chirp's parameters using Algorithm 1, which associates likely detections with each chirp, performs a least-squares regression, and updates the covariance of its parameter estimates. This process is visualized in Fig. 3.5. The inputs to the algorithm are an initial estimated time for the chirp Δt_k , the set of detections D_{search} , and a prior measurement variance for detection frequencies σ_{freq}^2 . The output is a chirp slope estimate $\hat{\beta}_k$, a linear regression frequency offset \hat{f}_k , a vector of detection times $\mathbf{t}_{\text{match},k}$ associated with the chirp, and a vector of frequencies $\mathbf{f}_{\text{match},k}$ associated with the chirp. This algorithm is run for each chirp $k \in \hat{K}$. Let $n_{\text{start},k} = \text{argmin}_n (\mathbf{t}_{\text{match},k})_n$, the index of the first occurring matched detection. Then the k th chirp's start frequency is estimated as $\Delta \hat{f}_k = (\mathbf{f}_{\text{match},k})_{n_{\text{start},k}}$. The start time is estimated using the linear regression frequency offset as $\Delta \hat{t}_k = (\Delta \hat{f}_k - \hat{f}_k) / \hat{\beta}_k$. The spoofer now has an estimate of all signal parameters required to recreate the target signal accurately enough to begin tracking.

3.3.2 Tracking

After identifying the target radar's signal as described, the spoofer can track the signal using more traditional FMCW signal processing, similar to the processing described in [50]. During this tracking phase, the individual chirp parameters are refined to produce a mixed signal $m_{lk}^{ikr}(t)$ similar to what would arise when tracking a genuine reflection. Rather than using continuous frequency

Figure 3.5: A visualization of the detections obtained after a frequency search and how the chirp estimation algorithm operates. The circles indicate detections already associated with a chirp, the cones indicate the acceptable likelihood regions for associating new detections, and the arrows indicate prospective detections to be associated with each chirp. On the leftmost chirp, the prospective detection is accepted. On the rightmost chirp, the prospective detection is excluded.

Algorithm 1 Iterative Chirp Parameter Estimation

Input: Δt_k , D_{search} , σ_{freq}^2
Output: $\hat{\beta}_k$, \hat{f}_k , $\mathbf{t}_{\text{match},k}$, $\mathbf{f}_{\text{match},k}$

- 1: $\hat{\beta}_k \leftarrow 0$, $\hat{f}_k \leftarrow 0$, $\mathbf{K} \leftarrow \text{diag}\{[\infty, \infty]\}$
- 2: $\mathcal{D}' \leftarrow D_{\text{search}}$ sorted by distance from Δt_k
- 3: $(t_1, f_1) \leftarrow$ 1st entry in \mathcal{D}' , $\mathcal{D}' \leftarrow \mathcal{D}' \setminus (t_1, f_1)$
- 4: $\mathbf{t}_{\text{match}} \leftarrow [t_1]$, $\mathbf{f}_{\text{match}} \leftarrow [f_1]$
- 5: **for** $\{t, f\} \in \mathcal{D}'$ **do**
- 6: $\hat{f}_k \leftarrow \hat{\beta}_k t + f$
- 7: $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow [t \ 1]$
- 8: $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{freq}}^2 \leftarrow \mathbf{x} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{x}^H + \sigma_{\text{freq}}^2$
- 9: **if** $\frac{|f - \hat{f}_k|}{\hat{\sigma}_{\text{freq}}} < 2$ **then**
- 10: $\mathbf{t}_{\text{match},k} \leftarrow [\mathbf{t}_{\text{match},k}^T \ t]^T$, $\mathbf{f}_{\text{match},k} \leftarrow [\mathbf{f}_{\text{match},k}^T \ f]^T$
- 11: $\mathbf{X} \leftarrow [\mathbf{t}_{\text{match},k} \ \mathbf{1}]$
- 12: $[\hat{\beta}_k \ \hat{f}_k]^T \leftarrow (\mathbf{X}^H \mathbf{X})^{-1} \mathbf{X}^H \mathbf{f}_{\text{match},k}$
- 13: $\mathbf{K} \leftarrow \sigma_{\text{freq}}^2 (\mathbf{X}^H \mathbf{X})^{-1}$
- 14: **else**
- 15: **exit**
- 16: **end if**
- 17: **end for**

tones, as in the identification stage, the spoofer uses its estimated target signal in its mixer.

Recall that the spoofer collects a vector of samples during its frame denoted as $\mathbf{y}_i[n]$. Rather than sampling continuously over the entire frame, the spoofer now only samples during each chirp. The vector of sample indices corresponding to chirp k can be denoted as \mathbf{n}_k , containing N_{sample} samples, assuming the same number of samples are collected during each chirp. These samples can be structured into a 3-dimensional tensor $(\mathbf{Y}_i^{(k)})_{an} = (\mathbf{y}_i[(\mathbf{n}_k)_n])_a$, where the 1st dimension is the receive antenna index a , the 2nd dimension is the sample index n , and the 3rd dimension (denoted with the superscript) is the chirp index k . In the radar literature, this tensor is commonly referred to as the “radar data cube.”

The spoofer beamforms across receive antennas with an FFT across the 1st dimension of the radar data cube, creating $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_i^{(k)}$. The spoofer also performs range and Doppler processing with an FFT, as in [50], over the 2nd and 3rd dimensions of this tensor, creating $\check{\mathbf{Y}}_i^{(d)}$, where d is the post-FFT Doppler bin index. Note that this FFT processing assumes homogenous chirp slopes. For non-homogeneous chirps, the FFTs must be transformed to align in range, the details of which are omitted in this chapter. Next, the spoofer determines the beamforming, range, and Doppler bin indices (b , n , and d) that maximize the power of this processed tensor:

$$\hat{b}_{\max}, \hat{n}_{\max}, \hat{d}_{\max} = \underset{b,n,d}{\operatorname{argmax}} \left| \left(\check{\mathbf{Y}}_i^{(d)} \right)_{bn} \right|^2. \quad (3.13)$$

These indices are then converted into an angle $\hat{\theta}$ in radians, a time delay $\Delta \hat{t}$ in seconds, and a Doppler frequency \hat{f}_D in Hz. The spoofer implements a simple 1st-order tracker to place the peak at a desired time delay and Doppler frequency.

Due to inaccurate chirp timing and chirp slope estimates, the processed signal may appear spread out in range and Doppler, reducing or eliminating any clear peak. To address this, the spoofer first refines its individual chirp estimates using the beamformed signal prior to range and Doppler processing $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_i^{(k)}$. The spoofer takes the \hat{b}_{\max} th row of $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_i^{(k)}$, denoted $(\mathbf{z}_i^{(k)})^\top$, to beamform in the target’s direction. Then, it performs only range processing through an FFT of this vector, creating $\check{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(k)}$. This differs from $\check{\mathbf{Y}}_i^{(d)}$ since only the power-maximizing beam is used and Doppler processing is not performed, creating a separate range signal for each chirp. The range index n with the peak power is found as

$$\hat{n}_{\max,k} = \underset{n}{\operatorname{argmax}} \left| \left(\check{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(k)} \right)_n \right|^2. \quad (3.14)$$

The complex values at these peak-power range indices are $p_k = (\check{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(k)})_{\hat{n}_{\max,k}}$. Then, the range indices $\hat{n}_{\max,k}$ are converted into time delay estimates $\delta \hat{t}_k$. Let $\delta \bar{t}$ be the average of $\delta \hat{t}_k$ over k . The spoofer shifts the start time of the k th chirp by $\delta \hat{t}_k - \delta \bar{t}$ seconds to align all chirps at the same range.

Additionally, the spoofer can refine its estimate of each chirp’s slope. By (3.7), slope error causes the mixed signal to have a residual linear frequency slope. This is addressed by searching for the chirp slope rate that, when mixed with the samples prior to range processing, maximizes the power in the peak of the range FFT. For a residual slope $\hat{\beta}$, the slope-correction signal is $m_{\hat{\beta}}[n] = \exp(j\pi\hat{\beta}(T_s n)^2)$, $\forall n \in \{1, \dots, N_{\text{sample}}\}$, denoted in vector notation as $\mathbf{m}_{\hat{\beta}}$. This is mixed with the beamformed sample signal creating $\mathbf{z}_{i\hat{\beta}}^{(k)} = \mathbf{z}_i^{(k)} \odot \mathbf{m}_{\hat{\beta}}$ (with \odot being a Hadamard product). Then, the spoofer performs its range FFT, creating $\check{\mathbf{z}}_{i\hat{\beta}}^{(k)}$. The residual slope is estimated as

$$\delta \hat{\beta}_k = \underset{\beta}{\operatorname{argmax}} \max_n \left| \left(\check{\mathbf{z}}_{i\hat{\beta}}^{(k)} \right)_n \right|^2. \quad (3.15)$$

Figure 3.6: The estimated chirp phases at the peak power bin after range processing and beamforming, prior to (a) and after (b) correction. The phases exhibit a phase rotation over time due to residual Doppler while also showing a random 180° phase shift due to the coding. After correction, the phases can be quantized based on the detection regions shown.

The spoofer then adjusts the slope for the k th chirp by $-\delta\hat{\beta}_k$. The last chirp-level parameters to be estimated and compensated for are the chirp phase shifts ϕ_k , $\forall k \in \hat{K}$, which arise from both transmit phase weightings and the physical placement of transmit antennas. Recall the values p_k obtained earlier, containing the complex values at the power-maximizing range bin for each chirp, which can be stacked into a vector \mathbf{p} . Fig. 3.6a shows an example of the phases of \mathbf{p} where residual Doppler is present, despite the Doppler tracking. Therefore, a Viterbi and Viterbi (V&V) Algorithm [69] is used to wipe off any phase modulation for refined Doppler estimation. Assuming a modulation order of M_{mod} which is a power of 2, the modified values are $p_{V,k} = p_k^{\log_2(M_{\text{mod}})}$. The spoofer then finds the index corresponding to the peak of the FFT of $p_{V,k}$. This index is converted into a frequency estimate \hat{f}_V and a phase estimate $\hat{\phi}_V$. Let T_c be the average chirp interval. A correction signal is created $\hat{m}_V[n] = \exp(j2\pi\hat{f}_VT_cn + j\hat{\phi}_V)$, $\forall k \in \hat{K}$, denoted in vector notation as $\hat{\mathbf{m}}_V$. This signal is multiplied with \mathbf{p} , giving $\mathbf{p}_{\text{corr}} = \mathbf{p} \odot \hat{\mathbf{m}}_V$. In this new signal, phase shifts due to any residual Doppler are approximately removed, and the relative phase shift of each chirp can be estimated. The spoofer decodes the phase modulation of each chirp through detection regions defined by the modulation order M_{mod} , creating an estimate $\hat{\phi}_k$. This FFT-based approach relies on the chirp spacing being approximately uniform, but could be extended to use a non-uniform DFT when chirp spacing is non-uniform. Fig. 3.6b shows the phases of \mathbf{p}_{corr} derived from the same \mathbf{p} shown in Fig. 3.6a with QPSK detection regions overlaid.

3.4 Results

The results shown are from MATLAB simulation. The simulated scenario has one target radar, one spoofing radar, and one point reflector colocated with the target radar. The target radar transmits a frame with a standard time-multiplexed MIMO configuration across 3 transmit and 4 receive antennas. The IF bandwidth is 10 MHz and the target's chirps sweep a bandwidth of 500 MHz in $32\mu\text{s}$. A random binary phase code is applied to each chirp's weighting which repeats each frame. The spoofer radar is equipped with the same antenna elements and RF chains, but

Figure 3.7: The spoofer's range-Doppler processing in the 1st (a) and 12th (b) frames of the tracking stage. The signal is highly spread in range and Doppler in the 1st frame. The Doppler spreading is refined by correcting the chirp slope, timing, and phase code in the 12th frame, producing a clear peak.

Figure 3.8: (a) The width around the peak of the range-Doppler map containing 50 % of the signal power in the range dimension. (b) The width around the peak of the range-Doppler map containing 50 % of the signal power in the Doppler dimension. (c) The RMSE of the chirp slope estimates.

has 8 receive antennas. The radars are placed 50 m apart and have a relative velocity of 14.14 m/s.

Fig. 3.7a and Fig. 3.7b show the range-Doppler map that the spoofer perceives during the tracking stage. In Fig. 3.7a, the spoofer has just finished its identification stage. Due to coarse estimates of the chirp timings and slopes, the power is spread out in range and Doppler. Furthermore, the spoofer's tracker aims to place this signal at a perceived range of 100 m and Doppler of 0 Hz. In Fig. 3.7b, the tracker has shifted the signal to its desired range and refined its individual chirp timing and slope estimates, concentrating the power in range. The tracker has also corrected for its chirp phase estimates, concentrating the power in Doppler. The performance of the tracker can be quantified with three metrics: power concentration in range, power concentration in Doppler, and RMSE of the chirp slope estimates. Fig. 3.8a shows the concentration in range, measured by the width around the peak that contains 50 % of the signal's power. As the chirp timing and slope are refined, this width reduces to near 0.54 m. Fig. 3.8b shows the same analysis for Doppler. No improvement in Doppler spread is seen until frame 12 when the phase estimates are applied, decreasing the spread to near 63 Hz. After frame 12, some fluctuation is seen due to TX-dependent phase shifts from the array manifold as the target radar moves.

3.5 Conclusion

These results demonstrate how an intelligent adversary may successfully identify and track a mmWave FMCW radar using a COTS FMCW radar itself. This adversary does not require any prior knowledge of the target's signal's timing and chirp parameters, making such an attack effective in the real-world where the target's signal is unknown. After the described entrainment, the spoofer may transmit its signal, inducing the target to perceive very precisely controlled spoofed objects. In future analysis, it will be crucial to consider such an adversary when evaluating spoofing countermeasures.

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Chapter 4

Fooling Perception via Location: A Case of Region-of-Interest Attacks on Traffic Light Detection in Autonomous Driving

The perception module is the key to the security of Autonomous Driving systems. It perceives the environment through sensors to help make safe and correct driving decisions on the road. The localization module is usually considered to be independent of the perception module. However, we discover that the correctness of perception output highly depends on localization due to the widely used Region-of-Interest design adopted in perception. Leveraging this insight, we propose an ROI attack and perform a case study in the traffic light detection in Autonomous Driving systems. We evaluate the ROI attack on a production-grade Autonomous Driving system, named Baidu Apollo, under end-to-end simulation environments. We found our attack is able to make the victim a red light runner or cause denial-of-service with a 100% success rate.

This activity was originally reported in [3].

4.1 Introduction

In the automotive industry, a revolution is taking place: the rise of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs). AVs have been demonstrated to lower transportation costs and energy consumption, improve travel convenience and comfort, and reduce traffic accidents and congestion [70]. However, the Autonomous Driving (AD) system, which serves as the “brain” of an AV to make driving decisions, may have vulnerabilities that could lead to severe security threats to road safety. For example, vulnerabilities in the localization module, whose outputs are critical for route planning and navigation, can be exploited by attackers to manipulate the routes of AVs [71]. In fact, attacks on the localization will not only affect AVs’ route planning and navigation but also have direct effects in other modules such as the perception module to cause false detection.

The perception module processes sensor inputs to perceive the surrounding obstacles and traffic lights, which are necessary for planning a safe driving path and making the correct driving decision. Typically, the perception sensors (i.e., camera, LiDAR, radar, ultrasonic sensor) in the AD system [72,73] have wide ranges of views. For example, AVs are usually equipped with high-resolution cameras that are capable of detecting obstacles as far as 100 meters or more [72]. However, in this work, we discover an interesting design consideration, which is common in AD systems, that

enables an attacker to *blind or misguide the perception without tampering the perception sensor inputs themselves*.

The root cause for such a vulnerability is the design of Region-of-Interests (ROIs). ROI is a strategy commonly employed in AD perception that utilizes information from the localization to *narrow* the detection scope in the sensor inputs [72, 73]. It can effectively reduce the computation overhead by running detection algorithms on smaller input dimensions and filter detection noises by preventing ambiguous detection, e.g., when multiple traffic lights exist in the camera view. Despite the benefits in improving the detection efficiency and accuracy, the accuracy of ROI mainly depends on the localization results—a wrong localization would result into a wrong ROI, which in turn causes the perception module to look at a wrong area in the sensor input.

For AD systems, cameras are especially critical for traffic light (TL) detection since they are the only sensors that are able to accurately detect TL colors. Thus, as the first study, we start from the TL detection and leverage the existing GPS spoofing attacks [74, 75] on localization to demonstrate attack consequences of such ROI attacks in an end-to-end AD system. Attack demos showing the end-to-end attack consequences are at <https://sites.google.com/view/roiattack>.

Considering the severity of the attack, we hope this work can bring immediate attention to the AD system developers for more robust ROI designs. In summary, while this work is still work-in-progress, it makes the following contributions:

- We perform the first security analysis on the ROI design in the perception module in AD systems and identify a design-level vulnerability that allows the attacker to fool AD perception using GPS spoofing.
- We design a concrete ROI attack targeting the TL detection in AD perception. Results show that our attack is able to achieve a 100% success rate in causing the victim AV to run red lights or denial-of-service.

4.2 Background

4.2.1 AD Systems and TL Detection

Baidu Apollo overview. Baidu Apollo [72] is a production-grade open-source AD system for Level-4 AVs [76], which has already been deployed for RoboTaxi services in China [77]. It follows a typical Level-4 AD system design, which mainly consists of localization, perception, prediction, planning, and control modules [72]: the localization module localizes the AV on a map; the perception module uses perception sensors to detect obstacles and TLs; the prediction module predicts the future trajectories of the obstacles; the planning module incorporates maps, localization outputs, and predicted obstacle trajectories to calculate a safe driving trajectory; the control module executes the planned trajectory by actuating the steering, throttle, and brake on the AV. In this work, we focus on two of these modules: localization and perception.

The localization module takes inputs from sensors such as GPS and LiDAR to estimate the real-time position of the AV. Depending on the sensor availability, the localization module can be configured in GPS mode or Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) mode [78]. The GPS mode directly takes positioning from GPS, while the MSF mode combines GPS and LiDAR for more accurate and robust positioning. For example, Baidu Apollo, by default, uses MSF in the localization; however, it also provides a GPS mode when there is no LiDAR installed on the AV. Tesla Autopilot, as a Level-2 AD system [76], also do not use LiDARs and thus relies on GPS for localization [79].

Figure 4.1: Projection from world coordinates to image coordinates.

Figure 4.2: Illustration of the ROI in TL detection.

The perception module incorporates sensors such as cameras, radars, LiDARs, and ultrasonic sensors to recognize vehicles and pedestrians surrounding the AV. In addition, it also performs important tasks such as TL detection.

TL detection and ROI design. TL detection is an essential feature for Level-4 AVs. If an AV cannot detect and recognize TLs, it may violate traffic rules resulting in some catastrophic consequences, such as running red lights and causing car accidents. Recently, as Level-2 AV companies aiming to achieve higher level driving autonomy, companies such as Tesla starts to add TL detection into their AD systems [80]. TL detection leverages Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) to detect and classify TLs in the camera images [72, 73]. For example, Baidu Apollo applies two DNNs for TL detection; one for the object detection to recognize the TL object in the image, and the other for the classification to recognize the light color [72].

Since the camera image may contain multiple TLs, it is thus necessary to identify the correct TL for the current intersection. To address this, AD systems commonly adopt an ROI design [72, 73], which projects the current TL in the world coordinates obtained from the High-Definition (HD) map to image coordinates based on the localization outputs (Fig. 4.1). To compensate for any localization or HD map inaccuracies, an ROI area with an empirically determined radius or height/width centered at the projected image coordinates is selected for TL detection. Such an ROI design not only helps prevent ambiguous TL detection but also reduces the computation overhead. Fig. 4.2 show an example of the ROI in Baidu Apollo. As shown, the ROI anchor box is the projected position of the TL. However, due to inaccuracies in localization and HD map, the projected position is not perfectly aligned with the actual TL. Thus, Baidu Apollo defines a larger rectangle as the ROI for TL detection (② in Fig. 4.2). After that, it crops the ROI area from the image and applies DNNs to recognize all TL bounding boxes and their colors in the ROI. Finally, the TL bounding box (③ in Fig. 4.2), which is the closest to the ROI anchor box, is selected as the TL detection result.

4.2.2 GPS spoofing attacks to AD localization

Civilian GPS systems are known to be vulnerable to spoofing attacks due to the lack of signal authentication in the infrastructure. In the spoofing attack, the attacker broadcasts fake satellite signals to the victim GPS receiver to deceive it into resolving false positions specified by the attacker [74]. So far, GPS spoofing has been demonstrated to be feasible on various systems, including smartphones [81], drones [74], and vehicles such as Tesla [79].

The attack capabilities of GPS spoofing are different in GPS-based localization and MSF-based localization. In GPS mode, GPS inputs are the only positioning source for localization, and thus

Figure 4.3: Illustration of the ROI attack for TL detection.

GPS spoofing can directly control the localization outputs in the AD system. In MSF mode, since the positioning from GPS will be fused with LiDAR, GPS spoofing cannot set an arbitrary position in the localization output. Nevertheless, Shen et al. [75] have demonstrated that they can inject a large deviation in the MSF-based localization outputs using GPS spoofing.

4.3 Threat Model and Attack Goal

Threat model. Similar to the threat model used in prior works [75, 81], we assume a car-following model where the attacker launches GPS spoofing attack while tailgating the victim AV. We assume the attacker can arbitrarily manipulate the victim’s localization outputs under GPS spoofing, which is valid for AVs using only GPS for localization, such as Baidu Apollo in GPS mode and Tesla. We also assume the attacker can track the physical position of the victim AV, which is feasible if the attacker’s vehicle is also an AV [75].

Attack goal. The goal of our attack is to influence the position of ROI in the perception module via GPS spoofing, and thus cause the victim AV to detect a wrong TL to run the red light or fail to detect any TLs to stop at the green light (i.e., denial-of-service or DoS).

4.4 Attack Insight and Design

Attack insight. Although from high-level design, the localization and perception modules appear to be independent of each other, the perception module in fact heavily relies on the localization, especially for the ROI logic in TL detection as mentioned in §4.2.1. Since the localization output directly determines the ROI that the TL detection pipeline will be performed on, any errors in the localization would result in a wrong ROI and may cause incorrect TL detection.

Attack design. To perform the ROI attack on TL detection, the attacker launches GPS spoofing when the victim AV is in front of an intersection. When the victim AV drives towards the intersection, a longitudinal error in the localization would naturally have a smaller effect on the ROI position compared to a lateral deviation. Thus, to maximize the effect on the ROI, we design the attack as spoofing a *lateral* distance away from the physical position of the victim AV, e.g., the spoofing distance shown on the Fig. 4.3.

Fig. 4.3 illustrates the ROI attack for TL detection, which is composed of a reconnaissance stage and a spoofing stage. In the reconnaissance stage, the attacker examines the current TL status and determines the best attack parameters to be applied. Depending on the TL status, the

attacker will use different spoofing distances to achieve the desired attack goals. For example, when the TL is red, the attacker needs to spoof a distance such that the ROI includes another green TL in the camera view to cause false detection. Alternatively, if the TL is green, the attacker can simply spoof a distance large enough such that the ROI contains no TLs, which would trigger a safe stop in the planning since the AV knows from the HD map that there is a TL in the front but fails to detect one. In addition, we set an *attack range threshold* for determining the timing to launch the spoofing. If the attacker starts spoofing when the victim is too far or too close to the intersection, the victim might have already been deviated out of the road boundary that prevented it from reaching the intersection or have already detected the correct TL color and committed the correct driving decision. After that, the attacker closely monitors the victim’s position and spoofs the corresponding lateral distance when the victim enters the attack range.

4.5 Evaluation

Experimental setup. Due to the high cost of evaluating self-driving algorithms on real AVs, we follow the common practice for AV testing and perform a simulation-based evaluation, in which we run Baidu Apollo in an industry-grade AV simulator, LGSVL [82]. To facilitate AV simulation, LGSVL provides photo-realistic simulation environments with diverse road structures and a wide range of vehicle models. In our evaluation, we use the Shalun map and Lincoln MKZ vehicle. The Shalun map models a common two-lane road with multiple intersections along the road. We use Lincoln MKZ since it contains the compatible sensor configurations for Baidu Apollo. We simulate our attack on Baidu Apollo version 5.0, which is the latest version fully supported by LGSVL.

To simulate the attack consequences, we create two concrete attack scenarios: *red light detection* and *green light detection*. Specifically, for red light detection, we set the front TL in the first intersection to red and the back TL in the second intersection to green; for green light detection, we set the front TL to green and the back TL to red. We have confirmed that in benign driving, the AV will always correctly detect the front TLs, and make the correct driving decisions, i.e., stop before the intersection or drive through the intersection.

Evaluation metric. In our evaluation, we explore the attack effectiveness of the ROI attack under different attack range thresholds and spoofing distances, aiming to find the parameters that can achieve the highest attack effectiveness. We define a successful attack case as the victim AV mis-detects the front TL and commits the wrong driving decisions, i.e., running the red light or stopping in front of the green light. Since both Baidu Apollo and LGSVL involve random factors such as messaging delays, we calculate a success rate by repeating the simulation for 5 times for each attack parameter.

Attack construction. For the ease of evaluation, we implement the attack logic as an independent module in Baidu Apollo to receive original GPS inputs from LGSVL. If the victim AV is within the attack range threshold, we apply the spoofing distance to the original GPS positions. After that, we publish the spoofed GPS inputs to the localization module.

Results. As mentioned in §4.4, the red light detection scenario has a more restricted spoofing distance requirement since the attacker needs to spoof the GPS such that the ROI covers the back green TL but not the front red TL. Thus, we start by exploring the attack parameters for this scenario. The left figure in Fig. 4.4 shows the attack success rates when using different attack range thresholds, i.e., the distance from the AV to the TL that triggers the attack. During the experiments, a spoofing distance of 3 meters is applied to the victim’s GPS inputs. As shown, the best attack range threshold falls between 24 and 28 meters. When using a small attack range threshold (e.g., 22 meters), the attack fails because the victim is too close to the intersection, and

Figure 4.4: Attack success rates under different attack range thresholds (left) and spoofing distances (right).

it already executed the stop decision based on the TL detection prior to the attack. On the other hand, if the attack range threshold is too large (e.g., over 28 meters), the victim might already be deviated out of road boundary since the AD system is constantly correcting any deviation between the localization and the planned trajectory [75].

The right figure in Fig. 4.4 shows the attack success rates when using different spoofing distances. Based on the previous experiments on the attack range threshold, we launch the attack when the victim AV is 26 meters away from the TL. As shown in Fig. 4.4, a spoofing distance of smaller than or equal to 2 meters is too small to move the red TL out of the ROI, so the victim can still detect it. On the other hand, when the spoofing distance is larger than 4.5 meters, both front and back TLs are moved out of the ROI, causing the victim to fail to detect any TL and simply stop in front of the intersection. When the spoofing distance is 3–4.5 meters, the attack success rate is at least 80%, where the front red TL is moved out of the ROI, but the back green TL is still in and thus detected by the victim AV, causing it to continue driving forward to run the red light. In particular, a 100% attack success rate is achieved when using a spoofing distance of 3 meters.

In the green light detection scenario, instead of controlling the ROI to be at a particular position, the attacker can simply spoof the ROI to the area without any TLs. In such a case, the TL detector will report “unknown” as no TLs exist in the ROI. Consequently, the planning module in the AD system issues a stop decision conservatively. This results in a DoS attack since the victim stops at the green TL. Similarly, we evaluate this scenario and found that our ROI attack can achieve a 100% success rate when using a spoofing distance of 5 meters.

Attack demos. We create two attack demos to illustrate the severe consequences of the ROI attack. Fig. 4.5 and Fig. 4.6 show the snapshots when attacking the red and green light detections, respectively. The left sub-figures show the camera images with the ROI annotations, and the right sub-figures show the corresponding driving decisions in Baidu Apollo. As shown, our attack can successfully fool the victim AV to detect a wrong TL or fail to detect any TLs due to the ROI position shifts caused by GPS spoofing. Such an attack poses great dangers to road safety since it can cause the AV to violate traffic rules and may even lead to car crashing consequences, e.g., when another vehicle fails to yield in time when the victim AV is running the red light. Demo videos with and without attacks are available at <https://sites.google.com/view/roiattack>.

4.6 Related Work, Limitations, and Future Work

Related work. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to attack ROI and TL detection in AD systems. Since TL detection relies on DNNs and camera inputs, thus attacks to these two are direct threats to TL detection. Prior work used physical-world perturbations to fool the DNNs.

Figure 4.5: Snapshot of attacking the red light detection. The green TL at the next intersection is falsely detected by the AV due to the incorrect ROI.

Figure 4.6: Snapshot of attacking the green light detection. The TL detector failed to detect any light in the ROI, causing the victim to stop at the stop line despite the light is green.

For example, Eykholt et al. [83] uses stickers with carefully devised patterns to fool the stop sign detection. However, TLs are not as accessible as stop signs since they are usually installed at a high place and thus it is unclear how the attacker can put the stickers without alerting other drivers and law enforcement. Another line of research explored physical sensor attacks to blind the camera by shooting strong lights to it [84]. However, such attacks cannot cause the victim to be a red light runner and can only lead to denial-of-service. In this work, the ROI attack does not require any physical perturbations to the TLs and can achieve both attack goals.

Limitations and future work. As the first study of ROI attacks in AD perception using GPS spoofing, we start by attacking AD system with a GPS-based localization, where GPS is the only positioning resource. Indeed, for GPS-based localization, it is possible to simply spoof the GPS to a road without any TLs, such that the victim is not in a state where it realizes that it should sense a TL, resulting in red light running. However, this is not the case for MSF-based localization, which is predominantly adopted in today’s Level-4 AVs, since GPS alone can no longer dictate the localization output. Although MSF is considered to be more robust against GPS spoofing, prior work has demonstrated that MSF-based localization can be deviated by as large as 10 meters using GPS spoofing [75]. In the future, we plan to incorporate the MSF attack to improve the practicality of the ROI attack. Another limitation is that we only evaluate the attack on one AD system, i.e., Baidu Apollo [72]. Although Baidu Apollo implements a representative TL ROI design and is already in production, it is necessary to also evaluate on other TL ROI implementations (e.g., Autoware [73]) to show the generality of our attack. We leave this as a future work. Besides, since the attack parameters are highly dependent on factors such as victim’s speed and road shape, more diverse driving scenarios are needed to evaluate the applicability of our attack. In addition, currently the best attack parameters are found via exhaustive search. In the next step, we plan to use the victim AV/TL positions and camera configurations to calculate the best spoofing distances to be applied in different scenarios.

4.7 Conclusion

In this chapter, we perform the first security analysis on perception ROI design and take the TL detection as a case study. We discover that using GPS spoofing can cause the AV to recognize a wrong TL or fail to detect any TLs. Our study shows that strategic GPS spoofing can achieve a 100% success rate to fool TL detection in the AV, leading to red-light running or denial-of-service consequences, which can be detrimental to road safety. The future of AVs is bright, but more security investigations are still needed in the AD systems. We hope our research can bring more attention to the security threats to AVs, improving AD systems for safer AVs for the public.

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Chapter 5

Calibrating the Extrinsic and Intrinsic Parameters of the Inertial and Radar Sensors of a Vehicular Perception System

This chapter documents techniques developed for calibrating inertial sensors and radar units in a ground vehicle sensor suite. Together with the estimate of the center of rotation of a ground vehicle, this calibration enables long-term navigation in GNSS-denied conditions based solely on radar and inertial sensors. We demonstrate as much in real-world tests with a ground vehicle experiencing various levels of GNSS denial in downtown Austin, TX. It is shown that when operating with an industrial-grade MEMS IMU, the proposed system maintains 95th-percentile horizontal position errors below 6 m after 60 s and below 15 m after 300 s of GNSS outages.

This activity was originally reported in [4].

5.1 Background

Proprioceptive sensors such as inertial measurement units (IMUs) continue to operate regardless of external conditions such as GNSS denial. Coupling a Carrier-phase-differential GNSS (CDGNSS) receiver with a tactical-grade inertial sensor, as in [85–88] delivers robust high-accuracy positioning even during the extended signal outages, e.g., in urban or contested radio-frequency interference (RFI) environments, but such systems are exorbitantly expensive. Recent work has shown that 20-cm-accurate (95%) CDGNSS positioning is possible at low cost even in dense urban areas, but solution availability remains below 90%, with occasional long gaps between high-accuracy solutions [89]. Moreover, the global trend of increasing radio interference in the GNSS bands, whether accidental or deliberate [90], underscores the need for low-cost GNSS-independent localization.

Consider IMU-based dead reckoning for ground vehicles during periods of GNSS unavailability. Drift in position and orientation (collectively pose) is affected by a multitude of factors, including (1) IMU quality, (2) accuracy of accelerometer and gyro bias offline calibration and online estimation, and (3) calibration of other IMU extrinsic and intrinsic parameters such as lever arm, vehicle-body-to-IMU orientation, and scale factor errors.

Even when all significant extrinsic and intrinsic parameters have been accurately calibrated, IMU-derived pose will drift due to accelerometer and gyroscope white noise, as well as the inherent bias instability of the inertial sensors. Accelerometer biases are doubly integrated, yielding

quadratic growth in position error, and gyro biases are singly integrated, yielding quasi-linear growth. Attitude errors exacerbate position drift as gravitational acceleration leaks into the body horizontal axes. In fact, attitude errors are the dominant cause of long-term position drift [91].

In previous work we documented our success with kinematic motion model constraints. In particular, we showed that when a vehicle’s center of rotation is accurately estimated, a zero-sideslip constraint can be applied to effectively curtail IMU drift.

In this report we focus on calibration of the IMU and radar sensors.

5.2 Measurement Models & Calibration

This section details the measurement models for the various measurements applied to the error-state EKF, along with the calibration procedures necessary for the application of these measurements.

5.2.1 Inertial Measurements

IMUs measure the specific force and angular rate experienced by \mathbf{b} relative to an inertial frame. If the centripetal force due to earth’s rotation is absorbed in $\mathbf{g}^{\mathbf{n}}$, then the accelerometer and gyroscope measurements $\mathbf{z}_{a,k}^{\mathbf{b}}$ and $\mathbf{z}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}}$, respectively, are modeled as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{z}_{a,k}^{\mathbf{b}} &= R_k^{\mathbf{bn}} (\mathbf{a}_k^{\mathbf{n}} - \mathbf{g}^{\mathbf{n}}) + \mathbf{b}_{a,k}^{\mathbf{b}} + \mathbf{w}_{a,k}^{\mathbf{b}} \\ \mathbf{z}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}} &= \boldsymbol{\omega}_k^{\mathbf{b}} + R_k^{\mathbf{bn}} \boldsymbol{\omega}_e^{\mathbf{n}} + \mathbf{b}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}} + \mathbf{w}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}}\end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{a}_k^{\mathbf{n}}$ is the true acceleration of the IMU in the \mathbf{n} frame, which double-integrates to position deviation, and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_k^{\mathbf{b}}$ is the true angular rate of the IMU in the \mathbf{n} frame, which integrates to orientation deviation. For low-quality IMUs, accelerometer and gyroscope scale factors may also need to be modeled. For the MEMS IMU used in this work, it was observed that modeling the scale factors did not yield any performance benefit.

The stochastic models for IMU white noise and random walk process are derived from the IMU specifications. In addition to such intrinsic calibration, extrinsic calibration of the IMU with respect to \mathbf{s} is necessary for the application of other measurements expressed in \mathbf{s} . The vector $\mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{sb}}^{\mathbf{s}}$ from \mathbf{s} to \mathbf{b} is taken to be known from the mechanical specification since this is not strongly observable from the available measurements. It is, however, important to estimate any deviations from the mechanically specified orientation $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^{\mathbf{sb}}$ between \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{s} , since even sub-degree errors in the IMU orientation relative to \mathbf{s} may lead to substantial errors when multiplied with the lever arm to another sensor.

The orientation deviation of $\bar{\mathbf{q}}^{\mathbf{sb}}$ from truth, denoted $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\mathbf{sb}}^{\mathbf{s}}$, can be effectively estimated when CDGNSS measurements from multiple antennas are available to the EKF. For this, the EKF state vector $\delta \mathbf{x}_k$ is augmented with $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\mathbf{sb}}^{\mathbf{s}}$. Moreover, three scale factor parameters each for the accelerometer and the gyroscope are calibrated. Together with the orientation deviation, this full calibration procedure extends the EKF state by 9 elements.

This full IMU (intrinsic and extrinsic) calibration procedure is executed only during clear-sky periods during which an accurate CDGNSS fix is available. It must be noted, however, that since the IMU is mounted near the line connecting the Sensorium’s two GNSS antennas, only two of the three elements in $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\mathbf{sb}}^{\mathbf{s}}$ are strongly observable. Any orientation deviation about the vector joining the two antennas is poorly unobservable, and must be constrained by construction. Also note that estimation of $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\mathbf{sb}}^{\mathbf{s}}$ only need be performed once as long as all sensors are rigidly mounted, and may not even be necessary if the mechanical tolerances are acceptably small.

Together with the bias parameters for the accelerometer and gyros, which constitute 6 parameters, a total of $6 + 9 = 15$ state elements are devoted to IMU calibration. The observability of these quantities depends on vehicle motion [92]. In the case of the Sensorium, observability is further strengthened by the attitude information provided by having two RTK solutions to the two topside-mounted GNSS antennas with a known baseline between them. Note that by defining the state such that the position estimated is taken to be that of the IMU, the lever arm vanishes in state propagation, which eliminates the need to measure or estimate the time derivative of the angular rate vector.

Details about the variance and correlation properties of the various noise processes involved in the IMU models above, or their discrete-time versions, together with a mapping from standard IMU parameter values available from data sheets, are found in [93].

5.2.2 CDGNSS Measurements

CDGNSS offers cm-accurate position measurements under all weather conditions, but typically offers reduced solution availability in deep urban environments. This project takes the approach of incorporating CDGNSS measurements in the localization engine, whenever they are available, for periodic or one-time intrinsic and extrinsic calibration of other on-board sensors. During CDGNSS outages, the system relies on these calibrated sensors for accurate odometry.

Signals captured from the two GNSS antennas on the Sensorium are processed together with those from a nearby reference station to provide nearly-independent three-dimensional position measurements of the antennas in the \mathbf{n} frame. The position measurement for antenna \mathbf{a}_i , $i \in \{0, 1\}$ is modeled as

$$\mathbf{z}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}^{\mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{p}_k^{\mathbf{n}} + R_k^{\mathbf{nb}} R^{\mathbf{bs}} \mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{b}\mathbf{a}_i}^{\mathbf{s}} + \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k} \quad (5.1)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}$ is the CDGNSS measurement noise. The vector $\mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{b}\mathbf{a}_i}^{\mathbf{s}}$ from \mathbf{b} to the antenna \mathbf{a}_i , expressed in \mathbf{s} , is available from the mechanical specification. As discussed above, $R^{\mathbf{bs}}$ may be taken to be the same as $\bar{R}^{\mathbf{bs}}$ from the mechanical specification, or may be further calibrated by augmenting the state with $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{b}}^{\mathbf{s}}$.

Additionally, the error-state EKF requires the Jacobian of the measurement model with respect to the error state:

$$H_{\mathbf{a}_i,k} \triangleq \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \delta \mathbf{x}_k} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}=0}} = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_k} \right|_{\substack{\mathbf{x}_k=\mathbf{x}_{\text{nom},k} \\ \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}=0}} \cdot \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_k}{\partial \delta \mathbf{x}_k} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}=0}}$$

The nontrivial sub-blocks of $H_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}$ are documented in Appendix 5.5.

5.2.3 Radar Range Rate & Bearing Measurements

The range rate and bearing measurements from automotive radars provide a valuable velocity constraint for inertial navigation. Importantly, the FMCW signal used in automotive radars provides instantaneous range rate measurements to the detected targets, i.e., target tracking and/or matching across cluttered radar scans is not necessary to obtain and apply this measurement.

The relative velocity of a stationary target with respect to \mathbf{r}_i is given by the negative of the velocity with respect to \mathbf{n} of the i th radar, expressed in \mathbf{r}_i , written $-\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}_i,k}^{\mathbf{r}_i}$, as shown in Fig. 5.1. Assuming that the radar only detects targets in the two-dimensional plane of the linear phased array, the range rate measurement is modeled as

$$\dot{r}_{ij,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \theta_{ij,k} \\ -\cos \theta_{ij,k} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^{\top} R^{\mathbf{r}_i\mathbf{s}} R^{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{b}} \left(R_k^{\mathbf{bn}} \mathbf{v}_k^{\mathbf{n}} + \left(\boldsymbol{\omega}_k^{\mathbf{b}} \times R^{\mathbf{bs}} \mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{b}\mathbf{r}_i}^{\mathbf{s}} \right) \right) \quad (5.2)$$

Figure 5.1: A visual description of the radar range rate measurement model. Quantities labeled in green are measured by the radar. The relative velocity of a stationary target with respect to \mathbf{r}_i is the negative of the velocity with respect to \mathbf{n} of the i th radar, expressed in \mathbf{r}_i , written $-\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}_i}^{\mathbf{r}_i}$. The measured radial velocity \dot{r}_{ij} of the j th stationary target is the projection of $-\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}_i}^{\mathbf{r}_i}$ onto the line-of-sight direction between the i th radar and the j th target.

where the vector $\mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{br}_i}^{\mathbf{s}}$ and the radar orientation $R^{\mathbf{r}_i\mathbf{s}}$ may be taken from the mechanical specifications. Note that unlike typical measurement models where the right-hand side is composed of quantities that are either known or are being estimated, 5.2 has *measured* quantities $\theta_{ij,k}$ on the right-hand side of the equation. This implies that any errors in the bearing measurements will not be accounted for if the range rate measurements are modeled in the EKF as shown.

The application of range rate constraints comes with two major challenges. First, individual radar scans contain a number of spurious targets as discussed in Sec. 5.1. Second, automotive phased-array radars exhibit poor bearing resolution and accuracy, and this is further exacerbated by the unusual range rate measurement model described above. Both of these challenges are addressed by pre-processing the range rate and bearing measurements with a RANSAC routine that estimates a best-fit two-dimensional radar velocity model to the radar measurements. In particular, with N detected targets, the RANSAC operation finds a robust solution to the following system of equations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{r}_{i0} \\ \vdots \\ \dot{r}_{iN} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \theta_{i0} & -\cos \theta_{i0} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \sin \theta_{iN} & -\cos \theta_{iN} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{\mathbf{r}_i}^{\mathbf{r}_i,x} \\ v_{\mathbf{r}_i}^{\mathbf{r}_i,y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.3)$$

while eliminating the $(\dot{r}_{ij}, \theta_{ij})$ pairs that may be outliers. Example results from the RANSAC procedure are shown in Fig. 5.2. Ultimately, the solution to 5.3 is applied as a measurement to the EKF with the following measurement model:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_{\mathbf{r}_i,k}^{\mathbf{r}_i} &\triangleq \begin{bmatrix} v_{\mathbf{r}_i}^{\mathbf{r}_i,x} \\ v_{\mathbf{r}_i}^{\mathbf{r}_i,y} \end{bmatrix}_k \\ &= \left[R^{\mathbf{r}_i\mathbf{s}} R^{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{b}} \left(R_k^{\mathbf{bn}} \mathbf{v}_k^{\mathbf{n}} + \left(\boldsymbol{\omega}_k^{\mathbf{b}} \times R^{\mathbf{bs}} \mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{br}_i}^{\mathbf{s}} \right) \right) \right]_{[0,1]} + \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{r}_i,k} \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5.2: Example results of the RANSAC operation on radar range rate and bearing measurements. The two yellow sinusoidal curves represent the RANSAC-predicted radial velocities for the port and starboard radars from Fig. 5.5 as a function of the bearing. With a threshold of 0.2 m/s, RANSAC considers violet dots as inliers and magenta dots as outliers. Note that the radial velocity magnitude is maximized at -30° and 30° for the port and starboard radars, respectively, in agreement with the mounting angles of these radars on the vehicle.

where the subscript $[0, 1]$ denotes the first two elements of the three-element vector. Parts of the Jacobian of this measurement model with respect to the EKF error-state are documented in Appendix 5.5.

5.2.4 Radar Bearing Calibration

During periods where the CDGNSS system obtains an accurate pose solution for the vehicle, calibration of the radar units can be performed to improve accuracy of feature range, range rate, and azimuth measurement. One source of error that the radars are susceptible to is bearing error, which can arise from mounting angle errors and beam squint in the antenna arrays.

Let $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_p^s = [\hat{v}_x^s \ \hat{v}_y^s \ \hat{\omega}^s]^T$ denote the velocity vector from our pose estimate containing 2D linear velocities (\hat{v}_x^s and \hat{v}_y^s) and angular velocity ($\hat{\omega}^s$). All of these estimates are relative to the \mathbf{s} frame. The covariance of this estimate is Σ_p . For radar i , we model the reported bearing to target j as $\hat{\theta}_{ij} = s_i \theta_{ij} + \tilde{\theta}_i$, where s_i is a scaling factor, $\tilde{\theta}_i$ is the bearing bias, and θ is the true bearing. The scaling factor and bearing bias are our calibration parameters. Radar i 's 2D location relative to \mathbf{s} is $\mathbf{p}_{r_i}^s$, and the 2D rotation matrix to \mathbf{r}_i in \mathbf{s} is $R^{r_i s}$. Let $C^{r_i s} = [-\mathbf{p}_{r_i}^s(1) \ \mathbf{p}_{r_i}^s(0)]^T$ denote the cross product vector associated 2D rotation with 2D translation of point $\mathbf{p}_{r_i}^s$.

The predicted velocity at radar i is given as

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{r_i} = R^{r_i s} [\mathbf{I} \ C^{r_i s}] \hat{\mathbf{v}}_p^s.$$

Now let $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_i$ denote the bearing transform matrix

$$\hat{\mathbf{B}}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \hat{\theta}_{i0} & -\cos \hat{\theta}_{i0} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \sin \hat{\theta}_{iN} & -\cos \hat{\theta}_{iN} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The predicted range rates are then given as

$$\hat{\mathbf{r}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\mathbf{r}_i}.$$

Assume a range rate error with standard deviation σ_r and a measurement error covariance of $\Sigma_r = \sigma_r^2 \mathbf{I}$. The total measurement covariance Σ_i is given by

$$\Sigma_i = \left(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_i R^{r_i s} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & C^{r_i s} \end{bmatrix} \right) \Sigma_p \left(\hat{\mathbf{B}}_i R^{r_i s} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & C^{r_i s} \end{bmatrix} \right)^T + \Sigma_r.$$

The error between measured and predicted range rates is $\mathbf{e}_i = \dot{\mathbf{r}}_i - \hat{\mathbf{r}}_i$. We now use RANSAC on \mathbf{e}_i to reject outliers by fitting the errors. RANSAC fits the errors to a similar model as in 5.3:

$$\begin{bmatrix} e_{i0} \\ \vdots \\ e_{iN} \end{bmatrix} = \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i \begin{bmatrix} v_{\mathbf{r}_i, x} \\ v_{\mathbf{r}_i, y} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Now however, we are not interested in the velocities returned by RANSAC, instead only using the model fit to create a set of inlier bearings and range rates. From now on, all measurement variables and their associated covariance matrices are restricted to the found set of inliers, which will be denoted with a superscript ι . Assume N' inliers were selected. Let our state vector be $\mathbf{x}_i = [\tilde{\theta}_i \quad s_i]^T$. Let $\mathbf{J}_{\tilde{\theta}_i}$ be the Jacobian of $\hat{\mathbf{r}}'_i$ w.r.t. $\tilde{\theta}_i$ and \mathbf{J}_{s_i} be the Jacobian of $\hat{\mathbf{r}}'_i$ w.r.t. s_i . Also let $\nabla \hat{\mathbf{B}}'_i$ be the gradient of $\hat{\mathbf{B}}'_i$ w.r.t. $\hat{\theta}'_i$:

$$\nabla \hat{\mathbf{B}}'_i = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \hat{\theta}'_{i0} & \sin \hat{\theta}'_{i0} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \sin \hat{\theta}'_{iN'} & -\cos \hat{\theta}'_{iN'} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then the Jacobians are given as:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\tilde{\theta}_i} = \nabla \hat{\mathbf{B}}'_i \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\mathbf{r}_i}$$

$$\mathbf{J}_{s_i} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta'_{i0} \\ \vdots \\ \theta'_{iN'} \end{bmatrix} \odot \nabla \hat{\mathbf{B}}'_i \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\mathbf{r}_i}.$$

Stack these into the full Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{J}_{\hat{\theta}_i} \\ \mathbf{J}_{s_i} \end{bmatrix}$. We now perform an iterative bayesian update. Assume we have a covariance \mathbf{P}_i of our current estimate of the parameter vector \mathbf{x}_i . Let superscript (k) denote variables at iteration k . Initialize $\mathbf{x}_i^{(0)} = \mathbf{x}_i$. The update is then given by:

$$\mathbf{P}_i^{(k)} = \mathbf{P}_i - \mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{J}_i^T (\mathbf{J}_i \mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{J}_i^T + \Sigma_i')^{-1} \mathbf{J}_i \mathbf{P}_i$$

$$\mathbf{x}_i^{(k+1)} = \mathbf{x}_i^{(k)} \mathbf{P}_i^{(k)} \mathbf{J}_i^T (\Sigma_i')^{-1} \mathbf{e}_i' - \mathbf{P}_i^{(k)} \mathbf{P}_i^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_i^{(k)} - \mathbf{x}_i^{(0)}).$$

This update is iterated K times. These estimates can be updated again using new data by setting $\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{x}_i^{(K)}$ and $\mathbf{P}_i = \mathbf{P}_i^{(K)}$ and then repeating. In practice, each update is performed using multiple batches of radar returns and pose estimates by vertically stacking the measurements $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_i$, predictions $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_i$, and Jacobians \mathbf{J}_i . The measurement covariances Σ_i' must also be stacked in a block diagonal manner (if we assume temporal independence). When operating with batches of data, the RANSAC fitting uses all measurement errors \mathbf{e}_i together to fit the model and detect outliers. Since this operates on the errors, this outlier detection is robust against periods of acceleration where the ego velocities change significantly over the batching period. Additionally, our pose data and radar data arrive at different rates. The pose data is linearly interpolated to approximate values at the radar data timestamps. The pose data arrives at a higher rate than the radar data, so interpolation is performed over the pose data.

5.3 Experimental Results

The radar-inertial positioning system was evaluated experimentally using the dataset described in [94], collected during approximately 1.5 h of driving on two separate days in and around the urban center of Austin, TX. This section presents the evaluation results.

5.3.1 Dataset

Fig. 5.3 shows the route followed by the sensor-instrumented vehicle on Thursday, May 9, 2019 (in blue) and Sunday, May 12, 2019 (in red). The test route combs through every street in the Austin, TX downtown area, since such environments are the most challenging for CDGNSS-based positioning [89] and would benefit the most from radar-inertial positioning. The route was driven once on a weekday and again on the weekend to evaluate robustness of the proposed system to changes in the traffic and parking patterns.

Sensors

The Sensorium, shown in Figs. 5.4 and 5.5, features two types of automotive radars: one Delphi electronically-scanning radar (ESR) in the middle and two Delphi short-range radars (SRR2s) on the two sides. Both the ESR and the SRR2 are commercially available; similar radars are available on economy-class consumer vehicles. The ESR provides simultaneous sensing in a narrow ($\pm 10^\circ$) long-range (175 m) coverage area and a wider ($\pm 45^\circ$) medium-range (60 m) area. The SRR2 units each have a coverage area of $\pm 75^\circ$ and 80 m (see [95, Fig. 6]). Each SRR2 is installed facing outward from the center-line at an angle of 30° . The Sensorium's onboard computer timestamps and logs the radar returns from the three radar units.

Figure 5.3: Test route through The University of Texas west campus and Austin downtown. These areas are the most challenging for precise GNSS-based positioning and thus would benefit the most from radar-inertial positioning. The route was driven once on a weekday and again on the weekend to evaluate robustness of the system to changes in traffic and parking patterns.

The LORD MicroStrain 3DM-GX5-25 MEMS IMU is an industrial-grade inertial sensor that acts as the core sensor of the localization pipeline. The IMU provides temperature-compensated accelerometer and gyroscope readings at 100 Hz. Two Antcom G8Ant-3A4TNB1 high performance GNSS patch antennas pull in signals from all three GNSS frequency bands and include a 40 dB active low-noise amplifier.

The use of a detachable sensor platform such as the Sensorium is especially challenging since the mounting of the sensors relative to the vehicle changes from run to run.

Ground-Truth Trajectory

The ground-truth position and orientation trajectory for the data are generated with the iXblue ATLANS-C, a high-performance CDGNSS coupled fiber-optic gyroscope INS. The post-processed position solution obtained from the ATLANS-C is decimeter-accurate throughout the dataset.

Dataset Splits

With a limited amount of field data available for development and evaluation, it is critical to ensure that the proposed positioning pipeline does not overfit the design choices and hyper parameters to this particular dataset. Accordingly, the data used in the development of the algorithms were restricted to a fixed 30 min segment from one of the two data collection days. In contrast,

Figure 5.4: The University of Texas Sensorium is an integrated platform for automated and connected vehicle perception research. It includes three automotive radar units, one electronically-scanning radar (ESR) and two short-range radars (SRR2s); stereo visible light cameras; automotive- and industrial-grade IMUs; a dual-antenna, multi-frequency software-defined GNSS receiver; 4G cellular connectivity; and a powerful internal computer. An iXblue ATLANS-C CDGNSS-disciplined INS (not shown) is mounted at the rear of the platform to provide the ground truth trajectory.

during evaluation the full 62 min of data from each day were used. The algorithms have not been modified to maximize the performance over the evaluation dataset.

5.3.2 Offline Calibration

Extrinsic calibration among the IMU frame \mathbf{b} , the Sensorium frame \mathbf{s} , and the vehicle frame \mathbf{v} was performed offline with 125 s of sensor data with CDGNSS availability. While it is possible to estimate the calibration parameters online, it may not be desirable to do so if these parameters are not expected to change over time.

The orientation deviation $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{b}}^{\mathbf{s}}$ between the IMU body frame and the Sensorium frame was calibrated for the localization dataset, as described in Sec. 5.2.1. With two GNSS antennas, only two out of the three DoFs in $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{b}}^{\mathbf{s}}$ are observable. Accordingly, the orientation deviation around \mathbf{b}_x , which is mostly unobservable, was tightly constrained to the initial guess of zero. The deviations around \mathbf{b}_y and \mathbf{b}_z rapidly converged to sub-degree offsets from the mechanical specification.

Extrinsic calibration between \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{s} was similarly estimated over the 125 s period.

The commercial automotive radars on the Sensorium do not offer any mechanism to synchronize their scans with an external reference clock. Analysis of the radar range rate residuals in the EKF showed clear evidence of latency between the data logging timestamp and the true scan times. Accordingly, radar latency calibration was performed offline with a best fit approach.

5.3.3 Implementation Notes

A few implementation- and dataset-specific notes relating to the localization pipeline are documented below.

Figure 5.5: The University of Texas Sensorium mounted on a test vehicle.

CDGNSS Measurements & Outages The CDGNSS position measurements used in this evaluation are in fact the output of the post-processed ground-truth system, i.e., these measurements have not been obtained from an unaided CDGNSS receiver. This is equivalent to assuming a negligible false integer-fixing rate for the CDGNSS receiver. Since the objective of this project is to evaluate the odometry methods during CDGNSS outages, this assumption does not affect the conclusions from this study.

Measurement Noise Correlation Observations from the field data revealed that the measurement noise in the radar range rate measurements is not independent between consecutive radar scans. This is problematic since the EKF applied assumes each measurement to have errors that are uncorrelated in time. Accordingly, the radar range rate measurements were decimated to 1 Hz such that the measurements were spaced out by roughly the decorrelation time of the measurement noise. A more principled approach to this problem is to augment the state vector with states to pre-whiten the measurements. But this approach was empirically observed to not outperform the straightforward measurement decimation, while introducing additional complexity and tuning parameters.

Similarly, the NHC and ZUPT measurements can in theory be applied at every applicable IMU epoch. But to prevent correlated errors in these constraints (e.g., due to sideslip experienced while cornering) from making the EKF inconsistent, they are only applied at 1 Hz.

Filter Tuning Parameters The process noise covariance used in the EKF is derived from the IMU datasheet parameters [91, 96]. The measurement noise covariance associated with CDGNSS measurements is available directly from the ATLANS-C receiver. A few other measurement noise standard deviations and tuning parameters are documented in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: A List of Parameters Involved in the Localization Pipeline

$v_{\text{nhc},x}^{\mathbf{v}}$	(lateral) standard deviation	0.1 m/s
$v_{\text{nhc},z}^{\mathbf{v}}$	(vertical) standard deviation	0.2 m/s

5.3.4 Odometry Results

This section presents empirical error statistics obtained from field evaluation of the proposed system. Three different test scenarios are evaluated in this section, with artificial periodic CDGNSS outages of 10s, 60s, and 300s. A short interval of CDGNSS measurements between consecutive outages brings the EKF estimate close to the true vehicle trajectory.

Figs. 5.6, 5.7, and 5.8 show the east and north position error time histories from the above test scenarios for the May 9 dataset. In each of these figures, the top row shows the position errors for an unconstrained IMU, and the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. For 10s outages, the positioning performance with velocity aiding is only slightly better than unconstrained IMU. For longer outages, as expected, the position errors are much smaller for the cases where velocity constraints are applied. For the case of 60s outages in 5.7, the 95th-percentile horizontal position error is below 6m when all the motion model constraints are applied. For the case of 300s outages in 5.8, the 95th-percentile horizontal position error is below 15m when all the motion-model constraints are applied. Similar results from are obtained from the May 12 dataset (see Figs. 5.10, 5.11, and 5.12).

Fig. 5.9 shows vehicle orientation estimation errors for the 300s scenario. Results for shorter outages are omitted for brevity. As before, the top row shows the orientation errors for an unconstrained IMU, and the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. Heading estimation error, shown in the rightmost panels, is most important for ground vehicle applications. Interestingly, application of velocity constraints does not improve the heading accuracy. This is to be expected since knowledge of the instantaneous velocity in the local body frame provides no information about the absolute vehicle heading (defined relative to earth's north pole). Roll and pitch estimation errors become much smaller with velocity aiding, as compared to the unconstrained IMU case.

5.3.5 Radar Calibration Results

This section presents an example of the radar calibration procedure. Fig. 5.13 shows the estimate of the bearing bias, and Fig. 5.14 shows the estimate of the bearing scaling factor. Each figure has plots for the left, right, and front radar with 95th-percentile confidence regions plotted for each. In these examples, the initial bias estimates were intentionally offset by -5 deg from the coarsely estimated mounting angles. The calibration procedure is able to determine the bias within 1 deg in a single 1s batch and correct for finer biases within each radar as well. The procedure is also able to determine the scaling factor of the reported radar bearings. In the front radar, the estimated scale factor is 0.960, which corresponds to a 1.20 deg error at 30 deg. The left and right radars had less impactful scaling factors of 0.989 and 0.991, corresponding to errors of 0.33 deg and 0.27 deg at 30 deg.

5.4 Conclusion

This project developed and demonstrated a system for curtailing the drift in low-cost IMU-based dead reckoning for ground vehicles by calibrating parameters of the radar and inertial sensors. It has been shown that when operating with an industrial-grade MEMS IMU, the proposed system maintains 95th-percentile horizontal position errors below 6m after 60s and below 15m after 300s of GNSS outages.

Figure 5.6: East and north position error time histories for the May 9 dataset with periodic 10 s CDGNSS outages. The top row of charts shows the position errors for an unconstrained IMU, and the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. The horizontal axis spans one hour of time, with tickmarks spaced by 1000 seconds. With 10 s outages, the positioning performance with velocity aiding is only slightly better than unconstrained IMU performance.

Figure 5.7: East and north position error time histories for the May 9 dataset with periodic 60 s CDGNSS outages. The top row of charts shows the position errors for an unconstrained IMU, the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. The horizontal axis spans one hour of time, with tickmarks spaced by 1000 seconds. For 60 s outages, as expected, the position errors are much smaller for the cases where velocity constraints are applied. Additional radar aiding further improves the positioning performance. With 60 s outages, the 95th-percentile horizontal position error is below 2 m when all the constraints are applied.

Figure 5.8: East and north position error time histories for the May 9 dataset with periodic 300 s CDGNSS outages. The top row of charts shows the position errors for an unconstrained IMU, and the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. The horizontal axis spans one hour of time, with tickmarks spaced by 1000 seconds. For 300 s outages, as expected, the position errors are much smaller for the cases where velocity constraints are applied. With 300 s outages, the 95th-percentile horizontal position error is below 15 m when all vehicle motion constraints are applied.

Figure 5.9: Pitch, roll, and heading error time histories for the May 9 dataset with periodic 300s CDGNSS outages. The top row of charts shows the orientation errors for an unconstrained IMU, and the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. The horizontal axis spans one hour of time, with tickmarks spaced by 1000 seconds. Interestingly, application of velocity constraints does not improve the heading accuracy. This is to be expected since knowledge of the instantaneous velocity in the local body frame provides no information about the absolute vehicle heading (defined relative to earth's north pole). Roll and pitch estimation errors become much smaller with velocity aiding, as compared to the unconstrained IMU case. In particular, pitch estimation further improves with forward velocity measurements provided by the radars. Better estimation of roll and pitch is to be expected since the accelerometer can measure the direction of the gravity vector (vehicle tilt).

Figure 5.10: East and north position error time histories for the May 12 dataset with periodic 10 s CDGNSS outages. The top row of charts shows the position errors for an unconstrained IMU, and the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. The horizontal axis spans one hour of time, with tickmarks spaced by 1000 seconds. With 10 s outages, the positioning performance with velocity aiding is only slightly better than unconstrained IMU performance.

Figure 5.11: East and north position error time histories for the May 12 dataset with periodic 60 s CDGNSS outages. The top row of charts shows the position errors for an unconstrained IMU, and the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. The horizontal axis spans one hour of time, with tickmarks spaced by 1000 seconds. For 60 s outages, as expected, the position errors are much smaller for the cases where velocity constraints are applied. With 60 s outages, the 95th-percentile horizontal position error is below 6 m when the vehicle motion constraints are applied.

Figure 5.12: East and north position error time histories for the May 12 dataset with periodic 300 s CDGNSS outages. The top row of charts shows the position errors for an unconstrained IMU, and the bottom row for an IMU constrained with motion model constraints. The horizontal axis spans one hour of time, with tickmarks spaced by 1000 seconds. For 300 s outages, as expected, the position errors are much smaller for the cases where velocity constraints are applied. With 300 s outages, the 95th-percentile horizontal position error is below 15 m when the vehicle motion constraints are applied.

Figure 5.13: Estimates of the radar bearing bias for the left, right, and front radars over a timespan of 10 s. Radar measurements were batched together in periods of 1 s. Radar returns with a power below -20 dB were discarded due to their low SNR. During each update, 5 iterations were executed. 95th-percentile confidence regions are plotted in black.

Figure 5.14: Estimates of the radar bearing scale for the left, right, and front radars over a timespan of 10 s. Radar measurements were batched together in periods of 1 s. Radar returns with a power below -20 dB were discarded due to their low SNR. During each update, 5 iterations were executed. 95th-percentile confidence regions are plotted in black.

5.5 Appendix: Partial Derivatives

5.5.1 Linearized Forward Dynamics

A few block components of F_k and G_k are listed below.

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\partial \delta \mathbf{p}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}_k^{\mathbf{n}}} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{w}_k=0}} &= -\frac{T^2}{2} \left(\tilde{R}_k^{\mathbf{nb}} \left[\mathbf{z}_{a,k}^{\mathbf{b}} - \tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{a,k}^{\mathbf{b}} \right]_{\times} \right) \\ \left. \frac{\partial \delta \mathbf{p}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \delta \tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{a,k}^{\mathbf{b}}} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{w}_k=0}} &= -\frac{T^2}{2} \tilde{R}_k^{\mathbf{nb}} \end{aligned}$$

The partial derivatives of $\delta \mathbf{v}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{n}}$ with respect to $\delta \mathbf{x}_k$ follow similarly.

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}_k^{\mathbf{n}}} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{w}_k=0}} &\approx I_{3 \times 3} \\ \left. \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \delta \tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}}} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{w}_k=0}} &\approx -T \tilde{R}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{nb}} \mathbf{J}_r \left(\frac{T}{2} \left(\mathbf{z}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}} - \tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}} - \tilde{R}_k^{\mathbf{bn}} \boldsymbol{\omega}_e^{\mathbf{n}} \right) \right) \\ &\approx -T \tilde{R}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{nb}} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\mathbf{J}_r(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = I_{3 \times 3} - \frac{1 - \cos \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|}{\|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|^2} [\boldsymbol{\theta}]_{\times} + \frac{\|\boldsymbol{\theta}\| - \sin \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|}{\|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|^3} [\boldsymbol{\theta}]_{\times}^2$$

is the right Jacobian of $SO(3)$ [97].

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \mathbf{w}_{\omega,k}} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{w}_k=0}} &\approx T \tilde{R}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{nb}} \mathbf{J}_r \left(\frac{T}{2} \left(\mathbf{z}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}} - \tilde{\mathbf{b}}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}} - \tilde{R}_k^{\mathbf{bn}} \boldsymbol{\omega}_e^{\mathbf{n}} \right) \right) \\ &\approx T \tilde{R}_{k+1}^{\mathbf{nb}} \end{aligned}$$

5.5.2 Linearized Measurement Models

The partial derivative of the measurement $\mathbf{z}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}^{\mathbf{n}}$ from (5.1) can be expressed as

$$\left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \delta \mathbf{x}_k} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}=0}} = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}_k} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}=0}} \cdot \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_k}{\partial \delta \mathbf{x}_k} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}=0}}$$

where the non-trivial block matrices are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}^{\mathbf{n}}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{nb}}} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}=0}} &= \frac{\partial (\mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{nb}} \odot R^{\mathbf{bs}} \mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{b}\mathbf{a}_i}^{\mathbf{s}} \odot \mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{bn}})}{\partial \mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{nb}}} \\ \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{nb}}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}_k^{\mathbf{n}}} \right|_{\substack{\delta \mathbf{x}_k=0 \\ \mathbf{e}_{\mathbf{a}_i,k}=0}} &= \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} -q_x & -q_y & -q_z \\ q_w & q_z & -q_y \\ -q_z & q_w & q_x \\ q_y & -q_x & q_w \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

with $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}_k^{\mathbf{nb}} = [q_w, q_x, q_y, q_z]$. The expression for derivative of the rotation with respect to the quaternion can be found in [97, Sec. 4.3.2].

For the radar range rate measurement $z_{\mathbf{r}_i,k}^{\mathbf{r}_i}$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial z_{\mathbf{r}_i,k}^{\mathbf{r}_i}}{\partial \mathbf{v}_k^{\mathbf{n}}} &= R^{\mathbf{r}_i\mathbf{s}} R^{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{b}} \tilde{R}_k^{\mathbf{b}\mathbf{n}} \\ \frac{\partial z_{\mathbf{r}_i,k}^{\mathbf{r}_i}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{n}\mathbf{b}}} &= R^{\mathbf{r}_i\mathbf{s}} R^{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{b}} \frac{\partial (\mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{b}\mathbf{n}} \odot \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_k^{\mathbf{n}} \odot \mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{n}\mathbf{b}})}{\partial \mathbf{q}_k^{\mathbf{n}\mathbf{b}}} \\ \frac{\partial z_{\mathbf{r}_i,k}^{\mathbf{r}_i}}{\partial \mathbf{b}_{\omega,k}^{\mathbf{b}}} &= -R^{\mathbf{r}_i\mathbf{s}} R^{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{b}} \left[R^{\mathbf{b}\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{p}_{\mathbf{b}\mathbf{r}_i}^{\mathbf{s}} \right]_{\times}\end{aligned}$$

The partial derivatives of $z_{\mathbf{n}\mathbf{h}\mathbf{c},k}^{\mathbf{v}}$ and $z_{\mathbf{z}\mathbf{u}\mathbf{p}\mathbf{t},k}^{\mathbf{v}}$ follow similarly.

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Chapter 6

Low-Cost Inertial Aiding for Deep-Urban Tightly-Coupled Multi-Antenna Precise GNSS

A vehicular position and attitude estimation technique is presented that tightly couples multi-antenna carrier-phase differential GNSS (CDGNSS) with a low-cost MEMS inertial sensor and vehicle dynamics constraints. This chapter describes our effort that is the first to explore the use of consumer-grade inertial sensors for tightly-coupled urban CDGNSS, and first to explore the tightly-coupled combination of multi-antenna CDGNSS and inertial sensing (of any quality) for urban navigation. The multi-antenna CDGNSS measurement update is linearized via an unscented transform, allowing all baselines' integer ambiguities to be resolved using traditional integer least squares while both implicitly enforcing known-baseline-length constraints and optimally exploiting the correlations inherent to the multi-baseline problem. State propagation is driven by inertial measurements, with vehicle dynamics constraints applied as pseudo-measurements. A novel false fix detection and recovery technique is developed to mitigate the effect of conditioning the filter state on incorrect integer fixes. When evaluated on the publicly-available TEX-CUP urban positioning dataset, the proposed technique achieves, with consumer- and industrial-grade inertial sensors, respectively, a 96.6% and 97.5% integer fix availability, and 12.0 cm and 10.1 cm overall (fix and float) 95th percentile horizontal positioning error over more than 2 hours of driving in the urban core of Austin, Texas.

This activity was originally reported in [5].

6.1 Introduction

The rise of connected and automated vehicles has created a need for robust globally-referenced positioning with lane-level (e.g., sub-30-cm) accuracy [98]. Much automated ground vehicle (AGV) research focuses on use of LIDAR and cameras for navigation, but these sensing modalities often perform poorly in low illumination conditions or during adverse weather such as heavy fog or snowy white-out. By contrast, positioning techniques based on radio waves, such as automotive radar or GNSS, are robust to poor weather and lighting conditions [99]. Recent work has found that fusing measurements from low-cost automotive radars with inertial sensing can provide lane-level accuracy in urban environments [99]. But radar-based positioning in a global coordinate frame requires the production and maintenance of radar maps, which is a time-consuming and costly endeavor.

GNSS signals provide a source of high-accuracy all-weather absolute positioning that does not

require expensive investment in systems for map production, storage, maintenance, and dissemination. If the so-called integer ambiguities associated with the carrier phase measurements can be correctly resolved, carrier-phase based GNSS positioning offers exquisite accuracy. However, GNSS signal blockage, diffraction, and multipath effects make this family of techniques extremely challenging to use in urban areas. Carrier-phase differential GNSS (CDGNSS), whose real-time variant for mobile platforms is commonly known as real-time kinematic (RTK) GNSS, is a centimeter-accurate positioning technique that differences a receiver’s GNSS observables with those from a nearby fixed reference station to eliminate most sources of measurement error [100, Sec. 26.3]. Previous work by Humphreys et al. probed the limits of unaided CDGNSS in the deep urban environment, and found that the combination of a GNSS measurement engine optimized for urban positioning and robust estimation techniques for outlier exclusion make CDGNSS feasible in the deep urban environment [89]. But the unaided CDGNSS system described in [89] suffers from availability gaps of up to 90 seconds in duration, making it insufficient to serve as the sole navigation sensor for an AGV.

A natural method to bridge such availability gaps is to incorporate measurements from an inertial measurement unit (IMU). These measurements are uniquely valuable due to their invulnerability to environmental effects such as radio interference and weather. Combined GNSS and inertial navigation systems that incorporate only GNSS position solutions as measurements for a downstream navigation filter are termed *loosely coupled*, whereas *tightly coupled* systems directly incorporate raw GNSS observables (pseudorange, Doppler, or carrier phase) [100, Sec. 28.8]. While both loosely- and tightly-coupled aiding can bridge availability gaps, tightly-coupled aiding additionally reduces these gaps’ frequency and duration: the inertial sensor provides probabilistic constraints between GNSS measurement epochs that increase the success rate of carrier phase integer ambiguity resolution. These constraints additionally make the navigation solution observable with fewer GNSS measurements.

AGV navigation filter performance can be further improved by tightly coupling with so-called vehicle dynamics constraints (VDCs). One such technique exploits the natural motion constraints of four-wheeled ground vehicles, commonly referred to as non-holonomic constraints (NHCs). A second VDC technique infers a lack of vehicle motion by monitoring, for example, wheel odometry ticks, or by detecting a lack of road vibration. This constraint is then enforced as a strong zero-velocity pseudo-measurement, called a zero velocity update (ZUPT) in the literature.

This work extends the navigation filter component of the CDGNSS system described in [89] by tightly coupling with an inertial sensor and with vehicle dynamics constraints, and by incorporating measurements from multiple vehicle-mounted GNSS antennas. It also develops a novel robust estimation technique to mitigate the effects of multipath and allow graceful recovery from incorrect integer fixes.

6.1.1 Related work

This subsection reviews relevant existing literature on urban GNSS positioning, inertial aiding, vehicle motion constraints, and multi-antenna CDGNSS.

Unaided urban CDGNSS

Performance of CDGNSS unaided by inertial sensing in urban environments has historically been poor. Experiments in [101] suffered from poor availability (<60%) and large positioning errors (>9m RMS) in suburban and urban environments. A 2018 assessment of commercial CDGNSS receivers found that no low-cost solution offered greater than 35% fixed-integer solution availability

in urban environments [102]. Li et al. [103] achieved a 76.7% unaided correct integer fixing rate in urban Wuhan, China using dual-frequency CDGNSS with a professional-grade receiver. In 2019, Humphreys et al. [89] achieved an unaided correct integer fix rate of 84.8% in the urban core of Austin, Texas.

Inertial aiding

Tightly-coupled inertial aiding has long been employed as a method to increase CDGNSS solution availability and robustness. Early systems built around highly-accurate but expensive tactical-grade IMUs were capable of providing robust positioning in dense urban areas [85–88]. The recent emergence of inexpensive consumer- and industrial-grade micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS) inertial sensors has led to a new chapter of research in low-cost inertial aiding for urban CDGNSS.

In 2018, Li et al. [103] demonstrated that tight coupling of single-antenna professional-grade GNSS measurements with an industrial-grade MEMS IMU increased the integer fix availability of single-frequency CDGNSS from 44.7% to 86.1% on a test route in urban Wuhan, China. However, the authors did not provide the GNSS dataset, information on the incorrect integer fix rate, or a full error distribution, making these results difficult to assess.

This work, in contrast, is the first to demonstrate an increased CDGNSS integer fix rate in an urban environment via tightly coupling with a *consumer-grade* inertial sensor. Furthermore, it incorporates vehicle dynamics constraints and multiple vehicular GNSS baselines. The system’s performance is evaluated on a publicly-available urban positioning dataset, allowing for head-to-head comparison of techniques by the urban positioning research community.

Tightly-coupled urban PPP

One disadvantage of CDGNSS is that it requires observations from a nearby base station to eliminate modeling errors (e.g., for atmospheric delays or satellite clocks and orbits) common to both the base station (the reference) and the vehicle (the rover). Short-baseline CDGNSS, which offers the greatest robustness against urban multipath [104], is limited to reference-rover baseline lengths below approximately 10 km [105]. To avoid the requirement for a nearby base station, attention has recently focused on extending precise point positioning (PPP), which is based on precise orbit, clock, and atmospheric corrections, to urban areas by tightly coupling with inertial sensors.

Rabbou et al. in 2015 explored tight coupling of PPP with a tactical-grade inertial sensor in mostly open-sky conditions with simulated GNSS outages, achieving centimeter accuracy [106]. References [107] and [108] extended tightly-coupled PPP to industrial-grade MEMS inertial sensors in highway and suburban environments. More recently, [109] demonstrated tightly-coupled PPP using both a geodetic-grade and a low-cost GNSS receiver and an industrial-grade MEMS sensor along an urban route in downtown Toronto, Canada, but only achieved meter-level accuracy when using the low-cost GNSS receiver. A drawback of PPP-based positioning is that the aforementioned results all required a roughly 10-minute convergence period before producing an accurate navigation solution. Short-baseline CDGNSS positioning with a modern multi-frequency, multi-constellation receiver, by contrast, typically yields instantaneous initialization.

Vehicle dynamics constraints

Recent research has also explored the tight coupling of CDGNSS measurements with vehicle dynamics constraints. Nagai et al. [110] found in a simulation study using a realistic 3D map of an urban environment that a tightly-coupled CDGNSS system using GPS only could feasibly provide

high-integrity decimeter-level positioning when aided with vehicle-dynamics constraints, a tactical-grade IMU, and odometry based on wheel-speed sensors. Yang et al. in [111] tightly coupled single-antenna CDGNSS with non-holonomic constraints and a tactical-grade fiber-optic IMU, but only evaluated their system under open-sky GNSS conditions with simulated GNSS degradations.

Multi-antenna CDGNSS

Use of multiple GNSS antennas on the vehicle for CDGNSS offers four advantages. First, the full six-degree-of-freedom vehicle pose (position and orientation) becomes instantaneously observable when CDGNSS measurements are combined with the gravity vector as measured by an inertial sensor. With a single GNSS antenna, the vehicle yaw is observable only over multiple epochs, and only if the vehicle accelerates during the observations [92]. Second, the shared reference antenna creates redundancy in the measurement model that allows better ambiguity resolution performance than any CDGNSS baseline taken individually [112]. Third, the additional set of GNSS measurements at the second antenna provides reduced position estimation error. Fourth, a highly effective method for GNSS spoofing detection, the multi-antenna defense [113], can readily be implemented.

Multi-antenna GNSS has long been used for attitude determination applications with snapshot estimation methods such as C-LAMBDA [114] and MC-LAMBDA [115], which provide globally-optimal single-epoch maximum-likelihood solutions to the full nonlinear GNSS attitude determination problem, and have been successfully extended to the pose estimation case [116]. Other work has incorporated special cases of *a priori* attitude information into the nonlinear solution process [117]. These snapshot methods, however, are computationally demanding, and their extension to recursive estimation for tight coupling with other sensors is not straightforward and remains unexplored.

Fan et al. [118] found that a hard constraint using an *a priori* known vehicle attitude to combine CDGNSS observations from multiple vehicle antennas can increase ambiguity resolution and urban CDGNSS performance. However, this method requires a highly-accurate independent source of attitude information, such as from an expensive gyrocompass-capable tactical-grade IMU following an initial static alignment period.

Medina et al. [112] proposed pose estimation based on multiple vehicle antennas for inland waterway navigation. This work sidestepped the complexity of C-LAMBDA or MC-LAMBDA by linearizing the attitude model in an extended Kalman filter (EKF) update and propagating the state with a simple motion model. This formulation was found to increase ambiguity resolution performance over either the positioning or attitude determination problems taken independently. However, the authors made no attempt to incorporate an inertial sensor or additional motion constraints.

Hirokawa et al. [119] developed a multi-antenna GNSS system for aircraft pose estimation that tightly coupled with a MEMS inertial sensor, but only used CDGNSS for attitude measurements, relying on standard pseudorange measurements for the estimator's position component.

Henkel et al. [120] tightly coupled triple-antenna CDGNSS with an industrial-grade inertial sensor for a micro air vehicle navigation application, but only evaluated the system's performance over a single, short test flight in open-sky conditions, and did not compare against a "ground truth" reference.

Previous work [121, 122] by this chapter's authors explored a suboptimal "federated filtering" approach to the tightly-coupled multi-antenna CDGNSS + inertial problem, additionally incorporating monocular vision measurements in [121]. But the approach did not properly model the multi-antenna CDGNSS measurement update, instead resolving the position and attitude baselines

separately.

6.1.2 Contributions

This work makes five contributions:

1. An estimation technique that tightly couples multi-antenna CDGNSS with vehicle dynamics constraints and inertial measurements. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this work is the first in the open literature to explore the tightly-coupled combination of multi-antenna CDGNSS and inertial sensing for navigation in urban environments. Furthermore, it is the first to explore the use of *consumer-grade* inertial sensors for tightly-coupled deep urban CDGNSS (Sections 6.3 and 6.4).
2. A novel application of the unscented transform for the multi-baseline CDGNSS integer ambiguity resolution and measurement update step, which widens the operating regime of the filter to allow significantly greater attitude uncertainty without suffering from the excessive integer least squares (ILS) failures seen by existing EKF approaches (Section 6.3).
3. A novel false fix detection and recovery technique that limits the degree to which an incorrectly-resolved integer ambiguity can corrupt the tightly-coupled CDGNSS estimator's state (Section 6.4.4).
4. Demonstration of state-of-the-art deep urban CDGNSS performance, achieving, by tightly coupling with consumer-grade and industrial-grade inertial sensors, respectively, a 96.6% and 97.5% integer fix availability, and 12.0 cm and 10.1 cm overall (fix and float) 95th percentile horizontal positioning error on the publicly-available TEX-CUP urban positioning dataset [94] (Sections 6.5.1 to 6.5.3).
5. A detailed evaluation and breakdown of the positioning and ambiguity resolution performance contribution of various sensors and algorithmic components (Section 6.5.5).

6.2 Coordinate and Notation Conventions

6.2.1 Vector notation, sensor platform, and coordinate frames

Superscripts indicate the coordinate frames associated with vectors and rotation matrices. For example, $\mathbf{r}^{\mathbf{w}}$ denotes a vector \mathbf{r} expressed in the \mathbf{w} frame, and $\mathbf{R}^{\mathbf{wb}}$ denotes a rotation matrix that converts vectors from their representation in the \mathbf{b} frame to their representation in the \mathbf{w} frame, i.e., $\mathbf{r}^{\mathbf{w}} = \mathbf{R}^{\mathbf{wb}}\mathbf{r}^{\mathbf{b}}$.

The sensor platform described in this chapter and used in the evaluation in Section 6.5 is the University of Texas *Sensorium* [94], a roof-mounted vehicular perception platform incorporating multiple grades of inertial sensor, two GNSS antennas (denoted *primary* and *secondary*), stereo cameras, and three automotive radars. Only the inertial sensors and GNSS antennas are used in this work.

Several coordinate frames are referenced in this chapter:

- u:** The *IMU frame* is centered at and aligned with the IMU accelerometer triad.
- b:** The *body frame* has its origin at the phase center of the Sensorium's primary GNSS antenna. Its x axis points towards the phase center of the secondary antenna, its y axis is aligned with the boresight vector of the primary antenna, and its z axis completes the right-handed triad.

- v**: The *vehicle frame* is a body-fixed frame, centered at the vehicle's center of rotation as determined by an offline calibration using GNSS and IMU data. Its x axis points in the direction of vehicle travel with no steering angle deflection, its z axis points upwards, and its y axis completes the right-handed triad.
- w**: The *world frame* is a fixed geographic East-North-Up (ENU) frame, with its origin at the phase center of the reference GNSS antenna, which is located at a fixed base station with known coordinates.

Fig. 6.1 shows the relationships between these frames.

Figure 6.1: Diagram of relevant University of Texas Sensorium coordinate frames.

6.2.2 State representation and error-state filtering

The tightly-coupled navigation estimator described in this work is an unscented Kalman filter (UKF) that recursively fuses inertial measurements, double-difference GNSS pseudorange and carrier phase measurements, and vehicle dynamics pseudo-measurements. The estimator's state at epoch k is given by the ordered set

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \left(\mathbf{r}_k^{\mathbf{w}}, \mathbf{v}_k^{\mathbf{w}}, \mathbf{R}_k^{\mathbf{wb}}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{a}k}^{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{g}k}^{\mathbf{u}} \right)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_k^{\mathbf{w}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the position of the \mathbf{u} frame origin in the \mathbf{w} frame; $\mathbf{v}_k^{\mathbf{w}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the velocity of the \mathbf{u} frame origin relative to the \mathbf{w} frame, expressed in the \mathbf{w} frame; $\mathbf{R}_k^{\mathbf{wb}} \in \text{SO}(3)$ is the attitude of the \mathbf{b} frame relative to the \mathbf{w} frame; and $\mathbf{b}_{\text{a}k}^{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{g}k}^{\mathbf{u}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the IMU's accelerometer and gyro biases, respectively.

This chapter adopts the conventions and notation of Solá et al. [123], which appeals to Lie theory to unify and generalize various error-state filtering methods so that the filtering equations

are agnostic to the specific choice of attitude parameterization. The filter state \mathbf{x}_k is a point on the composite manifold $\mathcal{X} \triangleq \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3 \times \text{SO}(3) \times \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3$, which has $N_x = 15$ independent degrees of freedom. A state increment $\delta\mathbf{x}_k$ is defined on the tangent space of \mathcal{X} at \mathbf{x}_k , which can be parameterized with the vector space \mathbb{R}^{N_x} . These spaces are related using the operators $\oplus : \mathcal{X} \times \mathbb{R}^{N_x} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ and $\ominus : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$, which correspond to standard addition and subtraction for vector-valued components of \mathbf{x}_k and to more complex operations for the attitude component:

$$\mathbf{x}_k \oplus \delta\mathbf{x}_k \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_k^{\mathbf{w}} + \delta\mathbf{r}_k^{\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{v}_k^{\mathbf{w}} + \delta\mathbf{v}_k^{\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{R}_k^{\mathbf{wb}} \circ \text{Exp}(\delta\mathbf{R}_k^{\mathbf{wb}}) \\ \mathbf{b}_{ak}^{\mathbf{u}} + \delta\mathbf{b}_{ak}^{\mathbf{u}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{gk}^{\mathbf{u}} + \delta\mathbf{b}_{gk}^{\mathbf{u}} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathcal{X}$$

$$\mathbf{x}_k \ominus \mathbf{x}_j \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_k^{\mathbf{w}} - \mathbf{r}_j^{\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{v}_k^{\mathbf{w}} - \mathbf{v}_j^{\mathbf{w}} \\ \text{Log}(\mathbf{R}_k^{\mathbf{wb}} \circ \mathbf{R}_j^{\mathbf{wb}-1}) \\ \mathbf{b}_{ak}^{\mathbf{u}} - \mathbf{b}_{aj}^{\mathbf{u}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{gk}^{\mathbf{u}} - \mathbf{b}_{gj}^{\mathbf{u}} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$$

where \circ denotes rotation composition, $\text{Exp} : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \text{SO}(3)$, and $\text{Log} : \text{SO}(3) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$. With \mathbf{x}_k denoting the true system state at k , the filter's *a priori* estimate is denoted $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k$, with error covariance $\bar{\mathbf{P}}_k$. The *a posteriori* state is $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$, with error covariance $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_k$.

6.3 An Unscented Multi-Baseline CDGNSS Measurement Update

6.3.1 CDGNSS measurement model

At each GNSS measurement epoch, the estimator ingests N_k pairs of double-difference (DD) GNSS observables, each pair composed of a pseudorange and a carrier phase measurement, across all baselines. The baselines and relevant relative position vectors are shown in Fig. 6.2. The measurement vector at epoch k is

$$\mathbf{z}_{gk} \triangleq \left[\boldsymbol{\rho}_{1k}^{\mathbf{T}}, \boldsymbol{\phi}_{1k}^{\mathbf{T}}, \boldsymbol{\rho}_{2k}^{\mathbf{T}}, \boldsymbol{\phi}_{2k}^{\mathbf{T}} \right]^{\mathbf{T}} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N_k}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{mk}$ and $\boldsymbol{\phi}_{mk}$ are vectors of double-difference pseudorange and carrier phase measurements, both in meters, for baseline $m \in \{1, 2\}$ at epoch k . The measurement \mathbf{z}_{gk} is a function of the state \mathbf{x}_k , the integer ambiguity vector $\mathbf{n}_k \in \mathbb{Z}^{N_k}$, and zero-mean white Gaussian measurement noise $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk}$ [124]:

$$\mathbf{z}_{gk} = \mathbf{h}_{gk}(\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}_k), \mathbf{n}_k) + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk}, \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{gk}) \quad (6.1)$$

$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{gk}$ contains off-diagonal elements due to the effect of the shared pivot satellite. The function $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ relates the baseline vectors $\mathbf{b}_{1k}^{\mathbf{w}}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{2k}^{\mathbf{w}}$ shown in Fig. 6.2 to the position and attitude components of the state:

$$\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}_k) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_{1k}^{\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{b}_{2k}^{\mathbf{w}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_k^{\mathbf{w}} + \mathbf{R}_k^{\mathbf{wb}}(\mathbf{r}_p^{\mathbf{b}} - \mathbf{r}_u^{\mathbf{b}}) \\ \mathbf{R}_k^{\mathbf{wb}}(\mathbf{r}_s^{\mathbf{b}} - \mathbf{r}_p^{\mathbf{b}}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.2)$$

Here, $\mathbf{r}_u^{\mathbf{b}}$, $\mathbf{r}_p^{\mathbf{b}}$, and $\mathbf{r}_s^{\mathbf{b}}$ are the body-frame positions of the IMU, primary GNSS antenna, and secondary GNSS antenna, respectively. Under this formulation, the known length of $\mathbf{b}_{2k}^{\mathbf{w}}$ serves

Figure 6.2: Baseline and antenna-to-satellite vectors of the multi-antenna CDGNSS measurement model, for pivot satellite i and non-pivot satellite j . \mathbf{r}_{rik}^w , \mathbf{r}_{rjk}^w , and \mathbf{r}_{snk}^w refer to vectors pointing from the reference, primary, and secondary GNSS antennas, respectively, to the antenna phase center of GNSS satellite n at epoch k .

as an implicit constraint on integer ambiguity resolution due to the parameterization of \mathbf{b}_{2k}^w as a function solely of attitude.

Importantly, the off-diagonal blocks of the measurement noise covariance matrix Σ_{gk} are nonzero because baselines 1 and 2 share a GNSS antenna. By consuming the GNSS measurements for all baselines in a single update, this correlation is exploited and typically yields a higher integer fix success rate than either baseline taken individually [112]. Additionally, the vehicle attitude \mathbf{R}_k^{wb} is often known *a priori* to sub-degree precision, providing a tight constraint on all 3 degrees of freedom of \mathbf{b}_{2k}^w . This constraint both strengthens the combined integer model [118] and increases positioning accuracy, since the off-diagonal blocks of Σ_{gk} encode the sensitivity of GNSS measurements on the secondary vehicle antenna to \mathbf{r}_k^w .

6.3.2 Linearization

The function $\mathbf{h}_{gk}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{n}_k)$ is accurately modeled as linear due to the extreme distance to GNSS satellites relative to the CDGNSS baseline lengths:

$$\mathbf{h}_{gk}(\mathbf{b}(x_k), \mathbf{n}_k) = \begin{bmatrix} \rho_{1k} \\ \phi_{1k} \\ \rho_{2k} \\ \phi_{2k} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{G}_{1k} \mathbf{b}_1^w \\ \mathbf{G}_{1k} \mathbf{b}_1^w + \Lambda_1 \mathbf{n}_{1k} \\ \mathbf{G}_{2k} \mathbf{b}_2^w \\ \mathbf{G}_{2k} \mathbf{b}_2^w + \Lambda_2 \mathbf{n}_{2k} \end{bmatrix}$$

Here, $\mathbf{n}_{mk} \in \mathbb{Z}^{N_{mk}}$ is the vector of carrier-phase integer ambiguities for baseline m , $\mathbf{n}_k = [\mathbf{n}_{1k}^\top, \mathbf{n}_{2k}^\top]^\top$, and $\mathbf{\Lambda}_m$ is a diagonal matrix composed of the wavelengths in meters of each DD carrier phase measurement. The geometry matrix \mathbf{G}_{mk} is defined as

$$\mathbf{G}_{mk} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} (\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ik}^{\mathbf{w}} - \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{1k}^{\mathbf{w}})^\top \\ \vdots \\ (\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ik}^{\mathbf{w}} - \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{N_{mk}k}^{\mathbf{w}})^\top \end{bmatrix}$$

for pivot satellite i and non-pivot satellites 1 to N_{mk} , where $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{jk}^{\mathbf{w}}$ denotes a unit vector in the \mathbf{w} frame directed from a GNSS antenna to GNSS satellite j of baseline m at epoch k . Under the small-angle approximation, these unit vectors are assumed to be approximately equal for all receiver antennas involved:

$$\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ik}^{\mathbf{w}} \approx \frac{\mathbf{r}_{rik}^{\mathbf{w}}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{rik}^{\mathbf{w}}\|} \approx \frac{\mathbf{r}_{pik}^{\mathbf{w}}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{pik}^{\mathbf{w}}\|} \approx \frac{\mathbf{r}_{sik}^{\mathbf{w}}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{sik}^{\mathbf{w}}\|}$$

The nonlinearity of (6.2) due to the manifold structure of vehicle attitude $\mathbf{R}_k^{\mathbf{wb}}$ is nontrivial. Optimal snapshot estimators for the nonlinear GNSS attitude problem, such as C-LAMBDA [114] and MC-LAMBDA [115], have been studied, but these estimators are computationally expensive and their extension to recursive filtering does not seem straightforward. Instead, extant Kalman filtering-based multi-baseline CDGNSS estimators [112, 120] typically linearize the baseline measurement model about the current state estimate with a simple first-order Taylor expansion in order to perform integer ambiguity resolution with a standard ILS solver such as the well-known LAMBDA method [125]. This is essentially an extension of the LC-LAMBDA method described by Teunissen et al. in [126] to the multi-baseline recursive estimation case. As demonstrated in [126], this method performs poorly for ultra-short (length $\lesssim 1\text{m}$) baselines, for which the *a priori* attitude estimate and the pseudorange measurements cannot together offer a sufficiently accurate estimate about which to linearize.

Alternatives

Recursive Bayesian estimation of \mathbf{x}_k requires finding the distribution of $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ given a Gaussian prior for \mathbf{x}_k with mean $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k$ and covariance $\bar{\mathbf{P}}_k$. While the true distribution of $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ is nontrivial, it is desirable to approximate it as Gaussian to enable ambiguity resolution with standard ILS techniques, which are computationally efficient and well understood. Dropping the k subscripts for notational clarity, such an approximation produces a joint Gaussian distribution over \mathbf{x} and $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x})$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x} \\ \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}) \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{x}} \\ \bar{\mathbf{b}} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{P}} & \mathbf{P}_{xb} \\ \mathbf{P}_{xb}^\top & \mathbf{P}_{bb} \end{bmatrix} \right)$$

This can be parameterized in terms of mean $\bar{\mathbf{b}}$, Jacobian \mathbf{H}_b , and additional baseline uncertainty Σ_b^* that accounts for errors due to linearization:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_{bb} &\triangleq \mathbf{H}_b \bar{\mathbf{P}} \mathbf{H}_b^\top + \Sigma_b^* \\ \mathbf{P}_{xb} &\triangleq \bar{\mathbf{P}} \mathbf{H}_b^\top \end{aligned} \tag{6.3}$$

Extant multi-baseline CDGNSS Kalman filters obtain these parameters with a first-order Taylor expansion scheme, which is shown in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 linearizeEKF

Input: $\bar{\mathbf{x}}, \bar{\mathbf{P}}$
Output: $\bar{\mathbf{b}}, \mathbf{H}_b, \Sigma_b^*$

- 1: $\bar{\mathbf{b}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1^w(\bar{\mathbf{x}}) \\ \mathbf{b}_2^w(\bar{\mathbf{x}}) \end{bmatrix}$
 - 2: $\mathbf{H}_b = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}_1^w(\mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}_2^w(\mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \end{bmatrix} \Big|_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}}$
 - 3: $\Sigma_b^* = \mathbf{0}$
-

An alternative approach is to approximate the distribution of $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x})$ using a deterministic sampling technique such as the unscented transform (UT), which is used in the UKF [127]. The UT infers the probability distribution of a transformed Gaussian by transforming a set of weighted “sigma points” through the nonlinearity and evaluating the statistics of the transformed points. The UT implementation used by this work’s CDGNSS measurement update is shown in Algorithm 3.

A simplified 2-dimensional example of the two linearization schemes for a single constrained baseline is shown in Fig. 6.3. The UT yields an approximate Gaussian distribution over the baseline vector that more closely matches the true mean and covariance of $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x})$. For this reason, ILS-based ambiguity resolution has a higher success rate when linearization is based on `linearizeUkf` rather than `linearizeEkf` under large *a priori* attitude uncertainty, as will be demonstrated in Section 6.3.4.

Figure 6.3: Simplified 2-dimensional example of Gaussian distributions produced by `linearizeEkf` and `linearizeUkf` for a single constrained baseline of length 1 m with a Gaussian prior over the attitude angle. The lines represent the cost contours in the position domain associated with each Gaussian distribution at the 3σ likelihood; the \times symbols represent the means. The EKF distribution is infinitely thin, as EKF linearizations only consider baseline vectors on a plane tangent to the true spherical distribution at the *a priori* estimate, causing ILS failures when the *a priori* uncertainty is large enough that the sphere significantly diverges from the tangent plane.

Algorithm 3 linearizeUKF

Input: $\bar{\mathbf{x}}, \bar{\mathbf{P}}$
Output: $\bar{\mathbf{b}}, \mathbf{H}_b, \Sigma_b^*$

- 1: $\alpha = 0.001, \kappa = 0$
- 2: $\lambda = \alpha^2 (N_x + \kappa) - N_x$
- 3: $\mathbf{S} = [\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{N_x}] = \text{chol}(\bar{\mathbf{P}})^\top$
- 4: $\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(0)} = \bar{\mathbf{x}}$
- 5: $\bar{\mathbf{b}}^{(0)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1^w(\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(0)}) \\ \mathbf{b}_2^w(\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(0)}) \end{bmatrix}$
- 6: $w_m^{(0)} = \frac{\lambda}{N_x + \lambda}$
- 7: $w_c^{(0)} = \frac{\lambda}{N_x + \lambda} + 1 - \alpha^2 + \beta$
- 8: **for** $i \in [1, 2N_x]$ **do**
- 9: $\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(i)} = \begin{cases} \bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(0)} \oplus \sqrt{N_x + \lambda} \mathbf{s}_i & i \in [1, N_x] \\ \bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(0)} \oplus -\sqrt{N_x - \lambda} \mathbf{s}_i & i \in [N_x + 1, 2N_x] \end{cases}$
- 10:
- 11: $\bar{\mathbf{b}}^{(i)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1^w(\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(i)}) \\ \mathbf{b}_2^w(\bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(i)}) \end{bmatrix}$
- 12: $w_m^{(i)} = w_c^{(i)} = \frac{1}{2(N_x + \lambda)}$
- 13: **end for**
- 14: $\bar{\mathbf{b}} = \sum_{i=0}^{2N_x} w_m^{(i)} \bar{\mathbf{b}}^{(i)}$
- 15: $\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{xx} & \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{xb} \\ \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{xb}^\top & \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{bb} \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{i=0}^{2N_x} \left(w_c^{(i)} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(i)} \ominus \bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(0)} \\ \bar{\mathbf{b}}^{(i)} - \bar{\mathbf{b}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(i)} \ominus \bar{\mathbf{x}}^{(0)} \\ \bar{\mathbf{b}}^{(i)} - \bar{\mathbf{b}} \end{bmatrix}^\top \right)$
- 16: $\mathbf{H}_b = (\bar{\mathbf{P}}_{xx}^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{xb})^\top$
- 17: $\Sigma_b^* = \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{bb} - (\mathbf{H}_b \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{xx} \mathbf{H}_b^\top)$

UKF measurement update

A vector \mathbf{z}_{gk} of DD GNSS observables is ingested by the estimator at epoch k . Linearizing about the *a priori* state estimate $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k$

$$[\bar{\mathbf{b}}_k, \mathbf{H}_{bk}, \Sigma_{bk}^*] = \text{linearizeUkf}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k, \bar{\mathbf{P}}_k)$$

yields the following approximation of the measurement model for innovations vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{gk} \triangleq \mathbf{z}_{gk} - \mathbf{h}_{gk}(\bar{\mathbf{b}}_k, \mathbf{0})$:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{gk} &= \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{G}_{1k} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{G}_{1k} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{G}_{2k} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{G}_{2k} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{H}_{rk}} \mathbf{H}_{bk} \delta \mathbf{x}_k + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \Lambda_1 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \Lambda_2 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{H}_{nk}} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_{1k} \\ \mathbf{n}_{2k} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{n}_k} \\ &+ \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk}^* \\ &= \mathbf{H}_{rk} \delta \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{H}_{nk} \mathbf{n}_k + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk}^* \\ &\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk}^* \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{H}_{bk} \Sigma_{bk}^* \mathbf{H}_{bk}^\top) \end{aligned}$$

Here the state estimate error vector $\delta \mathbf{x}_k \triangleq \bar{\mathbf{x}}_k \ominus \mathbf{x}_k$ is expressed in the tangent space of \mathcal{X} at $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k$, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{gk}^*$ represents additional measurement error caused by approximation of $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}_k)$.

6.3.3 Square-root formulation

The CDGNSS measurement update can be cast in square-root form for greater numerical robustness and algorithmic clarity [128]. Given $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{gk}$, \mathbf{H}_{rk} , \mathbf{H}_{nk} , $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_k$, and $\bar{\mathbf{P}}_k$, the measurement update can be defined as finding $\delta \mathbf{x}_k$ and \mathbf{n}_k to minimize the cost function

$$J_k(\delta \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{n}_k) = \|\boldsymbol{\nu}_{gk} - \mathbf{H}_{rk} \delta \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{H}_{nk} \mathbf{n}_k\|_{\Sigma_k^{-1}}^2 + \|\delta \mathbf{x}_k\|_{\bar{\mathbf{P}}_k^{-1}}^2$$

where $\Sigma_k = \Sigma_{gk} + \mathbf{H}_b \Sigma_{bk}^* \mathbf{H}_b^\top$. The vector cost components can be normalized by left multiplying with square-root information matrices based on Cholesky factorization $\mathbf{R}_{gk} = \text{chol}(\Sigma_k^{-1})$, $\bar{\mathbf{R}}_{xxk} = \text{chol}(\bar{\mathbf{P}}_k^{-1})$:

$$\begin{aligned} J_k(\delta \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{n}_k) &= \left\| \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{R}_{gk} \boldsymbol{\nu}_{gk} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{R}}_{xxk} \\ \mathbf{R}_{gk} \mathbf{H}_{rk} \end{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{x}_k - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{R}_{gk} \mathbf{H}_{nk} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{n}_k \right\|^2 \\ &= \left\| \boldsymbol{\nu}'_k - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}'_{rk} \\ \mathbf{H}'_{nk} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{x}_k \\ \mathbf{n}_k \end{bmatrix} \right\|^2 \end{aligned}$$

The cost J_k can be decomposed via QR factorization

$$[\mathbf{Q}_k, \mathbf{R}_k] = \text{qr} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}'_{rk} \\ \mathbf{H}'_{nk} \end{bmatrix} \right)$$

where matrix \mathbf{Q}_k is orthogonal and \mathbf{R}_k is upper triangular. Because \mathbf{Q}_k is orthogonal, the components of J_k inside the norm can be left-multiplied by \mathbf{Q}_k^\top without changing the cost, and J_k can be

decomposed into 3 terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_k(\delta \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{n}_k) &= \left\| \mathbf{Q}_k^\top \boldsymbol{\nu}'_k - \mathbf{R}_k \begin{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{x}_k \\ \mathbf{n}_k \end{bmatrix} \right\|^2 \\
 &= \left\| \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}''_{1k} \\ \boldsymbol{\nu}''_{2k} \\ \boldsymbol{\nu}''_{3k} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{xxk} & \mathbf{R}_{xnk} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}_{nnk} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{x}_k \\ \mathbf{n}_k \end{bmatrix} \right\|^2 \\
 &= \underbrace{\left\| \boldsymbol{\nu}''_{1k} - \mathbf{R}_{xxk} \delta \mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{R}_{xnk} \mathbf{n}_k \right\|^2}_{J_{1k}(\delta \mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{n}_k)} + \underbrace{\left\| \boldsymbol{\nu}''_{2k} - \mathbf{R}_{nnk} \mathbf{n}_k \right\|^2}_{J_{2k}(\mathbf{n}_k)} \\
 &\quad + \underbrace{\left\| \boldsymbol{\nu}''_{3k} \right\|^2}_{J_{3k}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.4}$$

If both the measurement model and $\bar{\mathbf{R}}_{xxk}$ are not ill-conditioned, then \mathbf{R}_{xxk} and \mathbf{R}_{nnk} are invertible. J_{3k} is the irreducible cost, and, under a single-epoch ambiguity resolution scheme, can be shown to be equal to the normalized innovations squared (NIS) associated with the double-difference pseudorange measurements. J_{2k} is the extra cost incurred by enforcing the integer constraint on \mathbf{n}_k . If \mathbf{n}_k is allowed to take any real value (the *float solution*), J_{2k} can be zeroed due to the invertibility of \mathbf{R}_{nnk} . Similarly, J_{1k} can be zeroed for any value of \mathbf{n}_k due to the invertibility of \mathbf{R}_{xxk} . The float solution, $\{\delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_k\}$, can therefore be formed by choosing $\delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_k$ to zero J_{1k} and J_{2k} . Because \mathbf{R}_k is upper triangular, these values can be found by efficient backsubstitution. The *fixed solution*, $\{\delta \check{\mathbf{x}}_k, \check{\mathbf{n}}_k\}$, is found via an ILS solver, yielding

$$\begin{aligned}
 \check{\mathbf{n}}_k &= \arg \min_{\mathbf{n}_k \in \mathbb{Z}^n} J_{2k}(\mathbf{n}_k) \\
 \delta \check{\mathbf{x}}_k &= \mathbf{R}_{xxk}^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\nu}''_{1k} - \mathbf{R}_{xnk} \check{\mathbf{n}}_k)
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.5}$$

\mathbf{R}_{xxk} is the *a posteriori* state vector square-root information matrix conditioned on $\mathbf{n}_k = \check{\mathbf{n}}_k$. Therefore, if the fixed solution is accepted (having passed validation via an integer aperture test), the *a posteriori* state and covariance are

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k &= \bar{\mathbf{x}}_k \oplus \delta \check{\mathbf{x}}_k \\
 \hat{\mathbf{P}}_k &= \left(\mathbf{R}_{xxk}^\top \mathbf{R}_{xxk} \right)^{-1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.6}$$

If instead the float solution is accepted, the *a posteriori* state and covariance are found by marginalizing over the distribution of \mathbf{n}_k :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k &= \bar{\mathbf{x}}_k \oplus \delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k \\
 \hat{\mathbf{P}}_k &= (\mathbf{R}_k^\top \mathbf{R}_k)_{[1:N_x, 1:N_x]}^{-1}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.7}$$

Here, $[1 : n, 1 : n]$ denotes taking the first n rows and columns of the matrix.

6.3.4 Evaluation of unscented multi-antenna update

The UKF linearization of $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ yields a Gaussian prior in the position domain that better captures the true mean and covariance of the constrained attitude baseline than the EKF linearization. Consequently, the UKF linearization achieves a higher ILS success rate than the EKF linearization when attitude uncertainty is large.

Fig. 6.4 demonstrates this effect by evaluating integer aperture success, failure, and float rates (note that $P_u = 1 - P_f - P_s$ [129]) for a multi-baseline CDGNSS measurement update via Monte

Figure 6.4: Integer aperture (IA) success (validated correct fix), failure (validated false fix), and float (failed IA validation) rates found via Section 6.3.4’s Monte Carlo simulation of a multi-baseline CDGNSS measurement update with varying *a priori* attitude uncertainty. UKF and EKF denote the ILS success rates for models derived from `linearizeUkf` and `linearizeEkf`, respectively. Linearization error causes the true failure rate P_f of the EKF linearization to greatly exceed \bar{P}_f as the yaw uncertainty increases beyond approximately 8° . In contrast, the integrity of the integer aperture test is maintained for the UKF case due to the approximate linearization error term Σ_b^* provided by the UKF linearization. Note that $P_u = 1 - P_f - P_s$.

Carlo simulation with 10^6 samples. The vehicle pitch and roll angles were assumed to be known to 2° (1σ), and the *a priori* yaw angle uncertainty was varied from 0° to 90° (1σ). The simulation assumed GPS L1 C/A signals visible from the equator with a representative satellite constellation and a 15° elevation mask angle. Two vehicle GNSS antennas were simulated, with a baseline length of 1.0668 m (equivalent to that of the Sensorium). Other GNSS measurement model parameters were selected as in Table 6.3. The threshold function approximation to the fixed-failure rate distance test [130] was used with fixed failure rate $\bar{P}_f = 0.01$.

For a dual-antenna platform similar to that of the University of Texas Sensorium with loose yaw knowledge, this effect becomes apparent as 1σ yaw uncertainty exceeds approximately 8° , whereupon the ILS success rate with the EKF linearization begins a rapid decline with increasing uncertainty, eventually falling below even that of the unconstrained multi-antenna CDGNSS snapshot estimator.

The UKF linearization expands the operating regime of the CDGNSS navigation estimator to greater levels of attitude uncertainty than with the EKF linearization. This effect is relevant for low-cost urban CDGNSS: while even a low-cost accelerometer can provide pitch and roll angles with

degree-level accuracy, it is desirable to tolerate large yaw uncertainty, as may occur, for example, following a long GNSS outage in a parking garage. Upon emerging from such an outage, a system using an EKF linearization may require re-initialization using a snapshot attitude estimator. This scheme also allows initialization of the estimator with loose attitude knowledge, as may be provided, for example, by a magnetometer whose heading measurement may be uncertain in the presence of nearby buildings and vehicles.

6.4 Tightly-Coupled Navigation Filter

This section presents the remaining development of the full tightly-coupled multi-antenna CDGNSS recursive estimator with vehicle dynamics constraints and false integer fix mitigation.

6.4.1 Propagation step

State propagation is based on a model replacement approach in which IMU measurements supplant a vehicle dynamics and kinematics model. This is implemented as a standard UKF time update step, and is described in detail in this chapter's supplemental material.

6.4.2 Vehicle dynamics constraints

This work adopts the VDC scheme of [99] with minor modifications to the NHC sideslip model and ZUPT detection mechanism. Details of the VDC scheme are provided in this chapter's supplemental material.

6.4.3 Outlier rejection using pseudorange innovations

Let $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{\rho k} = [\nu_{\rho k 1}, \dots, \nu_{\rho k n}]^T$ contain the elements of the GNSS innovation vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{gk}$ that correspond to pseudorange measurements. Its covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\nu}_{\rho k}$ is

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{P}}_{\rho\rho k} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{G}_{1k} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \boldsymbol{G}_{2k} \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{P}_{bbk} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{G}_{1k} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \boldsymbol{G}_{2k} \end{bmatrix}^T + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\rho k} \quad (6.8)$$

where \boldsymbol{P}_{bbk} is formed as in (6.3), and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\rho k}$ is formed by selecting the rows and columns of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{gk}$ that correspond to pseudorange measurements. If the estimator is consistent and the pseudorange measurements are not corrupted by large multipath errors, then $\nu_{\rho kn} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, (\bar{\boldsymbol{P}}_{\rho\rho k})_{nn})$. A test can be used to detect outlier pseudorange measurements using the detection statistic

$$q_{kn} = \nu_{\rho k, n}^2 / (\bar{\boldsymbol{P}}_{\rho\rho k})_{nn}$$

with a threshold γ^2 selected to yield a sufficiently low false-positive rate. If a pseudorange outlier is detected for some index n (i.e., $q_{kn} > \gamma^2$), then the corresponding DD pseudorange measurement is assumed to be corrupted by multipath. Because the effect of multipath on GNSS signals is primarily a function of the line-of-sight vector to the transmitter, all pseudorange and carrier phase measurements associated with the offending non-pivot satellite on all frequencies and baselines are assumed to be corrupt. They are removed from the measurement vector \boldsymbol{z}_{gk} before proceeding with the measurement update.

6.4.4 False fix detection and recovery

Single-epoch ambiguity resolution

An optimal CDGNSS filter (in the maximum *a posteriori* sense) must append a new carrier phase integer ambiguity to its state each time a cycle slip is detected in a carrier tracking loop [131]. This causes the update and ILS solve operations to quickly become computationally intractable when applied in an urban environment where cycle slips are common and detection of discrete cycle slips is often impossible.

A scheme could be imagined whereby cycle slips are modeled to occur with some probability P_{CS} at each epoch, and a suboptimal dynamic multiple-model estimator such as the interacting multiple-model or generalized pseudo-Bayesian estimator [132, Sec. 11.6] is used to handle the resulting multiple hypotheses over past cycle slips. However, for large P_{CS} , as is the case for urban CDGNSS, these methods would require measurement update and ILS solve operations for a quickly-growing number of alternate hypotheses. Such a method would be computationally prohibitive without aggressive hypothesis pruning.

This work’s estimator adopts a posture of maximum pessimism regarding cycle slips: each carrier tracking loop in the GNSS receiver is assumed to slip cycles between each pair of measurement epochs (i.e., $P_{CS} = 1$). Ambiguity state growth is curtailed by discarding all ambiguity states at every GNSS measurement epoch, either by *conditioning* the state vector on the candidate fixed solution (if the candidate fix is validated), as in (6.5) and (6.6), or by accepting the float solution and *marginalizing* over the ambiguities, as in (6.7). This single-epoch ambiguity resolution scheme is suboptimal because it discards what continuity may be present in the integer ambiguities from epoch to epoch, weakening the integer model strength. But it renders the navigation filter entirely insensitive to cycle slips, which may be a practical necessity for urban CDGNSS, and is computationally efficient. Moreover, the conditioning operation, when applied, greatly increases the integer model strength for subsequent epochs, allowing the filter to “hold on” to fixes by virtue of the tight epoch-to-epoch position domain constraint provided by the inertial sensor and the vehicle dynamics pseudo-measurements.

False integer fixes

Even in the absence of modeling errors and measurement outliers, the integer fixing procedure of Section 6.3.3 occasionally yields an incorrect integer vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_k$ that passes ambiguity validation tests, a situation referred to as a *false integer fix* or an *ambiguity resolution failure* [129]. This occurs because validation tests can only provide probabilistic guarantees of integer correctness [133]. In an urban environment, measurement outliers due to multipath and diffraction cause the true false integer fix rate P_f to greatly exceed the specified rate \bar{P}_f for the validation test [89]. Thus, conditioning the filter state on fixed and validated integers at each epoch, as is done under a single-epoch ambiguity resolution scheme, is perilous because false integer fixes eventually corrupt the filter state with incorrect but highly confident priors. This causes future GNSS measurement updates to accept a similarly incorrect fix with high probability, repeatedly conditioning the filter state on incorrect ambiguities. While the simple rectilinear motion model of the unaided estimator in [89] contains sufficient process noise that the filter eventually re-fixes to the correct ambiguities, the tight epoch-to-epoch constraints of the present work’s tightly-coupled estimator can cause these cycles of false fixes to persist indefinitely.

To mitigate the effect of conditioning on incorrect integer ambiguities, this work’s estimator employs a fault detection and exclusion technique based on solution separation. A *float-only* filter, configured to never attempt fixing integer ambiguities, is operated in parallel to the primary nav-

igation filter. Under the single-epoch ambiguity resolution scheme, the float-only filter’s behavior is equivalent to accepting only pseudorange measurements, discarding carrier phase measurements entirely.

Carrier phase residuals testing

Recall from (6.4) that $J_{2k}(\mathbf{n}_k)$ is the residual cost associated with the carrier phase in the square-root formulation of the CDGNSS measurement update. When evaluated at $\check{\mathbf{n}}_k$, the fixed solution for the integer vector \mathbf{n}_k found via an ILS solver, this cost becomes the fixed-ambiguity residual cost:

$$\epsilon_{\phi k} = J_{2k}(\check{\mathbf{n}}_k)$$

This quantity is small whenever the carrier phase measurements are consistent with the prior state estimate, the pseudorange measurements, and with the assumption of integer-valued carrier-phase ambiguities. It is one of several acceptance test statistics used to decide whether the fixed solution $\check{\mathbf{n}}_k$ is correct with high probability [100, Sec. 23].

In [134], $\epsilon_{\phi k}$ was incorporated in a statistic used to detect carrier cycle slips. It can similarly be used to detect false integer fixes (as a form of integer aperture test statistic) or the lingering effects of performing the conditioning operation in (6.6) on an incorrectly-fixed integer vector at some epoch in the past. A windowed sum of $\epsilon_{\phi k}$ offers even greater sensitivity to false fix events at the expense of a longer time to detect. The test statistic used to detect false fixes in this work’s estimator is the *windowed fixed-ambiguity residual cost* (WFARC), Ψ_k . This is calculated over a moving window of fixed length l of past GNSS measurement epochs. It has N_{Ψ_k} degrees of freedom and is calculated by

$$\Psi_k \triangleq \sum_{n=k-l+1}^k \epsilon_{\phi n}, \quad N_{\Psi_k} \triangleq \sum_{n=k-l+1}^k N_n$$

where N_k is the number of DD carrier phase measurements at epoch k . If the filter is consistent and the integer ambiguities are correctly resolved, then Ψ_k should be approximately χ^2 -distributed with N_{Ψ_k} degrees of freedom. (This distribution is approximate due to the “integer-folding” effect: large phase residuals are not possible because of integer-cycle phase wrapping.) A statistical consistency test can be performed by choosing a desired false-alarm rate $\bar{P}_{f,\Psi}$ and declaring a false fix if $\Psi_k > \gamma_{\Psi k}$, where the threshold $\gamma_{\Psi k}$ is calculated by evaluating the inverse cumulative distribution function (CDF) of $\chi^2(N_{\Psi_k})$ at $\bar{P}_{f,\Psi}$.

False fix recovery

If a false fix is detected ($\Psi_k > \gamma_{\Psi k}$), the estimator performs a *soft reset*, discarding the primary navigation filter’s state estimate and covariance and replacing them with a copy of the float-only filter’s state and covariance, as shown in Fig. 6.5.

Float-only estimator re-seeding

To increase the probability of a correct fix after a soft reset, the “float-only” filter is occasionally *re-seeded* with the state of the primary filter during epochs over which a set of heuristic criteria indicate that a correct fix is extremely likely. This operation carries the risk that the float-only filter could also be contaminated with information from a false integer fix in the primary filter. But in practice, heuristic criteria can be set to strictly limit this event’s probability. The four criteria used in the next section’s evaluation are given in Table 6.1.

Figure 6.5: A false-fix detection and recovery event. “!” denotes a test failure ($\Psi_k > \gamma_{\Psi_k}$) at $k = 4$. The primary navigation filter’s state estimate and covariance matrix are assumed to be contaminated by false integer fixes at past epochs and are discarded. They are replaced after epoch 4 with the less-certain but uncontaminated state and covariance of the float-only filter.

Figure 6.6: A “re-seed” event. “✓” denotes re-seed criteria being met at epoch 4, indicating very high confidence in the correctness of the primary filter’s integer fix and consistency of its state estimate. The estimator replaces the state estimate and covariance of the float-only filter with a copy of that of the primary navigation filter.

One might argue that these criteria for re-seeding the float-only filter are redundant because an integer aperture test for validating the primary filter’s integer estimate can be made arbitrarily strict, obviating additional validation. But integer aperture theory is founded on modeling measurement error distributions as Gaussian [135], which is a poor approximation in the urban environment, leading to low fixed solution availability [89]. Teunissen’s recent extension of so-called best integer equivariant estimation to the class of elliptically contoured distributions in [136] may offer a means of providing a better re-seed estimate for the float-only filter in urban environments, but it has not been tested with empirical urban data. Meanwhile, application of this work’s re-seeding technique with the criteria in Table 6.1 will be shown in the next section to significantly increase integer fix availability while respecting a low false fix rate.

6.5 Performance Evaluation in a Deep Urban Environment

6.5.1 Experimental setup

The tightly-coupled CDGNSS estimator described in the foregoing sections was implemented in C++ as a new version of the PpEngine sensor fusion engine [89], and was experimentally evaluated against the publicly-available TEX-CUP urban positioning dataset. TEX-CUP comprises raw GNSS intermediate-frequency (IF) samples and inertial data, which were collected on 9 and 12 May, 2019 using the University of Texas *Sensorium* vehicular perception research platform [94]. The dataset consists of a total of over 2 hours of driving in Austin, Texas in conditions ranging from light to dense urban; routes are shown in Fig. 6.7.

Two-bit-quantized IF samples were captured at the Sensorium and at the reference station

Normalized residual	$\frac{\epsilon_{\phi k}}{N_k} \leq 1.0$
Normalized WFARC	$\frac{\Psi_k}{N_{\Psi k}} \leq 0.5$
Last fix number of DD measurements	$N_k \geq 10$
Time since last soft reset	$t_{sr,k} \geq 2.0 \text{ s}$

Table 6.1: Re-seed criteria used in the evaluation of Section 6.5. A re-seed operation is performed if all four conditions are met.

through *RadioLynx*, a low-cost L1+L2 GNSS front end with a 5 MHz bandwidth at each frequency, and were processed with the PpRx software-defined GNSS receiver [89]. The Sensorium RadioLynx was connected to two Antcom G8 GNSS antennas separated by 1.0668 meters in the vehicle Y direction, and the reference RadioLynx was connected to a Trimble Zephyr II geodetic-grade GNSS antenna. The number of double-difference measurements available to PpEngine over the two datasets ranged from 1 to 25, with an average of 11.68.

The system’s performance was separately evaluated using inertial data from each of the Sensorium’s two MEMS inertial sensors. The first, a LORD MicroStrain 3DM-GX5-25, is an industrial-grade sensor. The second, a Bosch BMX055, is a surface-mount consumer-grade sensor. Their relevant datasheet specifications are compared in Table 6.2.

	Industrial Grade	Consumer Grade
	LORD MicroStrain 3DM-GX5-25	Bosch BMX055
Sampling rate	200 Hz	153 Hz
Gyro noise density	$0.005 \text{ }^\circ/\text{s}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$	$0.014 \text{ }^\circ/\text{s}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$
Gyro turn-on bias	$\pm 0.04 \text{ }^\circ/\text{s}$	$\pm 1 \text{ }^\circ/\text{s}$
Gyro in-run bias stability	$8 \text{ }^\circ/\text{hr}$	–
Accel. noise density	$25 \text{ } \mu\text{g}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$	$150 \text{ } \mu\text{g}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$
Accel. turn-on bias	$\pm 2 \text{ mg}$	$\pm 80 \text{ mg}$
Accel in-run bias stability	0.04 mg	–

Table 6.2: Datasheet specifications of inertial sensors used in the performance evaluation. “–” indicates that the parameter is unspecified in the datasheet.

The system’s positioning performance was evaluated by comparing with TEX-CUP’s forward-backward smoothed ground-truth reference trajectory. This ground truth was generated by post-processing the data from an iXblue ATLANS-C mobile mapping system comprising a Septentrio AsteRx4 RTK receiver and a high-end tactical-grade IMU. The AsteRx4 was configured to use additional constellations (BDS and GLONASS) and frequencies (GPS L5, Galileo E5, GLONASS L1 and L2) that were unavailable to PpEngine. The reported accuracy of the ground truth trajectory varied between 2 and 15 cm ($1\text{-}\sigma$) along the route. Due to the difficulty of directly evaluating

Figure 6.7: Overview of the CDGNSS reference station position and routes driven through the urban core of Austin, Texas in the TEX-CUP urban positioning datasets. Routes differ slightly from May 9 to May 12 due to road closures.

integer ambiguity resolution performance in the presence of outlier carrier phase measurements, the integer fixing performance in the following sections was evaluated by considering integer fixes to be correct if the 3D distance to the ground truth was below 30 cm, following [89].

One might naturally be concerned that the ground truth trajectory's reported accuracy, which degrades to 15 cm ($1\text{-}\sigma$) at some points along the route, may not be good enough to evaluate the accuracy of the proposed system, whose errors are also at the decimeter-level. However, the errors in the TEX-CUP ground truth dataset are likely to be substantially uncorrelated with the errors of the proposed system, for three reasons. First, the truth dataset employed an independent receiver with access to additional GNSS constellations (BeiDou and GLONASS) and frequencies (GPS L5, Galileo E5, GLONASS L1 and L2) that were unavailable to PpEngine for the experiments reported here. Second, the high-end tactical-grade IMU used to produce the ground truth has noise characteristics much different from the low-cost IMUs of the proposed system. Third, the estimation process that produced the ground truth was non-causal forward-backward smoothing,

whereas the proposed system processes the data only causally. Assuming that the ground truth errors and PpEngine’s errors are not strongly correlated, it follows that the results presented in this section will in fact be pessimistic compared to an evaluation against the absolute truth.

Because TEX-CUP contains several minutes of no motion in an open-sky environment at the beginning and end of each capture, the estimator was run on a subset of each capture beginning approximately 10 seconds before first motion and ending 10 seconds after last motion. On the May 9 dataset, the estimator was run and evaluated from GPS time of week (TOW) 411003 s to 415029 s, and on the May 12 dataset, from TOW 63770 s to 67972 s.

6.5.2 Baseline configuration

The performance of the tightly-coupled estimator with all proposed features and signals enabled (the “baseline configuration”) was evaluated using each IMU on the May 9 and May 12 TEX-CUP datasets. PpRx was configured for dual-frequency operation as described in [89], tracking the GPS L1 C/A, GPS L2C (combined CL+CM codes), Galileo E1 (combined B+C codes), and L1 SBAS (WAAS) signals on the reference and both rover antennas. Data bit prediction and wipeoff were performed on the GPS L1 C/A and SBAS signals. Reference and rover GNSS observables were produced at a rate of 5 Hz. PpEngine’s baseline configuration parameters are given in Table 6.3.

The phase center variation of the Sensorium antennas with respect to signal elevation angle was calibrated as in [89]. The orientation, body-frame position, axis scale factors, and steady-state biases of both inertial sensors were calibrated offline using a short period of dynamic open-sky GNSS data at the beginning of the May 12 dataset.

The position and attitude states of the tightly-coupled navigation estimator were initialized with the first available batch of GNSS observables and inertial measurements. The position state was initialized with the standard (single-ended) pseudorange position solution for the primary antenna. The attitude state was initialized by combining the gravity vector as determined by the IMU’s accelerometers with a constrained-baseline snapshot CDGNSS solution for the baseline connecting the primary and secondary vehicle antennas, as determined with a brute-force attitude-domain search.

6.5.3 Baseline performance

Ambiguity resolution and positioning

The achieved integer-fix availability was 97.52% and 96.62% when tightly coupled with the industrial-grade and consumer-grade IMUs, respectively, across both days of the dataset. When tightly coupled with the industrial-grade IMU, the 95th-percentile horizontal positioning error was 8.4 cm when fixed and 10.1 cm overall (fixed and float). Using the consumer-grade IMU, the 95th-percentile horizontal error was 9.2 cm when fixed and 12.0 cm overall. The empirical CDF of 3D positioning errors using both grades of inertial sensor is shown in Fig. 6.8. Detailed statistics of the estimator’s positioning performance in the baseline configuration are given in Table 6.4, and statistics of its attitude performance in Table 6.5. Figs. 6.9 and 6.10 show the position and attitude error, respectively, over time for the May 9 portion of TEX-CUP.

One may note that Table 6.4 appears to show that the consumer-grade IMU slightly outperformed the industrial-grade IMU by some metrics on the May 12 dataset. While the consumer-grade IMU did achieve a slightly higher P_V (and correspondingly lower RMS position error) than the industrial-grade, it should be noted that the P_f value was also slightly higher (i.e., worse), so a direct comparison cannot be drawn between the two P_V values. However, the consumer-grade

CDGNSS parameters	
Carrier-to-noise ratio threshold	$\frac{C}{N_0} \geq 40$ dB-Hz
Phase lock statistic threshold	$s_\theta \geq 0.8$
Elevation mask	$\theta_{el} \geq 10^\circ$
Integer aperture (IA) validation test	FF-difference test [130]
IA fixed failure rate	$\bar{P}_f = 0.001$
Undifferenced zenith pseudorange std	$\sigma_\rho = 1.5$ m
Undifferenced zenith phase std	$\sigma_\phi = 0.006$ m
Elevation-dependent weighting	$w_s = (1 + 10 \exp(-\theta_{el}/10^\circ))^{-1}$ [137, Eq. 7]
Pseudorange outlier threshold std	$\gamma = 1.5\sigma$
False fix detection window length	$l = 10$
False fix detection threshold	$\bar{P}_{f,\Psi} = 10^{-15}$
IMU parameters	
Accelerometer noise density	$\sqrt{S_a} = 100, 300 \mu g/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}^*$
Accelerometer bias steady-state std	$\sigma_{b_a} = 0.5, 10 \text{ mg}^*$
Accelerometer bias time constant	$\tau_a = 100$ s
Gyroscope noise density	$\sqrt{S_g} = 0.01, 0.05 (^\circ/\text{s})/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}^*$
Gyroscope bias steady-state std	$\sigma_{b_g} = 8, 30 ^\circ/\text{hr}^*$
Gyroscope bias time constant	$\tau_g = 100$ s
NHC parameters	
Lateral std	$\sigma_{\text{nhc},y} = 0.1$ m/s
Vertical std	$\sigma_{\text{nhc},z} = 0.2$ m/s
ZUPT parameters	
Longitudinal std	$\sigma_{zx} = 0.05$ m/s
Lateral/vertical std	$\sigma_{zy}, \sigma_{zz} = 0.01$ m/s
Accelerometer noise threshold	$\gamma_{\text{zupt},a} = 0.8$ m/s ²
Gyroscope noise threshold	$\gamma_{\text{zupt},g} = 0.006, 0.018$ rad/s*
ZUPT detection window	$N_{\text{zupt}} = 10, 30^*$
Innovations test threshold	$\bar{P}_{f,\text{zupt}} = 10^{-30}, 10^{-6}^*$

Table 6.3: Baseline PpEngine configuration parameters. Pairs marked with “*” indicate separate parameter values used with the industrial-grade and consumer-grade IMU, respectively. IMU noise parameters were increased from datasheet values for consistency with empirical observations. The elevation-dependent GNSS measurement weighting scheme is derived as noted above. Details of the NHC and ZUPT schemes are provided in this chapter’s supplemental information.

IMU allowed a few more large positioning error excursions than the industrial-grade, resulting in both P_f and d_{95} larger than those of the industrial-grade IMU.

Of the two datasets, the May 9th dataset had more difficult GNSS satellite geometry, yielding a lower P_V for both IMU grades vs. May 12. The tighter motion constraints provided by the industrial-grade IMU were able to overcome the degraded geometry to a greater degree than those provided by the consumer-grade IMU.

P_f , however, was worse for all estimators on May 12 than on May 9, despite generally better GNSS geometry. This appears to be because the May 12 dataset happened to contain more “trouble spots”: portions of the dataset with very heavy multipath that yielded frequent incorrect fixes, typically when the vehicle slowed down or came to a complete stop in the deepest urban canyon portions of the route.

Figure 6.8: Cumulative distribution functions of 3D positioning error of baseline estimator configuration across both days of the TEX-CUP urban positioning dataset.

Attitude

The attitude performance of the baseline estimator is excellent when tightly coupled with either the industrial-grade or consumer-grade inertial sensor, achieving single-degree-level precision in all three axes with the consumer-grade sensor, and sub-degree precision with the inertial sensor. Better performance with the industrial-grade sensor is as expected due to its significantly better gyroscope noise properties.

6.5.4 Effect of inertial tight coupling

To evaluate the benefit of inertial tight coupling, PpEngine was run in an “unaided” mode, using the nearly-constant-velocity motion model described in [89] for propagation in place of an inertial sensor. Attitude dynamics were modeled as a simple integrated white noise process, with noise intensity of $0.3 \frac{\circ}{\sqrt{s}}$ in the vehicle pitch and roll axes, and $5.7 \frac{\circ}{\sqrt{s}}$ in the vehicle yaw axis. Because vehicle pitch (rotation about the axis connecting the primary and secondary Sensorium antennas) is not strongly observable, a weak pseudo-measurement of zero pitch was added with standard deviation 10° at a rate of 5 Hz, which was found to provide good estimation performance.

The positioning and ambiguity resolution performance of the unaided estimator is shown in Table 6.4. Tight coupling with even a consumer-grade IMU has a clearly beneficial effect on ambiguity resolution, greatly increasing the fraction of fixed-integer epochs for comparable P_f , and reducing 95th-percentile and RMS positioning errors from meters to centimeters.

Dataset		Overall positioning performance (fix & float epochs)								
		Ambiguity Resolution		3D			Horizontal		Vertical	
		P_V (%)	P_f (%)	d_{95} (cm)	RMSE (cm)	d_{95h} (cm)	RMSE (cm)	d_{95v} (cm)	RMSE (cm)	
May 9	Unaided	77.31%	0.33%	742.1	1799.6	471.4	1713.3	209.3	550.5	
	Consumer-grade IMU	94.56%	0.19%	20.2	34.4	16.4	28.6	7.3	19.2	
	Industrial-grade IMU	97.28%	0.21%	13.8	20.6	10.6	18.9	4.0	8.1	
May 12	Unaided	76.94%	0.49%	860.5	571.9	525.5	406.1	467.9	402.7	
	Consumer-grade IMU	98.63%	0.56%	13.7	7.7	10.6	6.0	5.7	4.8	
	Industrial-grade IMU	97.74%	0.43%	12.3	13.8	9.7	12.5	4.9	5.8	

Table 6.4: Baseline estimator ambiguity resolution and positioning performance on each day of the TEX-CUP dataset. Position errors are reported relative to the TEX-CUP “ground truth” trajectory, which was generated with a survey-grade mobile mapping system as described in Sec. 5.1, with a self-reported accuracy varying between 2 and 15 cm ($1\text{-}\sigma$) along the route. “Unaided” indicates the use of the motion model of Humphreys2019 in lieu of inertial tight coupling, as described in Sec. 6.5.4. Quoted 95th percentile and RMS error quantities are over the entire dataset (i.e., for both float and fixed epochs). P_V denotes the availability of an aperture-test-validated fixed solution for conditioning in the primary filter. P_f denotes the false fix rate, as determined by an excursion of the primary filter beyond 30 cm from the ground truth when conditioned on fixed ambiguities.

Figure 6.9: Baseline estimator positioning error over time in the East, North, and Up directions for the May 9 TEX-CUP dataset. This day had worse GNSS satellite geometry and therefore lower positioning performance than on May 12. Gray shading indicates float epochs (periods when the estimator accepted the float CDGNSS solution). The longest two float periods seen with the industrial-grade IMU last 47 and 36 seconds, and exhibit position errors of a few meters. Positioning error “spikes” are visible during these float epochs as, under this work’s single-epoch ambiguity resolution scheme, only pseudorange measurements, which have meter-level accuracy, have any effect during float epochs. Some smaller error excursions are visible during fixed epochs, due to periods of poor satellite visibility and increased multipath error. “Elapsed time” indicates time since dataset start at GPS TOW 411003 s.

Figure 6.10: Baseline estimator attitude estimation error over time for the May 9 TEX-CUP dataset. Heading-dependent pitch and roll errors are evident when tightly coupled with the industrial-grade IMU; these are likely due to residual calibration errors.

Dataset	Roll ($^{\circ}$)		Pitch ($^{\circ}$)		Yaw ($^{\circ}$)	
	p_{95}	RMS	p_{95}	RMS	p_{95}	RMS
May 9						
Consumer-grade IMU	0.99	0.59	0.99	0.60	0.99	0.26
Industrial-grade IMU	0.28	0.21	0.28	0.18	0.28	0.22
May 12						
Consumer-grade IMU	0.84	0.43	0.84	0.41	0.84	0.27
Industrial-grade IMU	0.29	0.21	0.29	0.17	0.29	0.18

Table 6.5: Baseline estimator attitude performance on each day of the TEX-CUP dataset. Quoted 95th percentile and RMS error quantities are over the entire dataset (i.e., for both float and fixed epochs).

6.5.5 Performance in alternate configurations

Next, the estimator was run in a collection of alternate configurations (with various features disabled) in order to study its performance’s sensitivity to the presence of various algorithmic components. Results are given in Table 6.6.

Configuration	Industrial-grade IMU				Consumer-grade IMU				
	P_V (%)	P_f (%)	d_{95} (cm)	RMSE (cm)	P_V (%)	P_f (%)	d_{95} (cm)	RMSE (cm)	
1	Baseline (all features enabled)	97.52	0.33	13.0	17.5	96.62	0.38	16.2	24.8
2	Single vehicle antenna	96.89	0.55	16.2	25.3	95.73	0.53	19.3	30.6
3	Sans non-holonomic constraints	97.48	0.33	13.2	18.3	94.86	0.60	26.1	116.0
4	Sans zero-velocity updates	97.39	0.34	13.8	38.2	96.39	0.40	16.9	27.1
5	Sans pseudorange outlier exclusion (§6.4.3)	93.09	0.48	19.1	45.5	87.73	1.25	241.8	133.6
6	Sans re-seed (§6.4.4)	97.00	0.91	15.0	36.8	96.58	0.46	16.5	34.2
7	Sans false-fix detection & recovery (§6.4.4)	99.00	24.28	590.8	194.7	97.27	10.03	121.6	46.2
8	Single frequency (L1 only)	97.65	0.96	14.7	24.2	90.35	0.38	138.9	87.1
9	Sans SBAS	95.73	0.55	17.1	25.6	88.86	0.86	191.2	80.3
10	EKF CDGNSS Update (linearizeEKF)	97.52	0.33	13.0	17.5	96.62	0.38	16.2	24.8

Table 6.6: Estimator ambiguity resolution and positioning performance on the combined TEX-CUP May 9 and May 12 datasets with various estimator features disabled.

Performance in single-antenna mode

In Configuration 2, the estimator was run using only a single vehicle-mounted antenna. CDGNSS observables were formed for only a single baseline, between the reference antenna and the primary Sensorium GNSS antenna. Despite having fewer integer ambiguities (only one baseline’s worth) to fix at each measurement epoch, the integer fix availability was lower than for the multi-antenna case in this configuration because the estimator was no longer able to exploit the measurement noise cross-covariance between baselines due to the shared antenna. Positioning performance is slightly worse in the single-antenna case by all metrics, as would be expected due to the loss of half of all GNSS measurements.

Performance without vehicle motion constraints

The non-holonomic constraints were disabled in Configuration 3, and zero-velocity updates were disabled in Configuration 4. It can be seen that the non-holonomic constraints have only a small effect on performance when tightly coupling with the industrial-grade IMU. With the consumer-grade IMU, however, the effect is much greater. Clearly, non-holonomic constraints provide a major performance boost in the consumer-grade IMU case, cutting the number of float GNSS measurement epochs in half (fix availability increased from 94.86% to 96.62%).

The incorporation of zero-velocity updates improves all of the presented statistics when tightly coupling with either the industrial-grade or consumer-grade IMU. But for the consumer-grade IMU, the benefit of ZUPTs is minimal. This is likely because the poor noise properties of the consumer-grade IMU required such strict thresholds to limit false detections that many opportunities to apply a ZUPT were missed. However, ZUPTs have a clearly positive benefit on overall RMS position error, as they help to constrain against float-solution position error when the vehicle is stopped, which is when urban code multipath errors are largest.

Performance without pseudorange outlier exclusion

The pseudorange innovations-based outlier exclusion mechanism (Sec. 6.4.3) was disabled in Configuration 5. Without this mechanism, the availability of validated integer-fixed solutions de-

creased drastically due to the presence of outlier measurements caused by multipath. Interestingly, the false fix rate P_f was elevated, but not to extreme levels. This was likely because false fixes due to multipath-induced outliers were reverted by the false-fix recovery mechanism.

Performance without false-fix detection and recovery

In Configuration 6, the “re-seed” mechanism described in Sec. 6.4.4 was disabled, and in Configuration 7 the entire false-fix detection and recovery mechanism (Sec. 6.4.4) was disabled. Integer fix performance without the re-seed mechanism is appreciably reduced, as the estimation performance of the float-only estimator suffers without the ability to re-seed from especially trustworthy integer fixes. Disabling the false-fix detection and recovery mechanism has a catastrophic effect on false fixing rate P_f , for the reasons given in Sec. 6.4.4.

Performance on subsets of GNSS signals

In Configuration 8, the estimator was run using only L1 GNSS signals (i.e., GPS L2C was disabled), and in Configuration 9, SBAS L1 signals were disabled. Ambiguity resolution and positioning performance on these GNSS signal subsets was fairly close to the baseline case when using the industrial-grade IMU, but with the consumer-grade IMU a substantial loss of integer-fix availability occurred (down from 96.62% to 90.35% and 88.86% in each of these configurations, respectively). The weaker motion constraints provided by the consumer-grade IMU cause the estimator to require more GNSS signals for acceptable integer fix availability.

Performance with EKF-based linearization

The estimator was run using `linearizeEKF` in place of `linearizeUkf` in Configuration 10. Due to the excellent attitude performance of the estimator with either inertial sensor, no significant difference in performance arises on the TEX-CUP dataset by using the UKF update. This can be explained by referring to the results of Fig. 6.4, which show that the benefit of the UKF linearization is significant for the Sensorium’s inter-antenna distance only when attitude uncertainty exceeds approximately 8° on a single axis, whereas the attitude error on the TEX-CUP dataset never exceeded 2° .

6.6 Concluding Remarks

A vehicular pose estimation technique has been presented and evaluated that tightly-couples multi-antenna CDGNSS, a low-cost MEMS IMU, and vehicle dynamics constraints (non-holonomic constraints and zero-velocity updates). The unscented transform was used to linearize the multi-antenna CDGNSS update, allowing the use of a linear integer least squares solver for ambiguity resolution while exploiting between-baseline correlations and respecting the constraints provided by known vehicle antenna geometry, even under large attitude uncertainties. Robust estimation techniques were developed to mitigate the effects of urban multipath and signal blockage, and to recover from false integer fixes. The estimator was evaluated using the publicly-available TEX-CUP urban positioning dataset, yielding a 96.6% and 97.5% integer fix availability, and 12.0 cm and 10.1 cm overall (fix and float) 95-th percentile horizontal positioning error with a consumer-grade and industrial-grade inertial sensor, respectively, over more than two hours of driving in the urban core of Austin, Texas. A performance sensitivity analysis showed that the false-fix detection and recovery scheme is key to achieving an acceptably low false integer fixing rate of 0.3% and

0.4%, respectively. Having a second vehicle-mounted GNSS antenna significantly increased integer-fix availability, decreased false-fix rate, and improved both root-mean-square and 95th-percentile positioning performance as compared to a single-baseline CDGNSS configuration.

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Chapter 7

End-to-end Analysis and Uncertainty-based Mitigation of Adversarial Attacks to Automated Lane Centering Systems

In the development of advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) and autonomous vehicles, machine learning techniques that are based on deep neural networks (DNNs) have been widely used for vehicle perception. These techniques offer significant improvement on average perception accuracy over traditional methods, however they have been shown to be susceptible to adversarial attacks, where small perturbations in the input may cause significant errors in the perception results and lead to system failure. Most prior works addressing such adversarial attacks focus only on the sensing and perception modules. In this chapter, we propose an end-to-end approach that addresses the impact of adversarial attacks throughout the perception, planning, and control modules. In particular, we choose a target ADAS application, the automated lane centering system in OpenPilot, quantify the perception uncertainty under adversarial attacks, and design a robust planning and control module accordingly based on the uncertainty analysis.

We evaluate our proposed approach using both a public dataset and production-grade autonomous driving simulator. The experiment results demonstrate that our approach can effectively mitigate the impact of adversarial attack and can achieve 55% ~ 90% improvement over the original OpenPilot.

This activity was originally reported in [6, 7].

7.1 Introduction

Machine learning techniques have been widely adopted in the development of autonomous vehicles and advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS). Most autonomous driving and ADAS software stacks, such as Baidu Apollo [138] and OpenPilot [139], are generally composed of four-layered modules: sensing, perception, planning, and control [140]. The sensing and perception modules collect data from the surrounding environment via a variety of sensors such as cameras, LiDAR, radar, GPS and IMU, and use learning-based perception algorithms to process the collected data and understand the environment. The planning and control modules leverage the perception results to propose a feasible trajectory and generate detailed commands for the vehicle to track the trajectory. In those systems, deep neural networks (DNNs) are widely used for sensing and perception in

transportation scenarios [141–143], such as semantic segmentation, object detection and tracking, as they often provide significantly better average perception accuracy over traditional feature-based methods. For planning and control, there are also increasing interests in applying neural networks with techniques such as reinforcement learning and imitation learning [144], due to their capabilities of automatically learning a strategy within a complex environment.

However, the adoption of DNN-based techniques in ADAS and autonomous driving also brings significant challenges to vehicle safety and security, given the ubiquitous uncertainties of the dynamic environment, the disturbances from environment interference, transient faults, and malicious attacks, and the lack of methodologies for predicting DNN behavior [145, 146]. In particular, extensive studies have shown that DNN-based perception tasks, such as image classification and object detection, may be susceptible to adversarial attacks [83, 147], where small perturbations to sensing input could result in drastically different perception results. There are also recent works on attacking DNN-based perception in ADAS and autonomous vehicles by adding adversarial perturbations to the physical environment in a stealthy way [83, 148–150]. For instance, [149] generates a dirty road patch with carefully-designed adversarial patterns, which can appear as normal dirty patterns for human drivers while leading to significant perception errors and causing vehicles to deviate from their lanes within as short as 1 second.

The prior works addressing adversarial attacks mostly focus on detecting anomaly in the input data [151–153] or making the perception neural networks themselves more robust against input perturbations [154–156]. In ADAS and autonomous driving, however, the impact of adversarial attacks on system safety and performance is eventually reflected through vehicle movement, taking into account of planning and control decisions. Thus, we believe that for those systems, it is important to take a holistic and end-to-end approach that addresses adversarial attacks throughout the sensing, perception, planning and control pipeline.

In our previously published work-in-progress paper [157], we studied the automated lane centring (ALC) system in OpenPilot [139], a popular open-source ADAS implementation, and investigated how the dirty road patch attack from [149] could affect perception, planning and control modules. We discovered that a *confidence score* generated by the perception module could serve as a sensitive signal for detecting such attack, however it does not quantitatively measure the extent of the attack and cannot be effectively used for mitigation. In this report, motivated by the findings from [157], we propose a novel end-to-end approach for *detecting and mitigating* the adversarial attacks on the ALC system. Our approach quantitatively estimates the *uncertainty* of the perception results, and develops an adaptive planning and control method based on the uncertainty analysis to improve system safety and robustness.

In the literature, methods have been proposed to address the uncertainties of various modules in the ADAS and autonomous driving pipeline. For instance, the method proposed in [158] utilizes estimated uncertainty as a threshold to decide which sensor is reliable. In the OpenPilot implementation, Multiple Hypothesis Prediction [159] is utilized to estimate the prediction confidence. Some works propose methods to detect out-of-distribution inputs [160] and design probabilistic deep learning based perception models [161] and planning models [162]. Different from these prior methods, our approach takes a system-level view and addresses the uncertainty from adversarial attacks throughout sensing, perception, planning and control. While this work focuses on the dirty road patch attack, we believe that our methodology can be applied to other adversarial attacks that cause perception uncertainties, and may be extended to address more general uncertainties (e.g., those caused by environment interference or transient faults). Specifically, our work makes the following contributions:

- We analyzed the impact of dirty road patch attack across the ADAS pipeline, and developed

a method to quantitatively measure the perception uncertainty under attack, based on the analysis of both model and data uncertainties in the perception neural network.

- We developed an uncertainty-aware adaptive planning and control method to improve system safety and robustness under adversarial attacks.
- We conducted experiments on both public dataset and LGSVL [163], a production-grade autonomous driving simulator. The results demonstrate that our approach can significantly improve the system robustness over the original OpenPilot implementation when under adversarial attacks, reducing the deviation of lateral deviation by 55% \sim 90%.

The rest of the chapter is organized as follows. Section 7.2 introduces the ALC system in OpenPilot and the adversarial attack model to this system. Section 7.3 presents our uncertainty-based mitigation approach to address such adversarial attacks. Section 7.4 shows the experimental results.

7.2 ALC System and Adversarial Attacks

The Automated Lane Centering (ALC) system, one of the Level 2 autonomous driving systems, are widely deployed in modern commercial vehicles. For example, many OEM vehicles such as Mercedes-Benz C-class, Tesla and GM CT6 come with lane centering feature. Moreover, there are also third party open-source autonomous driving software stacks (e.g., OpenPilot, Baidu Apollo, Autoware) that integrate ALC. In the ALC system, the perception module collects vision and distance input from cameras and radars, and outputs the perception of the environment to the planning and control module, which generates a desired trajectory and controls vehicle steering and acceleration. In the following, we will take the open-source software Openpilot (Fig. 7.1) as an example to illustrate ALC’s architecture. As is common, this ALC involves three major modules: *perception*, *planning* and *control*. The perception module takes sensor data as input and then detects lane lines and predicts any other objects on the road (e.g., vehicles, obstacles). The planning module mainly calculates the desired trajectory based on the output of perception module. The control module then calculates a desired steering angle and speed that will be applied to the vehicle actuators. Each module is introduced below.

7.2.1 DNN-based Perception Module

Traditional perception modules uses edge detection algorithms to detect lane lines from images captured by the front camera [164]. Recently, DNN-based models achieve the state-of-the-art performance in lane detection tasks [165] and are widely adopted in production-level ALC systems today such as Tesla AutoPilot [166] and OpenPilot. The DNN-based perception module can detect lane lines and objects and provide necessary information for the planning and control module.

In ALC tasks, since the lane lines are continuous across consecutive frames, recurrent neural network (RNN) is typically applied to utilize the time-series information to make the prediction more stable [167]. A convolutional neural network (CNN) processes the current frame and feeds the combination of the CNN’s and RNN’s outputs into a fully-connect network. The OpenPilot lane detection model leverages Multiple Hypotheses Prediction (MHP) [159] to capture ambiguity in the prediction. The concatenated output includes a predicted path (an estimation of the path to follow based on perception history), the detected right and left lane lines, and corresponding probabilities to indicate the detection confidence of each lane line. Note that the lane detection

Figure 7.1: OpenPilot pipeline: the ALC system consists of a DNN-based perception module, a trajectory planning module, and an MPC controller.

model first predicts lane points and then fits them into polynomial curves in post-processing for denoising and data compression.

7.2.2 Planning and Control Modules

The planning module generates a trajectory for the vehicle to follow. Sampling based methods, model based methods and deep learning models are often applied to the trajectory planning [168]. For ALC, the desired path generated by the planner should be located in the middle between the left lane line and the right lane line. The planner module in OpenPilot generates an estimation of this desired path by calculating a weighted average of the detected left lane line, right lane line and predicted path, with the weights being the confidence scores outputted by the perception module. Intuitively, if the perception module is less confident on the predicted lanes, the generated desired path relies more on the predicted path; otherwise, it will be closer to the weighted average of the predicted left lane line and right lane line [139, 157].

Given the desired path to follow, the lower-level controller calculates the vehicle maneuver and generates commands to control throttle, brake, and steering angle. In OpenPilot ALC, model predictive control (MPC) [169] is used to calculate the steering angle based on simplified system dynamics, vehicle heading constraints, and maximum steering angle constraints. MPC-based approach permits high-precision planning and a certain degree of robustness. For longitudinal control, the acceleration is generated by a PID controller by setting an appropriate reference speed.

7.2.3 Attack Model

In this work, we assume a similar attack model as prior work [149]. We focus on attacks achieved through external physical world. In particular, we assume that the attacker cannot hack through software interfaces nor modify the victim vehicle. However, the attacker can deliberately change the physical environment that is perceived by the on-board sensors of the victim vehicle (e.g., cameras). Furthermore, we assume that the attacker is able to get knowledge of the victim’s ADAS/autonomous driving system and can drive the same model vehicle to collect necessary data. This can be achieved by obtaining a victim vehicle model and conducting reverse engineering, as demonstrated in [170, 171]. The attacker’s goal is to design the appearance of certain object (in our case, a dirty patch) on the road such that

1. the adversarial object appears as normal/seemingly-benign for human drivers, and
2. it can cause the ADAS/autonomous driving system to deviate from the driver’s intended trajectory.

There are many adversarial attacks against deep learning based tasks such as image classification and object detection, but we focus on attacks specially targeting deep learning based driving assistance systems so as to analyze and evaluate the safety of those systems. For example, the work in [148] generates an adversarial billboard to cause steering angle error and [149] generates a gray scale dirty patch on the road such that vehicles passing through the patch will deviate from its original lane, which is the first attack systematically designed for the ALC system and reaches state-of-art attack effect on production-level ADAS. Through our experiments, we will use the dirty road patch attack [149] as a case study, but we believe that our approach can be extended to other similar physical environment attacks. These physical attacks typically will render abnormal behavior in the perception output and then propagate through the entire pipeline.

Figure 7.2: The trajectory of the vehicle when the dirty patch is placed on different locations of the road.

7.3 Our End-to-end Uncertainty-based Mitigation Approach for Adversarial Attacks

As shown later in Fig. 7.5, the perception module in our approach involves two neural network models. The original OpenPilot perception model is used in the normal operation mode (i.e., when the overall prediction confidence is high), where it outputs predicted path, lanes and confidence scores. When anomaly is detected, a new perception neural network, obtained by adding dropout layers to the fully-connected layers in the original OpenPilot driving model, is used to estimate model uncertainty while generating perception output. The trajectory planner will take the uncertainties into consideration and generate a desired path that is less affected by the adversarial attack. Correspondingly, in the lower-level control, more conservative and uncertainty-aware constraints are used in the MPC and a speed adaptation method is applied to ensure safety. The details of our proposed approach are introduced below.

7.3.1 Preliminary Case Study

To evaluate the effectiveness of the attack, we conducted a series of experiments with different settings of the patch [157]. We performed the ALC attack in a simulation environment, bridging the product-level simulator LGSVL with OpenPilot and placing a carefully designed patch on the road [149]. During each simulation step, we obtained the image frame captured by the front camera and the vehicle status through the API provided by the LGSVL simulator. We then passed these data to OpenPilot, which would calculate a desired steering angle for the next simulation step. Then, the steering command is sent back to LGSVL through the API.

Figure 7.2 shows the trajectory of the ego vehicle when we put the patch on different locations of the road. The maximum lateral deviation is over 1 meter, which will cause the vehicle to drive into the opposite lane. Although the ego vehicle finally drives back to its original lane after it has passed through the dirty patch area, this behavior is extremely dangerous.

Then, we gradually reduced the perturbation area of the patch. Here, the perturbation area ratio (PAR) denotes the percentage of the pixels on the patch that can be perturbed. For example, 30% PAR means that only 30% of pixels can be perturbed while the rest 70% pixels have the same color as the road. Figure 7.3 shows the trajectory of the ego vehicle under different level of PAR.

Figure 7.3: The trajectory of the vehicle when the dirty patch is designed with different values of the PAR.

The ego vehicle drives off the road when PAR is 50% or 30%. When PAR is 10%, the ego vehicle can stay in the lane but the patch still can impact its stability.

7.3.2 Perception Confidence as Signal of Attack

Measuring the confidence of the DNN’s prediction is a significant challenge. In different perception tasks, various methods are applied to estimate the perception confidence. For instance, in YOLO [172], intersection over union (IOU) measures the confidence of regression. In OpenPilot’s neural network, a multiple hypotheses prediction (MHP) [159] classifier is trained with cross entropy loss and its output can represent how confident the lane line is predicted correctly [173].

To investigate how the perception confidence affects the system safety, we conducted a series of experiments with different settings of the attacks. As indicated in Fig. 7.4a, we observe a general phenomenon that the confidence score of the perception module drops significantly when the vehicle is approaching the dirty patch, while the confidence score keeps in a relatively stable level in benign cases or under ineffective noises. Fig. 7.4 also shows the consistency between the drop in confidence score and the vehicle’s lateral deviation under attack. As discussed in Section 7.2, the desired path generated by OpenPilot’s path planner can be considered as a weighted average of the predicted left lane, predicted right lane, and the predicted path, with the confidence scores as weights. Under the impact of the dirty patch, confidence of the predicted two lanes drops, resulting in more weights on predicted path. However, the predicted path deviates from the middle of the line eventually, and the desired path leans towards wrong directions.

Based on such observations, we think that the perception confidence is an interface between the perception and the following planning and control modules: it can both indicate whether perception module is under adversarial attack and influence the planned trajectory. Our mitigation strategy leverages this interface to switch between different perception modules and applies adaptive planning and control accordingly.

7.3.3 Uncertainty Estimation and Safety Bound

While the confidence scores generated by the OpenPilot perception module *qualitatively* show the existence of the attack, they do not *quantitatively* measure the extent of the attack and cannot

(a)

(b)

Figure 7.4: The patch starts around 40 meters and is 96 meters long. (a) shows that the confidence of the prediction drops, (b) plots the lateral deviation of the ego vehicle.

Figure 7.5: Overview of our proposed ALC pipeline with uncertainty-based mitigation for adversarial attacks.

be effectively used for mitigation. Thus, we developed a new approach for quantifying the perception *uncertainty* that considers both data uncertainty and model uncertainty. Data uncertainty is caused by the input noise/disturbance and intrinsic randomness of the real data while model uncertainty results from a lack of training data in certain areas of the input domain and the test example being out of distribution. By assuming that the data uncertainty follows a normal distribution, we can estimate it by using maximum likelihood approach. In neural networks, the model can take mean negative log-likelihood function as a loss function in the training to capture the aleatory uncertainty [174]. For the perception module, x is the image input and y is the ground truth of left and right lane lines. In Equation (7.1) below, $\hat{\mu}$ is the predicted mean value and the standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}$ is the estimated data uncertainty:

$$\mathcal{L}(x, y) = \frac{\log \hat{\sigma}_{data}^2(x)}{2} + \frac{(y - \hat{\mu}(x))^2}{2\hat{\sigma}_{data}^2(x)} \quad (7.1)$$

To estimate model uncertainty, similarly to the Bayesian approaches, we consider that there are distributions over the weights of neural networks and the parameters of the distribution are trained on the training dataset. The weight distribution after training can then be written as $p(\omega | \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y})$ where \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y} represent input and corresponding target. We apply the Monte Carlo methods to estimate the distribution by adding dropout layers to sample weights with dropout rate Φ [175]:

$$p(\omega | \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) \approx \text{Bern}(\omega; \Phi) \quad (7.2)$$

Therefore, the model uncertainty can be estimated as [176]:

$$\sigma_{model}^2 = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (\mu_t - \bar{\mu})^2 \quad (7.3)$$

The total variance can be derived by adding the model variance σ_{model}^2 and the data variance σ_{data}^2 , as shown in Equation (7.4). Since the data uncertainty is always assumed to follow the normal distribution, we can adjust the data uncertainty interval based on different scenarios. To the best of our knowledge, current commercial driving assistance systems do not take the perception uncertainty into consideration.

$$\sigma_{total}^2 = \sigma_{model}^2 + \sigma_{data}^2 \quad (7.4)$$

When the overall prediction confidence drops below a threshold, we deem that the ego vehicle is experiencing significant environment noise or under adversarial attack. Instead of using the original prediction result, we leverage the obtained prediction uncertainties to more conservatively measure the bounds of left lane and right lane. Let μ_i be the predicted mean of the i -th point of the lane and $\sigma_{total,i}$ be the corresponding error, then $[\mu_i - \sigma_{total,i}, \mu_i + \sigma_{total,i}]$ can be considered as the range where the “true” lane point may reside. Specifically, we use $\mu_i - \sigma_{total,i}$ as the lower bound of left lane if μ_i is a point on the left lane while $\mu_i + \sigma_{total,i}$ as the upper bound if it is a point on the right lane. We use a polynomial function $p(i)$ to approximate the points along the lane. The problem can be cast as a weighted least square fitting. For left lane, we fit the curve by minimizing $\sum_i^N w_i |p(i) - (\mu_i - \sigma_{total,i})|$; for right lane, we minimize $\sum_i^N w_i |p(i) - (\mu_i + \sigma_{total,i})|$. Here, w_i is the weight. Since points further away tend to exhibit larger uncertainties, we assign closer points with larger weights by setting $w_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_{data}}$. Fig. 7.8 shows the bounded predicted lanes using our approach. As we can see, the bounded prediction is more conservative compared to the original approach. In most cases, the bounded left lane and right lane tend to intersect at some point.

7.3.4 Uncertainty-aware Trajectory Planner

In the original design of OpenPilot, the desired path can be considered as a weighted sum of the left lane, right lane and predicted path (generated by the perception module). Lanes/path with higher confidence score will be assigned with larger weights and have more impact on the desired path. However, we find out that this approach cannot handle adversarial scenarios. Consider that the attacker can manipulate sensor data such that the confidence scores of the predicted left lane and right lane are much lower while the predicted path is bent towards left. In this case, the desired path will also lean towards left even though the vehicle is driving on a straight road. We argue that, when the confidence score drops below certain threshold, we should explicitly consider the uncertainties instead of just relying on the predicted road curves. That is, we use the uncertainty-bound area derived above to constrain vehicle’s speed and steering angle.

The pseudo-code to calculate the desire path in our uncertainty-aware approach is shown in Algorithm 4. The overall confidence lr_{conf} is calculated by considering the confidence of each lane, i.e., $lr_{conf} = l_{conf} + r_{conf} - l_{conf} * r_{conf}$. Lines 5-6 calculate the accumulated uncertainties along the left lane and right lane. ω_{left} and ω_{right} are the corresponding weights assigned to the bounded left lane and bounded right lane. $p_{weighted}$ is the weighted path and the final desired path is the weighted average of $p_{weighted}$ and $p_{openpilot}$ (the latter is the desired path obtained by running the original OpenPilot). The intuition is that if the current prediction has low overall confidence, we will rely more on the uncertainty-aware bounded prediction to mitigate the adversarial attack.

Besides utilizing the estimated uncertainty to bound the safe trajectory area and produce the desired path, we also make use of the temporal locality of the path prediction. We notice that the perception and planning modules can produce a safe desired path for about 100 meters with frequency of 20 Hz while the vehicle will only move forward up to several meters in the period. Therefore, the information of consecutive frames has considerable locality and relevance. We maintain a state cache to store the perception output of most recent k consecutive frames. In our experiment, we pick $k = 7$ to store the information of the past 0.35 seconds. In case of adversarial scenarios, the system will select the perception output with highest confidence score from the state cache as the planner input. Taking advantage of the locality, the system robustness to short-term inference will be improved.

Algorithm 4 DesiredPath: Uncertainty-aware Desired Path Calculation

Require: Polynomial for lane lines: p_l, p_r ; the overall confidence of the prediction: lr_{conf}

- 1: **if** total confidence lr_{conf} is less than $Conf_Threshold$ **then**
 - 2: use the original Openpilot to generate the desired path $p_{openpilot}$
 - 3: **return** $p_{openpilot}$
 - 4: **else**
 - 5: $left_{sum} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{left,i}$
 - 6: $right_{sum} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_{right,i}$
 - 7: $total_{sum} = left_{sum} + right_{sum}$
 - 8: $\omega_{left} = \frac{right_{sum}}{total_{sum}}$
 - 9: $\omega_{right} = \frac{left_{sum}}{total_{sum}}$
 - 10: $p_{weighted} = \omega_{left} * p_l + \omega_{right} * p_r$
 - 11: $desired\ path = (1 - lr_{conf}) * p_{weighted} + lr_{conf} * p_{openpilot}$
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **return** $desired\ path$
-

7.3.5 Adaptive Controller

Uncertainty-aware cost function

An MPC controller is used to generate an appropriate steering command based on the ego vehicle status and the desired path. We modify the MPC controller by explicitly considering the more conservative uncertainty-aware bounded lanes. The optimization objective can be written in the form of the summation of a running cost and a terminal cost:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{W}_{1,i} \|\mathbf{H}_r(x_i, u_i)\|^2 + \mathbf{W}_{2,i} \|\mathbf{H}_t(x_N)\|^2 \quad (7.5)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_{1,i}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{2,i}$ are weight matrices; \mathbf{H}_r is the reference function to capture the difference between current ego vehicle states and the desired path. \mathbf{H}_t is a measurement function regarding the ego vehicle states at the end of prediction horizon. Intuitively, given the desired path, we want the vehicle to drive along the reference path, but we also want the vehicle to driven on the center of traffic lanes. This is achieved by considering the the distance errors with respect to the desired lane and traffic lanes. However, we argue that the distance error regarding the left lane and right lane should adopt the bounded prediction instead of the original OpenPilot prediction. Specifically, the reference function is written as:

$$\mathbf{H}_r(x_i, u_i) = \begin{bmatrix} p_d(x_i) - y_i & e^{-(p_l(x_i) - y_i)} & e^{p_r(x_i) - y_i} & \epsilon_h & \epsilon_a & u^2 \end{bmatrix}^T$$

where p_d is the polynomial representing the desired path, p_l and p_r are fitted polynomial representing bounded left and bounded right lane respectively. ϵ_h and ϵ_a are the error regarding the ego vehicle heading and angular rate respectively. u^2 is a penalty term to avoid aggressive steering. The measurement function \mathbf{H}_t is similar as \mathbf{H}_r , except that it does not consider angular rate and penalty. The constraints include

1. system dynamics
2. vehicle heading is limited to $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ and
3. the maximum steering angle is 50° .

Speed Adaptation

Generally, the uncertainty for further-way points tends to be considerably large (e.g., Fig. 7.7) even for benign driving scenario. This means that, for safety consideration, the ego vehicle is not sure about the road structures that are far away. To prevent the vehicle from driving too fast under uncertain scenarios, we apply an emergency brake to the vehicle if its current speed is too fast. Specifically, when the overall prediction confidence drops below the threshold $Conf_Threshold$, a deceleration α_{max} is applied. The entire end-to-end pipeline of our approach is shown in Algorithm 5. Lines 1-3 calculate prediction uncertainties. Then the result is pushed into state cache. If the confidence of the prediction is too low, we pick the perception result with the highest confidence score from the state cache (line 5-7). Then the bounded predicted lane curves are used to calculate the desired path as in Algorithm 4. Moreover, if the confidence score drops below the threshold, we apply an emergency brake to slow down the vehicle. Here, v_{min} is the minimum speed required. Finally, the MPC controller calculates the steering angle for the next period (line 12).

Algorithm 5 Our Uncertainty-aware pipeline for ALC

Require: Current speed $v_{current}$, reference speed v_{ref} and input image $Input$

```

1:  $lr_{conf}, pts_{lane}, \sigma_{data}^2 = NN(Input)$ 
2:  $\sigma_{model}^2 = Monte\_Carlo\_Dropout(Input)$ 
3:  $\sigma_{total}^2 = \sigma_{model}^2 + \sigma_{data}^2$ 
4: push  $lr_{conf}, pts_{lane}$  into  $state\_cache$ 
5: if  $lr_{conf} < Conf\_Threshold$  then
6:    $pts_{lane}, lr_{conf} = \arg \max_{lr_{conf}}(state\_queue)$ 
7: end if
8:  $desired\_path = DesirePath(pts_{lane}, lr_{conf}, \sigma_{total}^2)$ 
9: if  $lr_{conf} < Conf\_Threshold$  then
10:   $v_{ref} = \max(v_{current} - \alpha_{max} * \Delta t, v_{min})$ 
11: end if
12:  $steering\_angle, acc = MPC(desired\_path, v_{ref})$ 
13: return  $steering\_angle, acc$ 

```

7.4 Experimental Results

We implement our design within the open-source driving assistance system OpenPilot. We test our proposed approach using both open dataset (comma2k19 dataset [177]) and synthetic scenarios with an autonomous driving simulator.

For the open dataset, we adopt the kinematic bicycle model [178] as the motion model for the ego vehicle. The kinematic bicycle model is commonly used to simulate how vehicles move according to speed and the front steering angle. The kinematic model can produce the vehicle trajectory and obtain the lateral deviation to measure the effectiveness of our proposed mitigation strategy. Moreover, as the trajectory calculated by the motion model may deviate from the original trace, we adopt the motion model based input generation from [149] that combines motion model with perspective transformation to dynamically calculate camera frame updates due to attack-influenced vehicle control.

For synthetic scenarios, we combine OpenPilot with LGSVL [163] to set up a closed-loop simulation environment. LGSVL is a Unity-based multi-robot simulator developed by LG Electronics America R&D Center. We reuse the LGSVL-OpenPilot bridge [149] to transfer sensor data and

driving command between the LGSVL simulator and OpenPilot. For both simulation methods, we test the original OpenPilot and our proposed design under different attacks as well as in benign situation.

7.4.1 Adversarial Attacks

In our work, as mentioned in previous sections, we applied the optimization-based physical attack in [149]. The attack works by placing an optimized patch on the road and it can lead the vehicle out of the lane within 1 second (which means the lateral deviation is larger than 0.735m in highway). The attack against OpenPilot shows high success rate and significant attack effect. To analyze the safety of the system and evaluate our proposed design, we conduct experiments under different settings (perturbation area, stealthiness levels, etc). The benign and attacked inputs are shown in Fig. 7.6.

Figure 7.6: Input images in benign scenario and under attack.

7.4.2 Results for Uncertainty Estimation

For each input frame, our system will calculate the data uncertainty by distributional parameter estimation and model uncertainty by Monte Carlo Dropout methods. The distributional parameter estimation is embedded in the original OpenPilot perception neural network. For the Monte Carlo Dropout, we only activate dropout in inference. There is always a trade-off between inference speed and estimation accuracy: larger number of samples results in higher accuracy and longer time. According to the analysis in [176] and our experiments, we set the dropout rate as 0.2 and the number of samples as 20. In this setting, the system can obtain precise variance estimation and reach a processing frequency of about 20Hz. The system will estimate uncertainties for 192 points of the predicted lane line in every frame. In experiments, we find that in most cases, data uncertainty and model uncertainty are at roughly the same order of magnitude (left subgraph in Fig. 7.7). The uncertainty is relatively large when the vehicle is approaching the adversarial patch, which is consistent with the observations in confidence estimation. An example for our uncertainty estimation is shown in Fig. 7.7. In a single frame, the uncertainties increase with the distance from the current position. This observation facilitates the planner to estimate a safe bound. As shown in Fig. 7.8, the uncertainty bound will form a triangle-like safe area and we will get a desired path from our planner, which is less affected by the attacks.

7.4.3 Mitigation Results for Open Dataset

We first test our proposed pipeline with highway image dataset and kinematic model. The input is consecutive image frames captured in a straight four-lane highway and the vehicle’s speed is 20 m/s. In the benign case, our proposed systems and the original OpenPilot can both drive in the center of the lane. Fig. 7.9 shows that the adversarial attacks can lead the vehicle with the original

Figure 7.7: Data uncertainty and model uncertainty from selected and representative frames. The left figure shows the overall uncertainties in different frames. The right figure shows the uncertainties increase with the distance in one frame.

Figure 7.8: The shaded gray area indicates the safe area bounded by our estimation of uncertainties. The bounded area and the desired path don't deviate to the left under attacks.

OpenPilot out of road and the deviation is more than 1.5 meters. In contrast, the system with our proposed uncertainty estimation and adaptive uncertainty-aware planner and controller can significantly mitigate the attack's effect, reducing the maximum lateral deviation by about 66.8%. Besides, the experiments specifically demonstrate that the adversarial attack's effect can be further mitigated by utilizing the temporal locality with state cache. However, in this simulation setting, it is difficult for us to change the vehicle's speed and perception sampling frequency since they were determined by the driving scenario and sensor configurations in the dataset, which motivates us to conduct the following closed-loop simulation in LGSVL.

Figure 7.9: Comparison of our proposed method (with or without state cache) with the original OpenPilot and reference benign situation in terms of lateral deviation. The y-axis positive direction means left.

7.4.4 Mitigation Results in LGSVL-OpenPilot Environment

In the closed-loop LGSVL simulation, we set the vehicle to follow a reference speed (20m/s) and control the throttle using a PID controller. Fig. 7.10 compares our proposed approach with the original OpenPilot under adversarial scenario. The baseline is the solid blue curve which is the trajectory of the original OpenPilot driving under benign scenario. The solid green curve is the trajectory of the original OpenPilot driving under adversarial scenario where the patch is placed at 40 meters. As we can see, the original OpenPilot does not take prediction uncertainties under consideration and can deviate significantly under adversarial attack. Our proposed is also affected by the patch on the road but can significantly alleviate the adversarial impact.

To further evaluate our proposed approach, we conduct the experiments with different settings of the patch. We place the patch on different positions along the road (40m, 80m and 120m along the longitudinal direction) and adapt the perturbation area ratio (PAR) of the patch. The improvement of our proposed approach over the original OpenPilot ALC is shown in Table 7.1. The perturbation area ratio denotes the percentage of the pixels on the patch that are allowed to be perturbed. For our experiment, we generate dirty road patch with PAR ranging from 25% to 100%. The maximum lateral deviation varies depending on different experiment settings. Throughout our experiments, the lateral deviation of the original OpenPilot ALC ranges from 0.8 to 1.2 meters, which is large enough to drive the victim vehicle out of the lane boundary. In contrast, the lateral deviation of our proposed approach ranges from 0.1 to 0.4 meter (still within the lane boundary). Overall, our approach can reduce the lateral deviation by 55.34% \sim 90.76%, under various patch settings.

Figure 7.10: Ego vehicle trajectory under different scenarios.

Table 7.1: Improvement of our proposed approach over the original OpenPilot ALC, tested in LGSVL-OpenPilot environment under different experiment settings: the perturbation area ratio (PAR) and the patch’s position along the longitudinal direction.

PAR (%)	Position (m)		
	40	80	120
100	59.33%	66.96%	76.15%
75	66.44%	90.76%	82.24%
50	55.34%	76.72%	71.93%
25	61.07%	66.07%	65.74%

7.5 Conclusions

We argue that it is essential to address adversarial attacks on driving assistance systems from an end-to-end perspective, by quantitatively analyzing the impact of those attacks across the ADAS or autonomous driving pipeline and designing mitigation strategies in a holistic manner. In our preliminary work, we studied an ALC system, analyzed how different modules interact under dirty road patch attacks, and identified a sensitive signal that can be leveraged to detect those attacks.

We then proposed a novel end-to-end uncertainty-based mitigation approach for adversarial attacks to the automated lane centering system. Our approach includes an uncertainty estimation method considering both data and model uncertainties, an uncertainty-aware trajectory planner, and an uncertainty-aware adaptive controller. Experiments on public datasets and a production-grade simulator demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach in mitigating the attack effect. We believe that our methodology can be applied to other ADAS and autonomous driving functions, and will explore them in future work.

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Chapter 8

Drift with Devil: Security of Multi-Sensor Fusion based Localization in High-Level Autonomous Driving under GPS Spoofing

For high-level Autonomous Vehicles (AV), localization is highly security and safety critical. One direct threat to it is GPS spoofing, but fortunately, AV systems today predominantly use Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) algorithms that are generally believed to have the potential to practically defeat GPS spoofing. However, no prior work has studied whether today’s MSF algorithms are indeed sufficiently secure under GPS spoofing, especially in AV settings. In this chapter, we perform the first study to fill this critical gap. As the first study, we focus on a production-grade MSF with both design and implementation level representativeness, and identify two AV-specific attack goals, off-road and wrong-way attacks.

To systematically understand the security property, we first analyze the upper-bound attack effectiveness, and discover a take-over effect that can fundamentally defeat the MSF design principle. We perform a cause analysis and find that such vulnerability only appears dynamically and non-deterministically. Leveraging this insight, we design FusionRipper, a novel and general attack that opportunistically captures and exploits take-over vulnerabilities. We evaluate it on 6 real-world sensor traces, and find that FusionRipper can achieve at least 97% and 91.3% success rates in all traces for off-road and wrong-way attacks respectively. We also find that it is highly robust to practical factors such as spoofing inaccuracies. To improve the practicality, we further design an offline method that can effectively identify attack parameters with over 80% average success rates for both attack goals, with the cost of at most half a day. We also discuss promising defense directions.

This activity was originally reported in [8].

8.1 Introduction

Today, various companies are developing high-level self-driving cars [179] such as Level-4 Autonomous Vehicles (AV) [76], and some of them are already providing services on public roads such

as self-driving taxi from Google’s Waymo One [180] and self-driving trucks from TuSimple [181]. To enable such high-level driving automation, the Autonomous Driving (AD) system in an AV needs to not only perform the perception of surrounding obstacles, but also *centimeter-level localization* of its own global positions on the map [98, 182]. Such localization function is highly security and safety critical in the AV context, since positioning errors can directly cause an AV to drive off road or onto a wrong way. Since in high-level AD systems the perception module is only designed for obstacle detection and the localization module is in full charge of identifying road deviations [72, 73, 183–185], even when the perception module is functioning perfectly, it cannot prevent a variety of road hazards specific to localization errors such as driving off road to hit road curbs, falling down the highway cliff, or being hit by other vehicles that fail to yield, especially when the AV is on the wrong way. However, recent security research in AD systems concentrates on AD perception, *e.g.*, malicious stickers on traffic signs [83, 186–188], which leaves the security of AD localization an open problem.

For outdoor localization in general, GPS is the *de facto* location source, and thus a direct threat to it is GPS spoofing, a long-existing but still unsolved security problem with practicality proven on a wide range of end systems [74, 79, 81, 189–194], including low-autonomy AVs such as Tesla cars [79]. Fortunately, to achieve robust localization, real-world high-level AD systems today predominantly use Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) algorithms that combine GPS input with position inputs from other sensors, typically IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) and LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) [78, 183, 195–202]. Since in such design GPS input alone can not dictate the localization output, it is generally believed to have the potential to practically defeat GPS spoofing [81, 193, 203–205]. However, state-of-the-art MSF algorithms are mainly designed for improving accuracy and robustness, instead of security. This thus makes it largely unclear how secure they can be under GPS spoofing. Given its widespread use in AVs and high importance to road safety, it is thus imperative to systematically understand this as early as possible.

To fill this critical research gap, in this work we perform the first study on the security property of MSF-based localization in AV settings. As the very first study in this direction, we focus on GPS spoofing as the attack vector since it is one of the most mature attack vectors to the MSF input sources. We focus on a production-grade MSF implementation, Baidu Apollo MSF (BA-MSF), due to its high representativeness in both design (KF-based MSF) and implementation (centimeter-level accuracy evaluated by real-world AV fleet), which will be detailed later in §8.2.1. We consider the attack goal as using GPS spoofing to cause large *lateral* deviations in the MSF output, *i.e.*, deviating to the left or right. This can cause the AV to drive off road or onto a wrong way, which we call *off-road attack* and *wrong-way attack* respectively.

To systematically understand the security property, we first analyze the upper-bound attack effectiveness via a dynamic blackbox analysis since BA-MSF is released in the binary form. We find that in the real-world trace, the majority (71%) of even such upper-bound attack results can only cause less than 50 cm deviation, which is far from causing either off-road or wrong-way attacks (need over 90 cm and 2.4 m respectively). This shows that MSF can indeed generally enhance the security against GPS spoofing. Interestingly, we also observe that there still exist a few upper-bound attack results that can cause over 2 meters deviations. For all of them, we find that GPS spoofing is able to cause *exponential growths* of deviations. This allows the spoofed GPS to become the dominating input source in the fusion process and eventually cause the MSF to reject other input sources, which thus *fundamentally defeats the design principle of MSF*. In this chapter, we call it a *take-over effect*. We then perform a cause analysis and find that this only appears when the MSF is in relatively *unconfident* periods due to a combination of dynamic and non-deterministic real-world factors such as sensor noises and algorithm inaccuracies.

Such take-over vulnerabilities are highly attractive for attackers since they can exploit the expo-

ponential deviation growths to achieve *arbitrary* deviation goals. However, as discovered earlier, the vulnerable periods are created dynamically and non-deterministically. Thus, we design *FusionRipper*, a novel and general attack that opportunistically captures and exploits take-over vulnerabilities with 2 stages: (1) *vulnerability profiling*, which measures when vulnerable periods appear, and (2) *aggressive spoofing*, which performs exponential spoofing to exploit the take-over opportunity.

We implement FusionRipper and evaluate it on 6 real-world sensor traces from Apollo and the KAIST Complex Urban dataset. Our results show that when the attack can last 2 minutes, there *always* exists a set of attack parameters for FusionRipper to achieve *at least* 97% and 91.3% success rates in *all* traces for the off-road and wrong-way attacks respectively, with less than 35 seconds success time on average. To understand the attack practicality, we evaluate it with practical factors such as (1) spoofing inaccuracies, and (2) AD control taking effect, and find that for both cases the attack success rates are affected by less than 4%. Attack demos showing the end-to-end attack impact are available at <https://sites.google.com/view/cav-sec/fusionripper>.

In addition, we observe that the attack effectiveness is sensitive to the selection of the attack parameters. Thus, to improve the practicality, we further design an offline attack parameter profiling method that can collect effective parameters without causing obvious safety problems during such profiling to stay stealthy. Our results on real-world traces show that our method can effectively identify attack parameters with 84.2% and 80.7% success rates for off-road and wrong-way attacks respectively, with the profiling cost of at most half a day.

Considering the critical role of localization for safe and correct AV driving, the discovered attack against the state-of-the-art MSF algorithm requires immediate attention and defense discussion. To facilitate this, we also discuss both long-term and short-term defense directions.

In summary, this work makes the following contributions:

- We perform the first security study on MSF-based localization in high-level AV settings under GPS spoofing. We focus on a production-grade MSF with both design and implementation level representativeness, and identify two attack goals specific to the AV settings.
- We analyze the upper-bound attack effectiveness, and discover a take-over effect that can fundamentally defeat the MSF design principle. We further perform a cause analysis and find that such vulnerability only appears dynamically and non-deterministically.
- We design FusionRipper, a novel and general attack that opportunistically captures and exploits the take-over vulnerability we discover. We evaluate it on 6 real-world sensor traces, and find that it can achieve high effectiveness (over 97% and 91.3% success rates) for both off-road and wrong-way attacks. We also find that such high effectiveness is robust to various practical factors.
- To improve the attack practicality, we further design an offline attack parameter profiling method that can effectively identify attack parameters with 84.2% and 80.7% success rates for off-road and wrong-way attacks respectively, with the profiling cost of at most half a day. We also discuss promising defenses directions.

8.2 Background

8.2.1 AD Localization and Multi-Sensor Fusion

In real-world high-level (*e.g.*, Level 4 [76]) AD system design, localization is a critical module that needs to compute global vehicle positions on the map in the real time based on positioning sensor inputs [72, 73, 183–185]. As shown in Fig. 8.1, its output is used by various other modules in the AD system, *e.g.*, the perception module for detecting obstacles, the planning module for

Figure 8.1: MSF-based localization and its use in high-level AD systems.

driving decision making, and the control module for executing these decisions. Such direct impact on various critical decision making steps in AV driving thus makes localization outputs highly security and safety critical.

To ensure safe and correct driving, AD localization needs to not only have *centimeter-level* accuracy to localize the AV at traffic lane level [98, 182, 206], but also have high robustness under various road and weather conditions [206]. Thus, Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) based design has become the mainstream in both academia and industry since it can fuse results from multiple independent positioning sensors, typically GPS, IMU, and LiDAR, and thus produce results with overall higher accuracy and robustness [78, 183–185, 195–202]. For example, modern AV-grade GPS receivers can achieve centimeter-level positioning accuracy with the error correction from ground stations [207]. However, GPS signal quality can be easily degraded due to natural phenomena such as atmosphere delays and multi-path effect [208]. LiDAR-based localization algorithms, or LiDAR locators [195, 209–211], match laser scans to pre-generated ones in a High Definition Map (HD Map) [212] in order to provide highly accurate positioning. However, the performance of such matching is susceptible to poor weather conditions such as rain or fog and the outdatedness of the HD Map. Thus, the goal of MSF is to leverage the strengths of these different sources while compensating their weaknesses.

Kalman Filter (KF) based MSF and its representativeness. Among MSF-based localization algorithms for AD systems, KF-based MSF is adopted most extensively in both academia and industry [78, 195, 197, 198, 200–202], and shown to have the state-of-the-art performance [78]. To concretely show its representativeness, we survey the MSF-based localization papers from top-tier robotics conferences [213] in the most recent 2 years (2018, 2019). As shown in Table 8.1, 14 (77.8%) of the total 18 papers adopt KF-based MSF, showing a clear predominance in today's MSF designs. Such representativeness can also be shown by the fact that it is taught in all Self-Driving Car courses from Udacity [183, 184] and Coursera [185].

KF is a Bayesian filter that calculates an *optimal* state distribution with the *lowest* uncertainty from the sensor measurement distributions. In the context of AD localization, the state is composed of the vehicle's *position*, *velocity*, and *attitude* (PVA) and their *uncertainties* (or co-variance or variance matrices). Specifically, KF iteratively applies two steps: *prediction* and *update*, as il-

Table 8.1: Survey of MSF-based localization designs in papers published in top-tier robotics conferences (IROS, ICRA, and RSS) in the most recent 2 years (2018 and 2019).

MSF Design		Papers	Percentage	
Category	Name			
KF-based	Linear KF	[78, 215–220]	7/18 (38.9%)	14/18 (77.8%)
	Extended KF	[221–224]	4/18 (22.2%)	
	Unscented KF	[225–227]	3/18 (16.7%)	
Others (<i>e.g.</i> , Particle Filter)		[228–231]	4/18 (22.2%)	

illustrated in Fig. 8.1. In the prediction step, the acceleration and angular velocity from IMU are integrated in the KF to generate an intermediate state (black arrows in Fig. 8.1). In the update step, KF takes the position measurements from GPS or LiDAR locator, and updates a fraction of it to the KF state based on the uncertainties of the KF state and the measurement. A larger KF state uncertainty or a smaller measurement uncertainty will cause more updates to the KF state. Please refer to the extended version [214] of this chapter for more details.

Outlier detection. To prevent KF state from being easily disrupted by occasional measurements that are too noisy in the real world, the KF update is usually bounded by an *outlier detector*. Fig. 8.1 shows an example where a GPS measurement is discarded since its position deviates too much from the KF state. Chi-squared test is one of the most widely used outlier detectors for KF [198, 202, 232], which considers a measurement as an outlier if the Chi-squared test value is larger than a statistical significance threshold (usually 3.841 [233]). An outlier measurement can be either discarded or partially updated.

Targeted MSF implementations and representativeness. In this work, we perform our security study on concrete MSF implementations for practicality and realism. In particular, our main target is an MSF design and implementation from the Baidu Apollo team, which we call *BA-MSF*. It is published in ICRA 2018 [78], a top-tier robotics conference [213], and follows the KF-based MSF design using high-end GPS, LiDAR, and IMU, with the Chi-squared test as the outlier detector conforming to the common practice [198, 202, 232]. As described earlier, such design is the most representative in today’s MSF-based AD localization (Table 8.1).

Besides its design, the implementation of BA-MSF is also highly representative in today’s MSF-based AD localization: it has been tested using a large AV fleet in various challenging scenarios such as urban downtown, highways, and tunnels [78], and shown the *highest* localization accuracy (0.054 m) among *all* MSF-based localization papers (including both KF-based and non KF-based) in the top-tier robotics conferences [213] of the most recent 2 years. Today, it is already adopted in Baidu Apollo [72], a production-grade AD system currently providing self-driving taxi services in China [77].

Besides BA-MSF, we also consider two other publicly-available KF-based MSFs for generality evaluations (§8.6.4). We follow the common parameter tuning process [234] but can only reach at most 1-2 meter accuracy, which is far from the centimeter-level accuracy required by AD systems [98, 182]. Thus, in the majority of our experiments, we target BA-MSF as it is much more representative for AD systems.

8.2.2 GPS Spoofing and the Practicality

GPS spoofing has been a fundamental problem for civilian GPS systems due to the lack of signal authentication in the infrastructure. In GPS spoofing, the attacker transmits fabricated

GPS signals with stronger power than the authentic ones, and thus causes the victim receiver to lock onto the attacker’s signals and resolve positions controlled by the attacker. GPS spoofing has been proven feasible theoretically [189] and empirically [190]. So far, it has been demonstrated on various end systems such as smartphones [81, 191], drones [74, 192], yachts [193], and recently also low-level AVs such as Tesla cars [79]. Recently, a year-long investigation identified 9,883 spoofing events that affected 1,311 civilian vessel systems in Russia since 2016 [235]. Although GPS spoofers are illegal to be sold in the U.S., they can be made cheaply from commercial off-the-shelf components. For example, a low-end spoofer is as cheap as \$223 [81], and higher-end ones that can simultaneously track 10+ satellites and transmit 10+ fake GPS signals only cost similar to a laptop [190, 236]. Considering such high realism, in this work we consider it as a practical attack vector to AD localization.

8.3 Attack Model and Problem Formulation

8.3.1 Attack Goal and Incentives

Figure 8.2: Illustration of the 2-stage attack design and consequences of FusionRipper.

Table 8.2: Required deviations for the two attack goals considered in this chapter. The values are calculated based on common AV, lane, and road shoulder widths (detailed in Appendix 8.12).

Attack Goal	Required Deviation (m)	
	Local	Highway
Off-Road Attack	0.895	1.945
Wrong-Way Attack	2.405	2.855

Attack goals. In this work, we target an attack scenario where an attack vehicle tailgates a victim AV while launching a GPS spoofing attack, which is both practical and effective as evaluated by previous work using real cars [81]. In such a scenario, we consider an attack goal of introducing large *lateral* deviations to the localization output of the victim AV, *i.e.*, deviating to the left or right. Since all vehicles need to drive within their designated road lanes for safety protections, such lateral deviations can pose a direct threat to road safety.

In particular, in this chapter we consider two concrete attack goals specific to the AV context: *off-road attacks* and *wrong-way attack*. As illustrated in Fig. 8.2, the former aims at deviating to either left or right until the victim drives off the road pavement, while the latter aims at deviating to the left until the victim drives on the opposite traffic lane. Table 8.2 lists the required deviations to achieve these two goals, which will be used in our subsequent security analysis.

In the AV context, these two attack goals can cause various *safety hazards specific to localization errors* such as driving off road to hit road curbs or falling down the highway cliff. Since in high-level AD systems the perception module is only designed for obstacle detection and the localization module is in full charge of identifying road deviations [72, 73, 183–185], these hazards cannot be prevented even when the perception module is functioning perfectly. Moreover, such hazards cannot be prevented even if high-level AD systems directly use perception sensors, e.g., cameras and ultrasonic sensors, for collision avoidance. These two attack goals can also cause *vehicle collisions*, e.g., with vehicles in adjacent or opposite traffic lanes. Even when the AV can perform automatic emergency brake, it cannot avoid being hit by other vehicles that fail to yield on time, especially those human driving ones with over 2 sec average driver reaction time [237].

Attack incentives. No matter whether road accidents are caused, the victim AVs under the two attack goals are already violating the traffic rules [238, 239] and exhibiting unsafe driving behaviors. These can already damage the reputation of the corresponding AV company. Thus, a likely attack incentive is *business competition*, which can allow one AV company to deliberately damage the reputation of its rival AV companies and thus unfairly gain competitive advantages. This is especially realistic today considering that there are over 40 companies competing in the AV market [179]. Meanwhile, considering the direct safety impact, we also cannot rule out the possible incentives for terrorist attacks or targeted murders, e.g., against civilians, or controversial politicians or celebrities.

8.3.2 Threat Model

Attacker’s capability. We assume that the attacker can launch GPS spoofing (§8.2.2) to control the positioning measurements of the victim’s GPS receiver, with a similar level of measurement uncertainty as the natural GPS signals. We also assume that the attacker can track the physical positions of the victim AV in the real time during the tailgating. This can be achieved by computing the attack vehicle’s own position and offsetting it with the relative position between the attack vehicle and the victim. One concrete scenario is that the attack vehicle is also an AV with a similar set of sensors and run state-of-the-art AD localization algorithms for its own position and AD perception algorithms for the relative position. Under this scenario, the attacker can thus accurately track the victim positions since for AVs precisely tracking the positions of surrounding obstacles in the real time is one of the most basic tasks for ensuring correct and safe driving. Such a scenario is especially realistic when the attack is from rival AV companies (incentive discussed in §8.3.1).

AV control assumption. We assume that AD systems are designed to drive on the center of traffic lanes, and constantly tries to correct any deviation to the center. State-of-the-art AD systems from both the academia [240] and industry [72, 73] follow such design and use lateral controllers to enforce it at a high frequency in the control module (e.g., 100 Hz in Apollo [72]). This means that when the attacker introduces a deviation to the MSF output (e.g., to the right in Fig. 8.2), the victim AV will actively correct it and thus cause its physical-world position to have the same amount of deviation but to the *opposite* direction (e.g., to the left in Fig. 8.2).

8.3.3 Attack Formulation

Based on the attack model above, the attack in our study can be formulated as the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\{\delta_k^a | k=1, \dots, n\}} \quad & \mathcal{D}(x_n^a, \{x_k | k = 1, \dots, n\}) \\ \text{where} \quad & x_k^a = \mathcal{M}(x_{k-1}^a, r_k + \delta_k^a, z_k^{\text{lidar}}, imu_k), x_0^a = x_0, \end{aligned} \quad (8.1)$$

where δ_k^a is the GPS spoofing distance to the victim’s physical-world position r_k on the road plane, x_k is the MSF output without the attack, x_k^a is the MSF output with the attack, z_k^{lidar} is the LiDAR locator output, imu_k is the IMU measurement, $\mathcal{D}(\cdot)$ denotes the lateral deviation between a position and a trajectory, and $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$ denotes an iteration in the KF-based MSF algorithm (introduced in §8.2.1), and k is the iteration index. As shown, mathematically our attack on MSF is to find a sequence of spoofing distances $\{\delta_k^a | k = 1, \dots, n\}$ that can maximize the deviation of the n -th attacked MSF output to the original trajectory $\{x_k | k = 1, \dots, n\}$.

8.4 Security Analysis of MSF Algorithm

To systematically understand the security property of MSF-based AD localization, we start with the necessary first step: understanding the upper-bound attack effectiveness, *i.e.*, the maximum possible deviation, under the attack formulation.

8.4.1 Upper-Bound Attack Effectiveness

Analysis methodology. To analyze the upper-bound attack effectiveness, we perform exhaustive search of possible attack inputs $\{\delta_k^a | k = 1, \dots, n\}$ to the representative MSF implementation, BA-MSF, to find the one that can maximize Eq. 8.1. We did not choose to use an optimizer since the BA-MSF implementation is released in the binary form and thus we cannot directly get its analytical formula. For a given sensor input trace in our analysis, there are multiple possible *attack windows*, *i.e.*, from one GPS input to another later. For each attack window, we iteratively search for the δ_k^a that can deviate the most from x_k , which is a method also used in previous theoretical work on the security of single-source KF [241–244]. In accordance with our threat model, we set the measurement uncertainty of GPS spoofing inputs as the median value in real-world sensor input traces of BA-MSF.

We perform the analysis above on two types of sensor input traces: (1) real-world trace, and (2) synthetic noise-free trace. The former is obtained by directly recording the run-time MSF input while the AV is driving in the real world. Analysis results from this type of traces have the highest realism, but the types of analysis we can perform are limited since we cannot easily modify the sensor data without violating the consistency among different sensor inputs, and the analysis insights can be less clean due to real-world sensor noises. Thus, we complement it with the latter, which synthesizes MSF inputs following a given driving trajectory, with all the LiDAR locator and non-spoofed GPS inputs set to the ground truth positions, their measurement uncertainty set to the medium value in the real-world trace, and the IMU measurements calculated according to the driving trajectory.

Experimental setup. We obtain the official BA-MSF implementation from the Apollo AD system code base [72]. For the real-world trace, we use the BA-MSF input trace released by Apollo, which is recorded in Sunnyvale, CA and 4-min long [245]. In this chapter, we denote it as *ba-local*. For the synthetic trace, we generate one for a common driving trajectory: driving on a straight

Figure 8.3: (a) CDF of the maximum deviations for attack windows in real-world and synthetic traces. Attack goals are marked in red dotted lines. (b) Maximum deviations and best fitted exponential bases of attack windows in the two traces.

road with a constant velocity of 45 mph. In our analysis, we use an attack window of 10 attack inputs, which is 10 seconds since the GPS input is 1 Hz in Apollo. In the exhaustive search, we enumerate δ_k^a from 0 to 10 meters with step size of 0.04 meters on both left and right sides, since we find that in our experiments GPS input deviations larger than that are identified as outliers by the Chi-squared test in BA-MSF. The medium measurement uncertainty values for GPS and LiDAR locator are calculated from trace *ba-local*.

Results. Fig. 8.3 (a) shows the distribution of the upper-bound deviations achieved in the 10-point attack windows for each trace. As shown, in both real-world and synthetic traces, even such maximum possible attack effectiveness is very limited: majority (76.0%) of the attack windows in the real-world trace and *all* of those in the synthetic trace cannot reach even the lowest required deviations (0.895 m) in Table 8.2. The main reason behind such poor attack performances is as follows. First, due to outlier detection, the maximum deviation achievable by the first attack input is very small, *e.g.*, at most 0.06 meters. Next, such tiny deviation can be quickly corrected by LiDAR locator inputs since in between two GPS attack inputs there are 5 LiDAR locator inputs (5 Hz in Apollo). This makes it highly difficult for subsequent attack inputs to build upon the deviations achieved by previous attack input. Thus, production-grade KF-based MSF algorithms today can indeed generally enhance the security against GPS spoofing.

At the same time, we also observe that the results between the real-world trace and the synthetic trace have very sharp differences: in the synthetic trace, the upper-bound deviations for all attack windows are at most 0.076 meters, while those in the real-world trace is generally larger, with 90.3% of them larger than 0.076 meters. This suggests that *sensor noises in the real world can generally degrade the security of MSF*. As shown later, such real-world factors can actually enable highly effective attacks that fundamentally break MSF in practice.

Observation: take-over effect. While our results show a general lack of attack capability to achieve even the easiest attack goal in Table 8.2, we also observe that for the real-world trace there still exist 14% attack windows that can actually achieve over 2 meters deviations, which are large enough for some of our attack goals. For all of these windows, we find that GPS spoofing is able to cause *an exponential growth* of deviations, and one such example is shown on the left of Fig. 8.4. As shown, its deviation trend is very different from those in majority of other attack windows as shown on the right of Fig. 8.4, which is almost flat.

Figure 8.4: The deviations and best fitted exponential bases of two example attack windows in the real-world trace. Left is with take-over effect; Right is without take-over effect.

To more quantitatively measure such observation, for each window, we fit an exponential function $f(x) = a^x + b$ to the deviations, where x is the x -th attack point and $f(x)$ is the deviations. For each 10-point window, we use the exponential base a in the best fitted function (based on the mean squared error) to measure the exponential growth trend. As shown in Fig. 8.3 (b), such exponential growth trends have strict positive correlation with the upper-bound deviations in the attack windows, and all windows that can have very large deviations, *e.g.*, over 3 meters for achieving *all* attack goals in Table 8.2, have very clear exponential growth trend, *e.g.*, with a being at least 1.3 (the trend on the left of Fig. 8.4).

Such exponential growth trend is very similar to the situation when the spoofed GPS is the only positioning source in KF updates, which is confirmed by re-running the upper-bound attack analysis in the synthetic trace without LiDAR locator inputs as shown in Fig. 8.5. This means that for these windows with exponential deviation growths, GPS inputs somehow become the dominating KF update source (we will analyze the cause later). In fact, according to the Chi-squared test values in the analysis logs, we find that LiDAR locator inputs actually become outliers in the latter parts of these windows and then can not provide corrections any more. This thus *fundamentally defeats the design principle of MSF, i.e., the fusion of multiple input sources for more robustness and accuracy*. In this chapter, we call it *take-over effect*.

For an attacker, such take-over effect is the most desired attack outcome, since it can efficiently cause *arbitrary deviations* and thus lead to both off-road and wrong-way attacks, and even larger ones if desired. Thus, in the next section we perform a cause analysis to understand why such take-over effect appears in the real-world trace.

8.4.2 Cause Analysis

Since take-over effect does not appear in all attack windows, there must be some factors other than the attack input δ_k^a that contribute to the take-over opportunity. To analyze the causes for take-over effect, we first identify possible contributing factors using theoretical analysis and experimental validation, and then use correlation analysis to identify the most important factors for the observed take-over effect in our analysis.

Contributing factor identification. To identify the set of possible contributing factors to the deviations in MSF, we first perform theoretical analysis based on the general KF-based MSF design (§8.2.1). From the analysis (mathematical derivations in the extended version [214]), we identify

Figure 8.5: The deviation growth and the best fitted exponential base for BA-MSF with only the spoofed GPS input in KF updates (or a *single-source* KF-based MSF) in the synthetic trace under exhaustive search.

4 theoretical contributing factors besides the attack input δ_k^g : (1) initial MSF state uncertainty \mathbf{P}_0 , (2) LiDAR measurement uncertainty $\mathbf{R}^{\text{lidar}}$, (3) difference between LiDAR position and the original MSF output without attack Δ_{lidar} , and (4) IMU measurement imu . To validate that these 4 factors indeed affect the actual BA-MSF implementation, we model each of them in the synthetic trace, and experimentally measure their relationship with the deviation. Our results show that all 4 factors can positively affect the deviation. More details are in the extended version [214].

Factor importance analysis. With the 4 contributing factors identified, we then use popular causality analysis methods to understand the importance of these factors on causing the take-over effect observed in §8.4.1. Specifically, we perform the exponentiation function fitting as described in §8.4.1, and label the windows with exponential base a over 1.1 as windows with take-over effect. As shown in Fig. 8.3 (b), for windows without any take-over effect, *e.g.*, the ones for the synthetic trace, the exponential base a is way below 1.1. With the exponential fitting results, we identify the first point of the exponential growth to obtain \mathbf{P}_0 . For $\mathbf{R}^{\text{lidar}}$, Δ_{lidar} , and imu , we use the average values from the first point of the exponential growth to the end of the window. We use 2 statistical testing methods commonly used for causality analysis [246–248]: Pearson’s Correlation and Fisher’s Exact Test.

Analysis results. Table 8.3 shows the experiment results. For the two statistical testing methods, $p < 0.05$ is considered statistically significant, and $r > 0.5$ and $or > 9$ are considered strongly correlated for Pearson’s Correlation and Fisher’s Exact Test respectively [249]. As shown, only the p values for \mathbf{P}_0 and $\mathbf{R}^{\text{lidar}}$ are statistically significant for both methods, with their r values very close to showing strong correlations, and their or values showing strong correlations. In contrast, neither of the r or or values for Δ_{lidar} and imu show strong correlations, and for imu , the results are not even statistically significant. This suggests that the take-over effect we observe in our upper-bound analysis is most likely caused by relatively large \mathbf{P}_0 and $\mathbf{R}^{\text{lidar}}$ in the corresponding attack windows.

For these two most important contributing factors, $\mathbf{R}^{\text{lidar}}$ reflects the lack of confidence in the LiDAR-based localization algorithm during the attack window, and \mathbf{P}_0 reflects the lack of confidence in the KF states at the beginning of the attack window. This means that *take-over opportunities, or vulnerabilities, appear when the MSF is in relatively unconfident periods*. Because of this, the MSF algorithm needs to take more updates from the GPS inputs, the relatively most confident input source in that period, which thus allows GPS inputs to dominate KF updates and trigger the take-over effect.

Table 8.3: Correlations between the contributing factors and the take-over vulnerability. Results with statistically strong correlation are highlighted in bold.

Correlation Method	Factor Importance			
	\mathbf{P}_0	$\mathbf{R}^{\text{lidar}}$	Δ_{lidar}	<i>imu</i>
Pearson’s Correlation	0.42 (2.0e-10)	0.44 (3.5e-11)	0.12 (8.4e-2)	0.01 (8.6e-1)
Fisher’s Exact Test	21.09 (8.6e-6)	11.78 (5.2e-8)	5.91 (3.2e-4)	1.95 (1.1e-1)
Pearson’s correlation: r (p -value), where r is the correlation coefficient				
Fisher’s exact test: or (p -value), where or is the odds ratio				

Since $\mathbf{R}^{\text{lidar}}$ is the uncertainty reported by LiDAR locator, a large $\mathbf{R}^{\text{lidar}}$ is caused by the inaccuracies of such locator algorithm in practice. From the KF equations (detailed in the extended version [214]), a large \mathbf{P}_0 is mainly caused by larger uncertainties from the LiDAR locator and GPS updates before the attack window, which is thus due to algorithm inaccuracies in LiDAR locator and noises in GPS signals. Thus, unconfident periods in MSF are mainly created by practical factors such as algorithm inaccuracies and sensor noises. This also explains why we cannot observe any take-over effect in synthetic noise-free trace. These practical factors are fundamentally difficult to avoid in practice, which is exactly why MSF is designed to compensate such inaccuracies and noises from individual sources [78, 183, 195–202]. However, as shown in our analysis, *even for the high-end sensors used in AVs today, these inaccuracies and noises are unfortunately large and frequent enough for GPS spoofing to exploit and fundamentally break MSF in practice.*

8.5 Attack Design: FusionRipper

Although our analysis in §8.4 reveals that there do exist take-over vulnerabilities for MSF in the real world, such vulnerabilities only appear in the unconfident periods created by dynamic and non-deterministic practical factors such as algorithm inaccuracies and sensor noises, which is not observable by the attacker in a tailgating attack vehicle (§8.3) and are highly difficult, if not impossible, to directly control. Thus, the attacker has to *opportunistically* capture and exploit such vulnerable periods in the actual attack time.

Leveraging this idea, we propose a novel attack design against MSF-based AD localization, called *FusionRipper*, which consists of 2 stages as depicted in Fig. 8.2:

Stage 1: Vulnerability profiling. In this stage, the attacker performs GPS spoofing and measures the feedback from the victim AV to profile when vulnerable periods appear. In our design, we aim for as fewer attack parameters as possible to maximize the ease of implementation and robustness, and thus choose to use *constant spoofing* for this stage, *i.e.*, always setting δ_k^a to a constant d as shown in Fig. 8.2. Although such profiling method is simple, our evaluation results later in §8.6 show that it is able to achieve a high attack success rate that is very close to the theoretical upper bound.

While performing constant spoofing, the attacker tracks victim’s physical positions in real time and measures their deviations to the center of traffic lane (described in §8.3). If such deviation is as large as causing the AV to exhibit unsafe driving behaviors, *e.g.*, about to have unnecessary lane straddling, the victim AV is considered as in the vulnerable period. Our design uses the deviation that can touch the left or right lane line on local roads (0.295 meters, detailed in Appendix 8.12) as the threshold to determine vulnerable periods. The intuition is that a properly designed and

tested AD system should very rarely have large position deviations that can cause unsafe driving behaviors under normal fluctuations of sensor inputs. For example, the errors of BA-MSF evaluated by Baidu Apollo AVs on real roads are within 0.054 meters [78], which is far less than 0.295 meters. Thus, when such rare deviation appears, it is very likely caused by the constant spoofing, and the MSF algorithm is very likely in an unconfident period since it takes larger update from the spoofed GPS inputs.

Stage 2: Aggressive spoofing. After the vulnerable period is identified, the attacker can then perform aggressive spoofing to trigger the take-over effect and thus quickly induce large deviations. As shown in our security analysis in §8.4.1, the deviations grow exponentially during the take-over effect, and thus we choose exponential spoofing in the aggressive spoofing stage. As shown in Fig. 8.2, as soon as the attacker identifies a vulnerable period, she switches to use spoofing distance $d \times f^i$, where an exponential base f is cumulatively multiplied to previous spoofing distance at each of the spoofing points, and i is the index of the aggressive spoofing inputs.

Generality. Since FusionRipper is designed to exploit the take-over vulnerability that is general to any KF-based MSF as discussed in our cause analysis based on the general form of KF-based MSF (§8.4.2), its design is generally applicable to any KF-based MSF algorithms. As shown in our generality evaluation later (§8.6.4), FusionRipper is highly effective on different KF-based MSF designs and implementations.

8.6 Attack Evaluation

8.6.1 Evaluation Methodology

Experimental setup. Following the common practice among AV companies [250, 251], we evaluate FusionRipper on real-world sensor traces. Specifically, we use the real-world trace *ba-local* used in our security analysis earlier (§8.4), and also traces from KAIST Complex Urban [252], a dataset for evaluating AD systems. Since *ba-local* is collected by the Apollo team and is designed specifically for evaluating MSF-based localization algorithms for Apollo, it is by default compatible with BA-MSF with a complete positioning sensor set as well as the HD Map for running the LiDAR locator¹.

Similar to *ba-local*, the traces in the KAIST dataset are also collected by high-end AV-grade positioning sensors [252]. But unfortunately, they do not provide the HD Map for running the LiDAR locator in BA-MSF. To address this, we assume an *ideal* LiDAR locator which always outputs the ground truth positions provided in the KAIST dataset, with their measurement uncertainty set to the median value of that in *ba-local*. Considering that one of the likely causes for the take-over effect is the LiDAR locator inaccuracies, especially the measurement uncertainty values (§8.4.2), this assumption only makes the attack harder and thus the results will provide the worst-case attack effectiveness on the KAIST traces.

The KAIST dataset includes 18 local traces and 2 highway traces that are compatible with BA-MSF, and we select 3 local ones and both the 2 highway ones. We truncate them to the first 5 minutes to keep the evaluation time manageable. In the selection of local traces, we select the ones with the smallest average MSF state uncertainty (*i.e.*, most confident). Considering that state uncertainty is one of the two most important contributing factors to the take-over effect (§8.4.1), the evaluation results on these traces provide the worst-case attack effectiveness for the KAIST traces. The detailed trace selection process can be found in the extended version [214].

¹Apollo released 8 sensor traces recorded with localization, but only *ba-local* has both the complete sensor set and compatible format with BA-MSF.

Evaluation metrics. To evaluate the attack effectiveness, we apply attack parameters d and f from all possible attack starting points, *i.e.*, when the GPS input comes, in each trace, since the attacker can discover the victim at any moment in the trace and start performing the attack. As described earlier in §8.5, the attacker switches to aggressive spoofing when the lateral deviation between the spoofed MSF output and the non-spoofed MSF output is over 0.295 meters, which is just about to have lane straddling on local roads.

We consider the attack as successful when the lateral deviation of the MSF output is over the required deviations for the off-road and wrong-way attacks according to Table 8.2. This follows our AD control assumption (§8.3), which can directly considers the amount of deviation at the MSF output level as the amount of physical position deviations in the opposite direction to the center line. Later in §8.7.2, we will concretely evaluate this assumption using an end-to-end evaluation with the AD control taking effect. The *success rate* is calculated as the fraction of the successful attack starting points out of all starting points. For each attack starting point, we enumerate the combinations of d from 0.3 to 2.0 meters, with step size 0.1 meters, and f from 1.1 to 2.0, with step size 0.1. We choose these ranges because we do not find the values out of these ranges can improve the attack effectiveness in our experiments. Each d and f combination is then applied to both the left and right side of the driving direction, since both sides are valid for achieving off-road attack (detailed in §8.3.1). Since it takes time to (1) capture a take-over vulnerability, which is created dynamically and non-deterministically, and (2) reach the required deviations even during take-over effects (§8.4.1), we also consider *minimum attack duration* when calculating success rate, *i.e.*, how much time the attack can last when tailgating the victim AV. Intuitively, the longer such duration is, the higher chance she can have to hit a vulnerable period.

Table 8.4: Real-world sensor traces used in our evaluation.

Source	Trace Label	Road Type	Duration	HD Map
Apollo	<i>ba-local</i>	Local	257s	Yes
	<i>ka-local08</i>	Local	289s	
KAIST	<i>ka-local31</i>	Local	1014s	
Complex	<i>ka-local07</i>	Local	553s	No
Urban	<i>ka-highway17</i>	Highway	1186s	
	<i>ka-highway06</i>	Highway	1937s	

 Figure 8.6: Average attack success rates of (a) *off-road* attack and (b) *wrong-way* attack under different minimum attack duration.

Table 8.5: Ablation study results on *ba-local* trace.

Attack Config.	Off-Road		Wrong-Way	
	Succ. Rate	Succ. Time	Succ. Rate	Succ. Time
FusionRipper	98.0%	29s	97.0%	33s
Vulnerability Profiling Stage Only	14.1%	26s	7.0%	29s
Aggressive Spoofing Stage Only	10.1%	8s	5.0%	13s

Figure 8.7: Average success rate under different required attack deviations when the minimum attack duration is 2 minutes.

Figure 8.8: Average success time for reaching required deviations in off-road and wrong-way attacks under different minimum attack duration.

8.6.2 Attack Effectiveness

Attack success rates. Fig. 8.6 shows the best success rates of FusionRipper among all the combinations of d and f for the two attack goals. It shows both the results for individual traces and the average result among all traces (the thick pink line). As shown, for all traces, the average success rate is always over 75% for both attack goals even when the minimum attack duration is as low as 30 seconds. When the minimum attack duration increases, the success rates for all traces increase accordingly, which is expected since the attacker has higher chance to capture a vulnerable period. In particular, when the attack can last 2 minutes, *there exists at least one combination of d and f that can achieve over 97% success rate (98.6% on average) for the off-road attack and over 91% success rate (95.9% on average) for the wrong-way attack, for all traces in our evaluation.* Note that this is in fact the worst-case results for KAIST traces as discussed in §8.6.1. Since a normal taxi or truck trip is usually at least 10 minutes, it is highly likely that an attacker can find such a 2-minute tailgating opportunity in practice to launch the FusionRipper attack.

Among all the traces, *ka-local08* and *ka-highway17* shows the lowest success rate in general, especially when the required deviation is large. As shown in the extended version [214], both traces have smallest average MSF state uncertainty in their categories (*i.e.*, local and highway). This means that their MSF outputs have the highest confidence and thus are the most difficult to attack as we expect in §8.6.1. This also confirms that we are evaluating the worst-case attack effectiveness on KAIST traces.

Table 8.6: Top 3 attack parameters with the highest attack success rates when minimum attack duration is 2 min.

Attack	Rank	<i>ba-local</i>			<i>ka-local08</i>			<i>ka-local31</i>			<i>ka-local07</i>			<i>ka-highway17</i>			<i>ka-highway06</i>		
		<i>d</i>	<i>f</i>	Succ. Rate	<i>d</i>	<i>f</i>	Succ. Rate	<i>d</i>	<i>f</i>	Succ. Rate	<i>d</i>	<i>f</i>	Succ. Rate	<i>d</i>	<i>f</i>	Succ. Rate	<i>d</i>	<i>f</i>	Succ. Rate
Off-Road	Top 1	0.6	1.5	98.0%	0.7	1.1	100%	0.5	1.2	99.4%	0.3	1.1	98.9%	0.3	1.2	97.0%	1.1	1.5	98.2%
	Top 2	0.6	1.6	98.0%	0.7	1.2	100%	1.0	1.3	99.4%	0.3	1.2	98.3%	0.3	1.3	97.0%	1.1	1.3	98.2%
	Top 3	0.6	1.7	98.0%	0.7	1.3	100%	1.0	1.4	99.4%	0.4	1.2	98.3%	0.3	1.4	94.0%	1.3	1.3	98.2%
Wrong-Way	Top 1	0.6	1.5	97.0%	0.3	1.2	93.8%	1.0	1.3	98.3%	0.3	1.4	91.1%	0.3	1.2	97.0%	1.2	1.3	98.2%
	Top 2	0.6	1.3	95.0%	0.3	1.3	93.8%	1.0	1.2	97.8%	0.3	1.5	90.6%	0.3	1.3	97.0%	1.3	1.3	98.2%
	Top 3	0.6	1.4	95.0%	0.5	1.3	92.1%	1.1	1.2	97.8%	0.3	1.3	88.3%	0.3	1.4	94.0%	1.1	1.3	97.6%

Between the two attack goals, the success rates only slightly drop for wrong-way attack since it has a larger required deviation. This means that the majority of the captured vulnerable periods have a successful take-over effect that can be exploited to cause different required deviations. To confirm this, we further evaluate the success rates of FusionRipper for even larger required deviations, and find that when the minimum attack duration is 2 minutes, FusionRipper is able to maintain an average success rate over 91.3% even when the required deviation is 10 meters as shown in Fig. 8.7.

Sensitivity to attack parameters. Table 8.6 lists the top 3 combinations for each trace. As shown, the attack effectiveness of FusionRipper is sensitive to the combinations of d and f . For example, the best d and f combinations are *all different* for the 6 traces. This motivates us to design an offline method to identify effective d and f combinations to increase the attack practicality, which is detailed later in §8.8.

Ablation study. The high attack effectiveness is a result of the combination of the two attack stages. To concretely understand this, we conduct an ablation study on *ba-local*, where we remove one of the two stages in the experiments. For *Vulnerability Profiling Stage Only*, we apply the constant spoofing distance d from each starting point. For *Aggressive Spoofing Stage Only*, we directly scale the spoofing distance using different combinations of d and f from each starting point. For both configurations, we obtain the *highest* success rates by enumerating d or f in the range specified in §8.6.1.

Table 8.5 shows the experiment results for *ba-local* when the minimum attack duration is 2 minutes. As shown, both configurations can only achieve at most 14% and 7% for the two attack goals, which is far less than 98% and 97% by FusionRipper. This means that there are still some very unconfident periods that even stage 1 or stage 2 alone can succeed, but as shown, without the help of each other, the success rate is very limited. This concretely demonstrates the necessity of the current 2-stage design of FusionRipper. Note that FusionRipper has longer attack success time than *Aggressive Spoofing Stage Only* due to the time spent on the vulnerability profiling stage. However, since the current ~ 30 seconds attack time on average is already quite affordable for a tailgating attacker in practice, such advantage is much less important than the much higher success rates by FusionRipper.

Attack success time. For the attack success time, overall the average success time and the standard deviations are very similar under different minimum attack duration as shown in Fig. 8.8. When the minimum attack duration is 2 minutes, the average success time is less than 30 seconds with a standard deviation of around 25 seconds for both off-road and wrong-way attacks. This shows that FusionRipper can generally succeed very fast, *e.g.*, within a minute, even when the

attacker plans to attack for over 2 minutes.

8.6.3 Comparison with Naive Attack Method

In this section, we compare FusionRipper with a more naive attack method: *random attack*, which randomly spoofs a deviation within a distance range for each GPS spoofing point.

Experimental setup. We perform experiments by applying FusionRipper and random attack on *ba-local*. In the random attack, we uniformly sample the position deviation between 0 to 10 meters for each spoofing point. The experiments are repeated for 30 trials. In each trial, the spoofing is performed for each attack starting point and on both the left and right. The higher success rate between that of the left and that of the right is taken as the final success rate for each trial.

Results. The first row in Table 8.7 shows the experiment results when the minimum attack duration is 2 minutes. We find that the random attack can barely reach any large deviation, and as shown, its success rates are as low as 3.7% and 0.2% on average for the two attack goals respectively, which are much lower than those from FusionRipper (98.0% and 97%).

8.6.4 Generality of FusionRipper

In this section, we aim at understanding the generality of FusionRipper by evaluating it on more KF-based MSF implementations. Ideally we hope to find other production-grade implementations for AD systems similar to BA-MSF, but to best of our knowledge, BA-MSF is the only publicly-available one so far. Nevertheless, we still try our best to implement/port and evaluate on two other popular KF-based MSF designs, denoted as *JS-MSF* and *ETH-MSF*, which are both designed for general robotics localization instead of for AVs.

Experimental setup. BA-MSF adopts a Linear KF, the most popular KF design for MSF-based localization (Table 8.1). Thus, we follow a popular Linear KF based MSF design published by Joan Solà [253] and implement JS-MSF. ETH-MSF [254] is an open-source project developed by researchers from ETH Zürich for drones [255], which implements an Extended KF based MSF, the second popular KF design for MSF-based localization (Table 8.1). It has received over 500 stars on GitHub, which is the *highest* among the repositories under the search keyword “kalman filter sensor fusion”. Both implementations use a Chi-squared test based outlier detector and directly reject outlier measurements. We follow a common parameter tuning process [234] and reach at most 1.91 and 1.17 meters localization accuracies on *ba-local* for JS-MSF and ETH-MSF respectively. Although such accuracies are far from the centimeter-level accuracy required by AD systems, they are common for general robotics localization [216, 217, 225].

Results. Table 8.7 shows the attack success rates of FusionRipper and random attack on *ba-local* for all 3 KF-based MSF implementations. As shown, FusionRipper can generally achieve high success rates on all three MSFs, which are 100% on both JS-MSF and ETH-MSF for both attack goals. However, we also notice that even random attack can also achieve over 95% success rates for the off-road attack, and over 70% for the wrong-way attack. This suggests that JS-MSF and ETH-MSF are both very unstable, which can also be seen by the fact that their natural localization errors are already 1.17 and 1.91 meters. In contrast, BA-MSF can achieve 0.054 meters accuracy, which is likely due to additional design features such as zero-velocity update [78], and better parameter tuning by professional AV engineers. Thus, while our results show that FusionRipper is general for all 3 KF-based MSF implementations, we believe that the results on BA-MSF can more representatively indicate the security status of production-grade MSF-based AD localization today.

Table 8.7: Attack success rates of FusionRipper and random attack on 3 MSF implementations. The attacks are evaluated on *ba-local* with 2-minute minimum attack duration.

Attacked MSF	FusionRipper		Random Attack (avg. of 30 trials)	
	Off-Road	Wrong-Way	Off-Road	Wrong-Way
BA-MSF	98.0%	97.0%	3.7%	0.2%
JS-MSF	100%	100%	97.4%	92.4%
ETH-MSF	100%	100%†	95.9%	72.5%

†Achieves 100% success rate when using a smaller f (1.02).

8.7 Practical Attack Considerations

Although FusionRipper already shows very high effectiveness in §8.6, we haven’t considered two factors that may affect the attack effectiveness in practice: (1) the variations in the spoofed positions and their measurement uncertainty at the victim’s GPS receiver, and (2) sensor input changes due to AD control during the attack. In this section, we evaluate the robustness of FusionRipper under these two practical factors. The experiments in this section are mainly performed on the *ba-local* trace since it has the complete set of real-world sensor inputs for BA-MSF and thus has the highest realism.

8.7.1 Robustness Against Spoofing Inaccuracies

In §8.6, we directly set spoofed GPS inputs $r_k + \delta_k^a$ based on d and f , and set their uncertainty R_k as the medium value in real-world traces. However, in practice both can have variations due to sensor noises. In this section, we denote the variances to $r_k + \delta_k^a$ as σ_{pos} , and those to R_k as σ_{var} .

Inaccuracy sources and modeling. As specified in our threat model (§8.3), we assume that the attacker can estimate the victim AV’s real-time positions based on her own position and the distance to the victim. Thus, there are three possible error sources for σ_{pos} : 1) localization error σ_1 in attacker’s self-localization process, 2) distance measurement error σ_2 in the measured distance between the attack vehicle and the victim AV, and 3) GPS receiver error σ_3 , *i.e.*, the difference between the position the attacker intended to set and the actual received position at the victim side. Assuming the attacker is equipped with the same sensor set used in an AD system and can run an MSF algorithm of similar quality, σ_1 will be similar to the inaccuracies of BA-MSF algorithm, which is reported as 0.054 meters in [78]. Since LiDAR can be used to measure the distance to the victim, σ_2 is thus the distance measurement error in the LiDAR sensor, which is 0.02 meters as specified in the datasheet according to the LiDAR model used in Apollo [256]. For σ_3 , we directly use the positioning error, 0.01 meters, as specified in the datasheet of the GPS model used in Apollo [207]. Assuming that these errors are normally distributed with a zero-mean (common practice in robotics [257]), the combined distribution for σ_{pos} is conforming to $N(0, \sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 + \sigma_3^2) = N(0, 0.058^2)$. For the measurement uncertainty error σ_{var} during spoofing, we measure the distribution of GPS measurement uncertainty in the *ba-local* trace, and take the standard deviation $\sigma_{\text{var}} = 0.008$.

Experimental setup. We apply these error distributions to the FusionRipper attack in *ba-local* using the best attack parameter in *ba-local* with 2-minute minimum attack duration. For each GPS spoofing input, we randomly sample a position error from $N(0, \sigma_{\text{pos}}^2)$ and the error direction from a uniform distribution between 0 to 360 degrees, and apply them to the spoofed input. Similarly, we randomly sample an error value from $N(0, \sigma_{\text{var}}^2)$ and apply it to the measurement uncertainty

Figure 8.9: Attack success rate for different amounts of spoofing errors. Experiment of each error amount is repeated 100 times.

of each spoofing input. To further explore the impact of these errors, we also apply $2\times$ and $3\times$ amounts of the normal error (σ_{pos} and σ_{var}), in our evaluation. We repeat the experiment 100 times for each error amount.

Results. Fig. 8.9 shows the attack success rates under each error amount. As shown, under normal error amount ($1 \times \{\sigma_{pos}, \sigma_{var}\}$), the success rate is only reduced by 0.2% for the off-road attack, and by 0.8% for the wrong-way attack. Even when the error amount is $3\times$ than normal, meaning that the error can be as large as 0.174 meters, the success rate is still 84.3% and 74.2% on average for off-road and wrong-way attacks respectively. This shows that FusionRipper is highly robust to spoofing inaccuracies in practice.

8.7.2 End-to-End Attack Impact Evaluation

In §8.6, we assume the amount of deviation in MSF outputs is the same as the amount of physical position deviations to the center line. In this section, we concretely evaluate this assumption by performing an end-to-end attack impact evaluation with the AD control taking effect.

Evaluation methodology. In this evaluation, we adopt two evaluation methods popularly used in AV industry [250, 258]: *trace based* and *simulation based*. In the trace-based evaluation, we still use the original real-world sensor trace *ba-local*, and synthesize the sensor input changes corresponding to the output of the control module in Apollo. Specifically, the lateral controller in Apollo runs a linear-quadratic regulator algorithm [259] on the lateral deviation in the MSF output, which calculates the amount of steering that will be applied to correct the deviation. We thus mathematically translate such steering into physical position and heading rate changes (detailed in Appendix 8.13), and add them to the original LiDAR locator position and IMU values to get the changed ones due to AD control. The benefit of this method is that it contains real-world sensor noises, which is the key contributor to the take-over vulnerability (§8.4). However, it does not model more complicated sensing and vehicle motion factors such as raw LiDAR point cloud changes and tire-road frictions, which thus may have limited synthesizing accuracy.

In the simulation-based evaluation, we directly use an AD simulator to dynamically generate raw sensor inputs to Apollo according to its control decisions in the real time, which has more advanced sensor and vehicle motion modelling. However, a common limitation for AD simulators

today [82, 260] is that they do not consider generating sensor data with real-world noises. To address this, we model the LiDAR noises as position errors following a normal distribution with a zero mean for each point of the raw LiDAR point cloud generated from the simulator according to the LiDAR datasheet [256].

Experimental setup. In the trace-based evaluation, we run Apollo version 2.5 (the latest version directly compatible with *ba-local*) with the control module enabled on a GPU server, and feed trace *ba-local*. We write a standalone ROS node that feeds the spoofed GPS inputs and also performs the LiDAR locator and IMU input changes described above. For FusionRipper, we use the best attack parameter in *ba-local* with 2-minute minimum attack duration. We do not run the perception module since in Apollo the perception module only outputs detected road obstacles and the system solely relies on the localization module to identify deviations on the road. This is the most popular design modularization for high-level AD systems today [72, 73, 183–185], which lets the localization module to take charge of all aspects related to vehicle positioning.

In the simulation-based evaluation, we use LGSVL, a production-grade AD simulator that can interface with Apollo version 5.0 [82]. Since Apollo version 5.0 replaces the ROS runtime with Cyber [72], we implement the attack logic and noise modeling in a Cyber node instead. Different from the trace-based evaluation, we run the simulation on the *complete* Baidu Apollo AD system with all functional modules enabled, *i.e.*, localization, transform, perception, prediction, planning, routing, and control [72]. We simulate two attack scenarios with one attacking to the left of the road and another to the right, where both have concrete safety consequences such as hitting the road barrier or traffic sign.

Trace-based evaluation results. Our results show that FusionRipper achieves 97.0% and 93.9% success rates for off-road and wrong-way attacks respectively, which is only slightly lower than those in the MSF algorithm-only analysis (98.0% and 97.0%). Such slightly effectiveness drop may be due to run-time randomness when running the end-to-end Apollo system since it uses multi-threading when feeding the sensor inputs to BA-MSF.

Simulation-based evaluation results and attack demos. Our simulation results show that FusionRipper can successfully deviate the victim AV to hit the road barrier or traffic sign even with the complete end-to-end Baidu Apollo AD system operating. We record attack demo videos for these two simulation scenarios, available at our project website <https://sites.google.com/view/cav-sec/fusionripper>. Fig. 8.10 shows a snapshot of the demos [261]. As shown, to correct the MSF output deviation to the right/left of the planned trajectory (*i.e.*, lane center), the AV in the physical world deviates to the left/right and eventually hit the road barrier or the stop sign.

8.8 Offline Attack Parameter Profiling

Our results so far show that for each trace there always exist an attack parameter combination, *i.e.*, d and f , that can achieve high success rates (§8.6) with high robustness to practical factors (§8.7). However, in §8.6.2 we also observe that such high effectiveness is sensitive to the selection of attack parameters. Thus, it is highly desired if there exists an offline method that can efficiently identify highly effective attack parameters before the actual attack. In this section, we thus explore the possibility of designing such a method to further improve the practicality of FusionRipper.

8.8.1 Problem Settings and Design

Problem Settings. To find the effective attack parameters offline, we assume that the attacker can perform trials of FusionRipper attacks with different combinations of d and f on AVs of the *same model* as that of the victim AV, *i.e.*, having the same sensor set, AD system, and vehicle

Figure 8.10: Snapshots of our end-to-end attack demos. MSF View: input sensor positions and MSF outputs; Physical World View: victim AV’s physical world position.

model. This is realistic since any AV models developed for commercial purpose need to be mass produced for the ease of management and reducing the development cost for the self-driving taxi or truck services today [77, 262–264]. For example, Waymo’s 20,000 self-driving taxis in Phoenix are deployed with the same sensor suite on the same car model [265]. In this process, the attack trials can be performed *actively*, by requesting self-driving taxi or truck services that use the targeted AV model, or directly purchasing an AV of the same model.

In such profiling process, it is necessary to prevent causing obvious safety problems both for the attacker’s own safety and for remaining stealthy. Thus, in such offline profiling we choose a *safe profiling design*, which still performs the FusionRipper attack but stops the attack right after the physical-world deviation of the AV is over a *safe profiling threshold*. This will thus let the non-spoofed GPS and other positioning sources to drag the MSF output deviations back.

Offline profiling algorithm design. Under the problem settings above, our profiling method is designed following a simple strategy: performing attack trials using different combinations of d and f until we find a combination with a sufficiently high success rate. More specifically, the trials are performed for a number of *profiling rounds*. In each round, the attacker picks one combination of d and f and tries it for multiple times. When picking the combinations, the attacker follows the order from the smallest one to the largest one in the parameter space, since larger ones can more easily make the spoofed inputs outliers and thus directly cause attack failure.

Due to the safety requirement, the attacker follows the safe profiling design above, and considers a d and f combination as successful once it reaches the safe profiling threshold. After each profiling round, the attacker can thus obtain a success rate for a d and f combination. Once the success rate of a combination in a round is over a *minimum profiling success rate*, the profiling terminates and such combination is selected for the actual attack. If the attack parameters space is exhausted, the combination with the highest success rate in profiling is selected. The pseudocode of this method is in Algorithm 6.

Algorithm 6 Offline Attack Parameter Profiling

Notations:ATTACKTRIALS(d, f, n, t): Profile n attack trials with parameters d, f , returns the number of trials that have deviations larger than t N : Number of attack trials in each profiling round S : Minimum profiling success rate T : Safe profiling threshold**Output:** d, f, cost **Initialize** $d, d_{\text{best}} \leftarrow d_{\text{min}}; f, f_{\text{best}} \leftarrow f_{\text{min}}; \text{SuccRate}_{\text{best}}, \text{cost} \leftarrow 0$

```

1: for each  $f \leftarrow f_{\text{min}}$  to  $f_{\text{max}}$  do
2:   for each  $d \leftarrow d_{\text{min}}$  to  $d_{\text{max}}$  do
3:     SuccCount  $\leftarrow$  ATTACKTRIALS( $d, f, N, T$ )
4:     cost  $\leftarrow$  cost +  $N$ 
5:     SuccRate  $\leftarrow$  SuccCount/ $N$ 
6:     if SuccRate  $\geq S$  then
7:       return  $d, f, \text{cost}$ 
8:     else
9:       if SuccRate > SuccRatebest then
10:         $d_{\text{best}} \leftarrow d, f_{\text{best}} \leftarrow f$ 
11:        SuccRatebest  $\leftarrow$  SuccRate
12:      end if
13:    end if
14:  end for
15: end for
16: return  $d_{\text{best}}, f_{\text{best}}, \text{cost}$ 

```

8.8.2 Experiments and Evaluation

Experimental setup. In this section, we use the 5 KAIST traces used in §8.6.2 since this represents the case with attacking the same AV model (the KAIST traces are collected using the same vehicle on different roads [252]). We split the 5 traces into two sets, with 4 as the *profiling traces*, *i.e.*, representing the attack trials in the offline profiling, and 1 as the *evaluation trace* for evaluating the selected d and f from profiling, *i.e.*, representing the actual attack on the victim AV. We evaluate all the 5 possible splittings, and then use their average success rate to measure the offline profiling effectiveness. We use the same parameter space as that in §8.6.

Algorithm parameter choices. In the profiling algorithm, there are two configurable parameters: *minimum profiling success rate*, and *safe profiling threshold*. Thus, we first perform experiments to understand how to best configure them. In these experiments, for each d and f combination we consider all attack starting points in the profiling traces as its corresponding set of attack trials in the profiling algorithm in order to understand general properties of different parameter values.

We first perform experiments by running the profiling algorithm for different minimum profiling success rates without considering safe profiling design. Our results show that the average success rate of the selected d and f does not change significantly overall. Particularly, it peaks when the minimum profiling success rate is 50% for both attack goals and drops after that, maybe due to the overfitting to the profiling traces. More details are in Fig. 8.15 (a) in the Appendix.

Next, with 50% as the minimum profiling success rate, we vary the safe profiling threshold, and find that reducing the safe profiling thresholds only slightly changes the average success rate of the selected d and f : the success rate differences between profiling threshold 0.3 and 0.9 meters are less than 4% for both attack goals. In particular, using 0.45 meters as the safe profiling threshold has the overall highest average success rate for both attack goals, which are 90.3% and 84.4% respectively. Details are in Fig. 8.15 (b) in the Appendix. Such 0.45 meters deviation does not

Figure 8.11: Average profiling effectiveness (bar graph) and costs (line graph) under different numbers of attack trials in each profiling round. Each profiling is repeated for 100 times.

cause the AV to drive off road on both local roads and highway (Table 8.2). On local roads, it will only cause very slightly lane straddling, and on the highway, it is far from even touching the left or right lane line (both visualized in Fig. 8.13 in Appendix). Thus, the attacker can choose to perform such safe profiling on the highway, or on the local roads with light traffic.

Evaluation results. With the algorithm parameter values decided, we then evaluate the algorithm effectiveness and the profiling cost with limited number of attack trials for each combination of d and f in the profiling round. We define profiling cost as the total number of attack trials spent in the profiling algorithm, since in our problem setting each trial corresponds to a self-driving trip the attacker needs to take, *e.g.*, from a targeted self-driving taxi service. For each attack trial, we limit its maximum duration to 90 seconds, which generally covers over 95% of the successful cases according to our earlier evaluation on attack success time (§8.6.2).

Fig. 8.11 shows the average success rates of the d and f output by the profiling algorithm and the average numbers of 90-sec profiling trips under different numbers of attack trials in each profiling round. In each profiling round, we randomly sample the corresponding number of attack trials from all attack starting points in the profiling traces. As shown, the average success rate increases as the attacker spends more trials in each profiling round since with more trials, the profiled success rate of a d and f combination in a profiling round is statistically closer to the ground truth. Particularly, when the number of trials in each profiling round is 40, our profiling algorithm can find a d and f combination with over 80% average success rate for both off-road and wrong-way attacks (84.2% and 80.7% respectively). In this case, *the profiling cost is only 42 1.5-minute trips on average, which in total is only slightly over 1 hour*. Since the attackers can actively perform such trials, *e.g.*, by requesting self-driving taxi services themselves, finishing this should take at most half a day.

8.9 Limitation and Defense Discussions

8.9.1 Limitations of Our Study

Study representativeness. As the first work to study the security of MSF-based AD localization, we choose to focus on the most representative design, KF-based MSF, and the most representative implementation we can find, BA-MSF (representativeness discussed in §8.2.1). However, it is still unclear whether other less common MSF designs (*e.g.*, particle filter based [228]) and outlier detection designs (*e.g.*, expectation-maximization based [266]) can be more secure, which can be potential future work directions.

Attack generality. Although our results have shown the generality of FusionRipper by showing high success rates on 3 different KF-based MSFs (§8.6.4), only one (BA-MSF) of them is production-grade implementation for AD systems. Ideally it is better to evaluate on other production-grade ones, but very unfortunately BA-MSF is the only one that is publicly available so far and it is unlikely for other AV companies to publicly release their implementations in the near future. Thus, due to the lack of information, it is unclear whether other leading AV companies, *e.g.*, Waymo and GM, are vulnerable to our attack. Nevertheless, since BA-MSF is representative both at the design and implementation levels (§8.2.1) and our attack is general to KF-based MSF by design (§8.4.2), if other AV companies also adopt such a representative design, at least at design level they are also susceptible to the discovered take-over vulnerability. Thus, as the first study, we believe our current discovery and evaluation results can already most generally benefit the understanding of the security property of MSF-based AD localization today.

Attack practicality. We evaluate FusionRipper on real-world traces and under various practical factors such as spoofing inaccuracies and AD control taking effect (§8.7). To further improve the attack practicality, we design an offline attack parameter profiling method that can achieve 84.2% and 80.7% success rates for off-road and wrong-way attacks, with the profiling cost of at most half a day. Nevertheless, due to the cost and legal regulation for GPS spoofing, we did not conduct attack experiments on real-world AVs, which thus can be a valuable future work. Note that GPS spoofing has been proven practical on various end systems [74, 79, 81, 189–193], including cars such as Tesla cars [79] (§8.2.2). Moreover, in this work, we model GPS spoofing based on attack capabilities shown in prior work [81, 191, 193] to minimize any unrealistic assumptions.

As mentioned in §8.3.2, we assume the attacker owns an AV and can leverage AD perception algorithms to track the physical position of the victim. Although accurate position-tracking of surrounding obstacles is a basic task for AVs, we did not conduct physical-world experiments to confirm this, which is thus left as a valuable future work.

8.9.2 Defense Discussions

In this section, we discuss the potential defense directions against FusionRipper.

Defend against GPS spoofing. Our attack depends on GPS spoofing, so one direct defense direction is to leverage existing GPS spoofing detection or prevention techniques. Unfortunately, neither GPS spoofing detection nor prevention are fully-solve problems today. On the detection side, numerous techniques have been proposed leveraging signal power monitoring [267–269], multi-antenna based signal arrival angle detection [268, 270], or crowdsourcing based cross-validation [271]. However, they either can be circumvented by more advanced spoofers [74, 268] or are only applicable to limited domains such as airborne GPS receivers [271]. On the prevention side, cryptographic authentication based civilian GPS infrastructure can fundamentally prevent direct fabrications of GPS signals [268]. However, it requires significant modifications to the existing satellite infrastructure and GPS receivers, and is still vulnerable to replay attacks [272]. Thus, one interesting future

work direction is to more concretely understand how effective the latest GPS spoofing defenses can be against the current or adapted versions of FusionRipper.

Improve confidence of MSF state and LiDAR locator. Another fundamental defense direction is to improve the positioning confidence of MSF state and LiDAR locator, the two most important factors to the take-over vulnerability in real-world trace (§8.4). Fundamentally, such lacks of confidence in practice result from algorithm inaccuracies and sensor noises (§8.4), and as shown in our analysis, even for the high-end sensors and production-grade LiDAR locator used in AVs today, these inaccuracies and noises are unfortunately large and frequent enough for FusionRipper to exploit. To improve on this, substantial technology breakthrough in sensing and LiDAR-based localization needs to take place. Unfortunately, it is unclear when such breakthrough can take place.

Leverage independent positioning sources (e.g., camera-based lane detection) as fail-safe features for high-level AD localization. Since fundamental defense directions above are not immediately deployable, it is highly desired to discuss the possibility of short-term mitigation solutions. One promising direction is to leverage independent positioning sources to cross-check the localization results and thus serve as *fail-safe* features for AD localization. For example, since both off-road and wrong-way attacks will cause the victim AV to deviate from the current lane, they should be detectable by *camera-based lane detection* [273], a mature technology available in many vehicle models today [274]. However, we find that in the high-level AD system design today, such a technology has not been generally considered for fail-safe purposes. For example, the latest release of Baidu Apollo (version 5.5) uses it only for camera calibration [72], while Autoware does not use it at all [73]. This might be because the lane detection output is local positioning within the current lane boundaries, and thus cannot be directly used for comparison against global positioning from MSF. However, the vulnerability discovered in this work strongly motivates the need for considering adding such kind of fail-safe features in future AD localization, at least for *anomaly detection*. Note that more investigations are needed to understand how effective and robust such kind of fail-safe features can be in the defense. For example, when camera-based lane detection is applied for anomaly detection, the precision/recall rates need to be further explored since it needs to carefully consider (1) AVs legitimately deviating from current lane due to routing requirements, and (2) lane line scratches or incompleteness. Moreover, camera-based lane detection itself is vulnerable to physical-world attacks [275, 276].

Note that even if such fail-safe features can perform perfect attack detection, our attack still causes denial-of-service of the victim’s global localization function, which can render the victim in unsafe scenarios, e.g., stopping in the middle of highway lanes, since the victim can neither correctly reach the destination nor safely locate the road shoulder to pull over. Thus, a more useful defense direction is to *correct* the attacked localization results. However, so far the global positioning accuracy of cameras is unsatisfying for high-level AD localization, especially along the longitudinal direction (forward/backward) since only the stop lines can be used as features [201, 277]. This is why LiDAR locator is used more predominantly in high-level AD localization (§8.2.1). Moreover, such correction is yet another multi-sensor fusion problem and thus is still fundamentally vulnerable to the take-over vulnerability discovered in this work (§8.4). Thus, how to leverage other independent positioning sources to effectively perform such correction under our attack is still an open research challenge, which can be a valuable future work direction.

8.10 Related Work

GPS spoofing on navigation systems. Recently, Zeng *et al.* [81] find that GPS spoofing can be used to stealthily deviate a victim car to an attacker-controlled destination. Later Narain *et al.* [191] further find that such attack also exists for a GPS/INS (Inertial Navigation System) navigation system. Compared to our work on MSF-based localization, these prior works target single-source localization systems without fusion from other position sources, such as a LiDAR locator.

Theoretical work on KF security. Existing theoretical works [241–244] from the control systems domain have studied the security of KF under sensor spoofing. Compared to our work, they only study single-source KFs without any sensor fusion. Also, they focus on the theoretical aspect of the KF and assume the attacker has full access to the KF internals, *e.g.*, KF state and uncertainties. In comparison, our work does not make such assumptions and hence is much more realistic.

AV-related attacks and defenses. Various previous works studied security problems on traditional vehicle systems [171, 278, 279], but not AD systems. Closer to this work, prior works discovered various sensor attack vectors on sensors related to AD systems, such as camera, LiDAR, IMU, radar, and ultrasonic sensors [27, 84, 188, 280–282]. However, none of them considers how to leverage these attack vectors to attack AD localization. On the defense side, recently Choi *et al.* [283] and Quinonez *et al.* [284] propose to use control or physical invariants to detect sensor attacks to small robotics vehicles such as drones and ground rovers. However, it is unclear how these methods can be effectively applied to AD systems, since AVs operate in highly complex and dynamic road conditions where the baseline/normal behaviors can be much harder to accurately model or predict.

8.11 Conclusion

In this work, we perform the first security study on MSF-based localization in high-level AV settings under GPS spoofing. We discover a take-over vulnerability that can fundamentally defeat the MSF design principle, and design FusionRipper, a novel and general attack that opportunistically captures and exploits it. Our evaluation on real-world traces shows that FusionRipper can achieve over 97% and 91.3% success rates in all traces for off-road and wrong-way attacks. Such high effectiveness is also found highly robust to various practical factors. We also design an offline method that can identify effective attack parameters within at most half a day. We also discuss both long-term and short-term defenses directions, and identify that a promising mitigation is to use camera-based lane detection as a fail-safe feature, which has not been generally considered for such purpose today. As the first study on AD localization security, we hope that our findings and insights can bring immediate attention and inspire the development of effective defenses considering the critical role of localization for safe and correct AV driving.

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8.12 Appendix: Calculation of Required Deviations in Attack Goals and Distances to Lane Line

The required deviations under off-road and wrong-way attacks are calculated based on common widths of the AV, lane, and road shoulder. These values differ in local and highway settings. Fig. 8.12 shows the measurements we used in the calculation. For the AV width, we use the width (including mirrors) of the Baidu Apollo’s reference car, Lincoln MKZ [285]. For the lane widths and shoulder widths, we refer to the design guidelines [286] published by the US Department of Transportation Federal Highway Administration. For off-road attack, we use the deviation when the AV goes *beyond* the road shoulder from the center of the lane as the required deviation, which is calculated using $\frac{L-C}{2} + S = 0.895m$ (local) and $1.945m$ (highway), where L is the lane width, C is the car width, and S is the road shoulder width. For wrong-way attack, we define the required deviation as the AV completely invades the neighbor lane, and it is calculated with $\frac{L}{2} + \frac{C}{2} = 2.405m$ (local) and $2.855m$ (highway). We calculate the deviation of *touching the lane line* using $\frac{L-C}{2}$, which is $0.295m$ on local roads and $0.745m$ on the highway.

Figure 8.12: Common AV, traffic lane, and road shoulder widths used in this chapter.

Figure 8.13: Visualization of the lateral deviation 0.45 meters on local and highway roads.

8.13 Appendix: Convert Steering to Lateral Position and Heading Rate Changes

Fig. 8.14 shows the mathematical conversion from the steering angle to physical world lateral position change. The position change can be calculated as $\delta_{\text{pos}} = vt \sin(\frac{\theta}{\phi})$, where v is the velocity, t is the cycle time of the controller, θ is the steering angle, and ϕ is the steering ratio, which is a constant describing the ratio of the turning angle of the steering wheel to that of the vehicle wheel. The steering angle can be directly converted to heading rate change using $\delta_{\omega} = \theta/\phi t$, where δ_{ω} is the yaw (*i.e.*, heading) rate change.

Figure 8.14: Conversion from the steering wheel angle to lateral position change.

Figure 8.15: Profiling results when using different (a) minimum profiling success rates, and (b) safe profiling thresholds.

Chapter 9

Anomaly Detection Against GPS Spoofing Attacks on Connected and Autonomous Vehicles Using Learning from Demonstration

GPS spoofing attacks pose great challenges to connected vehicle (CVs) safety applications and localization of autonomous vehicles (AVs). In this chapter, we propose to utilize transportation and vehicle engineering domain knowledge to detect GPS spoofing attacks towards CVs and AVs. A novel detection method using learning from demonstration is developed, which can be implemented in both vehicles and at the transportation infrastructure. A computational-efficient driving model, which can be learned from historical trajectories of the vehicles, is constructed to predict normal driving behaviors. Then a statistical method is developed to measure the dissimilarities between the observed trajectory and the predicted normal trajectory for anomaly detection. We validate the proposed method using two threat models (i.e., attacks targeting the multi-sensor fusion system of AVs and attacks targeting the intersection movement assist application of CVs) on two real-world datasets (i.e., KAIST and Michigan roundabout dataset). Results show that the proposed model is able to detect almost all of the attacks in time with low false positive and false negative rates.

This activity was originally reported in [9].

9.1 Introduction

Connected vehicles (CVs) and autonomous vehicles (AVs) benefit the transportation system from multiple aspects including reducing crashes, improving mobility and sustainability. In both types of vehicles, the localization module, from which the vehicle knows its global and local positions in the driving environment, plays a critical role in information sharing and vehicle navigation. For example, the Basic Safety Messages (BSMs) broadcast by CVs contain vehicle location and motion data for a wide range of applications [287–289], and AVs utilize the localization results for trajectory planning [98]. Among all sensors that participate in localization, the GPS receiver is the most important one that obtains global positions. Commercial-level GPS receivers can achieve an accuracy of 1 meter, and with dual-frequency GPS units, survey-grade GPS has an accuracy of a few centimeters [290]. Besides GPS, LiDAR locators and Inertial Measurement Units (IMU) are also implemented and tested on AVs [195, 200, 202] for localization purposes. It is critical to ensure that the localization module is accurate, reliable, and highly secure since inaccurate localization

results will significantly jeopardize AV trajectory planning and CV safety applications and may cause catastrophic consequences such as crashes.

Unfortunately, existing studies show that vehicle localization module is vulnerable to various types of cyberattacks. Spoofing attack is an emerging issue in modern GPS applications. The GPS spoofing attack generates fabricated GPS signals and interferes with the GPS receivers, which can degrade the performance of the localization system. The fake GPS signal usually has a higher strength to mislead the GPS receiver [291]. The practicality of the GPS spoofing attack has been proved in both research [75, 292] and real-world applications [293, 294]. In addition to the GPS spoofing attack, attacks targeting other sensors can also impact vehicle localization. For example, Petit et al. attacked the LiDAR by injecting false reflected light, and the LiDAR falsely detected a fake wall [84]. Although such LiDAR sensor attacks do not directly target the localization module, misinterpretation of the surrounding environment will also degrade the performance of the LiDAR locator, which is an important input source to the localization module. Usually, Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) algorithms are considered as one defense method against sensor attacks since it is highly unlikely that all sensors are compromised at the same time. However, a recent study from Shen et al. managed to construct an MSF attack method, which misleads the sensor fusion algorithms by only spoofing the GPS channel [75].

In general, anomaly detection is applied to defend against GPS spoofing attacks, which can be divided into two categories, node centric detection and data centric detection [295]. In the **node centric detection**, it examines the patterns in the behavior of specific nodes at the protocol level, which usually does not consider data semantics. Signatures are adopted to identify if the sender of the messages is malicious. The node centric detection can be further classified as behavioral or trust-based. The behavioral mechanism checks the packet header and metamessage information to detect the anomaly. Common behavioral mechanisms include watchdog [296] and flooding detection [297]. Trust-based mechanisms aggregate the trust of a node and distribute the trust among nodes to filter the malicious nodes. Trust-based mechanisms are usually vulnerable to Sybil attacks.

Different from node centric mechanisms, **data centric detection** mainly focus on data semantics, which can also be categorized into two groups, consistency-based and plausibility-based [295]. The consistency-based method examines the relations between packets to identify the anomaly of the newly received data. A cooperative approach can be adopted to analyze the information from multiple agents to identify conflicting messages [298, 299].

Plausibility-based methods filter out the packets according to the numerical plausibility value contained by the data received, which can be utilized to detect attacks with Sybil nodes. A majority of the plausibility-based detection focus on signal-based method [300–302]. The main shortage of signal-based methods is generalizability. For example, the method proposed for the anomaly detection of a GPS-only localization system may not be suitable for an MSF localization system. Another plausibility-based detection method is prediction-based. The prediction-based methods focus on predicting the behavior of vehicles and comparing the prediction with the observations. Kalman filter based approach is the most common method in this direction [303–305], in which the future trajectory of the vehicle is predicted with a Kalman filter. Other than only predicting the positions of vehicles, vehicle dynamics can be also integrated into the prediction-based mechanisms. For example, in [306], vehicle dynamics are considered to predict the bounding boxes of vehicles. The prediction-based methods can be viewed as driving model-based methods that make predictions of the vehicles to detect the anomaly. Such driving model-based methods may not be generalized to different driving scenarios (e.g. highway / urban).

Recent studies applied learning-based approaches to detect GPS spoofing attacks. Dasgupta et al. [307] implemented an LSTM neural network to predict AV’s travel distance between two consecutive timestamps. Spoofing attack detection was implemented based on the difference between

the perceived location shift and predicted location shift. Jiang et al. [308] applied deep neural networks to estimate vehicle speed and direction sequence and infer vehicle positions. A dynamic Time Wrapping algorithm was applied to measure the similarity between the reported and predicted trajectories. Note that both methods need thousands of vehicle trajectories in the training process, which may take a very long time to collect.

In this work, a new prediction based method is proposed, which combines model-driven and data-driven approaches for GPS spoofing attack detection, and is proved to have better generalizability in the experiments. The central hypothesis is that if the data in the GPS signal is compromised, the resultant information sharing from CVs or trajectory planning from AVs will be impacted, which generates abnormal driving behaviors (i.e., abnormal vehicle trajectories). Following this direction, transportation and vehicle domain knowledge is applied with the learning from demonstration framework. This method can be deployed in both vehicles and transportation infrastructure.

Figure 9.1 illustrates the concept of the proposed anomaly detection method. For the AV deployment, illustrated by the yellow block, the anomaly detection module is located before the trajectory planning module. Three types of information are used as the input to the detection module. First, information of the AV's principle other vehicles (POVs) captured by onboard sensors. The POVs are defined as nearby vehicles that may influence the behaviors of the AV (e.g., a leading vehicle in the same lane). Second, a digital map that contains roadway geometry information. Third, the localization results provided by the localization module. In the anomaly detection module, the normal driving behavior of the AV is represented by a computational-efficient driving model, which can be learned from the historical trajectories of the AV. The normal driving behavior is then compared with the trajectories from the localization module to detect the anomaly.

Figure 9.1: Concept of abnormal trajectory detection

For infrastructure deployment, a CV environment is assumed. In figure 9.1, the traffic scenario below the yellow block illustrates the anomaly detection concept at the infrastructure side. CVs broadcast their localization results in the form of BSMS. The infrastructure is equipped with Roadside Unit (RSU) to collect BSMS from the CVs and learns normal driving behaviors. When a CV is under a GPS spoofing attack, it broadcasts BSMS with falsified data elements such as location and speed. The infrastructure compares the learned normal driving behavior and the received CV trajectory to detect the anomaly and send warnings to the victim CV and nearby vehicles. Notice that in this case, we assume that the infrastructure does not have other sensors (e.g., cameras) to cross validate the integrity of the communication messages.

The most important component in the proposed anomaly detection framework is learning normal driving behaviors. Toward this end, we apply the learning from demonstration framework, in which an agent can learn expert behaviors with demonstrations (i.e., examples). The demonstrations are state-action pairs collected from a teacher when he/she performs certain tasks. In this work, learning from demonstration is implemented to learn a computational-efficient CV/AV driving model in different driving scenarios. After collecting a sufficient number of historical trajectories as the demonstrations, maximum entropy inverse reinforcement learning is adopted to derive the optimal driving policy (i.e., reward function). The learned driving policy is used to generate a predicted optimal trajectory, which is then compared with the observed trajectory to identify whether the observed trajectory is under attack or not. A statistical method is developed to measure the dissimilarities between the observed trajectory and the predicted optimal trajectory. With appropriate features that capture such dissimilarities, a decision-tree classifier is adopted to differentiate normal trajectories and trajectories under attack.

The proposed detection method is evaluated with two threat models. The first threat model aims at attacking the Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) based localization model of an AV. The goal of the attack is to generate lateral deviations to the original trajectory to make the subject AV hit the road curb or drive in the wrong direction. The second threat model aims at attacking the intersection movement assist (IMA) application on CVs. Experiments are conducted on two real-world datasets, KAIST [252] and Michigan roundabout datasets [309]. Experiment results show that the proposed model has a good performance in both offline detection and online detection with low false positive and false negative rates. Further adaptive attack study confirms the robustness of the model in detecting more stealthy attacks with reduced magnitude.

Contributions of this work are three-fold:

1. **We propose a generic detection framework to detect anomalies in the localization module of CV/AV using learning from demonstration.** The proposed detection framework directly examines the outputs of the localization module, regardless of the mechanism of the localization module and different attack types. Thus, it is generic and can be applied to detect various types of attacks. Moreover, the learning from demonstration framework requires much fewer data in the training process but still achieves very high accuracy.

2. **The proposed method integrates domain knowledge in detecting cyberattacks.** The methodology leverages transportation and vehicle domain knowledge to learn the driving policy through real-world demonstrations. Compared with other learning based approaches, our proposed framework requires much fewer data in the training stage. To our knowledge, this is the first work that utilizes learning from demonstration with domain specific knowledge for abnormal trajectory detection.

3. **The proposed detection method has low requirements for implementation.** For AV deployment, the anomaly detection requires onboard sensors and digital map information. Such onboard sensors and digital map information are standard for all the AV configurations [291, 310]. For infrastructure side deployment, no other infrastructure sensors are needed. The

required connected vehicle environment has been implemented and tested extensively in the past few years [311, 312].

The rest of the chapter is organized as follows: we first present the threat models (Section II). In section III, the methodology of the anomaly detection model is introduced. In section IV and V, the proposed model is validated on the AV threat model and CV threat model, respectively. Section VI extends the experiments on the AV threat model to adaptive attacks. Section VII concludes the chapter and lays out future research directions.

9.2 Threat model

9.2.1 Autonomous vehicle threat model

A real-world Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) attack conducted on the Baidu Apollo system is applied as the threat model for the AV anomaly detection [75]. In this study, a GPS spoofing attack towards the MSF-based localization system of AVs is designed, shown in Figure 9.2. At the top, the original MSF algorithm takes the input from GPS, IMU, and LiDAR to generate localization results. In the attack scenario, the GPS channel is spoofed by the FusionRipper algorithm proposed in [75], which can successfully mislead the MSF localization algorithm. The practicality of the GPS spoofing attack is also justified with existing literature in [75].

The FusionRipper algorithm consists of two phases: vulnerability profiling and aggressive spoofing. In the vulnerability profiling phase, the attacker performs a constant GPS spoofing attack and observes the localization results from the MSF system to profile when the vulnerable periods appear (i.e., lateral deviation ≥ 0.295 m on urban roads). After the vulnerable period is identified, the aggressive spoofing phase starts in which the attacker performs exponentially aggressive spoofing to quickly induce large lateral deviations. Two attack goals that cause safety hazards are considered, off-road (i.e., hitting road curbs) attack and wrong-way (i.e., driving to the opposite direction of the road) attack, and both attack goals are achieved by large lateral deviations. The off-road attack requires less lateral deviation (0.895m for urban roads) in the localization results to succeed than the wrong-way attack (1.945m for urban roads).

9.2.2 Connected vehicle threat model

In the CV environment, we choose a threat model towards the IMA system, which is an important CV safety application [313], [314]. The IMA application intends to warn the driver of the CV when it is unsafe to enter an unsignalized intersection in case of high collision probability with other vehicles. The application uses data (i.e., BSMs) received from other vehicles to determine if it is unsafe to enter the intersection. In this work, it is assumed that the IMA system only relies on the received CV messages (BSM) to trigger the warning [314]. In our study, we use a roundabout scenario to demonstrate the threat model.

The goal of the attack is to generate falsified BSMs through GPS spoofing to trigger the IMA warning of a CV. Figure 9.3 illustrates the concept of the attack. It is assumed that BSMs have lane level accuracy, which has been validated in previous studies [315]. In the figure, the blue rectangles denote the normal CV trajectory (i.e., true locations), which is located at the inner lane of the roundabout. The red rectangles represent the BSM trajectory under attack which changes lanes from the inner lane to the outer lane. The yellow rectangles denote the trajectory of the victim CV, located at the entry of the roundabout. A conflict point is defined as the intersection along the trajectories of the victim vehicle and the CV under attack. Given that lane changing behavior is not allowed in the roundabout, if the blue CV is not under attack, its trajectory should not conflict

Figure 9.2: Threat model on the AV MSF System

with the victim CV. The IMA warning should not be triggered at the victim CV. When the blue CV is under attack (becomes the red CV), the falsified lane change trajectory will trigger the IMA warning. The values within the rectangles denote timestamps, where at time t_0 , the attack starts. At time t_2 , the falsified BSM trajectory triggers the IMA warning of the victim (yellow) CV.

Figure 9.3: Threat model on intersection movement assist system

To generate feasible attack trajectories, the attack model is formulated as an optimization problem similar as in [316, 317]. The objective function contains two parts: 1) trigger the IMA warning of the victim CV; and 2) generate a smooth trajectory that is close to the real driving behavior. To achieve the first goal, the arrival time of the victim vehicle to the conflict point needs to be predicted. It is assumed that victim vehicle follows a constant speed to reach the conflict point. Based on the predicted arrival time, the first part of the objective function generates a lane change trajectory to reach the conflict point close to the arrival time of the victim CV to trigger the IMA warning. The second part of the objective function contains driving features such as minimizing acceleration and minimizing heading change rate.

The attack starts when the estimated arrival time to the conflict point between the vehicle under attack and the victim vehicle is less than 4s. The planning horizon for the attack trajectory is the same as the estimated arrival time for the victim vehicle to reach the conflict point. A rolling horizon scheme is applied, where the prediction is repeated every 0.4 seconds to minimize the prediction error. The attack trajectory is generated for the whole planning horizon, but only the first 0.4s will be executed. Assuming that the vehicle keeps a constant speed to reach the conflict point, Equation 9.1 denotes that the attack succeeds when the post encroachment time (PET) to the conflict point between the victim vehicle and the attack trajectory is less than T_g . D_{atk} denotes the distance to the conflict point. v_{atk} denotes the attack vehicle speed and T_g denotes the critical PET that triggers the IMA warning. In this work, $T_g = 2s$, which is consistent with existing studies ref [314].

$$D_{atk}/v_{atk} \leq T_g \quad (9.1)$$

9.3 Defense methodology

This section presents the anomaly detection method to identify the AV/CV attacks introduced in the previous section. There are two major challenges. **Challenge 1: real-time detection.** The operation of AV/CV is highly safety-critical. Therefore, it is vital to detect abnormal or hazardous driving behaviors in time. However, some GPS spoofing attacks can be stealthy (e.g., the first phase of the AV threat model in Section 9.2.1) while some can achieve the attack goal in a few seconds (e.g., the CV threat model in Section 9.2.2), which all pose great challenges in the detection model design. **Challenge 2: validity on different threat models.** Different threat models may cause different abnormal driving behaviors and a generic detection method is needed. It would be more meaningful if the anomaly detection method is effective under different types of attacks.

9.3.1 Defense framework

Figure 9.4 illustrates the anomaly detection framework consisting of two steps. On the left side (i.e., offline learning), learning from demonstration is adopted to learn the driving model via maximum entropy inverse reinforcement learning, using historical trajectories. Besides, a decision tree is trained with both historical trajectories and known attack trajectories by three features (objective ratio, normality score, and trajectory displacement). The trained models are applied in the online detection step as shown on the right side of the figure. When observing a trajectory from the localization module or from the CV, its initial state and environment state are utilized in the learned driving model to generate a predicted optimal trajectory, which is then compared with the observed trajectory in terms of the three features. The results are fed into the trained decision tree classifier, which will finally decide whether the vehicle is under attack or not.

9.3.2 Learning from demonstration

A general trajectory generation problem can be formulated as an optimization problem, shown in Equation 9.2. The objective of the optimization problem is the utility function of the driving behavior, in which θ is the weight vector associated with different driving utilities. \mathbf{s} is the decision variable of the optimization problem, which denotes the trajectory, a vector of trajectory points s_i . Each trajectory point s_i at time step i can be represented by $(x_i, y_i, v_i, a_i, \psi_i)$, in which x_i and y_i is the longitudinal and lateral coordinate, respectively, and ψ_i is the heading angle of the vehicle, between the longitudinal axis of the vehicle and the longitudinal direction of the road. v_i denotes the speed of the vehicle, and a_i denotes the acceleration. \mathbf{u} represents the initial condition and environment states, which serve as the input parameters for the optimization problem. The initial condition includes the initial position (x_0, y_0) , initial speed v_0 , initial acceleration a_0 , and initial heading angle ψ_0 . The environment states include the longitudinal coordinate and the lateral coordinate of the leading vehicle. $f(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{u})$ is a mapping function that maps the trajectory to a feature vector, which can be different under different maneuvers. The details of the features and vehicle dynamic constraints are introduced next.

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{s}} \quad & \theta^T f(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{u}) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \text{vehicle dynamic constraints} \end{aligned} \quad (9.2)$$

Figure 9.4: Anomaly detection framework

Vehicle dynamic constraints

The vehicle dynamic constraints represent the kinematics of vehicle motion, shown in Equations 9.3,9.4,9.5,9.6, where τ is the step size. Equation 9.3 reflects the relationship between the longitudinal coordinate change and the heading angle, and similarly, Equation 9.4 reflects the relationship between the lateral coordinate change and the heading angle. Equation 9.5 shows the relationship between the heading angle rate $\dot{\psi}$ and the heading angle. Equation 9.6 shows the vehicle dynamics between the velocity and the acceleration.

$$x(i+1) = x(i) + v(i)\cos(\psi(i) + \psi_r(i))\tau \quad (9.3)$$

$$y(i+1) = y(i) + v(i)\sin(\psi(i) + \psi_r(i))\tau \quad (9.4)$$

$$\dot{\psi}(i) = \frac{(\psi(i+1) - \psi(i))}{\tau} \quad (9.5)$$

$$a(i) = \frac{v(i+1) - v(i)}{\tau} \quad (9.6)$$

Feature vector

The feature vector represents a desired driving policy, which is a linear combination of multiple driving features. In our proposed model, nine features are designed to describe the driving policy including both longitudinal and lateral behaviors. The following provides detailed descriptions of the features, where N represents the total number of data points in a trajectory. In the AV experiment, (1) - (7) are selected as features, and in the CV experiment, (1)(2)(5)(6)(8)(9) are selected as features. The criteria for feature selection come from the differences in the driving scenarios. For example, feature 9 is selected for the CV experiment because we consider a roundabout scenario.

(1) Speed limit: $f_1 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (v_i - v^{lim})^2$. This feature measures the difference between the speed at each time step v_i and the speed limit v^{lim} , which models the driving incentive of approaching the desired speed (i.e., speed limit).

(2) Acceleration: $f_2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i a_i^2$. It is the summation of the square of the acceleration at each time step, which represents the smoothness of driving behaviors.

(3) Car following: $f_3 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \frac{1}{\min(d_i, d_i/v_i)^2}$. d_i is the distance to the leading vehicle at time step i . $\min(d_i, \frac{d_i}{v_i})$ chooses the smaller value between the distance and time headway. When the vehicle moves in free flow, the time headway makes an impact. When the vehicle is about to stop, the distance to the leading vehicle makes an impact. This feature models the car-following behavior of the vehicles.

(4) Lateral acceleration: $f_4 = \frac{1}{N} (a_i \sin(\psi_i))^2$. It is the summation of the square of the lateral acceleration at each time step, which measures the smoothness of lateral driving behaviors.

(5) Heading angle: $f_5 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \psi_i^2 (1 - I^{lanechange})$. ψ_i is the heading angle at time step i . $I^{lanechange}$ is the indicator of lane change, which is 1 if the heading angle between the longitudinal axis of the vehicle and the longitudinal direction of the road is larger than a threshold.

(6) Heading rate: $f_6 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (\dot{\psi}_i)^2$. $\dot{\psi}_i$ is the heading angle change rate at time step i .

(7) Heading rate rate: $f_7 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_i (\dot{\psi}_{i+1} - \dot{\psi}_i)^2$. This feature measures the change rate of the heading angle rate. Features 5-7 represent the smoothness of the heading angle to measure the smoothness of lateral driving behaviors of the vehicle.

(8) Interaction: $f_8 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \frac{1}{(x_i - x_i^{other})^2 + (y_i - y_i^{other})^2}$. This feature measures the interaction between two vehicles in Euclidean distance. Here, $(x_i^{other}, y_i^{other})$ denotes the position of the other interactive vehicle w.r.t. the ego vehicle at time step i .

(9) Curvature: $f_9 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (\sqrt{(x_i - x_i^c)^2 + (y_i - y_i^c)^2} - r_i)^2$. When the vehicle is turning, this feature captures the curvature following behavior. (x^c, y^c) is the center of the turning circle, and r denotes the turning radius.

Maximum Entropy Inverse Reinforcement Learning

Before solving the optimization problem, the weight vector θ needs to be determined, which balances the driving features in the feature vector. It is usually difficult to specify proper weights, which represent the desired driving policy. In this study, we apply maximum entropy inverse reinforcement learning to determine the weight vector θ . Considering the vehicle trajectory planning as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) with a discounted cost as Equation 9.7, in which γ is the discounted factor and r is a reward function. If the discounted factor is taken as 1, then the total return is $\theta^T f(s, u)$, for each trajectory s . The goal of inverse reinforcement learning is to find the weight vector θ that maximizes the log-likelihood function $L(\theta)$, shown in Equation 9.8. D is the demonstration trajectory dataset collected, including m trajectories. $P(s_j|\theta, u_j)$ is the probability of trajectory s_j given parameter θ and the initial condition as well as the environment state of trajectory s_j (i.e., u_j), so when maximizing $L(\theta)$, the likelihood of using weight θ to generate all trajectories in the dataset is maximized. When the policy of the MDP is the maximum entropy policy [318], $P(s_j|\theta, u_j)$ can be written as Equation 9.9.

$$\text{discountedcost} = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \gamma^i r(s_i) \approx \theta^T f(s, u) \quad (9.7)$$

$$L(\theta) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{s_j \in D} \ln P(s_j|\theta, u_j) \quad (9.8)$$

$$p(s_j|\theta, u_j) = \frac{e^{-\theta^T f(s_j, u_j)}}{\sum_{s_k \in C_j} e^{-\theta^T f(s_k, u_j)}} \quad (9.9)$$

In this way, the gradient of $L(\theta)$ can be calculated as Equation 9.10, in which $\tilde{f} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{s_j \in D} f(s_j, u_j)$ denotes the empirical feature vector. Thus, the gradient of $L(\theta)$ is the difference between the expected feature vector with respect to weight θ and the empirical feature vector calculated from the dataset (i.e., observations). Furthermore, the expected feature vector can be approximated by the feature vector of the most likely trajectory.

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\theta} L(\theta) &= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{s_j \in D} E_{p(s_j|\theta, u_j)}[f(s_j, u_j)] - \tilde{f} \\ &\approx \frac{1}{m} \sum_{s_j \in D} f(\text{argmin}_{s_j} \theta^T f(s_j, u_j)) - \tilde{f} \end{aligned} \quad (9.10)$$

With the gradient of the log-likelihood function, the pseudo-code of the maximum entropy inverse reinforcement learning algorithm can be summarized in Algorithm 1, given a set of demonstration trajectories $D = s_1, \dots, s_m$.

9.3.3 Anomaly Classifier

To differentiate normal trajectories from abnormal ones, the difference between the observed trajectory and the predicted optimal trajectory should be measured quantitatively by some statistics. In this work, three statistical features are adopted. The first statistical feature is the maximum

Algorithm 7 Maximum Entropy Inverse Reinforcement Learning

- 1: Compute the empirical feature vector over all demonstrations $\tilde{f}_0 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{s_j \in D} f(s_j, u_j)$. Normalize the feature vector. The normalized feature vector is denoted as \tilde{f}
 - 2: Initialize every entry of the weight vector θ .
 - 3: **while** $\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m f(s_j^\theta, u_j) - \tilde{f} > threshold$ **do**
 - 4: **for** For each demonstrated trajectory in the dataset **do**
 - 5: Fix the initial condition and the environment states and optimize the trajectory using equation 9.2. The optimized trajectories are denoted as $s_1^\theta, \dots, s_m^\theta$.
 - 6: **end for**
 - 7: The gradient can be calculated as $\nabla_\theta L(\theta) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m f(s_j, u_j) - \tilde{f}$.
 - 8: Update the parameter vector: $\theta(k+1) = \theta(k) + \gamma \nabla_\theta L(\theta)$, in which γ is the learning rate.
 - 9: **end while**
-

value of the objective ratio OR_t of all the trajectory points until time step t , calculated by Equation 9.11. OR_t represents the ratio between the summation of the objective value of the observed trajectory (i.e., $\sum_{\tau=1}^t observed\ objective_\tau$) and the summation of the objective value of the predicted optimal trajectory via the learned model (i.e., $\sum_{\tau=1}^t optimal\ objective_\tau$) at time step t . It measures how different the observed trajectory is from the optimal trajectory.

$$OR = \max_{1..t} OR_t = \frac{\sum_{\tau=1}^t observed\ objective_\tau}{\sum_{\tau=1}^t optimal\ objective_\tau} \quad (9.11)$$

The second statistical feature adopted is the max value of the normality score NS_t of all the observed trajectory points until time step t , calculated by Equation 9.12. NS_t measures the variation of the objective value of the observed trajectory. $objective_t$ denotes the objective value of the observed trajectory at time step t . $objective\ mean_{1..t}$ is the mean objective value of all the observed time steps until t , $objective\ std_{1..t}$ is the standard deviation of the objective value of all the observed time steps until t .

$$NS = \max_{1..t} NS_t = \frac{objective_t - objective\ mean_{1..t}}{objective\ std_{1..t}} \quad (9.12)$$

The last statistical feature is the maximum value of the average displacement error ED_t with the prediction horizon of T between the observed trajectory and optimized trajectory at time step t , calculated by Equation 9.13. The average displacement error at time step t (i.e. ED_t) can be calculated by measuring the average point-wise Euclidean distance between the observed trajectory (x^{obs}, y^{obs}) and the predicted trajectory (x^{pred}, y^{pred}) within the prediction horizon T . This feature captures the difference between the observation and the optimization results in terms of the Euclidean distance in the 2-D space.

$$\begin{aligned} ED &= \max_{1..t} ED_t \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=t}^{t+T} \sqrt{(x_i^{obs} - x_i^{pred})^2 + (y_i^{obs} - y_i^{pred})^2} \end{aligned} \quad (9.13)$$

With three statistical features defined as the input, a decision tree classifier is applied to differentiate the abnormal trajectories from normal trajectories. More information of the decision tree classifier can be found in [319].

9.4 Detection model evaluation on AV threat model

The AV threat model (i.e., FusionRipper [75]) is implemented on the KAIST Complex Urban dataset [252], which is an AV driving dataset in both urban and highway driving scenarios based on the Apollo system. Figure 9.5 illustrates a sample trajectory (in red) that consists of both urban and highway driving scenarios in the KAIST dataset. The dataset provides raw data from Lidar, stereo camera, GPS, and IMU. The FusionRipper algorithm takes them as the input and applies the MSF module in Apollo to obtain the compromised localization results. Specifically, lateral deviations are added to the original trajectory data. In this study, the deviated trajectory generated by FusionRipper is considered as the trajectory under attack. Meanwhile, we extract the original AV trajectories in the data as ground truth.

Figure 9.5: A sample trajectory in KAIST dataset

9.4.1 Data processing

Before applying the proposed detection method, the original KAIST trajectory data set needs to be processed to calculate two additional data elements (road orientation and car-following distance) that are needed for the proposed learning from demonstration model. The heading angle of the trajectory is the relative angle between the longitudinal axis of the vehicle and the longitudinal direction of the road, but the road orientation is not included in the raw data. To calculate the relative heading angle, vehicle trajectories are allocated to the closest road segment on the

OpenStreetMap [320], and then the road orientation is extracted from the waypoints of the OpenStreetMap. In the feature vector, the distance to the leading vehicle is also required to calculate the car-following distance, which is extracted from the raw images from the forward-facing stereo cameras installed on the vehicle, using the YOLO (You only look once) algorithm [172]. The disparity of the detected vehicle between the left and right stereo camera is obtained from the images to calculate the distance to the leading vehicle using triangulation. Interpolation is applied when the front vehicle is missing. Figure 9.6 presents an example of the detected leading vehicle denoted by the yellow rectangle, and distance measurement in meters denoted by the red number. With the road orientation and distance to the leading vehicle processed, all the features in the learning from demonstration model can be calculated.

Figure 9.6: Vehicle detection and distance measurement result

9.4.2 Experiment setting

In total, 78 ground truth trajectories are obtained from the KAIST dataset. The ground truth trajectories include both in-lane driving and lane changing cases. We deliberately include the lane changing cases in the training dataset because the FusionRipper attack aims to create abnormal lateral deviations of a trajectory to achieve the off-road or wrong-way attack goal. It is critical to differentiate between a normal lane changing process, which also includes lateral deviations, and the lateral deviations caused by the attack. 51 ground truth trajectories are adopted in IRL to learn the driving model, which is significantly less than the trajectories used in other learning-based detection methods [307, 308]. 88 attacked trajectories from the FusionRipper attack and all ground truth trajectories are utilized in the experiments for detection.

In the experiments, we mainly evaluate the proposed detection method against the off-road attack, which requires less lateral deviation and thus is more difficult for the detection model. Two types of detection mechanisms, namely offline detection and online detection, are designed and evaluated. In the offline detection, the detection is performed after the full trajectory of the vehicle is observed. In the online detection mode, the anomaly classifier checks the trajectory every 0.5 seconds until classified as abnormal or reaching the end of the attack. The online detection mode is designed to detect the abnormal trajectories in real-time as soon as possible, which is critical to the safety performance of the AVs, but also more challenging.

9.4.3 Experiment results

Figure 9.7 illustrates the performance of the learning from demonstration model, by comparing a ground truth trajectory (i.e., green curve) with its corresponding predicted optimal trajectory from the learned model (i.e., blue curve). Subfigure (a) shows the position profile and subfigure (b) shows the speed profile. The prediction horizon is 2 seconds, indicating that the learned model takes an accurate position (i.e., the same as the ground truth position profile) and the corresponding speed as the input every 2 seconds. The generated trajectory is very close to the ground truth trajectory. To quantitatively measure the difference between the learned model and the ground truth trajectory, the Average Displacement Error (ADE) between the ground truth trajectory and the predicted optimal trajectory is calculated as 0.76m. The calculation of the ADE is based on the of ED_t in Equation 9.13. The ADE is less than 1m, which indicates that the predicted optimal trajectory fits the ground truth very well. Comparing with other learning-based approaches such as LSTM [321], the ADE is lower.

Based on the learned model, the value of the objective function of both observed trajectories and predicted optimal trajectories (by solving Equation 9.2) can be calculated by evaluating $\theta^T f(s, u)$, in which θ is optimized by the maximal entropy inverse reinforcement learning model. Intuitively, if the vehicle is not under attack, the value of the objective function calculated from the observed trajectory should be close to the value calculated from the predicted optimal trajectory. If the vehicle is under attack, then the two values should deviate from each other. Figure 9.8 illustrates a comparison of the objective values of the attacked trajectory, ground truth trajectory, and predicted optimal trajectory. The red curve is the objective of the attacked trajectory, and the green curve denotes the objective of the ground truth trajectory. The blue curves in both subfigures denote the objective value of the predicted optimal trajectory. In subfigure (a), when the attack is about to succeed (i.e., time ≥ 14 s), the objective value of the attacked trajectory deviates from the optimal value significantly. By comparing subfigures (a) and (b), the objective of the ground truth trajectory is much closer to its corresponding optimal objective value than the attacked trajectory.

Figure 9.9 shows the 3D (subfigure (a)) and 2D (subfigure (b)) scatter plots of the decision tree classification result. The red dots represent the attacked trajectories, and the black dots represent the ground truth trajectories. In the 3D scatter plot, three axes represent the three statistical features introduced in section 9.3.3, which are objective ratio, normality score, and average displacement error. With three features, the normal trajectories in the ground truth can be separated from the attacked trajectories, as shown in the 3D scatter plot. Subfigure (b) shows the distribution of trajectories if the average displacement error feature is removed. The classifier is difficult to differentiate since the normal trajectories and the attacked trajectories are mixed together. The scatter plots illustrate that the choice of these three statistical features is appropriate.

Next, we show the results of the offline and online detection respectively. In the offline detection, false positive (Type I error) indicates that a ground truth trajectory is classified as an attacked trajectory. On the contrary, false negative (Type II error) means that an attacked trajectory is not identified correctly. The false positive rate of offline detection is 8.7% (2/23), and the false negative rate is 3.7% (1/27). Figure 9.10 illustrates a false positive case and a false negative case. In subfigure (a) and (b), green curves represent the ground truth trajectories in the dataset, and the blue curves denote the optimized trajectories, respectively. Subfigure (a) shows the false positive case in the 2-D space, in which the optimized trajectory does not fit the ground truth very well, compared to a true positive case in subfigure (b) where the optimized trajectories almost overlap with the ground truth trajectory. The reason for the unsatisfying fitting in the false positive case is that the road orientation at this road segment calculated from the map data is not accurate. The KAIST dataset doesn't contain HD map information, we use the OpenStreetMap in calculating

(a)

(b)

Figure 9.7: Comparison between a ground truth trajectory and a predicted optimal trajectory ((a): trajectory profile in 2-D space. (b): speed profile)

(a)

(b)

Figure 9.8: Objective value comparison of the attacked trajectory and the ground truth trajectory ((a): objective value comparison of an attacked trajectory (b): objective value comparison of a ground truth trajectory)

(a)

(b)

Figure 9.9: Scatter plot of the classification problem ((a): scatter plot with three features. (b): scatter plot with two features.)

Figure 9.10: Misclassification examples of the KAIST experiments ((a): trajectory profile of the FP case. (b): baseline trajectory profile for the FP case. (c) heading rate profile of the FN case)

the road orientation. Thus, the optimized trajectory tries to follow the road direction within the prediction horizon and deviates from the ground truth trajectory. Such an issue may be resolved when the AV is equipped with a HD map, which is a standard module. Subfigure (c) shows the heading rate profile of the false negative case that an attacked trajectory is misclassified. The red curve denotes the heading rate profile of the attacked trajectory, and the blue curve denotes the heading rate profile from a ground truth trajectory. The heading rate is a key feature in the learned driving model, and in this case, the heading rate of the attacked trajectory is similar to the heading rate of the ground truth trajectory, which makes the attacked trajectory difficult to be identified.

Figure 9.11 further shows the heading rate profile comparison, which reveals the reason why the attacked trajectories can be differentiated from the ground truth trajectories. The red curve denotes the heading rate profile of the attacked trajectory, and the green curve denotes the heading rate profile of the ground truth trajectory. The blue curves in both subfigures denote the heading rate profiles of the corresponding predicted optimal trajectories. Notice that the heading rate profiles of the predicted optimal trajectories fluctuate every 2 seconds since the prediction horizon is 2 seconds. In subfigure (a), the heading rate profile of the attacked trajectory has larger fluctuations compared to the predicted optimal trajectory. The ground truth trajectory, on the contrary, has smaller values and small fluctuations. Such differences are reflected in the objective function value, which is one feature in the classification model.

In the online detection, the anomaly classifier checks the trajectory every 0.5 seconds. The performance of the online detection is shown in Table 9.1. The false positive rate is 8.7% (2/23), and the false negative rate is 3.7% (1/27), which is the same as the offline detection results. For online detection, it is important to identify the attacked trajectory as early as possible, but at least before the attack succeeds. Therefore, we further calculate the mean detection time to compare it with the mean attack success time. The mean success time of the off-road attack is 28.7 s, and the mean detection time is 12.7 s. The time to attack success is defined as the time duration from the success time of the detection to the success time of the attack, which measures how early the attack can be detected before attack success. In the online detection, the attacked trajectories can be identified 16.0 s before the attack success time on average.

Table 9.1: Performance of online detection

FP	FN	Mean attack success time (s)	Mean detection time (s)	Mean time to attack success (s)
2/23	1/23	28.7	12.7	16.0

Figure 9.12 further illustrates the detection time (i.e., blue bars) in the online detection, compared to the duration of attack phases one and two. The green bars denote the duration of phase one (i.e., vulnerability profiling), and the red bars denote the attack success time, which is the end of phase two (i.e., aggressive spoofing). In general, except for the false negative case 7109, the detection time of all other test cases is not longer than the attack success time, which indicates that the anomaly classifier can successfully detect the spoofing attack before it achieves the attack goal. For most of the test cases, the detection time is even less than the duration of the vulnerability profiling phase, which leaves sufficient time for applying further mitigation strategies.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9.11: Heading rate profiles of the attacked trajectory and the ground truth trajectory ((a): attacked trajectory. (b): ground truth trajectory)

Figure 9.12: Detection time in online anomaly detection for KAIST experiments

9.5 Detection model evaluation on CV threat model

To validate the CV threat model, experiments are conducted using a dataset collected from a two-lane roundabout in Ann Arbor, Michigan [309]. Infrastructure sensors (i.e. cameras and radars) are installed at the four corners of the roundabout, to detect all vehicles approaching and entering the roundabout. The trajectory dataset is collected at a 2.5 Hz frequency in a 24/7 manner. Figure 9.13 illustrates the trajectory overview at the two-lane roundabout

In this experiment, 841 ground truth trajectories from the dataset are extracted. 809 attack trajectories are generated with the attack model illustrated in Section 9.2.2. Overall, there are 1650 trajectories in the experiment. 182 ground truth trajectories are utilized in learning the driving model with IRL, which is still much fewer compared with other learning-based detection algorithms [307, 308]. 70% of the trajectories in the dataset are used as the training data, and the rest 30% are used as the testing data. Compared to the threat model for AV, the CV threat model is much more aggressive with a much shorter attack duration, which greatly increases the difficulty for both offline and online detection. Besides, the frequency of the ground truth data is only 2.5 Hz, which also makes the defense more challenging. Similar as in the AV case, in offline detection, the detection is performed after the full trajectory of the vehicle is observed. In online detection, after a sufficient number of trajectory points are observed from a vehicle (e.g., 5 data points), the online detection is conducted at every time step.

In offline detection, the false positive rate is 0.004% (1 out of 252), and the false negative rate is 2.0% (5 out of 243). Overall, the anomaly detection model shows a very good performance in offline detection. In online detection, the anomaly classifier checks the trajectory every 0.4 seconds until classified as abnormal or reaching the end of the attack. Overall, the false positive rate is 0.008%

Figure 9.13: Trajectory overview at the two-lane roundabout

(2 out of 252), and the false negative rate is 0% (0 out of 243). Notice that in the online detection, all the attack trajectories can be identified by the proposed anomaly detector. Figure 9.14 shows the relationship between the detection time (blue bar) and the attack success time (orange bar) in the first 50 cases. All the cases can be detected before the attack success time, and the average detection time is 2.0 seconds after the attack starts. The average attack success time is 2.8 seconds, and the average time to attack success is 0.8 seconds. Thus, even with very short attack duration, the proposed anomaly detection still manages to identify the falsified trajectories before the attack succeeds.

Figure 9.15 shows a misclassification example of a false positive (FP) case in the online detection. The purple trajectory denotes the trajectory of the vehicle at the entrance link. The orange trajectory denotes a ground truth trajectory traversing the roundabout, and the black trajectory with crosses denotes the predicted optimal trajectory w.r.t. the orange trajectory. The x-axis and y-axis represent the local coordinate system in meters. In 3.6 seconds, the ground truth trajectory drives 12.7 m in total, and the average speed of the vehicle in the roundabout is only 3.5 m/s. Such low speed is very rare at this roundabout, which makes the proposed anomaly detector consider it as an abnormal trajectory. In fact, identifying this uncommon behavior in the ground truth trajectory also enriches the usage of the proposed anomaly detection framework. Other than detecting cyber attacks, this method may also be utilized to identify abnormal driving behaviors.

Figure 9.14: Detection time in online anomaly detection for roundabout experiments

9.6 Detection on adaptive attack

To further evaluate the capability of the proposed anomaly detection model, an adaptive attack scenario is designed and implemented. In the AV threat model, the key idea is to add lateral deviations to the original trajectory, which either causes the subject AV hit the roadside, or leads to the emergency behavior of the victim vehicle. To make the attack more stealthy and difficult to be detected, the adaptive attack reduces the magnitude of the lateral deviations added to the ground truth trajectory, and we use the adaptive ratio to represent the significance of the magnitude reduction, ranging from 0 to 1. Figure 9.16 shows an example of the adaptive attack implemented on the KAIST dataset. The green curve denotes the ground truth trajectory that is not attacked (i.e., adaptive ratio = 0). The blue curve denotes the original attack trajectory that is evaluated in section 9.4 (i.e., adaptive ratio = 1). The orange curve denotes the trajectory under adaptive attack, with the adaptive ratio of 0.5. Notice that the lateral deviations of the orange trajectory are half of the lateral deviations of the original attack trajectory, w.r.t. the ground truth trajectory. In this way, as the adaptive ratio decreases, the adaptive attack trajectories become more and more similar to the ground truth trajectory. The adaptive attack trajectories with a very small adaptive ratio (e.g., 0.1) can be very close to the ground truth trajectories, which are very difficult to identify.

The adaptive attack is implemented on the KAIST dataset with the adaptive ratios of 0.8, 0.5, and 0.2. The experiment setting is the same as in section 9.4, and the driving models and the decision tree classifier are also the same. Table 9.2 shows the anomaly detection performance on the adaptive attack. When the adaptive ratio is 0.8, the performance of the anomaly detection degrades a little, with a false negative rate of 2/27. Nonetheless, the detection results are still satisfying,

Figure 9.15: Misclassification examples of the roundabout experiments (a FP case)

Figure 9.16: Adaptive attack example on the KAIST dataset

and most of the attacked trajectories can be identified correctly. When the adaptive ratio is 0.5, the performance of the anomaly detection is the same as the performance with the adaptive ratio of 0.8. When the adaptive ratio is 0.2, the false negative rate become 10/27. However, in this case, the adaptive attack trajectories are very close to the ground truth trajectories. In the urban scenario, the success criterion of the off-road attack is 0.895 m [75]. With the adaptive ratio of 0.2, the final lateral deviation w.r.t. the ground truth trajectory is only 0.179 m. In such cases, the subject AV is still driving within the original lane. Although the proposed model fails to detect some attack trajectories, the consequence is not hazardous.

Table 9.2: Detection performance on the adaptive attack

Adaptive ratio	False positive	False negative
0.8	2/23	2/27
0.5	2/23	2/27
0.2	2/23	10/27

9.7 Discussion and Conclusion

In this work, an anomaly detection model using learning from demonstration is proposed to detect GPS spoofing attacks towards the localization system of the CV/AV. Maximum entropy inverse reinforcement learning is applied to learn the normal driving model. The learned driving model is then utilized to generate optimal vehicle trajectories which are compared with the observed vehicle trajectories using a decision tree classifier to determine whether the observed trajectories

are under attack. The proposed detection method is evaluated in two realistic GPS spoofing attacks on AV and CV, respectively.

In both AV and CV experiments, the proposed anomaly detection method can identify most of the abnormal trajectories before the attacks succeed. Such experiment results validate the generality of the proposed model. Notice that although in this chapter, the anomaly detection model is only validated by GPS spoofing attack experiments, we do not utilize any specific feature of GPS signals in the model. In other words, the proposed model has the potential to detect a variety of sensor attacks towards the localization system as well. The reason is that the key concept of the proposed model is to compare normal versus abnormal driving behaviors. Thus, it is not sensitive to the input types or states of the localization system. As long as the driving behaviors are affected by certain cyber attacks, the proposed method can be applied to detect anomaly.

One limitation of the proposed method is that it can be only applied to detect known attacks, because the decision tree classifier requires attack trajectories as training data. To extend the proposed method to detect unknown attacks and to be more generic, we will explore one-class classification methods [322] where only the ground truth trajectories are needed for training a single classifier. Another limitation of this work is that it mainly focuses on the detection of GPS spoofing attacks without proposing defense solutions. In future work, we will investigate corresponding mitigation strategies. For example, when a trajectory is identified as abnormal, its autonomous driving functions can be temporarily suspended. In the online detection, a warning can be sent to the trajectory planning module of the AV to choose safe maneuvers (e.g., stop) or directly ask the driver to take over. In a CV environment, the certificate of the vehicle could be revoked so that the messages sent from this particular CV will be discarded by other vehicles.

Chapter 10

Methodology for Hazard Identification and Mitigation Strategies Applied to an Overtaking Assistant ADAS

In this chapter we propose a methodology for analyzing the hazards and potential mitigation of faults and failures in an Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS) which is applicable to individual systems and subsystems of a larger automated vehicle implementation. To illustrate the methodology, we outline the structure of a notional overtaking assistant. An overtaking assistant for automated vehicles is considered a type of Advanced Driver Assistance System (ADAS) that assists a partially or fully automated vehicle with an overtaking maneuver consisting of acceleration and steering control during a double lane change. Crash data indicates that although only 19% of the US population inhabits rural zones, 54% of the vehicular crashes happen on rural roads [323], with a high number of those events occurring during an overtaking maneuver on two-lane rural roads. While such an overtaking assistant would help to minimize these collision events, no commercial product is yet available due in part to the challenge of defining what constitutes *safe* navigation in these systems.

The structure of the overtaking assistant system includes not only internal sensors such as global navigation satellite system (GNSS) receivers, map data, and other motion and localization sensors and external sensors such as radars, lidars, and vision systems but also access to cooperative positioning information through a wireless connected vehicular network in order to identify the location of oncoming traffic.

We perform the hazard analysis of this subsystem utilizing a combination of methods. For the vehicle level hazard analysis we use Hazard Operability Study (HAZOP) and the first step of System Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA), and for the overall safety analysis we use Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) and the second step of STPA. The analysis performed on the system is presented and is proposed for use as a general methodology to analyze hazards in any ADAS system or subsystem. The summary of the analysis results provided here include a list of hazards and mitigation strategies for the proposed two-lane rural road scenario.

This activity was originally reported in [10].

10.1 Introduction

Vehicle automation and Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems (ADAS) have evolved from being relatively simple, self-contained systems to increasingly complex systems that handle a significant

number of driving functions and involve a number of disparate sensors, estimation, control, and behavior generation algorithms, and coordination and cooperation both on-board the vehicle and with other vehicles, road users, and infrastructure components. As these systems increase in complexity, it becomes more challenging for control and systems engineers to identify and quantify potential failure and attack modes and provide mitigation strategies to ensure safety in the face of hardware or software failures or operation in unintended domains, especially when meeting failures of the intended function of the system.

In general, the types of hazards that may appear in complex systems are addressed by two standards. The Road Vehicle Functional Safety standard (ISO 26262) [324] considers hazards that are induced by software or hardware failures. The Road Vehicle Safety of the Intended Functionality standard (SOTIF ISO/PAS 21448) [325] seeks to identify performance shortcomings in ADAS systems that may occur not because of a system failure but rather due to limitations in the nominal system performance.

There are several hazard analysis techniques that are applied to the aforementioned standards. Due to space constraints, we focus on analyzing hazards related to limitations in the nominal performance of the system as a whole instead of analyzing specific software or hardware failures.

The traditional Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) and Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) are methods that consider that hazards are the result of a sequence of chain events caused by individual components' failures that propagate throughout the system. The difference between both methods is that FMEA uses a bottom-up cause-effect model while FTA is an top-down effect-cause approach. This means that FTA is concerned with one defined failure at a time and FMEA implicitly considers all effects that could happen because of any single failure. For this reason, we consider FMEA over FTA for the analysis.

Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP) is a qualitative top down hazard analysis method for complex systems that consists of evaluating each component in a chain process and finding potential situations that would provoke hazards. Finally, System Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) [326] provides a systematic process to evaluate interfaces between system components, controllers and people, using process feedback loops, functional control diagram, system requirements, hazard scenarios, safety constraints and safety requirements. Furthermore, previous studies have shown that the combination of two or more hazard analysis methods leads to better identification of potential hazards and mitigation strategies [327–330].

The application of hazard analysis techniques to an automotive ADAS subsystems is not new. Brewer et al. [331] presented a very detailed STPA+HAZOP+FMEA analysis for a generic automated lane centering system. Similarly, Becker et al. [327], developed the same analysis for a generic SAE level-3 highway chauffeur system, including lane changing and lane centering maneuvers, while Koelln et al. [332] presents the STPA comparison in general for a vehicle SAE level-4 and level-5. Mahajan et al. [329] presents an STPA for a lane keeping assistance system, while Abdulkhaleq et al. [333] applies STPA to the lane change functionality of a cruising chauffeur. Macher et al. [334] introduced a security aware hazard and risk analysis method whose focus is in newer electronic devices. It is a combination of the automotive Hazard Analysis and Risk Approach (HARA) and the security domain STRIDE approach that allows identifying computer security threats. Sulaman [335] makes a comparison of the outputs of a forward collision avoidance (FCA) system using FMEA and STPA. Unlike other works mentioned in this section, the analysis is carried independently using each hazard analysis method, and the outputs are compared qualitatively. However, as explained in [327,332], it is more effective to combine methods instead of using them independently.

ADAS are very common nowadays as the list of vehicle manufacturers that include one or more types of ADAS is extensive [336]. For example, the Autonomous Emergency Braking (AEB) system will apply brakes if an imminent collision is sensed. The Lane Keeping Assistant (LKA)

system can help to keep the vehicle between the lane boundaries. An Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC) helps the vehicle maintain a safe cruising speed while reacting to leading traffic by means of acceleration/deceleration.

Lately, some manufacturers have released a lane change maneuver assistant, but such a system is not yet common. An especially challenging ADAS is the overtaking assistant, which to the best of our knowledge is not readily available commercially at present. The risks during an overtaking maneuver include detecting oncoming traffic too late or incorrectly estimating the relative speeds and distances of the vehicle being overtaken and of oncoming traffic. This can lead to particularly dangerous scenarios on two-lane rural roads, where an overtaking assistant system has to execute lane-change maneuvers and acceleration and braking actions on a narrow road with potentially limited line-of-sight visibility [337]. Since there is more interest in designing an overtaking assistant as an ADAS, it is important to evaluate its possible hazards and anticipate mitigation strategies. Thus we have selected this functionality to illustrate our analysis.

It has been shown that collaborative navigation is a valid solution for Positioning, Navigation and Timing (PNT) applications in GNSS challenged environments [338], so using wireless connected vehicle technologies to prevent collisions is a reasonable approach. Works by Motro et al. [337], Bae et al. [339] and Mo et al. [340] present different Vehicular Ad hoc NETworks (VANET) rule-based overtaking assistance systems that are evaluated using simulation. To analyze the effectiveness of their approach, the previous works opted to vary the Operational Design Domain (ODD) specification of the selected scenarios by modifying the initialization of actors in the simulation [337, 339], road conditions [340], etc.

While some of the previous works analyze generic SAE J3016 vehicles level-3, level-4 and level-5, to the best of our knowledge, none has considered the implications of having a PNT system that includes a vehicle network that can also be a source of hazard. Our contribution is then threefold:

- A general overtaking assistant structure.
- A template for analyzing any ADAS-like subsystem of an autonomous vehicle with special focus on the navigation systems.
- Summary of hazards and mitigation strategies for the proposed overtaking assistant.

We limit our work to the hazard and mitigation analysis, leaving the verification and validation stage for a future work.

This chapter is organized as follows. Section 10.2 introduces the preliminaries of this work, including the design of the overtaking assistant and the explanation of the integrated analysis approach. The most important outputs of the hazard analysis are then shown in Section 10.2.3, including the most important mitigation strategies obtained from the analysis. Section 10.4 provides some insights on the results and finally, section 10.5 presents conclusions of this work.

10.2 Preliminaries

We frame our work as the hazard analysis for a component of a vehicle SAE level-3 or level-4 and not for the system as a whole. It has been shown that the discovery of hazards and mitigation strategies commonly fails when the system hierarchy is not analyzed in detail [332]. In order to perform the proposed hazard analysis, the functionalities of the subsystem of study have to be defined. We present the specific ODD considerations for a general overtaking assistant structure and then explain how the integrated hazard analysis is performed.

10.2.1 ODD configuration

We consider that the ADAS can be activated by the human driver on long stretches of rural roads without intersections. These roads have one lane for each direction of travel. This means that the vehicle will have to invade the oncoming road to perform any overtaking maneuver. The analysis is general, so it is not subject to any specific weather conditions, road shape or road grade.

10.2.2 Overtaking Assistant

Fig. 10.1 shows the general high level automated vehicle structure considered for this study. The vehicle is at the lowest level and includes its internal sensors. The steering, throttle and powertrain systems are the longitudinal, lateral and safety/non-safety critical actuators.

Figure 10.1: High level block diagram control structure for the automated vehicle considered for this study.

The positioning sensors include GNSS, map information and access to the vehicle-to-vehicle infrastructure. Other sensors are cameras, lidars and radars. The information from all the sensors feed into the control unit which has two major components: the sensor interface module and the path planning module. Within the sensor interface we have sensor fusion, localization, and environment modeling. The path planning module performs the situation assessment, decision making, path selection and motion control. The proposed overtaking assistant will basically take over the functionality of the control unit. The human machine interface (HMI) provides alerts

and warnings to the human operator, and the human operator can interact with it to engage or disengage certain ADAS components. The human driver is a passenger for SAE level-5 vehicles, but an essential component of the operation for level-2, level-3 and level-4 vehicles.

The control unit is of interest for our proposed overtaking assistant. We make some slight modifications to the conceptual framework of Hegeman et al. [341] that divides the complexity of the maneuver into five stages: decide whether to overtake, prepare to overtake, change lanes, pass, and return to the original lane. Fig. 10.2 shows this decomposition and indicates the sections where the navigation PNT systems are relevant.

The first stage of the assistance system is to decide whether an overtaking is needed, is allowed, and if there is a safe opportunity. If the answer is affirmative, we proceed to the second stage of preparation for overtaking. If the gap in the target lane is large enough, we check two conditions: if the lead vehicle is changing lanes and if there is on-coming traffic in the target lane. If neither is true, the overtaking assistant helps the vehicle maintain a safe gap, activates the vehicle's turn signal, and proceeds to the third stage. This stage is the first lane change. The vehicle starts changing lanes by steering, accelerating and constantly monitoring traffic using both sensors and communicated information.

Since we proposed using vehicular networks, we obtain anticipated information about probable collisions and can decide whether to continue or abort the maneuver. Once the assistant checks that there is no deviation from the lead vehicle and no traffic blocking the target lane, the vehicle continues into the target lane and completes its first lane change.

Then, in the fourth stage the ego vehicle needs to pass the lead vehicle. Sensor information is used to check whether there is a sufficiently large gap. If the gap is not large enough and a specified time threshold has elapsed, the maneuver is aborted and the vehicle returns to its original lane behind the lead vehicle. If the gap is large enough, the vehicle passes the lead vehicle while monitoring its sensors and the vehicular network to determine if there is another vehicle to pass and a gap in front of it. If the extra maneuver is possible, it is executed, otherwise the vehicle activates its turn signal again and enters the fifth stage, the return to its original lane.

In this final stage, the vehicle steers and accelerates while monitoring traffic and finally deactivating the indicator light. Finally, the assistant checks if the vehicle is cruising at the desired speed and takes action in case it is not. At this point, the overtaking assistant ADAS disengages and another ADAS (e.g. LKA or ACC) can assume control.

Fig. 10.1 also includes the potential capability of the vehicle sending relevant information to the manufacturer for debugging purposes and receiving remote software and data updates, a functionality that could even involve regulatory agencies. However, this functionality is not considered in this study.

10.2.3 Integrated Analysis Approach

The template for the safety analysis is adapted from [327, 331], and is presented in Fig. 10.3. The analysis starts with the item definition, where the ADAS subject of the analysis is defined and its inherent functionality is obtained through hierarchical decomposition. In this step, the system functions, boundaries and assumptions are documented as discussed in Section 10.2.2.

The second step consists of performing the vehicle-level hazard analysis. Any method consistent with the procedures from the SOTIF [325] standard would work, but it has been shown that combining two methods provides a better insight into the problem. In this case, we have chosen to use HAZOP and the first step of STPA called Unsafe Control Actions. The output of this initial analysis is a series of potential vehicle-level hazards as shown in Table 10.2.

Third, a risk assessment analysis is applied to the identified vehicle-level hazards. To comply

Figure 10.2: Overtaking Assistant flow diagram.

with ISO 26262 [324], an automotive safety integrity level (ASIL) rating is assigned to the potential hazardous events. To define this rating, we refer to Table 10.1. A certain level of severity, controllability and exposure is assigned to each potential hazardous event, and depending on these, the event can be QM, that is have no safety requirement, ASIL-A, the lowest safety rating in ISO 26262, ASIL-B, ASIL-C, or ASIL-D, the highest safety rating in ISO 26262, as shown in Table 10.3. After obtaining the hazardous events, we propose some vehicle-level safety goals for the identified hazards as shown in Table 10.4.

Next, the safety analysis and the identification and evaluation of triggering events is performed. For this stage, we choose to use functional FMEA and STPA Causal Scenarios (step 2). Causal Scenarios from STPA generates a very lengthy analysis of different ODD configurations, so only the triggering events from the analysis are presented in this chapter in Table 10.5.

Finally, the functional safety concept and the functional modifications for the proposed system are presented in the form of mitigation strategies, shown in Table 10.6.

Figure 10.3: Safety Analysis and Requirements Development Process, adapted from Becker2020.

Table 10.1: ASIL rating table

Controllability	Exposure	Severity			
		S_0	S_1	S_2	S_3
C_1	E_1	QM	QM	QM	QM
	E_2	QM	QM	QM	QM
	E_3	QM	QM	QM	A
	E_4	QM	QM	A	B
C_2	E_1	QM	QM	QM	QM
	E_2	QM	QM	QM	A
	E_3	QM	QM	A	B
	E_4	QM	A	B	C
C_3	E_1	QM	QM	QM	A
	E_2	QM	QM	A	B
	E_3	QM	A	B	C
	E_4	QM	B	C	D

10.3 Hazard Analysis

We present a compilation of results for the hazard analysis executed on the overtaking assistant by following the process in Fig. 10.3. The item definition and hierarchical system diagram are given in Section 10.2.2. To narrow down the length of this section, and to avoid repetitive outputs from previous works ([327, 332]), we focus on analyzing the proposed system in a two-lane rural road (predefined scenario) and target the hazards and mitigations produced by the PNT module, i.e. GNSS, Map and the chosen vehicular network VANET.

10.3.1 Vehicle-level hazard analysis

Table 10.2 presents the potential vehicle-level hazards obtained using the STPA and HAZOP analysis. We only include in this summary those hazards associated with the specific sensors of interest in the two-lane rural road scenario. These hazards are obtained following the STPA unsafe control actions procedure, which are analogous to the potentially hazardous behaviors from the

standard PAS 21448 [325].

Table 10.2: Potential vehicle-level hazards

ID	Hazard explanation
H_1	Lane departure when there is not enough line-of-sight of oncoming traffic.
H_2	Lane departure to target lane with close on-coming traffic.
H_3	Vehicle disengages overtaking assistant in the middle of the maneuver.
H_4	Vehicle starts lane change but does not complete it.
H_5	Overtaking assistant interferes with another ADAS, like the Lane Keeping Assistant.

Table 10.3: Risk assessment for potential hazardous events

ID	Potential Hazardous Event	Potential Crash	ASIL rating
H_1	Lane departure when there is occlusion on current lane, find unexpected on-coming vehicle on adjacent lane.	Forward impact (with vehicle)	C
H_1	Lane departure when there is occlusion in current lane, find pedestrian on the side of the adjacent lane.	Forward impact (with pedestrian)	C
H_2	Vehicle initiates lane change when there is stopped traffic on adjacent lane and occlusion in current lane.	Forward impact Side impact (with vehicle)	D
H_2	Vehicle initiates lane change when on-coming traffic was not detected or detected too late.	Forward impact (with vehicle)	D
H_3	Overtaking assistant losses access to one or more sensor information and disengages.	Forward impact (with vehicle)	B
H_3	Driver accidentally disengages overtaking assistant during lane change maneuver.	Forward impact Side impact (with vehicle)	B
H_4	Attack on VANET system overloads overtaking assistant with on-coming traffic messages, system stops.	Forward impact Side impact (with vehicle)	C
H_4	Attack on VANET system delays oncoming traffic information, assistant has to return to original lane.	Side impact (with vehicle)	C
H_5	Map information falsely indicates that an overtaking maneuver is not allowed, lane keeping assistant has higher priority.	Rear-end (with vehicle)	A
H_5	Adaptive cruise controller assistant engages after overtaking assistant due to localization error.	Rear-end (with vehicle)	A

10.3.2 ASIL Risk Assessment

After the initial hazard analysis, we perform a risk assessment analysis to provide the hazardous events with an ASIL safety rating. The summary of this analysis is shown in Table 10.3. Usually, human driver crash data is used to assign the controllability, exposure and security rating, but in many cases it is not possible to directly map crash information to hazards. We use previous research on overtaking maneuvers [337, 339, 340] to define these ratings.

10.3.3 Example Safety Goals

The possible safety goals, shown in Table 10.4, were obtained from the initial vehicle-level hazard analysis, and they should be traceable from the SOTIF measures to the hazard level analysis. In the case of analyzing various subsystems with this method, it may be possible to obtain a general high-level safety goal with sub-goals for every individual system.

Table 10.4: Vehicle-level safety goals from the identified hazards

Related Hazard ID	Safety Goal ID	Possible Safety Goal
H_1, H_2, H_3	SG_1	Ensure that the overtaking assistant is receiving information from all the PNT systems, namely GNSS, Maps and VANET, before engaging.
H_1, H_2	SG_2	If there is an occlusion, add a security factor to the measurements provided by the radars and lidars. Make sure occlusion is detected.
H_4	SG_3	Provide the driver a warning when the overtaking assistant senses something wrong with PNT systems, return safely to original lane. Vehicle speed should be less or equal than the lead vehicle's speed.
H_4	SG_4	If all PNT systems fail, disengage ADAS and inform the driver to take over completely.
H_5	SG_5	Consider adding dead times for padding before engaging a different ADAS.

10.3.4 Overall safety hazard analysis

Table 10.5 presents the triggering events focusing on PNT technologies for the overtaking assistant in the two-lane rural road scenario. The IDs are assigned with respect to the sensor, so G represents GNSS, GM is GNSS/Map, M is Map alone, and V represents VANET.

10.3.5 Results

We present a compilation of the most important functional safety concepts and functional modifications from this analysis in the form of mitigation strategies in Table 10.6. While we can identify some mitigation strategies against the designed safety goals, we have to mention that relying on the vehicular network, while proving to be very useful for the overtaking maneuver, is harder to analyze from the standpoint of an individual vehicle since it involves cooperative sensing and navigation and depends on more than just the overtaking assistant. In this case, a higher level of the communication network should be analyzed including infrastructure issues. However, there are some mitigation strategies that can be proposed from only the vehicle's standpoint.

10.4 Discussion

The analysis has been divided into two stages: vehicle-level and overall-safety level, which allows one to decompose and explore the individual components while also analyzing the system as a whole. The set of obtained hazards and mitigations is not exhaustive, and rather represents a

Table 10.5: Summary of triggering events for PNT technologies for the proposed overtaking assistant

ID	Triggering Event	Hazard
G_1	Delay in the update rate.	H_1, H_2, H_3
G_2	Too high tolerance for host vehicle position.	H_1, H_2, H_3
GM_1	Outdated GPS or map data.	H_1, H_2, H_3, H_5
M_1	Map is not validated, i.e. has distance errors.	H_1, H_2, H_3, H_5
V_1	Denial of Service (DoS) attack, transmission of dummy messages.	$H_1, H_2, H_3,$ H_4, H_5
V_2	Timing attack, malware and spam attack to on-board units and road side units. Affects the transmission latency.	$H_1, H_2, H_3,$ H_4, H_5
V_3	Bogus information, Man in the Middle Attack (MiMA), purposeful attack. Wrong information about traffic conditions, can transmit that road is clear when it is not, forcing an overtake.	$H_1, H_2, H_3,$ H_4, H_5
V_4	Masquerade, purposeful attack. Another vehicle "fakes" identity and forces ego vehicle to yield or stop (for example).	$H_1, H_2, H_3,$ H_4, H_5
V_6	Black hole attack, wormhole attack, illusion attack, purposeful attack. The ego vehicle stops receiving data packets, so it is forced to rely on on-board sensors alone for perception.	$H_1, H_2, H_3,$ H_4, H_5
V_7	Sybil attack, impersonation. Generate message overload to vehicles in the network, can produce traffic jams or accidents.	$H_1, H_2, H_3,$ H_4, H_5

methodology and a working point of a certain scenario. To improve the analysis in future works, we consider that adversarial testing can be of great use, as shown in our previous work [342]. We are preparing a simulation setup that will allow us to perform additional advanced analysis for future works.

The combination of analysis methods used in this study allows us to leverage each methods' advantages and overcome their shortcomings. STPA was used to obtain the unexpected control actions (UCAs) for step 1 and those results are used to obtain potential causal scenarios to find the triggering events. The UCAs from the STPA analysis were further expanded using the HAZOP study to analyze the operability of the proposed system. The triggering events were obtained using FMEA and the STPA Causal Scenarios technique (step 2), but were reduced in number because we have limited our analysis to a specific scenario (two-lane rural road). While FMEA proves useful to analyze many possible failures of the system, if we want to focus on a specific failure we should also use FTA. This method is able to find redundant paths in a system functionality when focusing on one specific hazard.

We find that the mixed combination of analysis methods for this subsystem uncovers hazards and mitigation strategies that would not have been attained either when analyzing individual components, as it loses focus on the overall system, or by analyzing the system as a whole, as it loses focus on the individual components.

10.5 Conclusions

This chapter presents a detailed hazard analysis for a proposed ADAS overtaking assistant system. Analyzing this system is useful due to the high number of fatal crashes that take place in two-lane rural roads. We found that even though we restricted the analysis to a specific ADAS (overtaking assistant) and a specific scenario (two-lane rural road), the analysis can become quite extensive, so it is very important to delimit the analysis tools and the expected functionality of the

Table 10.6: Mitigation strategies

Mitigation Measure ID	Example mitigation measure	Relevant Safety Goal
M_1	Synchronize update time for vehicle position information, map and vehicle network information.	SG_1, SG_2, SG_5
M_2	Verify that localization on the road is accurate to the centimeter every defined time horizon.	SG_4, SG_5
M_3	Have a redundant control algorithm that constantly generates localization information based on the vehicle position and road model. Compare every defined time horizon with sensed information.	SG_1, SG_2, SG_3 SG_5
M_4	Consider that connectivity has been lost after a defined time horizon and report information.	SG_4, SG_5
M_5	Use of message authentication algorithms with hashing techniques to keep network messages secure (e.g. Elliptic Curve Digital Signature ECDSA).	SG_1, SG_2, SG_4
M_6	Use centralized administration for receiving network messages to avoid network malware and spam.	SG_1, SG_2, SG_3 SG_4, SG_5

system carefully to avoid falling into generalizations.

We consider that the analysis method used in this work is easy to replicate, especially when working with subsystems of autonomous vehicles. By obtaining Tables 10.2-10.6 we obtain a good idea of the subsystem weaknesses and strengths. The analysis of several subsystems would output hazards and mitigation strategies that may overlap but complement each other. Future work includes finalizing a simulation environment that can recreate the hazards proposed in this analysis and will allow the identified mitigation strategies to be tested.

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Chapter 11

On the Validation of Adversarial Threats to Cooperative Unmanned Aerial Systems for Search and Rescue Missions

This chapter studies the effects of adversarial threats on the localization stack of cooperative Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) that perform cooperative search and rescue missions (CooSAR). We propose a methodology for incorporating different types of attacks in the localization stack of the UAS to spoof the sensors and actuators of the vehicles with two goals: fail the mission (not locate the target) and fly off path. For this purpose, we resort to a progressive-spiral-in (PSI) search path with theoretical success guarantees to cover the search area in finite time given at least a certain minimum number of aerial vehicles. Then, we formulate a control strategy for each UAS and implement two types of spoofing attacks: i) attack to the sensors and actuators, and ii) attack to the residuals of the GNSS localization measurements. We evaluate the effects of the attacks by measuring the decrease in effectiveness in finding the target and the reduction in area coverage when the UAS are subject to the attack. The attack is applied to one UAS at a time (the one closest to the target), and we find that even with this simple approach, the probability of finding the target is greatly reduced up to 36%.

This activity was originally reported in [11].

11.1 Introduction

Cooperative search and rescue (CooSAR) algorithms for Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) aim to coordinate the deployment of multiple UAS for disaster response scenarios. Their objective is to enhance coverage, reduce overlap, and increase the likelihood of timely target location.

However, there is a risk of attackers exploiting vulnerabilities in the localization or communication systems of the UAS group to gain access to information about the search area or the target's location. Previous research has explored various strategies for forming a UAS group to ensure successful target capture [343–345] and for analyzing multisensor fusion techniques, including Kalman and particle filters, for localization [74, 346–348]. Additionally, there have been examinations of spoofing attacks on GNSS, some of which are designed to evade fault detectors in the multisensor fusion filter, thereby posing a potential single point of failure [346, 349].

Figure 11.1: Overview of the search process. The group of UAS begins at a certain location (11.1a) and take their initial positions around the search area to start the search (11.1b). There are two outcomes possible, the target is found (11.1c) or not found (11.1d). We use an exhaustive search method with guaranteed performance for the group of UAS, so the only way a target is not found is through one of the designed spoofing methods.

Nevertheless, prior studies often overlook the full range of nonlinearities in vehicles and the adverse effects of malicious disturbances, resulting in reduced control performance and instability. Neglecting the security measures in sensor design for autonomous vehicles is a significant vulnerability, as cyber-attacks can compromise the safe operation of the UAS, possibly leading to accidents and being a menace to users [350]. In the considered case study, UAS are deployed for rescuing a target in a specific search area, and one of the threats is insufficient coverage of the region resulting in failure to locate the target. Each UAS is considered to be a cyber-physical system modeled as a discrete-time stochastic linear system with Gaussian noise. To perform the attack detection and analysis, a steady-state Kalman Filter (KF) is used to fuse the noisy sensors' measurements. We consider the 2D motion of the UAS, since as shown by [74, 351], the loose coupling between GNSS position and velocity and attitude estimations effectively uncouples the attitude dynamics, so spoofing alone has limited impact on the attitude of the UAS.

To analyze the effects of attacks in this scenario, we combine an exhaustive search method [352] with a multisensor fusion approach (INS+GNSS) for the cooperative UAS group under investigation [74]. We consider a covert capture type of spoofing. In this type of attack, it is assumed that the UAS under attack is equipped with spoofing detectors that will be triggered if the attack violates a certain statistical hypothesis testing condition.

The spoofing attacks used in this work have two objectives: i) to divert the trajectory of the closest UAS to target from its original trajectory without triggering fault detectors, and ii) to fail the mission, namely, fail to locate the target within a finite time. We consider two approaches for the attacks. First, we implement an attack on the sensors and actuators of the UAS with a theoretical guarantee to stay covert while potentially causing an unbounded estimation error [346]. Then, we implement an attack on the sensor measurement by designing a malicious residual [349]. Both attacks have the goal of driving the UAS under attack to inappropriate destinations. Fig 11.1 shows an overview of the problem.

The contribution of this work can be summarized as follows:

- Joint cooperative UAS model with multisensor fusion adaptability that can be extended to other types of sensors.
- Algorithm for attack prioritization when attacking cooperative vehicles.
- Integration of path-planning, attack detection, attack design and evaluation for general cooperative missions.

This chapter is organized as follows: Section 11.2 presents a review of some related literature. Section 11.3 introduces the model of the UAS with the integration of the measurement, noise and possible attacks, and also presents the model and defined motion of the target. It also defines the Problem Statement for this work. Section 11.4 introduces some considerations needed for the UAS motion, the attack detection method and the design of the spoofing attacks, and introduces Algorithm 8 that summarizes the behavior of every element in the system. Section 11.5 presents the results of the case study and finally Section 11.6 presents the conclusions of this work and future directions.

11.2 Related works

The problem of cooperative search for a moving target using a group of Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) has gained significant attention and finds applications in diverse scenarios such as planetary exploration, military missions, and search and rescue operations. In these situations, the UAS group exhibits a certain level of cooperation and utilizes sensors for localization and perception, such as cameras or LiDARs with a defined field of view (FOV) to detect the target [350, 353]. In this work, locating the target is understood as the target appearing within the searching agent's sensor FOV [354].

Building on these concepts, in order to validate the performance of adversarial threats to UAS in Cooperative Search and Rescue (CooSAR) missions, it is crucial to explore the design of multi-UAS cooperative systems, path-planning patterns in search areas, cooperative control approaches, and to review GNSS/IMU fusion algorithm weaknesses against the designed attacks and attack detection methods. These investigations contribute to improving the resilience and security of UAS operations in challenging environments.

Numerous studies propose real-time path-planning solutions [355], cooperative control approaches [353, 354, 356], and escape-proof formations for multi-UAS systems [352] in CooSAR

missions. These aim to optimize search efficiency, coordination, and target localization within the search area. Leader-follower formation algorithms are commonly used due to their simplicity and scalability in formation control [357]. These algorithms offer advantages over other cooperative control methods, such as resource utilization and fault tolerance [358], simpler communication protocols [359], and continuum deformation shape and motion profiles [360].

In the context of attacks, the localization stack of the UAS is often targeted. Localization algorithms commonly employ Kalman [74, 346, 349] or particle filters [347], which are vulnerable to crafted attacks. However, most studies focus on defining attacks rather than considering defense mechanisms for UAS groups [361]. Methods for detecting cyber-attacks on UAS include monitoring error vectors of Extended Kalman Filters (EKF) to compare sensor values [350], combining different detection strategies for spoofing attacks [362], and monitoring discrepancies between GNSS-derived measurements and corresponding sensor readings [363].

11.3 Preliminaries and Problem Definition

11.3.1 UAS model

Assume there is a group of Q UAS that will perform the CooSAR mission. There is no prior information on the location of the target, so the group of UAS will perform an exhaustive search of a region.

The block diagram of each individual UAS is shown in Figure 11.2. It is considered that each individual UAS obtains its localization information by performing multisensor fusion of two sensors: GNSS and INS. The attacker introduces actuator and sensor attack sequences, $f_a(k)$ and $f_s(k)$, into the system's network layer to target actuators and/or sensors. Sensor output measurements are then transmitted to the state estimator. Location estimates from sensors are integrated using a fusion method, such as a Kalman filter. The output from this estimation is sent to the detection mechanism, which compares it with previous outputs or estimates or calculates the covariance in the output's evolution, identifying potential attacks. If detected, an alert is triggered and a countermeasure strategy may be employed to mitigate the attack.

Without loss of generality, for the i -th individual agent ($i \in \{0, \dots, Q\}$),

$$\dot{s}_i = f_i(s_i, u_i, t), s_i \in \mathcal{S}_i \subset \mathbb{R}^n, u_i \in \mathcal{U}_i \subset \mathbb{R}^m. \quad (11.1)$$

For the remainder of this section, the subscript i is omitted for general discussions of the motion of the UAS.

Field tests conducted by Kerns et al. [74] showed that the designed spoofing attacks have little impact the attitude of a UAS. Similarly, [351] found that specific spoofing strategies, different from those used to attack position and velocity measurements, should be used to attack the attitude of the group of UAS. For these reasons, we consider the 2D motion of the vehicles and model each individual system as a discrete-time stochastic linear system with Gaussian noise using

$$s(k+1) = As(k) + Bu(k) + B_a f_a(k) + \eta_1(k), \quad (11.2)$$

$$y(k) = Cs(k) + B_s f_s(k) + \eta_2(k), \quad (11.3)$$

where the state $s(k) = [p_x(k), v_x(k), p_y(k), v_y(k)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$ represents the position $pos_s = [p_x, p_y]^\top$ and velocity $vel_s = [v_x, v_y]^\top$ of the vehicle in the 2D plane. The instantaneous velocity of the UAS at any given time is $v_s = \|vel_s\|$. The input consists of accelerations in the 2D plane $u(k) = [a_x(k), a_y(k)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^2$, with instantaneous acceleration $a = \sqrt{a_x^2 + a_y^2}$. The output $y(k)$ represents

Figure 11.2: Cyber-attack detection mechanism for the UAS

the GNSS measurement. We consider that the acceleration measurement by the INS has noise $\eta_1 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Gamma_1)$ and the GNSS measurement noise is $\eta_2 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Gamma_2)$. The attack sequences $f_a(k)$ and $f_s(k)$ are injected into the actuators and sensors of the system, respectively, and B_a, B_f are corresponding matrices of appropriate dimensions. The system matrices A and B consider timestep Δ and are given by

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \Delta \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta^2/2 & 0 \\ \Delta & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta^2/2 \\ 0 & \Delta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11.4)$$

The noisy measurements are fed into a steady-state Kalman filter (KF) to obtain the state estimation. Then, the estimation result is

$$\hat{s}(k+1) = A\hat{s}(k) + Bu(k) + L(k+1)(y(k+1) - \hat{y}(k+1)), \quad (11.5)$$

where $L(k+1)$ is the steady-state Kalman filter given by

$$L(k+1) = A\Sigma(k+1)C^\top (C\Sigma(k+1)C^\top + \Gamma_2)^{-1}. \quad (11.6)$$

The error covariance $\Sigma(k+1)$ must satisfy the discrete-time algebraic Ricatti equation (ARE)

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma(k+1) = & A\Sigma(k+1)A^\top + \Gamma_1 - A\Sigma(k+1)C^\top \\ & (C\Sigma(k+1)C^\top + \Gamma_2)^{-1}C\Sigma(k+1)A^\top. \end{aligned} \quad (11.7)$$

Additionally, each UAS is considered to have a sensor with a disk-shaped field of view (FOV) of diameter D and centered at pos_s .

11.3.2 Target motion

A 2D point-mass model is considered for the target, where

$$p_x(k+1) = p_x(k) + v_m \cos \theta(k) \Delta, \quad (11.8)$$

$$p_y(k+1) = p_y(k) + v_m \sin \theta(k) \Delta, \quad (11.9)$$

$$\theta(k+1) = \theta(k) + \omega(k) \Delta \quad (11.10)$$

with state $m(k) = [p_x(k), p_y(k), \theta(k)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$, and input $u(k) = \omega(k)$.

The 2D position of the target is given by $pos_m = [p_{m_x}, p_{m_y}] \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and its orientation is θ . To have a theoretical guarantee of locating the target under optimal conditions, the target speed is chosen as $v_m = v_s/6$ following [352].

The target starts in a random position within the search area $pos_{m_0} \sim U(\mathcal{SA})$ and its initial orientation is drawn uniformly from the unit circle, i.e. $\theta_0 := \theta(0) \sim U(-\pi/2, \pi/2)$. Then, two types of target motion are considered:

1. The target moves continuously with the same orientation $\theta(k) = \theta_0$ and $\omega(k) = 0, \forall k = 0, \dots, T$
2. The target changes orientation according to a random walk of the angular velocity input, namely $\omega(k) = \omega_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \Omega_j$, where $\Omega_j \sim U(-10, 10)$ every N timesteps.

11.3.3 Problem Definition

The purpose of this work is to evaluate spoofing attacks that cause harm to the group of cooperative UAS and to identify how the attacks affect their performance regarding the following metrics:

- Percentage of detection: exhaustive search algorithm achieves a $98\% \pm 2\%$ chance of success.
- Area of coverage: current exhaustive search algorithm achieves 100% coverage.

11.4 Methods

11.4.1 UAS motion

The UAS baseline motion is a leader-follower formation that follows an escape-proof cooperative path, proposed initially in [352], and referred to as the Progressively-Spiral-In (PSI) algorithm. Without loss of generality, consider that the search area \mathcal{SA} is a convex hull, i.e. $\mathcal{SA} := Conv(SA), SA \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The motion plan of each UAS_{*i*} is generated based on a series of clockwise spiral-in cycles, which form the trajectory \mathcal{C}_{PSI} with vertices $\{(x_l, y_l)\}_{l=0,1,2,\dots}$ that can be enclosed by the curve \mathcal{C}_0 . The parameter d_k is a user-defined, non-negative parameter that controls the centripetal speed of the k -th spiral-in cycles. The construction of each spiral-in cycle involves considering a circle of radius $D/2$ rolling along $\mathcal{C}_{PSI}(k, dk)$, which also works as the trace of the center of the circle. After each spiral-in cycle, UAS_{*i*} will complete a 360° turn. The path is guaranteed to be non-escape as long as the following sufficient condition regarding Q , the number of UAS available, is met

$$Q > Q_{max} = \frac{(P + \pi D)v_m}{Dv_s}, \quad (11.11)$$

where P is the perimeter of the search area, D is the sensor FOV diameter, v_s is the UAS reference speed and v_m is the target's speed. Furthermore, the algorithm ensures that the target will be

detected by at least one UAS in finite time as long as the target's speed $v_m \leq v_s/6$ and the initial distance between the UAS along the curve \mathcal{C}_0 is Dv_s/v_m .

The points in \mathcal{C}_{PSI} are then evenly interpolated to generate the waypoints for each one of the UAS. The reference trajectory for the UAS is obtained by propagating the model of the UAS through the waypoints obtained from the PSI algorithm

$$s_{ref}(k+1) = As_{ref}(k) + Ba_{ref}(k). \quad (11.12)$$

Since the PSI path is composed of linear segments joined together, the reference acceleration a_{ref} remains $\mathbf{0}$ throughout most of the path except at its vertices.

11.4.2 Attack Detection

According to [346], fault diagnosis algorithms can be used for cyber-attack detection as the attacks can be interpreted as faults in the system. Thus we can use the residuals generated by the steady-state KF. The residual is defined as

$$r(k+1) := y(k+1) - CA\hat{s}(k) - CBu(k). \quad (11.13)$$

If there are no cyber attacks, the residual has a zero mean Gaussian distribution with a constant covariance matrix $\Sigma_r(k) = C\Sigma(k)C^\top + \Gamma_2$ and $r^\top(k)\Sigma_r^{-1}(k)r(k)$ follows a χ^2 distribution with n degrees of freedom, where $\mathbb{E}[r^\top(k)\Sigma_r^{-1}(k)r(k)] = n$. The dimension of the measurement vector $y(k)$ coincides with $\dim(s(k))$, i.e. $\dim(y(k)) = n$.

To detect whether the system is under attack, we refer to the *Compound Scalar Testing* method [364], and check the following statistical hypotheses:

$$\mathcal{H}_0 : r(k) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_r), \quad (11.14)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_1 : r(k) \not\sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_r). \quad (11.15)$$

Let the *power* of residuals be defined as $\text{pwr}(k) := r^\top(k)\Sigma_r^{-1}(k)r(k)$. Then

$$\begin{cases} \text{Accept } \mathcal{H}_0 \text{ if } \text{pwr}(k) \leq h \\ \text{Accept } \mathcal{H}_1 \text{ if } \text{pwr}(k) > h \end{cases} \quad (11.16)$$

where $h > n$ is the threshold value. If the hypothesis \mathcal{H}_1 is accepted, it means that the attacker caused a large increase in the power of the residuals, hence a flag will be triggered.

11.4.3 Attack models

A simple proportional controller is designed for each individual UAS, as in [74, 349]. Then

$$u(k) = -K(\hat{s}(k) - s_{ref}(k)), \quad (11.17)$$

where the control gain K is chosen so that the eigenvalues of $(A - BK)$ can be placed in the left-hand plane, given that (A, B) is a controllable pair.

Now, consider that when there is a cyber-attack, the input of the system becomes

$$u_{attack} = u(k) + Baf_a(k) + \eta_1(k). \quad (11.18)$$

Then, the updated filter dynamics of the system are

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{s}(k+1) &= A\hat{s}(k) + Bu_{attack}(k) \\ &\quad + L(y(k+1) - CA\hat{s}(k) - CBu_{attack}(k)). \end{aligned} \quad (11.19)$$

Attack 1: Attack to actuators and sensors

Based on Corollaries 1 and 2 from [74], we obtain the malicious inputs $f_a(k)$ and $f_s(k)$ that guarantee a stealthy covert attack. Consider that the attacker has access to all inputs and outputs of the system, so that $B_a = B$ and $B_s = B$. To drive the UAS to a malicious destination s_N in finite time N , define the objective error state as $e_f = \|s_N - \hat{s}(k)\|_2$. Then,

$$f_s(k) = -B_s^+ C \sum_{\tau=1}^{k-1} (A^{(k-1)-\tau} B_a f_a(\tau)), \forall f_a(k), \quad (11.20)$$

where $B_s^+ = [B_s^\top B_s]^{-1} B_s^\top$ is the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of B_s , and $f_a(\cdot)$ is obtained from

$$f_a(k) = -B_a^\top A^{(N-1)-k^\top} W_c^{-1}(N) e_f, \quad (11.21)$$

with discrete time controllability Gramian

$$W_c(N) = \sum_{\tau=1}^{N-1} (A^{N-1-\tau} B_a B_a^\top A^{(N-1)-\tau^\top}). \quad (11.22)$$

Attack 2: Attack to measurement

To directly affect the GNSS measurement, we resort to designing the residual (11.13) to drive the UAS to malicious location s_N . From (11.13), we see that the falsified measurement from the GNSS is

$$y(k) = C A \hat{s}(k-1) + C B u(k-1) + r_o(k), \quad (11.23)$$

when we find the numerical optimal solution for the residual $r_o(k)$. The following is the optimization program, adapted from [349].

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{r(k)} \quad & \|s_N - F \hat{s}(k)\| \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & r^\top(k) \Sigma_r^{-1}(k) r(k) \leq h, \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \end{aligned} \quad (11.24)$$

with $F = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ that transforms into

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{r(k)} \quad & r^\top(k) L^\top K^\top B^\top F^\top F B K L r(k) \\ & + 2\lambda^\top(k) F B K L r(k) + \lambda^\top(k) \lambda(k), \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & r^\top(k) \Sigma_r^{-1}(k) r(k) \leq h \end{aligned} \quad (11.25)$$

with $\lambda(k)$ representing the deterministic part of the equation

$$\lambda(k) = s_N - F A s(k) + F B K \hat{s}(k-1) - F B K s_{ref}(k). \quad (11.26)$$

The program in (11.25) turns out to be a quadratic program with quadratic constraints, so to solve it, it is necessary to introduce a Lagrangian multiplier $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$. The Lagrangian function is then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_k(r(k), \gamma) = & r^\top(k) L^\top K^\top B^\top F^\top F B K L r(k) \\ & + 2\lambda^\top(k) F B K L r(k) + \lambda^\top(k) \lambda(k) \\ & + \gamma \left(r^\top(k) \Sigma_r^{-1}(k) r(k) - h \right), \end{aligned} \quad (11.27)$$

where $r_o(k) = \operatorname{argmin}_{r(k)} \max_{\gamma} \mathcal{L}_k(r^\top(k), \gamma)$ is the solution to the dual problem of (11.25) and has the following *Karush-Kuhn-Tucker* (KKT) conditions that are necessary and sufficient [349]:

$$\begin{cases} \bullet \gamma_o > 0 \\ \bullet \gamma_o (r_o^\top(k) \Sigma_r^{-1}(k) r_o(k) - h) = 0 \\ \bullet L^\top K^\top B^\top F^\top FBK L r_o(k) + 2\lambda^\top(k) FBKL \\ \quad + \gamma_o \Sigma_r^{-1}(k) r_o(k) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (11.28)$$

11.4.4 Framework

The complete performance of the attacks on the UAS is summarized in Algorithm 8. The first step in the algorithm is to analyze the search area \mathcal{SA} and obtain the reference trajectory s_{ref} for each of the UAS. Then, the attack horizon is defined as N . The duration of the simulation is given as T_{sim} . For each timestep, the attack will be directed to the UAS that is closest to the target in order to force it to fail the mission (line 8 in Algorithm 8). Then, the type of attack is selected and the pertinent output is computed and applied to the corresponding UAS. The rest of the simulation evolves by one timestep and then the cycle is repeated. If the closest UAS to the target changes after one timestep, the attack sequence is regenerated for the new UAS of interest in order to maximize the effect of the attack in the mission. The mission ends if the target is found for timestep $< T_{sim}$ and fails if the target was not found within the allotted T_{sim} .

Algorithm 8 Cooperative UAS spoofing attack.

Require: Vertex coordinates of the convex search area \mathcal{SA} .

Ensure: Target found or Target not found.

- 1: Apply PSI algorithm to get the corner points of the escape-proof path $\mathcal{C}_{PSI} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=0,1,2,\dots}$
 - 2: Compute # UAS $Q > Q_{max} = \frac{(P+\pi D)v_m}{Dv_s}$
 - 3: Generate waypoints for each UAS and propagate through the UAS model to get $s_{ref}(k)_{\{k=0,1,2,\dots\}}$
 - 4: Initialize group of UAS $\{s_i(0)\}_{i=1,\dots,Q}$
 - 5: Initialize target $m(0)$
 - 6: Define attack horizon N
 - 7: **while** timestep $< T_{sim}$ **do**
 - 8: Get UAS_i closest to target $i = \operatorname{argmin}_{i=1,\dots,Q} d(pos_{s_i}, pos_m)$
 - 9: **while** $k \leq N$ and $i_{new} == i$ **do**
 - 10: **if** Case Attack 1 **then**
 - 11: Generate attack sequence $\{f_a(k), f_s(k)\}_{k=0,\dots,N}$
 - 12: Apply $\{f_a(k), f_s(k)\}$ to UAS_i
 - 13: **end if**
 - 14: **if** Case Attack 2 **then**
 - 15: Generate optimal residual $r_o(k)_{k=0,\dots,N}$
 - 16: Apply $r_o(k)$ to UAS_i
 - 17: **end if**
 - 18: Update $i_{new} = \operatorname{argmin}_{i=1,\dots,Q} (d(pos_{s_i}, pos_m))$
 - 19: timestep = timestep+1
 - 20: **if** $pos_m(k) \in FOV(UAS_i)_{i=1,\dots,Q}$ **then**
 - 21: **return** Target found by UAS
 - 22: **break**
 - 23: **end if**
 - 24: **end while**
 - 25: **end while**
 - 26: **return** Target not found
-

Figure 11.3: PSI reference path for the CooSAR mission, dimensions are in meters.

11.5 Case Study

11.5.1 Experimental setting

We consider an square search area \mathcal{SA} of $800 \times 800m$. The PSI path for this \mathcal{SA} is shown in Fig. 11.3. Let E be the event where the target is detected, and $P(E < T)$ the probability of detecting the target in less than T timesteps. We run 200k Montecarlo experiments, 100 experiments for each incremental timestep from 0 to 2000. We ascertain that $P(E < T) \rightarrow 1$ as $T \rightarrow 2000$ timesteps. The two histograms of Fig. 11.4 show the difference in the distribution of the success timestamp when the target has different motion (random walk vs straight line). For that reason, we consider the worst-case motion to be the random walk. Fig. 11.5 shows that the detection probability reaches a 100% detection rate within 200 seconds or 2000 timesteps when there are no attacks and considering the worst-case situation (random walk of the target's orientation). Hence, we choose the simulation time $T_{sim} = 2000$ and $\Delta = 0.1s$. The diameter of the FOV $D = 200m$, $v_s = 100m/s$ and $v_m = v_s/6$.

Following [349, 365], we set a time horizon of 30 seconds or 300 timesteps. The constant gain of the UAS controller is $K = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$ and we choose $h = 4.5$ since the $\dim(y(k)) = 4$. Additionally, both types of attack depend on choosing the appropriate malicious destination s_N . We have chosen a naive approach to select this destination, so we base s_N in the reference trajectory s_{ref} as follows

$$s_N = s_{ref}(k + N) + Jpos_{attack}, \quad (11.29)$$

$$pos_{attack} \sim U([-20, 20]m \times [-20, 20]m), \quad (11.30)$$

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^\top. \quad (11.31)$$

(a) Target moves in straight line with orientation θ_0 (b) Target's orientation changes according to random walk

Figure 11.4: Histograms for successful target location according to target's motion over 2000 timesteps for 1000 experiments. The horizontal axis represents the timestep and the vertical axis is the occurrence frequency in percentage. The worst-case scenario turns out to be the random walk, as the cooperative UAS requires up to 2000 timesteps to successfully find the target whereas at most only approximately 600 timesteps are required when the target moves in a straight line.

Table 11.1: Results summary

	% target location success		% area coverage
	Random walk	Straight line	
No attack	98.77% \pm 0.12%	99.92% \pm 0.08%	100%
Attack 1	84.5% \pm 2.02%	63.9% \pm 4.87%	87% \pm 7%
Attack 2	81.9% \pm 3.08%	86.3% \pm 11.3%	88% \pm 12%

Thus, we find the probability of detection of the target under nominal system performance and under attacks 1 and 2, shown in Fig. 11.5. We see that the probability evolves in a similar manner under every operation mode, but when being attacked, the percentage of successful location drops.

11.5.2 Discussion

We perform 1000 runs of MonteCarlo simulation for each case: nominal (No attack), attack on sensors and actuators (Attack 1) and attack on residual (Attack 2); and repeat the experiment 200 times. We provide representative snapshots of the simulation in Fig. 11.6 and a summary of the success metrics in Table 11.1.

We observe a sharp decline in the percentage of location success of the group of UAS. However, the CooSAR mission is still successful in more than 60% of the cases. It is evident that this is an advantage of the UAS cooperative mission, as it inherently makes the system more robust to

Figure 11.5: Probability of detection of the target under normal circumstances versus search timestep for 200k experiments. Target motion is random walk (worst-case). Noisy data were smoothed using a Savitzky-Golay filter of window 51 and order 3.

cyberattacks. Actually, when choosing random walk for the target, there is only a slight decline of the percentage of success of the mission. This can be understood by looking at Fig. 11.6b.2 and Fig. 11.6c.2. The attacks on the UAS simply allow the target with random motion to stay in the vicinity for longer. On the contrary, the attacks have a greater impact when the target has a straight line motion. The attacks delay the movement of the UAS, allowing the target to *escape* the search area. For the area of coverage, we considered the area covered until the simulation was terminated against the nominal case. Then, we find that even though the UAS are being deviated from their prescribed paths, they still manage to provide good coverage of the search area. However, it may be that the naive choice of the malicious destination s_N is not optimal. A better design for s_N would help improve the quality of the attacks.

Figure 11.6: System snapshots for the (a) Nominal, (b) Attack 1, and (c) Attack 2 cases for target's straight motion (left column) and target's random motion (right column). Success in locating the target is shown with a faded yellow circle. Notice how the motion of the closest UAS to target changes for the Attacks. We include two snapshots of the target "escaping" the search area in (b.1) and (c.1).

11.6 Conclusions

In this work, we considered the worst-case scenario, assuming that the attacker had complete knowledge of the system's inputs and outputs. Surprisingly, our findings demonstrate the system's remarkable resilience, as it consistently maintained a significant level of success in locating the target despite the adversarial conditions. These results highlight the system's robustness and its ability to effectively accomplish its mission objectives even when subjected to disruptive attacks. In the future, it is important to evaluate the system's performance across varying levels of attacker knowledge and capabilities to gain a comprehensive understanding of its resilience in real-world scenarios.

One limitation of our study pertains to the insufficient consideration given to proper connectivity among the UAS group members. Establishing a redundant communication system, enabling the exchange of positional information between vehicles, would offer an effective mitigation strategy. This approach aligns with the principles of the Multiple-Model methodology presented in [366], where diverse operational modes of the UAS group can be harnessed to enhance mission reliability.

In conclusion, we found that even though a cooperative group of UAS presents stronger resilience to cyber-attacks (compared to one individual UAS), it is not immune to them, so more sophisticated methods of attack detection are needed in order to ensure the accomplishment of their mission.

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Chapter 12

Cooperative Navigation Strategy for Connected Autonomous Vehicle Operating at Smart Intersection

This chapter focuses on the cooperative navigation strategy for connected autonomous vehicles operating at smart intersections. The goal of this work is a cooperative navigation system to achieve cooperative collision avoidance for enhancing the safety and capacity of the intersection. This work considers cooperative connected autonomous vehicles operating simultaneously with non-cooperative autonomous vehicles, and uses beyond-visual range scenarios to reduce vulnerable situations. The safety of Vulnerable road users and the framework of Cooperative navigation is accomplished by using the data from the Road-Side Units (RSU) and On-board Units (OBU). Signalized intersection scenario uses information from the RSU, OBU, Autonomous Intersection Management (AIM) system, and Smart Traffic Lights (STL). Jamming of infrastructure devices and interference into the OBU is enforced to evaluate the cooperative navigation framework in vulnerable situations occurring at the intersection. Threats and vulnerabilities are identified and validated by the design and test of the cooperative navigation algorithm and their quantitative results. Multiple threat scenarios were simulated and results of separation between ego vehicle and actor vehicles were presented, showing the separation time within the set upper and lower bounds. That ensures that the ego vehicle does not collide with others at the intersection. Safety results are also used to generate the Threat Assessment and Risk Analysis (TARA) matrix for quantities analysis.

The cooperative collision avoidance algorithm guides the ego vehicle as soon as the ego vehicle comes in the range of the intersection service area, which increases the safety and capacity of the intersection. This strategy is comfortably used for both an unsignalized and signalized intersection. In an unsignalized intersection scenario, the ego vehicle uses an onboard unit. In signalized intersection scenario, the ego vehicle uses a roadside unit, onboard unit, autonomous intersection management system, and smart traffic lights. The proposed framework is the near-future requirement where the connected autonomous vehicle utilizes the information from smart infrastructure devices.

This activity was originally reported in [12].

12.1 Introduction

Recent advancements in the automotive industry focus on autonomous vehicles. Technology innovations such as Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) communication, Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I) communication, Vehicle to Cloud (V2C), Vehicle to Pedestrian (V2P) communication, and guidance, navigation, and control system continue to propagate to provide a safe environment for Connected Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) and all road users. Government agencies are creating investment opportunities for automotive manufacturers, technology companies, and research institutes in this area for better future perspectives [20]. Smart Columbus is one of the major projects supported by the U.S. Department of Transportation (USDOT) to develop Columbus as a model smart connected city for CAVs to improve people’s quality of life, economic growth, sustainability, and safety [21]. Researchers and scientists are making remarkable efforts to develop a secure and highly reliable autonomous system for smart cities. These systems categorize into two major domains, (i) infrastructure development approach and (ii) vehicular control approach for connected autonomous vehicles.

Technological development in infrastructure related to the automobile industry is focusing on roadside computing and communication devices called Road Side Unit (RSU), Smart Traffic Lights (STL), Smart Traffic Signs (STS), Autonomous Intersections Management (AIM) system, Cloud Storage and Connectivity, and Automated Traffic Management (ATM) System. RSU’s are edge computing devices that establish communication between vehicles and infrastructure. They use the Dedicated Short Range Communication (DSRC) channel to exchange information between infrastructure and vehicles. The OnBoard Unit (OBU) is the second technological development that assists CAVs by utilizing distributed vehicular control approach. Hence safe transit operations in different scenarios such as lane change scenarios, lane merging, lane bi-parting, non-signalized intersections, and roundabout and signalized intersections can be accomplished.

Researchers have proposed different management strategies for Automated Intersection Management (AIM) systems in past few years. However, vehicular control approach-based navigation had many subsystems of the automatic driving systems (way-points positioning system, path planning system, lane-keeping system, etc.) that make vehicles smart enough to operate safely in a vulnerable environment. All subsystems are crucial to converting a vehicle into Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) and Highly Smart Vehicles (HSVs) to operate in vulnerable environments or situations.

In [367], the authors developed the algorithm for the smart intersection that can minimize the headway time and increase the throughput. It is based on the assumption that the lead vehicle was exempt from optimization of headway. In [368], the author proposed the algorithm that controls the SPaT information and prioritizes the signal information or signal phase according to the need for urgency. This work does not discuss the challenges faced by CAVs at the intersection. In [369], the authors present the autonomous traffic management system that can safely route the connected autonomous vehicle across the intersection without collision. In [370], the authors developed the testing framework at CARLA for path following and collision avoidance of connected autonomous vehicles. The path-following and collision avoidance using a non-linear model predicted controller in a straight road driving scenario was developed in [371]. The vehicle level control strategy for collision avoidance and path following are presented and demonstrated in [372]. From the above discussion, it is concluded that the efforts were made in the direction of (i) infrastructure development approach, which is developed only for the smart intersection, and (ii) vehicular control approach, which only works for the un-signalized intersection using V2V communication. Intersection management strategies use a reservation approach for CAVs, compromising the intersection’s capacity. On the other hand, the vehicular navigation strategies mostly use the game theory approach for CAVs at the intersection which compromises safety where beyond visual information is not available [20].

To the best of the authors' knowledge, No cooperative navigation algorithm that uses infrastructure information is found in the literature. Hence, there is a need to develop a novel framework that can eliminate the cons and combine the pros of the above-mention two research directions. The proposed framework utilizes the V2I and V2V information to decide the efficient realization of systems in the smart intersection and non-smart intersections. It will reduce the hazards due to hacking and system failure in the vulnerable environment and enhance the safety, and capacity of CAVs operating at smart intersections. The rapid development of smart cities required the proposed cooperative navigation strategy for CAVs operating at the smart intersection. The main contribution of the proposed work is in the domain of safety and capacity of the smart intersections.

- Safety is achieved using infrastructure devices and vehicle sensors simultaneously by a cooperative navigation framework.
- Capacity and safety are achieved by velocity optimization in a cooperative collision avoidance algorithm.

A summary of the contributions outlined in this work is:

- Quantifies the various ways to deceive HAVs when they are operating at smart intersections.
- Analyzes the effects of jamming, spoofing, and other types of attacks on infrastructure devices and the vulnerable surfaces of the sensors used for HAVs.
- Validates the impact of jamming or altering information on infrastructure devices such as RSU, AIM, and STL.
- Verifies the existence of threats and attacks through quantitative analysis performed in six different threat scenarios.

The chapter consists of five sections: section 2 discusses the problem formulation and mathematical modeling of the CAVs. Section 3 presents the cooperative navigation strategy to avoid collisions for CAVs. Section 4 details the results of the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm, followed by the concluding remarks in section 5.

12.2 Problem formulation

Operations over intersections are the core interest for the researchers as it contains the maximum number of merge, diverge and cross conflict points. The focus of the presented work is to develop a cooperative position, navigation, and timing (PNT) solution for the ego vehicle based on other vehicles operating at the same intersection. It is accomplished keeping in view the navigation strategy to realize the collision avoidance at the smart intersection.

We have developed a cooperative navigation framework to provide awareness of beyond visual range scenarios to the HAVs to avoid collision. The realization of the proposed work assumes that the smart intersection is equipped with RSU, AIM, and STL. Due to the presence of the mentioned devices, the SPaT, intersection parameters, MAP, time-slots, and other lane vehicle information are available for the ego vehicle. All actor vehicles are non-cooperative vehicles. Actor vehicles only share their velocity profiles and do not respond to the other vehicle's actions. Ego vehicle uses the information from all other vehicles. The cooperative navigation algorithm used the information to process and find conflicting situations and then optimized the ego vehicle velocity to generate an optimized ego vehicle velocity profile. Optimized ego vehicle velocity profiles have a constraint

Figure 12.1: Overview of simulation Scenario of smart intersection contains RSU, AIM, and STL. If any actor vehicle does not follow SPaT or AIM, the ego vehicle will collide at the highlighted conflict points.

depending on other vehicles in different lanes at the intersection. Hence, this information is used to calculate the other vehicle's future path with the time of arrival at the conflict point to find potential conflicting situations.

Problem formulation has been done based on conflict points, intersection parameters, and CAV's future path. Fig. 12.1 shows the intersection scenario that has the three vehicles in each lane and each following a different path: straight, right turn, or left turn. The leading vehicle in the i lane is the ego CAV that has to follow the left turn path. A vehicle in the j lane is another CAV that has to follow the straight path. CAV in the k lane has to follow the right turn path, and CAV in l lane has to follow the left turn path. This specific scenario generates two conflict points with respect to the latitude and longitude positions of the ego vehicle within the scenario time frame. There are also three conflicting situations with respect to each vehicle.

The vehicle shares information such as forward and rear lengths of the GPS receiver point, turn indication, the width of the vehicle, the height of the vehicle, the current position of the vehicle in terms of latitude and longitude, the velocity at which its approaching intersection, and heading angle of the vehicle. It assumed that all perception sensors were performing well and generating relative positioning and speed information of other vehicles and their surrounding obstacles. The scenario simulation only deals with the leading vehicles in lanes, but the proposed solution can be implemented for other vehicles in each lane.

12.2.1 CAVs Mathematical model

The dynamic model of the vehicle has been taken into account while developing the simulation framework. The tire modeling is used to depict the nonlinear behavior of the vehicles [373]. The effects of tire slip with steering angle also considered for the evaluation. (12.1) is the $3DOF$ mathematical modeling of CAVs operating at the intersection. Dynamic modeling is referred and modeled according to the SAE J670e standards [374].

$$\begin{cases} I\ddot{\phi} = aP_{if}^n\delta + bF_{ilf}^n - bF_{ilr}^n \\ m(\dot{V}_{iy}^n + V_{ix}^n\dot{\phi}) = \delta P_{if}^n + F_{ilf}^n + F_{ilr}^n \\ m(\dot{V}_{ix}^n + V_{iy}^n\dot{\phi}) = P_{if}^n + P_{ir}^n + F_{ilr}^n\delta \\ \dot{x}_i^n = V_{ix}^n\cos\phi - V_{iy}^n\sin\phi \\ \dot{y}_i^n = V_{iy}^n\cos\phi + V_{ix}^n\sin\phi \end{cases} \quad (12.1)$$

where I is the inertia of the vehicle, ϕ is the yaw angle, a and b are the forward and rear length of the vehicle from the center of gravity, P_f and P_r are longitudinal forces on the front and rear tires, F_{lf} and F_{lr} are lateral forces on the front and rear tires, m is the mass of the vehicle, V_x and V_y are longitudinal and lateral velocities, x and y are longitudinal and lateral positions and δ is the steering angle. ' i ' represents the lane ID of the intersection, and ' n ' represents the vehicle ID. Similar indexes were used for other actors vehicle dynamics, such as j , k , and l for different lanes and $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ for different vehicles. The terms δP_{if}^n and δF_{ilf}^n in (12.1) represent the effect of vehicle side-slip. It is necessary because the vehicle operating at the intersection needs to take a 90-degree turn. Since side-slip is the product of lateral force with steering angle as shown in (12.1). Therefore, as the velocity of the vehicle increases the side slip also increases [375]. Precise steering command signals depend on the side-slip of vehicle.

12.2.2 Intersection Mathematical Model

The intersection is modeled in terms of conflict points for each lane and path taken by the vehicle. The selection of the way-points is crucial for the accurate calculation of conflicting situations. As

Figure 12.2: Cooperative Navigation, Guidance and Control framework, communication network contains all edge devices and shared actor vehicle and environmental data to provide beyond visual range information.

shown in Fig. 12.1, if the selected consecutive way-points are far apart, there is a high probability that system not calculate highlighted conflict points. Since all vehicles are connected, ego CAV can develop a set of way-points for each leading vehicle that can create a conflicting situation. Hence, every next-way point is spaced by the length of the vehicle. (12.2) shows the number of conflict points in a path for a particular vehicle.

$$\begin{cases} q = \frac{R_l \theta}{L_i^n} \\ C_q^i = \Gamma_i^0 + qL_i^n \end{cases} \quad (12.2)$$

where R_l is the left turn radius of the intersection. Γ_i^n is a position where the intersection starts. L_i^n is the length of the vehicle, and C_q^i is the set of waypoints generated to follow the path. q is the number of conflict points for the vehicle. As soon as the vehicle leaves one conflict point, it will enter the next conflict point. This strategy provides all possible conflicting points in a path. Whereas other strategies found in the literature [[369]], and [[21]] use a maximum of 7 conflict points in any of the paths across the intersection. (12.2) can generate conflict points for any configuration of intersection. The value of the θ range for the path is from 0 to 90°. Therefore, the modeled intersection is in a perfect cross configuration. This ensures that the proposed system will work for any type of intersection with the ability to avoid collision.

12.3 Cooperative Navigation System

Navigation based on smart infrastructure relies on devices that share data using the DSRC communication channel. This type of guidance is prone to cyber security threat issues. While navigation using onboard sensors does not provide beyond visual range information. However, both pieces of information are necessary for operations at the smart intersection. The proposed cooperative navigation strategy using both (i) AIM, STL, and RSU information and (ii) Feedback from sensors simultaneously, to provide safe and effective cooperative navigation at the intersection of smart cities. Signalized intersection scenario is discussed in this chapter that has a single incoming lane on each side of the intersection as shown in Fig. 12.1. The number of vehicles in each lane is represented by a different group of vehicles as shown in Fig. 12.1 that is "i", "j", "k", and "l". The

formulation is done to maintain a safe distance within the same group of vehicles and simultaneously avoid conflicts between different groups of vehicles. Fig. 12.1 shows the potential conflict points over the signalized intersection of the simulation scenario highlighted by a circle. Fig. 12.2 shows an overview of cooperative navigation, guidance, and control system that depicts the flow and type of information that can be exchanged between RSU and OBUs of the vehicle. the cooperative collision avoidance block uses all actor vehicles, ego vehicle, and environmental parameters to calculate optimized velocity for the ego vehicle which avoids conflict in the vulnerable scenario. Velocity is used by the path following block to generate actuation command to vehicle dynamics block. Current state values are feedback to path following and send to OBU for cooperation with other vehicles. The cooperative collision avoidance algorithm uses other vehicle information such as position, velocity, length, width, heading angle, lane identity, and turn indication of vehicle. The cooperative collision avoidance algorithm resolves the conflict point between all leading vehicles from each lane and within the lane vehicle.

12.3.1 Collision Avoidance

There are several collision avoidance algorithms available in literature [376], [371], and [377] which address the collision avoidance at unsignalized intersection, also address cooperative scenario but not at signalized intersection. In this work, the collision avoidance algorithm will be part of the onboard computing system. It has capabilities of accessing the information from the modern developed technology such as AIM, RSU, and STL available at the smart intersection. If two of the vehicles have a common 3D positioning such as [lat, long, time] at any timestamp they will collide. The cooperative collision avoidance system calculates the desired velocity to avoid conflicts. Once algorithm optimized the velocity, it will share the velocity to the path following algorithm and repeat the process throughout the simulation. This will generate the velocity profile at which the vehicle follows its path across the intersection. The surrogate optimization fulfills the two basic requirements of real-time optimization in automotive applications. Surrogate consumes less time to optimize the solution and can find the optimal solution for the problem. In the proposed framework, SPaT information from STL, P_i , and turn indication I_i^n from the vehicle is the standard requirement to optimize the ego vehicle velocity. Surrogate optimizes the function within a bounded range defined by the scenario. The algorithm constructs a surrogate as an interpolation of the objective function by using a radial basis function (RBF) interpolator [378]. RBF interpolation has several convenient properties that make it suitable for constructing a surrogate. Evaluating an RBF interpolator takes little time. Which is an essential requirement for an automotive system.

The objective function defines in terms of the time of arrival, traveling time, and phase time of the signal. In (12.3) " T_i^n " is the time vehicle takes to travel from its current position to the next waypoint.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} T_i^n = \frac{C_q^i - x_{i1}^n}{V_i^n} + \tau_i^n \end{array} \right. \quad (12.3)$$

where x_i^n , V_i^n , τ_i^n represent the current position, velocity and minimal separation time of CAV respectively. τ_i^n is also the function of vehicle parameters as a vehicle having a larger size in length needs more separation time than a shorter vehicle. So the conflict situation arises when $C_q^i = C_q^j$ at any particular timestamp.

Let ζ be the difference in time of arrival from ego vehicle to another vehicle at the intersection. Therefore, the objective function in Eq. (12.4) is used to minimize the ζ for all the vehicles at the

Algorithm 9 Cooperative Collision Avoidance Algorithm

```

1: for Lane = 1 : St do
2:   Scan lane ID 'i', 'j', 'k', and 'l'
3:   Scan number of vehicles in each lane
4:   Scan AIM information fin
5:   Scan SPaT information Pi, Pj, Pk, Pl
6:   for Vehicles = 1 : n, . . . , do
7:     Initialized vehicles parameters Vxn, Vyn, δn, φn, an, bn, xn, yn, In, fn
8:     if Pi = In then
9:       Calculate Cqi, Cqj, Cqk, and Cql, based on vehicle parameters
10:      if Cqi = Cqj or Cqk or Cql then
11:        Optimize surrogate ζin, ζjn, ζkn, ζln wrt. v
12:        Share optimized solution to path the following algorithm
13:      end if
14:    end if
15:  end for
16: end for
    
```

intersection by using information from AIM, RSU, and OBUs.

$$\begin{cases}
 \zeta_i^n = |e^{I_i^n - P_i}|(f_i^n + T_i^n) - e^{|I_i^{n+1} - P_i|}(f_i^{n+1} + T_i^{n+1})| \\
 \zeta_j^n = |e^{I_i^n - P_i}|(f_i^n + T_i^n) - e^{|I_j^n - P_j|}(f_j^n + T_j^n)| \\
 \zeta_k^n = |e^{I_i^n - P_i}|(f_i^n + T_i^n) - e^{|I_k^n - P_k|}(f_k^n + T_k^n)| \\
 \zeta_l^n = |e^{I_i^n - P_i}|(f_i^n + T_i^n) - e^{|I_l^n - P_l|}(f_l^n + T_l^n)|
 \end{cases} \quad (12.4)$$

where f_i, f_j, f_k, f_l is the assign time for the vehicle generated by AIM system. $e^{|I_i^n - P_i|}$ is the conditional check on the vehicle to follow the intersection SPaT information. If $T_i^n = T_j^n$ or $T_i^n = T_k^n$ or $T_i^n = T_l^n$ or $T_i^n = T_i^{(n+1)}$ the ego vehicle will collide with any of the four vehicles. Ego CAV velocity is one control variable to avoid collision and following path. (12.4) contains all the parameters that are received by another vehicle in V2V communication. However, this cost function has an upper and lower bound to prevent unwanted delay and excessive speed while CAVs operate at the intersection. (12.5) shows the formulation of upper and lower bound constraints.

$$\left\{ \frac{D_{min}}{V_{max}} \leq \zeta_i^n \leq \frac{D_{max}}{V_{min}} \right. \quad (12.5)$$

where $D_{min} = 1m$ and $D_{max} = 7m$ is the separation distance and V_{min} and V_{max} is the upper and lower limit of ego velocity.

12.4 Results and Discussion

The cooperative navigation, guidance, and control strategy are implemented on Ego Vehicle using MATLAB/Simulink environment. Five vehicles simulated one actor vehicle in each lane and one ego vehicle in lane 'i', as shown in Figure 1. ζ is the separation time between ego vehicle and actor vehicles. The Separation time shown in Fig. 12.3, 12.4, and 12.5. Different color bar represents different actor vehicle in a scenario. Since the ego vehicle is the reference, therefore its bar height is zero and does not appear on the graph.

Figure 12.3: Cooperative collision avoidance results where V2V, AIM, and STL cooperation are available. SPaT information also provides collision avoidance to channel HAVs according to phase and time information.

The results of the cooperative navigation framework are presented in Figures 12.3 to 12.9 to validate the algorithm at different levels of cooperation and threat scenarios. The vertical axis shows the separation time concerning the ego vehicle at the conflict point identified by the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm. The horizontal axis is the sample for each second during the simulation. Non zero positive value of actor vehicle shows that at any instant, ego vehicle and actor vehicle do not collide based on velocity profile followed by actor vehicle and optimized velocity followed by ego vehicle. Negative value shows that the actor vehicle passes before the ego vehicle at a potential conflict point. Ego vehicle tries to maintain the least possible separation distance that also ensures the increase in intersection's capacity with safety. Simulation results show the effectiveness of the proposed optimization and control framework by ensuring that the values of the upper and lower bound constraints as defined in Eq. (12.5) are satisfied.

Figure 12.3 shows the results of cooperative collision avoidance when all communication devices, V2V, AIM, and STL, are available. The non-zero value of the actor vehicle indicates that the ego vehicle and the actor vehicle do not collide based on the velocity profiles followed by the actor and ego vehicle. Figure 12.3 also shows the optimized time separation between the ego vehicle and any other actor vehicle in a scenario where all communication devices cooperate and share information, indicating the value of adding SPaT information. Figure 12.4 shows the results of cooperative collision avoidance when both V2V and AIM devices are available. All bars show negative time separation, meaning all actor vehicles pass after the ego vehicle in the time frame. The optimized time separation depends on two factors in this scenario: the prescribed time slots provided by the AIM device to each vehicle and the minimum separation objective of the collision avoidance algorithm. Figure 12.5 shows the results of cooperative collision avoidance when only V2V cooperation is available. Therefore there is no SPaT information to provide collision avoidance for HAVs based on the signal phase and time information. Similarly, 12.7 to 12.9 can be interpreted and the height of the bar determines the separation between ego and actor vehicles.

12.4.1 PNT quantitative Threat Assessment and Remediation Analysis for HAVs

A quantitative analysis is carried out in a scenario where four vehicles pass through a smart intersection, each in a different lane. All of the vehicles have the ability to exchange information with one another through RSU and V2V communication, utilizing their OBUs to receive signals

Table 12.1: Qualitative TARA analysis of Ego vehicle to validate the threat scenarios for HAVs at the smart intersection.

<i>Ego Vehicle</i>	<i>V2V, AIM, and STL</i>	<i>Jamming of STL</i>	<i>Jamming of STL and AIM</i>	<i>Jamming of all communication devices</i>	<i>Interference in velocities V2V, AIM, and STL</i>	<i>Interference in velocities with STL jamming</i>	<i>Interference in velocities with STL and AIM jamming</i>
X(m)	-111	-111	-111	-111	-111	-111	-111
Y(m)	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5
Time (s)	4	6	8	14	6	7	8
Separation with A1 (s)	-16	-2	-1	-0.7	-0.6	-0.65	0.7
Separation with A2 (s)	-7	-4	-2	0.5	-0.92	-1.2	0.95
Separation with A3 (s)	-31	-5	0.7	0.3	-1.1	-1.7	0.7
Separation with A4 (s)	-2	-5.5	1.1	0.2	3.8	0.7	-0.7
Velocity (m/s)	10	9	8	6	10	9	8
Acceleration (m/s^2)	0.5	0.5	1	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
Steering (rad)	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.8	0.75	0.5	0.38

from each other, but only the ego vehicle is utilizing a cooperative navigation framework, while the other vehicles do not. In the previous section, threats and vulnerabilities of the sensors and sources were analyzed. In this section, the problem associated with the subsystem and sensors is validated through the simulation of different threat scenarios, and quantitative analysis is performed to verify the survey results. Three threat scenarios are simulated for quantitative analysis (i.e. jamming of AIM, jamming of STL with AIM, and interference in the ego vehicle velocity). These threat scenarios affect the PNT solutions of connected autonomous vehicles. The quantitative analysis shows the numerical results of time and distance offset due to threats generated. Table 12.1 depicts the quantitative analysis performed with respect to the ego vehicle. In Table 12.1 column 1 represents the results of cooperative navigation using all communication devices where values in green cells represent the safe separations of the actor vehicles when the ego vehicle is moving at a speed of 10 m/s. X and Y show the coordinates of the conflict points and the time column represents at what time the vehicle arrived at that conflict point. Since it is the analysis of one conflict point, therefore all columns show the same X and Y coordinate values. All green cells indicate that ego vehicles have a safe separation between ego and actor vehicles. All yellow cells show that ego vehicles and actor vehicles have a critically safe separation between them. While the red box shows that the ego vehicle and the actor vehicle are very close to each other and may collide in a vulnerable situation. The separation time in the table is further categorized into three ranges that are safe separation time is greater than 2 sec, critically safe separation time is between 0.8 sec to 1.9 sec, and unsafe separation is between 0.1 sec to 0.7 sec.

12.4.2 Jamming of STL

In this scenario, only the jamming of STL is implemented. STL provides the SPAT information of each lane and map information is still available. In Fig.12.4 vertical axis shows the ζ the separation distance between ego and actor vehicles and the horizontal axis shows the time at which actor and ego vehicles are at the intersection. The negative bar shows that actor vehicles cross the intersection before the ego vehicle. In Table 12.1, column "Jamming of STL" shows the numerical values for the separation time of the actor and ego vehicle. The results are compared with column-1

Figure 12.4: Cooperative collision avoidance results with V2V and AIM devices are available. All actor vehicles pass after the ego vehicle as the time stamp provided to the ego vehicle is much earlier than the actor vehicle.

where all communication devices are available. The second column (Table 12.1) shows the result of cooperative navigation when STL is jammed. Results show a time difference of 14 seconds in both columns. However, the separation distance between the ego vehicle and the actor vehicle "A1" is only 2 seconds, which is safe in this situation but may not be sufficient to prevent collisions in certain conditions and could lead to fatal crashes. Even though the values are within the safe range, as indicated by the green color box, it does not guarantee safety in critical scenarios.

12.4.3 Jamming of AIM and STL

In this scenario, both AIM and STL are jammed. It meant that the SPAT information and intersection reservation for a particular vehicle were not available. Reservation depends on the time of arrival of the vehicle.

Fig. 12.5 shows the plot for the cooperative collision avoidance result discussed in a scenario where only V2V cooperation is available. The high (positive) bars in the figure between iterations 10 to 18 show that the ego vehicle crosses the conflict point much earlier than the actor vehicle. Ego vehicle tries to maintain the least possible separation distance that also ensures the increase in intersection's capacity with safety.

In Fig. 12.5 we can observe that actor and ego vehicles cross the intersection with the cooperation of V2V cooperation and maintain a safe separation distance. whereas Table 12.1 in column 3 shows the quantitative results where actor 'A3' is very close to colliding and only has 0.7 seconds of separation time. Hence, it creates a critical danger situation that leads to fatal crashes. Secondly, actor 'A1' and actor 'A4' have 1 second and 1.1 second of separation time respectively. both actors are below recommended separation (i.e. 2 second).

12.4.4 Jamming of AIM, STL, RSU and V2V

The behavior of connected autonomous vehicles is observed when all communication devices are jammed. In this scenario. In this case, the information from AIM, STL, V2V, and RSU is unavailable. AIM provides guidance on approach velocity and time of arrival. STL provides information about signal phase and timing (SPAT), while RSU provides the map and dimensional information about the infrastructure, as well as creating a link between vehicles in other lanes

Figure 12.5: Cooperative Collision avoidance results where only V2V cooperation is available and AIM, STL, and RSU are jammed. Non zero value of the actor vehicle shows that at any instant, the ego vehicle and the actor vehicle do not collide based on the velocity profile followed by the actor and ego vehicle.

Figure 12.6: Collision results where there is no cooperation is available and AIM, V2V STL, and RSU are jammed.

Figure 12.7: Cooperative Collision avoidance results where all communication devices are available. Non zero value of the actor vehicle shows that at any instant, the ego vehicle and the actor vehicle do not collide based on the interference velocity profile followed by the actor vehicles.

that are out of range for V2V communication. RSU also shares critical information beyond visual range, which helps connected autonomous vehicles avoid conflicts. V2V communication provides the position and velocity profile of other vehicles. there is no cooperative collision avoidance result as there is no cooperation therefore algorithm is not executable. The results shown in Fig. 12.6 where the conflict zone represents the latitude, longitude, and time graph show instantaneous separation between ego and actor vehicles. The jamming of all communication devices column of Table 12.1 represents the quantitative outcome of simulation from the position vs time graph.

12.4.5 Interference's in velocities while all communication devices are active

HAVs operate in a scenario where all the devices are working properly but a malicious actor is present, which introduces interference in the actor vehicle velocities. The interruption of actor vehicle velocities leads to critical situations. Fig. 12.8 shows the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm results where there is interference in the actor vehicles' velocities. It can be observed that there is a huge change as compared to non-interference results in Fig. 12.3. The further quantitative analysis is presented in Table 12.1 in column 5, where values in the yellow box indicate that vehicles are close enough to cause conflicts. By comparing the values in column 1, where all communication devices are available, to the values in columns where one or more devices are jammed, it is clear that the lack of communication leads to an increase in potential conflicts. It is observed that although there is time separation between ego and actor vehicles due to the cooperative navigation algorithm, still the difference in time is enough to create highly vulnerable situations in real-time implementation. The results show that actor A1 is close enough to the ego vehicle, with a separation time of only 0.6 seconds. Actors A2, A3, and A4 have a separation of 0.92, 1.1, and 3.8 seconds respectively. Negative values indicate that the actor vehicles lead the ego at conflict points.

12.4.6 Interference in velocities with STL is Jammed

Quantitative analyses were performed for the scenario where STL is jammed and all other infrastructure and vehicles onboard units are working properly. Fig: 12.8 illustrate the results of the

Figure 12.8: Cooperative Collision avoidance results where STL communication devices are jammed. Non zero value of the actor vehicle shows that at any instant, the ego vehicle and the actor vehicle do not collide based on the interference in the velocity profile.

cooperative navigation algorithm with the interference in the actor vehicle velocities. Quantitative results in Table 12.1 column 6 show the separation time between ego vehicle and actor vehicles in the presence of jamming of STL signals. It is vivid from the results that there is a very small time separation (i.e. 0.92 seconds). According to the U.S. Department of Transportation, when vehicles are operating at speeds of 25 miles per hour, the minimum time separation between them should be 2 seconds. This rule was something I became familiar with while preparing for my driving test. However, since this research is focused on the validation of connected autonomous vehicles, which are capable of reacting to situations more quickly, the critical minimum separation time is reduced to 1 second. This is particularly relevant when the ego vehicle is crossing the intersection at a speed of 4 to 7 meters per second (9 to 16 miles per hour). Anything below 1 sec is considered unsafe for HAVs and anything above 2 sec is considered safe. In Table 1, three different colors are used to indicate the level of safety: red for unsafe critical scenarios, yellow for moderately safe scenarios, and green for safe operating scenarios.

12.4.7 Interference in velocities with STL and AIM are Jammed

Connected autonomous vehicles were observed in a critical scenario where STL and AIM are jammed with interference in actor vehicle velocities. Although the V2V network is not jammed and vehicles can share their state information with other vehicles. Fig. 12.9 shows the outcome of cooperative navigation results when there is interference in the actor vehicle velocities. The further quantitative analysis shown in the last column in Table 12.1 represents that all the actor vehicles are critically close to the ego vehicle and have a maximum time separation of 0.95 second in the case of actor vehicle 2 while all other actor vehicles are at a separation of 0.7 sec. Ego vehicle also drops its operating velocity from 10 m/s to 8 m/s. Hence, it shows that this scenario is not suitable for HAVs to operate in a smart intersection.

Figure 12.9: Cooperative Collision avoidance results where STL and AIM communication devices are jammed. Non zero value of the actor vehicle shows that at any instant, the ego vehicle and the actor vehicle do not collide based on the interference in the velocity profile.

Table 12.2: Qualitative analysis of actor 1

	X(m)	Y(m)	Time (s)
Actor 1	-110	3	12
Ego (Nc)	-110	3	12
Ego (V2V,AIM,STL)	-111	-101	12
Ego (V2V,AIM)	-106	-49	12
Ego (V2V)	-107	-32	12

12.4.8 Intersection Throughput Times and Ego Vehicle Velocities

Since vehicles enter and leave the intersection at a much faster speed, therefore, time spent by the vehicle at the intersection is less than the scenario where vehicles use V2V communication only. This in turn increases the throughput of the intersection. Table 12.2, 12.3 and 12.4 shows the quantitative analysis for actor 1, 2, and 3 respectively. The time column in the tables shows the reference time when actor vehicles collide with ego vehicles in a scenario where no cooperation is done between vehicles. The rows of the table show the level of cooperation of the ego vehicle. In the position column, Different position at the same time stamp at different cooperation level shows that the ego vehicle managed to avoid collision and move faster than when there is no cooperation. Where actors 1, 2, and 3 had conflicting situations at simulation times of 12, 18, and 16 seconds respectively. Actor 4 is in the same lane as the ego vehicle, therefore, it maintains a safe distance throughout the trajectory.

Fig. 12.10 shows the velocity profiles of actor vehicles and ego vehicles with respect to time in different simulation scenarios. As the path following algorithm receives guidance from the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm, it starts tracking the desired velocity. It is evident from Fig. 12.10 that the ego vehicle is following the reference velocity profile while crossing the intersection. Velocity tracking results show that cooperative collision avoidance algorithms provide different velocity profiles in different scenarios.

Cooperative collision avoidance reference velocity provided by V2V cooperation only is the

Table 12.3: Qualitative analysis of actor 2

	X(m)	Y(m)	Time (s)
Actor 2	-111	-16	18
Ego (Nc)	-111	-16	18
Ego (V2V,AIM,STL)	-104	-224	18
Ego (V2V,AIM)	-106	-100	18
Ego (V2V)	-107	-71	18

Table 12.4: Qualitative analysis of actor 3

	X(m)	Y(m)	Time (s)
Actor 3	-111	0	16
Ego (Nc)	-111	0	16
Ego (V2V,AIM,STL)	-104	-192	16
Ego (V2V,AIM)	-106	-85	16
Ego (V2V)	-107	-57	16

Figure 12.10: Velocity tracking results are shown in different cooperation scenarios: (i) V2V cooperation, (ii) V2V and AIM cooperation, and (iii) V2V, AIM, and STL cooperation.

slowest velocity profile to operate safely at the intersection and avoid the collision and vehicles had notable separation. The reference velocity profile provided by V2V and AIM Cooperation slightly increases the velocity of the ego vehicle within the bounds of safety limits provided by AIM which gives an ego vehicle an edge to move faster than it is moving in V2V cooperation. The reference velocity is at its maximum value when all V2V, AIM, and STL cooperation is available, hence giving maximum throughput and significantly reduced separation distance. Therefore proposed cooperative navigation, guidance, and control strategy increase the throughput with safety.

12.5 Conclusion

The proposed framework enables CAV to behave intelligently and cooperate with other vehicles while passing through the smart intersection. Simulation of the suggested framework of the cooperative navigation algorithm used infrastructure information with sensor feedback. The cooperative navigation Algorithm improved safety and intersection capacities while operating at the smart intersection. The efficacy of the proposed framework was evaluated and validated by static environmental parameters, which will be extended to the dynamic environment in the future. This work can also be extended to explore the action of CAVs in presence of threats. In the future, this work continues to evaluate the performance in different scenarios for the threat and vulnerabilities associated with CAVs having cooperative navigation technology.

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Chapter 13

Ensuring the Safety of Highly Automated Vehicles through Cooperative Navigation Methodology

The work described in this chapter quantifies the development of a methodological framework and scenario generation for the safety testing and validation of Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) by using cooperative navigation at smart intersections. The focus of the work is to enhance the safety of the intersection. The purposed methodology allows HAVs to safely navigate through intersections while operating with non-cooperative vehicles. One of the main challenges in this context is that city intersections are often complex environments where onboard sensors may not be able to detect all relevant information, such as vehicles or pedestrians behind obstructions. To address this issue, the proposed approach uses beyond-visual range information from vehicles that are transmitted via an everything communication network. This allows HAVs to perceive their surroundings and make safer navigation decisions.

The cooperative navigation of HAVs is achieved through the use of data from various sources, including Roadside Units (RSU), Onboard units (OBU), Autonomous Intersection Management (AIM) systems, and Smart Traffic Lights (STL). The proposed framework includes several key features, including cooperative collision avoidance (CCA), cooperative cruise control (CCC), and cooperative adaptive lane-keeping (CALK). In addition, HAVs can follow predefined paths using model predictive control. In the proposed framework each vehicle is an independent agent, makes its own decision based on the information available from the vehicle to the everything communication network, and uses a mathematical model to predict future behavior for optimized navigation solutions. To test the performance of the cooperative navigation framework, the authors have generated a scenario in which HAVs operate at a smart intersection. Results show that safety is ensured in a dynamic scenario. Hence the new proposed work is contributing to enhancing the safety of the intersection and development of a new methodological framework.

This activity was originally reported in [13].

13.1 Introduction

There has been a significant focus in the automotive industry on developing autonomous vehicles in recent years. These vehicles rely on a range of technologies, including vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communication, vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication, vehicle-to-cloud (V2C) communication, and vehicle-to-pedestrian (V2P) communication, to operate safely in their environment. In

addition, guidance, navigation, and control systems are essential for ensuring the safety of HAVs and all road users [20]. To advance autonomous systems' growth, government agencies have established investment opportunities for automotive manufacturers, technology companies, and research institutes. A prime illustration of this is the Smart Columbus project, which is backed by the U.S. Department of Transportation (USDOT) and endeavors to turn Columbus into a shining example of a smart connected city for HAVs. This project aims to enhance the quality of life, economic prosperity, sustainability, and safety in Columbus by integrating HAVs [21]. Researchers and scientists are making substantial contributions to the creation of a secure and highly dependable autonomous system for smart cities. There are several navigation methodologies used in different applications. Since HAVs can communicate with each other and their surrounding infrastructure to improve their navigation and decision-making abilities.

13.1.1 Existing HAVs Navigation Methodologies

Several methodological frameworks have been proposed for the cooperative navigation of HAVs, including:

Hierarchical Control: In this approach, a central controller coordinates the movements of multiple HAVs, taking into account the overall traffic flow and the individual objectives of each vehicle [379]. HAVs' longitudinal velocity depends on the central control system which means that malicious actors can disturb complete traffic flow by just interfering centralized control system.

Game-theoretic approaches: These frameworks use principles from game theory to model the interactions between HAVs and to design strategies for cooperation [377]. It increases the computational complexity and is based on the assumption of others' behavior which is not reliable in vulnerable situations.

Multi-agent systems: In this approach, each HAV is modeled as an independent agent that can make its own decisions based on local information and communication with other HAVs [380]. Multi-agent systems are flexible, scalable, robust, decentralized, and adaptable, and facilitate collaboration among agents. These properties make them well-suited for complex tasks and allow for more efficient use of resources, adaptability to changing circumstances, and improved performance, but no literature discusses its application in intersection scenarios.

Distributed optimization: This approach involves designing algorithms that allow HAVs to communicate and coordinate their movements to optimize some global objective, such as minimizing fuel consumption or travel time [381]. Implementing a distributed optimization navigation system at a signalized smart intersection requires a different framework and V2X communication, as the current approach focuses on unsignalized intersections. To effectively navigate a signalized intersection, a new system incorporating V2X communication and a tailored framework must be developed.

Machine learning: Machine learning algorithms can be used to predict the behavior of other HAVs and to optimize the navigation of an HAV based on this prediction [382]. Machine learning in HAV navigation may suffer from over-fitting and poor generalization, as well as a lack of transparency and explainability in decision-making. Additionally, collecting and labeling the necessary data for training can be a time-consuming and costly process.

Decentralized control: In this approach, each HAV makes its own navigation decisions based on local information and communication with its immediate neighbors, without needing a central controller [381]. Decentralized navigation in HAVs has several advantages, including increased scalability, flexibility, and robustness, as well as reduced risk of a single point of failure and improved resource utilization. Additionally, decentralized navigation enables collaboration between vehicles and allows for continuous improvement through learning and adaptation. The extensive survey

on intersection management for CAVs [383] and [384] shows that there is a lot of work going on for infrastructure devices such as Autonomous Intersection Management Systems (AIMS), which schedule the event for CAVs to cross the intersection. Hence it is concluded that there is a gap in the literature which discuss the onboard system that navigates the CAVs to operate independently at the intersection. This refers to the fact that there is a lack of research and development in the area of decentralized navigation for HAVs in smart intersection scenarios. The use of decentralized navigation in these scenarios is yet to be explored and documented in the literature.

Model-based predictive control: This approach uses a mathematical model of the HAVs' dynamics to predict its future behavior and optimize its navigation [385]. MPC is a popular control strategy for HAVs navigation due to its ability to handle constraints and optimally balance multiple objectives. MPC uses a model of the system to predict its behavior over a future horizon and generates control inputs that optimize a performance criterion based on the predicted behavior. It is not found in the literature that the combination of four different subsystems is used to generate the optimized output for a signalized smart intersection scenario using MPC.

Consensus-based approaches: These approaches involve designing algorithms that allow HAVs to reach a consensus on their navigation decisions through iterative communication and negotiation [386]. One of the main drawbacks of a consensus-based approach in HAV navigation is that it may not be efficient in handling large amounts of data in real-time. This is because each vehicle needs to exchange information with every other vehicle in the system, which can lead to increased communication overhead and decreased performance. Additionally, the consensus process can be vulnerable to errors or attacks, which can compromise the reliability of the navigation system

Graph-based methods: These methods involve representing the HAVs and their environment as a graph, and using graph-theoretic techniques to optimize the navigation of the HAVs [291]. The graph-based navigation system has some limitations, such as the difficulty of handling real-world scenarios with unpredictable elements, and the computational complexity of constructing and solving the graph. This can limit the efficiency and accuracy of the navigation system.

Reinforcement learning: Reinforcement learning algorithms can be used to learn optimal navigation strategies for HAVs through trial-and-error [387]. Reinforcement learning has some limitations including difficulty in modeling complex environments, lack of interpretability, and the need for a large amount of data and computational resources. Additionally, it can be difficult to ensure safe and reliable behavior in real-world applications due to the trial-and-error nature of reinforcement learning.

These are a few examples of the many approaches proposed in the literature for the cooperative navigation of HAVs. Research in this area is an active and rapidly-evolving field, and new approaches are being developed all the time. This chapter describes the new methodological framework inspired by a multi-agent system, decentralized control, and model-based predictive control framework used for HAVs navigation. In the proposed framework each HAV is an independent agent, makes its own decision based on the information available from the vehicle to everything (V2X) communication network, and uses a mathematical model of HAV to predict future behavior and optimize navigation solutions.

The proposed methodology is immune to interference in single-agent systems and requires less computational power compared to machine-learning navigation frameworks. In a signalized smart intersection scenario, where only leading vehicles collaborate to cross the intersection, the consensus-based approach is not appropriate. The graphical approach and reinforcement learning require a large amount of data exchange through V2X communication channels, which is not necessary for the proposed methodology but can pose challenges in real-time scenarios.

The chapter is comprised of six sections. Section I serves as an introduction and outlines existing methodologies for navigating HAVs. In Section II, the scenario in which HAVs operate

alongside other HAVs, but only the ego vehicles have the capabilities of the proposed methodology, is discussed. Section III details the proposed methodology, which includes the capabilities of CCA, CCC, and CALK. The results of the CCA are presented in Section IV, while Section V highlights the CCC and its results. Finally, Section VI covers the results of the CALK.

13.2 Intersection Scenario

We have designed a smart intersection scenario for evaluating HAVs. This intersection features advanced technology such as RSUs, AIM systems, and STL with short-range communication technologies (DSRC). RSUs serve as edge communication devices that transmit information about the infrastructure and receive basic safety messages (BSM) from vehicles. AIM is the intersection management system that synchronizes multiple connected intersections in an area to enhance the capacity, and safety at intersections and provide time slots for HAVs approaching an intersection to optimize fuel consumption at the smart intersection. STL is a smart traffic light system that can be controlled signal, phase, and time (SPaT) information according to the situation by the autonomous management system. The vehicles in this scenario share information about their state, such as their current position in terms of latitude and longitude, velocity, heading angle, and dimensions. The vehicles also share information about the GPS receiver location point and the status of the turn indicator. It is assumed that the vehicles' perception sensors are functioning correctly and providing accurate relative positioning and speed information about other vehicles and any surrounding obstacles. The scenario simulation presented in the chapter only considers the leading vehicles in each lane, however, the proposed solution can be extended to other vehicles in the same lane. This allows the vehicle to have a better understanding of the situation in the smart intersection and make critical decisions accordingly.

Fig 13.1 represents the smart intersection scenario equipped with RSU, AIM, and STL. HAVs operating at the smart intersection have OBU to communicate through V2V and V2I communication networks. The illustration in Fig. 13.1 showcases an intersection scenario with four vehicles one in each lane, all moving in different directions (left turns, right turns, and straight). The lead vehicle in lane "i" is an HAV that must take the left-turn path, with the ego vehicle following behind. Meanwhile, the HAV in lane "j" must continue straight, the HAV in lane "k" must make a right turn, and the HAV in lane "l" must also make a left turn. All actor vehicles have random velocity profiles and none of them moves with constant velocity. all vehicles started with an initial velocity of 4 m/s and vary throughout the journey. The ego vehicle adjusts its velocity according to the actor vehicle's velocity to avoid the collision. This scenario generates two conflict points in terms of the ego vehicle's latitude and longitude positions, and three conflicting situations in the given time frame. The scenario is designed to evaluate the cooperative navigation framework where other vehicles don't have the capability of an onboard cooperative navigation system. Therefore other vehicles are sharing their states but do not have onboard cooperative navigation capabilities for beyond visual range information. The purpose of this scenario is to test the proposed cooperative navigation framework in a complex situation and evaluate its impact on the safety and efficiency of the intersection for mixed traffic scenarios.

Intersection Scenario is developed in the RoadRunner environment and integrated with MATLAB/Simulink to generate the simulated results to validate the proposed methodology. The Cooperative Collision Avoidance layer is implemented in MATLAB editor and it provides the optimized velocity to cooperative cruise control. The Cooperative Cruise control and Cooperative Adaptive lane-keeping layer are implemented in Simulink. Both layers get the infrastructure, other vehicles, and roadside unit devices information from the driving scenario designer workspace. The ego and

Figure 13.1: Overview of simulation Scenario of smart intersection contains RSU, AIM, and STL. If any actor vehicle does not follow SPaT or AIM, the ego vehicle will collide at the highlighted conflict points

Figure 13.2: Methodological Framework for Cooperative Highly Automated Vehicles with the features of Cooperative Collision Avoidance, cooperative Cruise Control, and Cooperative lane-Keeping

actor vehicle uses a V2X communication channel based on the DSRC network.

13.3 Cooperative Navigation Methodology

Cooperative navigation is a method used by multiple autonomous agents, such as robots or drones, to navigate and accomplish tasks together. In a cooperative navigation system, the agents work together to achieve a common goal while taking into account the actions and positions of the other agents. This allows them to coordinate their actions and make efficient use of their resources, such as sensors (Radar, Camera, GPS, INS, and Lidar) or communication channels (V2V, V2I, V2P, V2C, and V2X). Cooperative navigation can be used in a variety of applications, such as search and rescue, surveillance, and exploration. In the automotive industry, it is used to enhance the safety, capacity, and fuel efficiency of HAVs especially when they are operating at the smart intersection. The proposed Methodological framework is inspired by a multi-agent system, Decentralized control, and Model predictive control. A multi-agent system and decentralized control provide robustness, flexibility, scalability, and efficiency while MPC can handle constraints, multiple objectives, a multi-variable nonlinear system, and also handle the uncertainty of the system. Therefore we developed a mixed approach that has all these capabilities.

The illustration in Fig. 13.2 presents a visual representation of the cooperative navigation methodology framework, highlighting the flow and type of information exchanged between smart infrastructure and HAVs. The CCC component makes use of all relevant information from the other vehicles on the road, the ego vehicle, and environmental factors to determine an optimized velocity for the ego vehicle, enabling it to navigate safely through potentially hazardous scenarios. Optimized velocity is shared with the path-following system and its sub-systems CCC and CALK. cooperative cruise control provides the adaptive velocity according to the scenario and lead vehicle, while cooperative lane-keeping provides the steering command according to the predefined path and current scenario of the ego vehicle. These signals are passed to the model predictive control (MPC) block and MPC predict the future of the ego HAV for the defined scenario based on HAV dynamic model and generate the optimized adaptive control signals to perform the safe operation

at the smart intersection. In this framework, only the GNSS and INS are used for the positioning of the ego vehicle. All other information was shared through the V2X communication network. The initial version of this framework was published before that has the capability of a cooperative collision avoidance system and path-following system based on information coming from the V2X communication network [23]. The proposed methodological framework is summarized as follows:

- Step 1: Collect information from infrastructure devices such as AIM, RSU, and STL
- Step 2: Scan the number of lanes, and the number of vehicles in each lane
- Step 3: Extract time slot " f_i^n ", " f_j^n ", " f_k^n ", " f_l^n " information for each vehicle from AIM data
- Step 4: Extract SPAT information P_i, P_j, P_k, P_l from STL
- Step 5: Extract vehicle states $V_{x_i}^n, V_{y_i}^n, \delta_i^n, \phi_i^n, a_i^n, b_i^n, x_i^n, y_i^n, I_i^n$, from OBU through V2V communication channel
- Step 6: Cooperative collision avoidance algorithm uses the information to generate a collision-free optimized velocity profile.
- Step 7: CCA calculates the conflict point for other actor vehicles operating at the intersection.
- Step 8: if collision exist based on followed velocity profile CCA optimizes the velocity profile using the Surrogate optimization tool.
- Step 9: CCA ensures the safe separation $\zeta_i^n, \zeta_j^n, \zeta_k^n, \zeta_l^n$ should be greater than 0.7s.
- Step 10: based on safe distance Optimized velocity profile is fed into the cooperative cruise control system.
- Step 11: Cooperative cruise control generates the following velocity based on feedback from inertial sensors, lead vehicle velocity, and optimized velocity from the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm.
- Step 12: The reference and lead velocity are input into a model predictive control (MPC) system and, based on predictions of the near future, the MPC control adjusts the ego vehicle velocity.
- Step 13: Simultaneously, the cooperative lane-keeping algorithm received information from infrastructure devices and generated a heading angle ' θ'_h ' and lane curvature angle ' θ'_c ' to follow and maintain the lane center.
- Step 14: Cooperative lane-keeping algorithm gets the feedback from the inertial sensor and feeds the steering angle to the MPC system.

where $f_i^n, f_j^n, f_k^n, f_l^n$ is the time slot of n^{th} vehicle in lane i, j, k , and l respectively provided by AIM to manage the capacity and safety of the intersection. P_i, P_j, P_k, P_l is the smart traffic signal phase information for each lane i, j, k , and l respectively according to the simulation reference time frame. $V_{x_i}^n, V_{y_i}^n, \delta_i^n, \phi_i^n, a_i^n, b_i^n, x_i^n, y_i^n, I_i^n$ is the longitudinal velocity, lateral velocity, steering angle, heading angle, front tire distance from the center of gravity (CG), rear tire distance from CG, longitudinal position coordinate and lateral position coordinate and turn indicator respectively for n^{th} vehicle in lane i . $\zeta_i^n, \zeta_j^n, \zeta_k^n, \zeta_l^n$ is the separation between ego and n^{th} actor vehicles in lane i, j, k , and l respectively.

13.3.1 Mathematical framework

The objective function defines in terms of the time of arrival, traveling time, and phase time of the signal. In (13.1) " T_i^n " is the time vehicle takes to travel from its current position to the next waypoint.

$$\begin{cases} T_i^n = \frac{C_q^i - x_{i1}^n}{V_i^n} + \tau_i^n \\ T_j^n = \frac{C_q^j - x_{j1}^n}{x_{j2}^n} + \tau_j^n \\ T_k^n = \frac{C_q^k - x_{k1}^n}{x_{k2}^n} + \tau_k^n \\ T_l^n = \frac{C_q^l - x_{l1}^n}{x_{l2}^n} + \tau_l^n \end{cases} \quad (13.1)$$

where x_i^n , V_i^n , τ_i^n , C_q^i represent the current position, velocity, minimal separation time, and conflict point of CAV respectively. τ_i^n is also the function of vehicle parameters as a vehicle having a larger size in length needs more separation time than a shorter vehicle. So the conflict situation arises when $C_q^i = C_q^j$ at any particular timestamp. Let ζ be the difference in time of arrival from the ego vehicle to another vehicle at the intersection. Therefore, the objective function in Eq. (13.2) is used to minimize the ζ for all the vehicles at the intersection by using information from AIM, RSU, and OBUs.

$$\begin{cases} \zeta_i^n = |e^{|I_i^n - P_i|} (f_i^n + T_i^n) - e^{|I_i^{n+1} - P_i|} (f_i^{n+1} + T_i^{n+1})| \\ \zeta_j^n = |e^{|I_i^n - P_i|} (f_i^n + T_i^n) - e^{|I_j^n - P_j|} (f_j^n + T_j^n)| \\ \zeta_k^n = |e^{|I_i^n - P_i|} (f_i^n + T_i^n) - e^{|I_k^n - P_k|} (f_k^n + T_k^n)| \\ \zeta_l^n = |e^{|I_i^n - P_i|} (f_i^n + T_i^n) - e^{|I_l^n - P_l|} (f_l^n + T_l^n)| \end{cases} \quad (13.2)$$

where f_i, f_j, f_k, f_l is the assigned time for the vehicle generated by the AIM system. $e^{|I_i^n - P_i|}$ is the conditional check on the vehicle to follow the intersection SPaT information. If $T_i^n = T_j^n$ or $T_i^n = T_k^n$ or $T_i^n = T_l^n$ or $T_i^n = T_i^{(n+1)}$ the ego vehicle will collide with any of the four vehicles. Ego CAV velocity is one control variable to avoid collision and following path. (13.2) contains all the parameters that are received by another vehicle in V2V communication. However, this cost function has an upper and lower bound to prevent unwanted delay and excessive speed while CAVs operate at the intersection. (13.3) shows the formulation of upper and lower bound constraints.

$$\left\{ \frac{D_{min}}{V_{max}} \leq \zeta_i^n \leq \frac{D_{max}}{V_{min}} \right. \quad (13.3)$$

where $D_{min} = 1m$ and $D_{max} = 7m$ is the separation distance and V_{min} and V_{max} is the upper and lower limit of ego velocity.

$$\begin{cases} V_{ego} = V_{rel} + V_{lead} \\ D_{min} = D_s + G_t * V_{ego} \\ \theta_e = \theta_h - \theta_c \end{cases} \quad (13.4)$$

Cooperative cruise control received that optimized velocity profile as the output from CCA using 13.1 and 13.2 and based on the constraint in 13.3. Since there is no sensor information involved in this framework, therefore, lead vehicle velocity is received from the V2V communication network. The first expression in 13.4 is for CCC where V_{ego} , V_{rel} , and V_{lead} is ego vehicle velocity, relative velocity, and lead vehicle velocity respectively. the second expression is the constraint on CCC to

maintain a safe minimum distance where D_s is the safe minimum spacing between lead vehicles and G_t is the minimum time gap between ego and the lead vehicle. The output of these expressions provides CCC velocity to operate safely at the intersection. The third expression in 13.4 is for adaptive lane-keeping where θ_e , θ_h , and θ_c is ego vehicle relative yaw angle, ego vehicle heading angle, and lane center-line angle respectively.

13.4 Cooperative Collision Avoidance

The field of collision avoidance has numerous existing algorithms documented in the literature, such as those discussed in [376], [371], and [377], which specifically address unsignalized intersections. However, these algorithms do not consider cooperative scenarios at signalized intersections. This study introduces a collision avoidance algorithm that is integrated into the onboard computing system of the HAVs. This algorithm takes advantage of modern technologies such as AIM, RSU, and STL, which are available at smart intersections, to access information and make decisions. If two vehicles have the same 3D position of [latitude, longitude, time], a collision would occur. The CCA system calculates the desired velocity to avoid conflicts and shares the optimized velocity with the path following the algorithm. The process is repeated throughout the simulation, generating a velocity profile for the vehicle to follow as it traverses the intersection. The use of surrogate optimization meets the two key requirements for real-time optimization in automotive applications: it is computationally efficient and able to find optimal solutions quickly.

In the proposed framework, optimizing the velocity of the ego vehicle requires standard information such as SPaT information from the STL, the phase P_i , and turn indication I_i^n of the vehicle. The surrogate optimization process involves finding the best solution within a defined range based on the scenario. This is achieved by using a radial basis function (RBF) interpolator to interpolate the objective function [378]. RBF interpolation is a suitable choice for constructing the surrogate because it is computationally efficient, which is an important consideration for an automotive system.

The cooperative collision avoidance mechanism is described in detail in a previous publication [23]. The results of the cooperative navigation in scenarios with jammed AIM and STL are shown in Fig. 13.3. The figure represents the separation time on the vertical axis and simulation time on the horizontal axis. The zero separation line is the reference of the ego vehicle therefore all separation is concerning the ego vehicle. It is observed that throughout the journey ego vehicle maintains the least minimum safe separation time which is 2 sec as shown in the figure. In the scenario, Actor 4 is in the same lane as the ego vehicle and also leads the ego vehicle, and the cooperative navigation framework uses information from the V2V communication channel to optimize the ego vehicle velocity.

Fig. 13.4 shows the results of a scenario where STL is jammed. It is observed that separation time bars increase to the 20-sec maximum since AIM provides the time slots information to each vehicle to cross the intersection and negative bars show that a particular actor vehicle crosses the intersection before the ego vehicle. Hence each vehicle crosses the intersection at its particular time slot. Actor 2 has minimum time separation with the ego vehicle since it takes the right turn.

Fig. 13.5 shows the results of a scenario where all communication is active. Therefore STL provides the SPAT information to vehicles and AIM provides the suggested time slots. It can be observed that the time separation bar increases to 38 sec as SPAT information restricts the vehicle to cross the intersection at any time. So vehicles only cross the intersection within the SPAT and AIM prescribed time slot. These Separation bar charts are the results of the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm where a separation time of more than 0.7 sec ensures that there is enough

Table 13.1: comparison analysis of Ego vehicles in different threat scenarios with the different driving strategies for HAVs at the signal-free smart intersection.

<i>Cooperative Navigation Strategy</i>	<i>Dynamic re-sequencing (DR) [388]</i>	<i>First in First out (FIFO) [388]</i>	<i>Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS) [388]</i>	<i>Proposed Cooperative Navigation Strategy (PCNS)</i>
Minimum time delay of any two successive vehicles (second)	4.43	6.6	3.93	4

separation between the actor and ego vehicle to avoid the collision which also ensures safety at the intersection.

In [388] author compares the different driving strategies such as Dynamic re-sequencing (DR), First In First Out (FIFO), and Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS) of CAVs operating at the signal-free intersection. where vehicle states are shared via V2I and I2V communication channels. The author defines the fixed distance of the control zone to the conflict zone which is 250m. Results in [388] show that each vehicle passes through the conflict zone in different time slots that ensure safety. Similarly Fig. 13.3 to 13.5 shows different color bars for CAVs operating at the intersection in different threat scenario. The vertical axis shows the time slot separation between the ego vehicle to other actor vehicles while passing through the same conflict point. Fig 13.4 presents the scenario where there is no traffic signal therefore we can compare the results in Fig. 13.4 with results in [388]. Table 13.1 represents the comparison of different driving strategies where MCTS gives minimum time delay in high-frequency traffic zone. The purposed Navigation strategy also provides better results for high-volume traffic zone.

Figure 13.3: Cooperative Collision Avoidance results in a threat scenario where AIM and STL are jammed by the attacker

Figure 13.4: Cooperative Collision Avoidance results in a threat scenario where STL is jammed by the attacker

Figure 13.5: Cooperative Collision Avoidance results in a threat scenario where all communication channels are active

13.5 Cooperative Cruise Control

CCC is the system that allows vehicles to communicate with each other and the infrastructure to improve traffic flow and reduce fuel consumption. In the literature, authors found a combination of radar, cameras, and V2V communication to sense the distance and speed of other vehicles and to adjust the speed of the vehicle in real-time to maintain a safe following distance. The system can also be integrated with traffic lights, road signs, and other infrastructure to optimize traffic flow and reduce congestion. Additionally, CCC can also be used to improve safety by providing advanced warning of potential collisions and supporting automated emergency braking. In the proposed framework, there is only V2X communication is realized to share velocities and the relative distance of other HAVs operating at the smart intersection. In order to validate the efficacy of the framework three different threat scenarios are considered where only infrastructure devices are available. Fig. 13.6 shows that there are some frequent variations in the ego vehicle velocity and the optimized velocity from cooperative collision avoidance. Fig 13.7 shows the lead vehicle velocity. Since the lead vehicle is connected with the ego vehicle but does not have the capability of cooperative navigation, therefore, its velocity profile remains the same in the different threat scenarios. In our analysis, it was determined that the ego vehicle must adhere to the optimized velocity determined by the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm. This means that the cooperative cruise control must be adjusted accordingly to comply with the reference velocity established by the cooperative collision avoidance system. Under all of the specified threat scenarios, the ego vehicle is able to maintain a safe distance from the lead vehicle and avoid collisions with other vehicles at the intersection. As shown in Fig. 13.7, there is a significant difference in the reference velocity from the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm and the velocity of the lead vehicle, which is traveling faster than the ego vehicle. This results in a large separation distance between the two vehicles. The methodology described in the framework permits the ego vehicle to follow the reference set by the cooperative collision avoidance algorithm, as shown in Fig. 13.6.

Figure 13.6: Cooperative cruise control velocity result in all threat scenarios

Figure 13.7: Lead vehicle velocity in all analyzed scenarios

13.6 Cooperative Adaptive lane-keeping

The CALK system is a subsystem of the Cooperative Autonomous Driving System (CADS) that uses a combination of sensors, cameras, and V2V communication to improve the lane-keeping and lane-change capabilities of a vehicle. It provides the driver with an additional level of support by detecting the position of the vehicle relative to the road markings, and by providing steering or braking assistance to help keep the vehicle in the correct lane. The system is also able to communicate with other vehicles on the road to coordinate lane changes and provide advanced warnings of potential collisions. The main objective of the CALK system is to increase the safety of the vehicle and its driver by reducing the risk of lane departure accidents and collisions caused by human error.

The results of three different threat scenarios using the proposed framework are shown in Fig. 13.8. The black curve in the figure represents the predefined curvature of the lane received by the ego vehicle from the RSU. The RSU has detailed information about each lane at the intersection, including the turn curvatures, which helps enhance the safety of the intersection. In the threat scenario where both AIM and STL communications are jammed, and the vehicles are limited to V2V communication, the ego vehicle crosses the intersection at a faster speed as depicted in Fig. 13.8. The blue curve and its comparison with the black curve demonstrate that the ego vehicle crosses the intersection from 9 sec to 12 sec in this scenario. In the scenario where only STL communication is jammed, the ego vehicle crosses the intersection from 13 sec to 17 sec, as depicted by the red curve in Fig. 13.8. The green curve in the figure represents the scenario where all communication channels are active and shows that the ego vehicle takes longer to cross the intersection, from 18 sec to 28 sec. As the level of cooperation increases, the ego vehicle spends more time crossing the intersection.

Figure 13.8: Cooperative lane keeping result in all threat scenarios

13.7 Conclusion

The proposed methodology in this work addresses the cooperative navigation of HAVs in smart intersections. It features four key components: cooperative collision avoidance, cooperative cruise control, cooperative lane-keeping, and path-following. Each vehicle acts as an independent agent, making decisions based on V2X communication and utilizing an adaptive model predictive control to predict the near future. Results from three threat scenarios show that the ego vehicle can maintain a safe distance in all cases, demonstrating the efficacy of the proposed methodology for cooperative navigation at smart intersections. This contribution enhances the safety and capacity of smart intersections and the authors aim to further improve the cooperation and safety of HAVs in future work.

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Chapter 14

Entropy Based Metric to Assess the Accuracy of PNT Information

Entropy measures uncertainty present within the data. Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) can navigate safely and efficiently if location information of occluded dynamic objects is available. It is assumed that dynamic objects have GPS receivers, and location information can be acquired through a fast communication link. However, GPS info can be easily modified or suffers from high error because the transmission link is not secure or due to Non Line of Sight (NLOS) between transmitter and receiver. To solve this problem, an entropy metric is introduced to ascertain the value of the supplied information and reject information with a high amount of error present within the data. This chapter focuses on pedestrians as dynamic objects and uses Finite State Machine (FSM) based hierarchical control to navigate HAVs. It is shown that the entropy metric can improve the efficiency of the control of HAVs.

This activity was originally reported in [14].

14.1 Introduction

Entropy is a tool frequently used in statistics to assess the average level of uncertainty present in the samples of a random variable. Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) have a level of autonomy 5 as per SAE standard, in an urban environment, HAVs are highly dependent on position information of occluded dynamic objects. Position information of occluded dynamic objects is critical for safe and efficient navigation for all the stakeholders. When collected through sensors, this information is vulnerable to hacking and high errors due to urban canyons. These errors can cause accidents and unnecessary delays in the navigation of HAVs. An entropy-based metric can be used to assess the value and reliability of data received. This work uses a simulation setup with occluded pedestrians, and control of HAVs to assess whether using such a metric would benefit the operation of HAVs. For explanation, three such scenarios are presented in section 1.2 and illustrated in Fig. 14.1.

The entropy of a random variable gives the value present within the information. In the case of highly likely events, information is less valuable and vice versa. Consider a discrete random variable $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ and Probability Mass Function (PMF) as $P(X)$. Then entropy can be explicitly written as shown in (14.1)

$$H(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n P(x_i) \log_b P(x_i). \quad (14.1)$$

where b is the base of the logarithm, we have used $b = 10$, which is used when the probability of the event occurring is $1/10$. If $H(x)$ has a high value, we can classify it as poor quality, meaning information with high error and data can be rejected.

14.1.1 Literature Review

Entropy has been used to control automated vehicles to assess the reliability of data received on several occasions. In [389], a method is presented for data fusion to track, recognize, and monitor Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS). In this problem, Robust data alignment is done for successful data fusion. A cost criterion based on entropy is proposed for outlier rejection. In [390] multiple targets must be tracked with multiple dynamic sensing agents. Mobile sensing agents plan their motion so that tracking can be efficient and accurate. An entropy-based cost function is utilized to reject information with an unacceptable error range.

In [391] a scenario is established where three types of vehicles exist on a highway. Namely, fully equipped, partially equipped, and not-equipped. A fully-equipped vehicle has local sensors and communication capability. In contrast, a partially-equipped vehicle can only communicate, and a not-equipped vehicle cannot communicate and does not have local sensors. The objective is to maintain a tracking list of all the vehicles present in the scenario with a tracking list in the partially and fully equipped vehicles. A Kalman Filter (KF) is used for data fusion and correction, and a covariance matrix generated through KF is used to measure the system's entropy. Data is rejected and considered unreliable if the entropy is beyond a threshold. This is used to determine location of occluded pedestrians in "occupancy grid"

In the present work, the pedestrian case is chosen because the safety of all the stakeholders is critical. As local sensors of ego vehicles cannot detect occluded pedestrians, communication setups have to be established. In our simulation setup, we use the information of occluded pedestrians through LTE/4G.

In case pedestrians are occluded, several methods are utilized to detect a pedestrian. In one method, using off-camera on the streets in an industrial area is used to detect the pedestrians through WiFi [392]. However, this solution is costly and not scalable. Another method by [393] utilizes software-defined radio to transmit the position of pedestrians that, in turn, is also very expensive as dedicated DSRC modules are too expensive. In [394] 802.11 b/g/n communication method is used so that HAVs can receive position information of occluded pedestrians, and the data is fused with LIDAR to get accurate results. However, this solution is also too expensive and not scalable. Currently, we do not have a vast network of WiFi routers in the road infrastructure. [395] used 3G/WLAN to communicate pedestrian information to the vehicle. However, it was not fast enough that the problem could become scalable and choke the network if the number of vehicles or pedestrians increased. With 4G/LTE and 5G, pedestrians can send their position information, and the communication modules are affordable. We suggest this communication protocol for sharing pedestrian location information with the vehicle. We have assumed all pedestrians have cell phones with GPS sensors available for pedestrian localization. The problem with GPS sensors is that it suffers from Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) in urban areas due to high-rise buildings and can have a high amount of position, navigation, and timing errors, which can have errors up to 50 meters. Also, GPS transmitting frequency can be easily generated, and fake information can be generated to misguide the sensor, resulting in accidents or unnecessary collision avoidance measures from the ego vehicle.

We have developed a process to detect occluded dynamic objects in our proposed method. We assume that the typical profile of errors in GPS position information is known, and we will use baseline controllers to compare with our design controller of ego vehicle to prove our system is more

efficient and safe using performance metrics.

Figure 14.1: Scenarios: (a) Pedestrian on street, (b) Bike from alleyway, (c) Bike in uncontrolled intersection

14.1.2 Simulation Case Study

To explain Vulnerable Road Users (VRU). We are presenting three cases in Fig. 14.1 taken from ISO standard 22737 section 3.1 [396]. Fig. 14.1(a) is inspired from section 3.1.1 and Fig. 14.1(b) and Fig. 14.1(c) is inspired from section 3.1.2. in (b), a bicyclist comes from an alleyway and appears suddenly in front of the ego vehicle. Similarly, in (c), a bicyclist appears from an uncontrolled intersection. Collectively pedestrians and bicyclists are classified as VRUs. The implemented simulation setup is shown in Fig. 14.1(a). A static pedestrian who is falsely reporting its position with high errors. An occluded dynamic pedestrian jaywalking and a parked vehicle on one road lane. Such a setup is created to show that using entropy and extra information from the environment can result in the safe and efficient control of HAVs. The goal is to test our proposed method with multiple baselines to show our method's effectiveness using some performance metrics. Goals achieved in this case study are listed below.

- Introduced an entropy-based metric that will assess the reliability of position information received
- Designed some metrics to measure the performance of HAVs in terms of energy consumed and minimum distance to a dynamic object maintained by HAVs
- Designed Finite State Machine based hierarchical control of ego vehicle

In the next section entire architecture of how communication setup is created and how entropy is performed to assess the position accuracy of the data and the metrics utilized to measure the performance of the process is defined, and results are provided in the next section with a concluding remarks in the last section.

14.2 Methodology

In this section, the whole process of how occluded pedestrian is detected and avoided successfully is explained. The complete process is shown in Fig. 14.2. Each block of the process will be explained in subsequent sections, and finally, brief information about the baseline controllers used for comparison is presented.

14.2.1 Environment

Ego vehicle is modeled with NVIDIA PhysX model which is similar to dynamic bicycle model. Streets and intersections are built in the environment. Position, velocity, and acceleration information can be extracted from the environment, and steering, throttle, and brake to control the vehicle. Pedestrians with a point mass model are also added within the environment, with speed and heading control available for the pedestrian. Their position can be extracted from the environment. The environment can be seen in Fig. 14.1(a).

14.2.2 Reliability of GPS data

It is assumed that all the pedestrians and vehicles have GPS receivers and 4G/5G transceivers present. Pedestrians are transmitting their position information to a cloud server. The cloud server will then send the data to vehicles in the vicinity of pedestrians to modify their trajectories to avoid collisions. In Urban scenarios GPS can have high error [397]. The primary reason for this error is high-rise buildings that block the transmitter and receiver's Line of Sight (LOS). A process

Figure 14.2: Block Diagram of the Process

is designed to assess the reliability of the amount of error present in the data. The process is explained in Fig. 14.3. In the first step, N samples are collected. N has to be small so that process can be executed in real-time. After that, L_2 norm of each two-dimensional sample is calculated. Afterward, a histogram is calculated as shown in (14.2). where s_j is each GPS sample collected from a pedestrian. In Fig. 14.3, it is to be noted that t seconds is different from T seconds as to evaluate histogram, we need some samples; therefore, in our work, $T=5t$.

$$P(s_j) = \frac{Histogram(s_j)}{\sum_{i=1}^n Histogram(s_i)}. \quad (14.2)$$

Then in the next step entropy is calculated as shown in (14.3) .

$$H(S) = - \sum_{j=1}^n P(s_j) \log_b P(s_j). \quad (14.3)$$

The process was applied on real-time data taken from the City of Cincinnati Department of Public Health [398] with two types of error added random walk and Gaussian Noise with shifted mean and high variance. Results in Fig. 14.4 show that a threshold (approximately 1.89) can be established to ascertain the variance of the data. Moreover, data can be rejected if the data has a high variance. The blue curve is the original data collected, while the green curve is when Gaussian error $X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 0, \sigma^2 = 10)$ is added into the data to show the effectiveness of the method. Similarly, in orange curve random walk error $X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 0, \sigma^2 = 3N)$ is added into the original data. where $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$. In Fig. 14.4 it can be seen that a threshold of approximately 1.8 can be used, and if the entropy value is below this threshold, data will be rejected.

14.2.3 GPS and LIDAR Fusion

To fuse data two step process is followed taken from [399]. Scan Matching is performed as shown in (14.4)

$$\min_{x_i^{sm}(t)} \left(\frac{1}{2} e_i^T(t) P_{rel} e_{ij}(t) + \frac{1}{2} e_i^T(t) P_{gps} e_i(t) \right). \quad (14.4)$$

Figure 14.3: Flow Diagram for Entropy Calculation

$$e_{ij}(t) = z_{ij}(t) - \max(\|x_i^{sm}, x_j^{gps}\|_2). \quad (14.5)$$

$$e_i(t) = x_i^{sm} - x_j^{gps}. \quad (14.6)$$

where x_i^{sm} is realigned position of ego vehicle and x_j^{gps} is the GPS measurement from pedestrian j . While $z_{ij}(t)$ is the relative position measurement from LIDAR where i is the ego vehicle and j is the j th pedestrian and P_{rel}, P_{gps} are covariance matrices.

The benefit of using scan matching is that not only LIDAR and GPS data is fused, but the error is also corrected. The next step in the process is Kalman Filtering (KF). The benefit of using KF is twofold we get the next predicted state of the pedestrian while the amount of error in the position is corrected. The model used to predict the next state of a pedestrian is based on the point mass model.

The next challenge in the process is that there are three possible detections because of communication errors and local sensor (LIDAR) limitations. The three cases and how they are handled to create a final list of position information of all dynamic objects presented are shown in Fig. 14.5. A similar approach is followed in all three cases. First, LIDAR detections are matched with GPS data using the vicinity rule. The vicinity rule means that in the Horizontal Alert Level (HAL) of LIDAR detection, it is assumed that GPS detection will be available and then processed through KF to get the final predicted positions. The rest of the data is processed through KF to generate a final list of detections.

Figure 14.4: Entropy of GPS Data from Cincinnati

Figure 14.5: GPS and LIDAR Data Fusion

Table 14.1: Flags and their Interpretation

Symbol	Definition
F_I	Intersection Flag
α	Distance to start decelerating
D_{d2p}	Distance to closest pedestrian
β	Distance to start hard decelerating
θ	Distance to start decelerating while turning
ξ	Distance to start hard decelerating while turning

14.2.4 Finite State Machine based Hierarchical Control

Finite State Machines (FSM) is a mathematical model through which a finite number of mathematical computations can be performed through a finite number of interconnected states. FSM is widely used to control machines requiring a sequence of operations. A machine can be in one of a finite number of states at any given time. State transitions happen based on indicators from the environment indicating the machine's state. Hierarchical FSM control is utilized to control the vehicle, and at a low-level PID control is implemented. The FSM controller is shown in Fig. 14.6. It has two higher-level states straight and turn. With a straight node, we have further three states: follow, brake, emergency brake, and similar three states in higher node turn but with different indicators to switch between states. The detail and function of each indicator are shown in Table 14.1.

Figure 14.6: Hierarchical Finite State Machine

14.2.5 Performance Metrics

To measure the performance of the designed process, three metrics are used. The first metric consists of using the vehicle's lateral position and angle, implying the collision avoidance measure used to avoid the pedestrian. The metric is shown in (14.7)

$$J1 = \sum_x x^T Q x + u_1^T R u_1. \quad (14.7)$$

where Q and R are positive definite and positive semi-definite matrices, respectively, x is the state vector with states, $[y \ \theta]$ where y is the vehicle's lateral position with respect to the origin and θ is the angle with respect to the ego vehicle. Furthermore, u_1 is the input vector with steering angle γ given to the vehicle.

This metric $J1$ is derived by implementing the observer model using the lateral position and angle of the dynamic model as shown in [400]. $J1$ is a convex function and can measure the energy consumed by the vehicle while performing evasive action to avoid the vehicle.

The second metric is based on the distance to the closest pedestrian maintained by the vehicle at all times and is shown in (14.8)

$$J2 = \frac{1}{D_{d2p}} + k\xi. \quad (14.8)$$

where D_{d2p} is the distance of the vehicle with the closest pedestrian and k is a very high gain, and ξ is a binary value which is one when the vehicle collides with the pedestrian.

This metric is derived such that when the vehicle gets closer to the pedestrian, it penalizes the metric heavily as it is inversely proportional to the distance to the vehicle and gives a very high penalty if the vehicle collides with the pedestrian. A binary term is added with a high gain to indicate a collision. The additional binary term is added because the distance is measured from the vehicle's center to the center of the pedestrian. It is to be noted that the binary term is piece-wise defined, and when a pedestrian is in close vicinity of the vehicle, it is considered a collision.

Finally, the last metric measures deceleration within the vehicle when it is performing evasive action to avoid the vehicle. The metric is shown in (14.9)

$$J3 = \sum h(u_2)^T Q h(u_2). \quad (14.9)$$

where $h(u_2)$ is shown in (14.10) and u_2 is the acceleration of the vehicle when it is performing an evasive action to avoid the pedestrian

$$h(u_2) = (-1 + \text{sign}(u_2))u_2. \quad (14.10)$$

14.2.6 Baseline Controllers for Comparison

To show a better performance. Three baseline controllers were used, the first one is vanilla PID control with longitudinal control to avoid dynamic objects, and the other two have similar architecture as in Fig. 14.2. Nevertheless, some blocks were removed. In the second baseline, the block labeled reliability of GPS data is removed. In the third baseline controller, both the blocks' reliability of GPS data and fusion of LIDAR and GPS functionalities were removed, and the performances were compared. Vanilla PID is utilized only in metric J2 because the FSM-based controller implemented has PID at a low-level hierarchical control. Consequently, if the proposed method performs better after removing the blocks, it will perform better if only vanilla PID is

compared. Vanilla PID is used in J2 to demonstrate that vehicle collides with a pedestrian in the absence of the proposed controller.

14.3 Results and Discussion

The simulation environment used to test the designed process is CARLA [401] open-source environment. The scenario is described in Fig. 14.1 part (a). The pedestrian moving has a GPS error of $X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 0, \sigma^2 = 3)$ and the pedestrian which is stopped on the sidewalk has an error of $X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu = 0, \sigma^2 = 10)$. These errors are chosen because GPS errors in the literature are modeled using the Gaussian error model [402], and variance is chosen such that it remains under the acceptable range. This reference [403] shows that the error variance is less than 10 meters. The required speed is 20 m/s because the maximum speed limit in US streets is 45mph, approximately equal to 20 m/s. The vehicle has to start decelerating if the distance to the pedestrian is less than seven meters and has to go into hard deceleration mode if the distance to the closest pedestrian is less than four meters. The results with each metric are shown in Fig. 14.7, Fig. 14.8 and Fig. 14.9.

The metrics are measured only when the vehicle takes action to avoid a collision with the pedestrian. In Metric $J1$ that is shown in section 14.2.5, we can see the results in Fig. 14.7. Until 15 seconds, the pedestrian is not detected. No energy is consumed to avoid the pedestrian. However, after that, it can be seen that until 40 seconds, baseline two and baseline three algorithms mentioned in section 14.2.6 are still consuming energy because the pedestrian on the sidewalk is reporting its position in the collision range of the vehicle and our process can reject this data using entropy metric as described earlier. In the second figure, Fig. 14.8 the baseline controller one collides with the pedestrian while other baselines and our complete process can avoid the pedestrian. The reason for this is that the setup provides occluded pedestrian's position beforehand, and it has knowledge well before there is a possibility of a collision, and the vehicle performs preemptive action. Moreover, the last metric $J3$ also shows similar results in Fig. 14.9 because of the same reasons described above. Vanilla PID is not used in Fig. 14.9 and Fig. 14.7 because low-level control of FSM includes PID, and the proposed method performs better when scan matching and KF are implemented within the system. Consequently, if the system outperforms when only specific features are turned off, it will certainly perform better than vanilla PID. In Fig. 14.8 it is explicitly used to show that the ego vehicle collides with the pedestrian and which is a safety hazard. Our process outperforms baseline controllers and can avoid pedestrians based on the metrics. However, it can be observed that baseline methods outperform the proposed method in some instances. This is because the entropy metric is not always perfect, and sometimes erroneous information results in extra energy consumption of energy, but the overall proposed method outperforms baseline methods. Another noteworthy thing is that having extra information prevents collision. Suppose such a system, as described above, had been developed and deployed. Arizona's fatal crash of a semi-automated vehicle with a pedestrian could have been avoided.

Figure 14.7: State Based Cost Metric

Figure 14.8: Distance to Pedestrian Based Cost Metric

Figure 14.9: Deceleration Based Cost Metric

14.4 Conclusion

In this work, a communication setup was provided to receive position information of the occluded so that collisions can be avoided. This solution is scalable because the communication protocol and access can be easily obtained as almost every pedestrian carries a GPS sensor and LTE/4G module in their cell phones. However, creating a solution in such a way creates a problem if the information has a significant amount of errors present within the information, which will reduce vehicle efficiency significantly. So to solve this problem, an entropy-based threshold is introduced to solve this problem. Then, the fusion process of LIDAR data with GPS data to remove other inaccuracies was introduced. Metrics were presented to show the performance of the proposed method. Results show that the proposed method can make HAVs safer for all the stakeholders present within the environment and make HAVs more efficient in terms of energy consumption to evade pedestrians. Since most pedestrians have LTE/4G modules and GPS devices within their cellular phones, Hardware Infrastructure is already present. Nothing new needs to be established. The method proposed is practical in the real world.

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Chapter 15

Infrastructure-Aided Defense for Autonomous Driving Systems: Opportunities and Challenges

With the growing interest and investment in leveraging intelligent infrastructure support for practical AD, AD system may have new opportunities to defend against existing AD attacks. In this chapter, we are the first to systematically explore such a new AD security design space leveraging emerging infrastructure-side support, which we call Infrastructure-Aided Autonomous Driving Defense (I-A2D2). We first taxonomize existing AD attacks based on infrastructure-side capabilities, and then analyze potential I-A2D2 design opportunities and requirements. We further discuss the potential design challenges for these I-A2D2 design directions to be effective in practice.

This activity was originally reported in [15].

15.1 Introduction

As Autonomous Driving (AD) technology becomes increasingly deployed and commercialized in the real world, more and more people start to consider the security of AD vehicles. There are a lot of researches trying to create adversarial examples for fooling AI components in AD systems. Zhao et al. introduce malicious stop signs that can not be detected by AD vehicles [404], while Cao et al. create printable objects that can not be perceived by both camera and LiDAR [405], leading to serious crashes. Some other works focus on the localization module. Shen et al. use GPS spoofing to lead the victim to crash into an incoming vehicle on the opposite lane [406].

On the other hand, the AD system design patterns are also evolving, with growing interests and investment in leveraging infrastructure-side support. Specifically, a new direction of AD design called Infrastructure-Aided Autonomous Driving (IAAD) is being developed recently, which uses infrastructure side communication and sensing abilities to improve AD reliability while reducing on-board sensing cost [407]. Today, there are many ongoing IAAD testing, and even deployment efforts by companies and institutes. For example, Baidu is currently testing intersections with IAAD deployed in several cities; to demonstrate the benefits of such infrastructure-side support on AD, they even showcase L4 AD capability only using infrastructure-side sensing *without using any on-boarding sensing* [408]. Seoul Robotics proposes to use sensors embedded in surrounding infrastructure to achieve L5 AD; BMW is currently testing that system at its Munich manufacturing facility [409]. HORIBA Institute for Mobility and Connectivity (HIMaC2) at UC Irvine plans to equip 25 intersections in Irvine with Velodyne's LiDAR-based intelligent infrastructure solution

Table 15.1: Categorization of existing AD attacks from the perspective of infrastructure-side capability requirements in I-A2D2 designs. Full version is Table 15.2 in Appendix.

Category	Attack	I-A2D2 design
A1: Perception of infrastructure-authoritative information	Sign hiding [404, 414–420]	Traffic sign
	Sign appearing [404, 419–421]	Traffic sign
	Traffic light changing [422, 423]	Traffic light
	Object hiding [405, 424–441]	Obstacle detection
A2: Perception of dynamic road objects	Object appearing [421, 423, 438, 441–445]	Obstacle detection
	Object relocation [446–449]	Obstacle detection
	Object detection disabling [438, 450]	Obstacle detection
A3: Localization	Trajectory shifting [406, 423, 451–453]	Localization
	Localization disabling [438]	Localization and lane

[410]. Among various different AD deployment scenarios today, IAAD is most attractive and thus likely to be first utilized by robo-taxi/ride-hailing services due to the cost considerations [411]. On the government side, some countries have already realized the importance and benefits of such smart transportation infrastructures not only to practical AD deployment but also to city functions (e.g., mobility and environmental aspects), and are thus making proactive policies for building such infrastructures [412, 413].

Considering such a new AD design trend, it is important to explore whether and how it may influence the existing AD security design space. In this work, we are the first to systematically discuss the opportunities and challenges for such a new AD security design space leveraging emerging infrastructure-side support, which we call Infrastructure-Aided Autonomous Driving Defense (I-A2D2).

15.2 I-A2D2 Design Opportunities

With infrastructure-side sensing and communication abilities, many existing attacks against AD systems can potentially have new defense opportunities. Due to the different nature of the attacks, different infrastructure-side capabilities can be required for effective and systematic I-A2D2 defense designs. We thus started by performing a comprehensive survey of representative AD attacks published in recent years, and classified them into 3 categories from such I-A2D2 design requirement perspective: (**A1**) *Perception of infrastructure-authoritative information*; (**A2**) *Perception of dynamic road objects*; (**A3**) *Localization*. A short version of such categorization is in Table 15.1; the full version is Table 15.2 in the Appendix.

15.2.1 A1: Perception of Infrastructure-Authoritative Information

Opportunities. Like human drivers, AD has to follow traffic rules, such as obeying the speed limit and waiting for a red light. Quite some existing works target their perception and thus trick the victim to break traffic rules; as in Table 15.1, there are 8 attacks trying to hide the traffic signs from being detected by AD vehicles, e.g., using stickers [404]; 4 attacks try to create non-existing traffic signs, e.g., using a projector [420]; 3 attacks try to change the traffic light result detected by AD vehicles, e.g., by exploiting ROI designs [422].

However, since traffic signs and traffic lights are under authoritative control of the government transportation agencies, the infrastructure is able and also authoritative to provide such information. For example, the infrastructure may broadcast the existence of a stop sign at a GPS coordinate to all passing-by AD vehicles. This can at least provide another (if not more trustworthy due to the source authoritativeness) information source to AD vehicles, which thus can enable at least direct attack detection capabilities against all these existing attack vectors targeting infrastructure-authoritative information such as traffic signs and lights.

Required infrastructure-side capability. To inform the AD vehicle of authoritative information, the infrastructure must be able to communicate with the AD vehicle in time. Currently, DSRC and C-V2X are the commonly used wireless communication technologies for cars, both of which are able to deliver a message within 100ms [454, 455]. On the other hand, since the information to transmit is known in advance, the infrastructure can send it before the AD vehicle needs to react to the information, such as informing the AD vehicle 200 m away from a stop sign. Thus, if designed properly, the infrastructure should be able to always ensure the information can arrive in time to the AD vehicle side to enable effective defense design opportunities. Such authoritative information also needs to be sent with the location information, e.g., absolute GPS coordinates. The AD vehicle can then use its own real-time localization to react at the correct position, e.g., stop when it's right in front of a stop sign.

15.2.2 A2: Perception of Dynamic Road Objects

Opportunities. To avoid collision, AD vehicles need to detect dynamic road objects and avoid them proactively. Some attacks aim at the obstacle detection component and try to hide, relocate, or create non-existing objects in front of the victim. The others directly disable the obstacle detection component. We find 20 attacks trying to hide objects using a variety of methods, e.g., using malicious shape changes [405]; 8 aim at adding non-existing objects to the detection results, e.g., using sensor spoofing [438, 442, 445]; 4 try to change the location of the object in the detection results, e.g., using malicious stickers/posters [449]; and 4 try to disable obstacle detection, e.g., using sensor jamming [438, 450]. To defend against such attacks, the infrastructure-side perception capabilities (e.g., camera and LiDAR) in the emerging IAAD designs [407–410] (§15.1) can be leveraged to help perceive maliciously hidden objects or eliminate attacker-introduced fake objects. The AD vehicle side can fuse their own detection results with such infrastructure-side detection results, which can at least detect (if not able to correct) the attacked results.

Required infrastructure-side capability. Defending against A2 requires better communication capabilities compared to A1 in both latency and bandwidth. The AD vehicle needs to be informed of the object in time so that it can have adequate time to make decisions and react (e.g., stop before crash or change lane). Since the objects are dynamic, to achieve this the infrastructure need to frequently transmit the most recent detection results, which thus requires a much smaller latency and higher bandwidth than A1. Failing to do that, the infrastructure can end up sending obsolete information that can be even misleading in extreme cases.

Besides the communication capability requirements, the infrastructure-side perception also needs to be accurate enough. To more concretely understand such accuracy requirement, we perform an estimation of the maximum allowed perception errors based on common lane width and car width. Here, the most error-sensitive scenario takes place when the detection results indicate that all obstacles are out of the current lane boundaries, but in reality the detection errors are large to the extent that there can be a misdetected obstacle with which a collision cannot be possibly avoided by the AD vehicle. Fig. 15.1 shows such a setup with the least error tolerance, where an obstacle is detected to locate on the boundary of the adjacent lane, but its actual location can

Figure 15.1: Estimation of the maximum allowed obstacle perception errors for I-A2D2 designs against A2 attacks.

collide with the AD vehicle even if the AD vehicle is choosing the safest possible route in the ego lane (e.g., on the rightmost side in Fig. 15.1). In this case, the maximum allowed detection error of such obstacle is $LaneWidth - VehicleWidth$. According to USDOT, the lane width ($LaneWidth$) of a local road should be at least 2.7 m [456]. As for vehicle width ($VehicleWidth$), we take the width of a common AD vehicle model, Lincoln MKZ, which is 2.12 m. Therefore, the maximum allowed errors for infrastructure-side dynamic object detection cannot be over 0.58 m (Fig. 15.1).

15.2.3 A3: Localization Attacks

Opportunities. Localization is a key component for AD to accomplish tasks such as navigation and path planning. The AD vehicles need to know where it is on the road or in the map to follow the lane and to decide whether to make a turn. It's also required to know the vehicle's ego position when using infrastructure-side authoritative information in A1 defenses (§15.2.1). We find 5 attacks targeting localization (Table 15.1), e.g., using GPS spoofing [406] and dirty road patches [452], which can cause severe consequences such as driving off the road and even crashing into the incoming vehicle from the opposite direction. Since camera is usually used for lane centering in L2 AD systems, camera blinding attack [438] can also disable the AD system's localization ability, which may cause potential shifting of the vehicle position.

Similar to A2 attacks (§15.2.2), the infrastructure-side perception capability can enable defense opportunities against A3 attacks. Specifically, the infrastructure side can keep sending information such as locations of all perceived in-road vehicles to the AD vehicle side. On the AD vehicle side, when it first receives such information, it uses its own localization result (e.g., from GPS) to find the closest infrastructure-side detected vehicle as the representation of itself. It then performs object tracking of such a vehicle in subsequent infrastructure-side sent frames, taking its real-time location as infrastructure-aided localization results. When the attack happens, there will be a mismatch between the AD vehicle's self-localization and such infrastructure-aided localization results; the AD vehicle can thus use the latter as an additional information source to at least perform attack detection. Note that such a design follows the trust-on-first-use (TOFU) assumption, i.e., assuming that the AD vehicle is not under localization attack the first time it receives the infrastructure-side information, so that it can correctly find the matching result from infrastructure-side detected vehicles.

Required infrastructure-side capability. Defending against A3 attacks requires similar communication capability as those against A2, as they both require real-time infrastructure-side perception. In terms of localization accuracy, in the infrastructure-aided localization discussed above, performing localization of AD vehicle is essentially performing object detection like I-A2D2 defenses against A2 (§15.2.2). However, comparing to A2 attacks, defending against A3 attacks needs a higher perception accuracy, as a deviation of $\frac{LaneWidth - VehicleWidth}{2}$, which is $\frac{2.7 - 2.12}{2} = 0.29m$ if using the same *LaneWidth* and *VehicleWidth* values as in §15.2.2, is already enough to cause a vehicle to have lane departure. To achieve such infrastructure-aided localization capabilities, it thus requires the infrastructure side to have better sensing ability and more reliable algorithm to perceive objects from the input data in the real time.

15.3 I-A2D2 Design Challenges

15.3.1 Precise Self-localization from Infrastructure Perception

As discussed in 15.2.3, to defend against localization attacks (A3), the infrastructure side needs to achieve sufficiently-accurate localization of pass-by vehicles. However, we find that achieving such required accuracy is non-trivial based on our preliminary experiments in a real IAAD-deployed road.

Experiment setup. We perform our preliminary experiments on a real road where IAAD is deployed for testing purposes. The IAAD-supported road segment is over 1000 meters long with full IAAD coverage. We experiment with two LiDAR obstacle detection models on the collected data: (1) the built-in segmentation model used in Apollo 5.0 [457], an open source industry-grade AD system, which we denote as “Apollo5”; (2) PIXOR [458] from Uber ATG. Among all the objects detected in each frame, we select the one closest to the ground truth as the infrastructure-aided localization result, and compare it with the ground truth. We calculate the error in each frame to evaluate the performance.

Results. The distribution of the errors of each frame and also their median are plotted in Fig. 15.2. As shown, the median error of Apollo5 is 0.68 m, while that of PIXOR is 0.82 m, both of which cannot meet the requirement identified in 15.2.3 (0.29 m). To understand the causes, we examine whether the distance from the infrastructure-side LiDAR to the vehicle can affect the accuracy of localization. We collect such distance and localization errors of the Apollo5 model in each frame, and plot all data points in Fig. 15.3a. As shown by the red line, the errors almost monotonically increase with the distance. That is likely because when the vehicle is farther away from the LiDAR, the laser points become more sparse and thus makes it more difficult to have accurate perception. We further group data points based on distance, and draw a box plot in Fig. 15.3b. One interesting observation is that, when the distance is small, there are some outliers with big errors. This is likely because the LiDAR is mounted in a high position (around 3 m), and only a few laser channels with large pitching angle can cover close areas, resulting in a sparse point cloud for nearby objects.

Future improvements. We plan to explore the following directions in the future to improve this: (1) Use newer point cloud object detection models and train them with infrastructure-side data; (2) Use Kalman Filter on the infrastructure-aided localization.

15.3.2 Adaptive Attacks

Attack infrastructure-side perception. Since the sensors and the AI components used for such perception are similar to those used on AD vehicles, the attackers can apply/adapt existing

Figure 15.2: Error distribution of both the Apollo LiDAR perception model (“Apollo5”) and the PIXOR model.

(a) All data points

(b) Box plot

Figure 15.3: Localization error of the Apollo LiDAR perception model (“Apollo5”) at different distance.

vehicle-side perception attacks to the infrastructure side, or even attack both AD vehicle and infrastructure perception at the same time [405].

Exploit fixed sensor positions. Because IAAD sensors are in fixed positions, when facing the same sensor attack, infrastructure can be more vulnerable comparing to AD vehicle (e.g. no need to perform tracking and aiming for laser shooting attacks [442]). In a similar vein, generating adversarial examples can be easier as well, since it no longer requires taking the vehicle motion dynamics into consideration like in [404, 452].

New cyber-attack surface. In IAAD/I-A2D2, the communication between infrastructure and AD vehicle can expose AD vehicle’s interior system to other devices, which thus introduces a new cyber-attack surface.

15.4 Conclusion

In this work, we are the first to systematically discuss the opportunities and challenges for the new Infrastructure-Aided Autonomous Driving Defense (I-A2D2) design space. We first taxonomize existing AD attacks based on infrastructure-side capabilities, and then analyze potential I-A2D2 design opportunities and requirements. We further discuss the potential design challenges for these I-A2D2 design directions to be effective in practice. We hope that our discussions and insights can inspire more future research into this promising but currently under-explored defense design space for AD system security.

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15.5 Appendix

The full version of our comprehensive survey of representative AD attacks published in recent years, classified into 3 categories from an I-A2D2 design requirement perspective: **(A1)** *Perception of infrastructure-authoritative information*; **(A2)** *Perception of dynamic road objects*; **(A3)** *Localization*.

Table 15.2: Categorization of existing AD attacks based on infrastructure-side capability requirements in I-A2D2 defense designs.

Category	Attack	Threat model	Impact							I-A2D2 design					
			Sign hiding	Sign appearing	Traffic light changing	Object hiding	Object appearing	Object relocation	Object detection disabling	Trajectory shifting	Localization disabling	Traffic sign	Traffic light	Lane	Obstacle location
A1: Perception of infrastructure-authoritative information	Lu et al. [414]	Stop sign poster	✓								✓				
	Chen et al. [415]	Stop sign poster	✓								✓				
	Lovisotto et al. [416]	Projection to camera	✓								✓				
	Zolfi et al. [417]	Patch to camera len	✓								✓				
	Dunn et al. [418]	Laser shooting to camera	✓								✓				
	Nassi et al. [421]	Projection and billboard		✓							✓				
	Song et al. [419]	Stop sign patch	✓	✓							✓				
	Zhao et al. [404]	Stop sign patch and poster	✓	✓							✓				
	Man et al. [420]	Projection to camera	✓	✓							✓				
	Tang et al. [422]	GPS spoofing			✓							✓			
	Wang et al. [423]	IR lights			✓							✓			
Man et al. [420]	Projection to camera			✓							✓				
A2: Perception of dynamic road objects	Wiyatno and Xu [424]	Poster				✓								✓	
	Xiao et al. [425]	Malicious object				✓								✓	
	Zhang et al. [426]	Patch on obstacles				✓								✓	
	Tu et al. [427]	Malicious object				✓								✓	
	Wu et al. [428]	Patch on obstacles				✓								✓	
	Xu et al. [429]	Adversarial T-shirts				✓								✓	
	Hau et al. [430]	Laser shooting to LiDAR				✓								✓	
	Zhu et al. [431]	Patch with bulbs				✓								✓	
	Ding et al. [432]	Malicious object				✓								✓	
	Tu et al. [433]	Malicious object				✓								✓	
	Li et al. [434]	GPS spoofing				✓								✓	
	Wang et al. [435]	Patch on obstacles				✓								✓	
	Köhler et al. [436]	Laser shooting to camera				✓								✓	
	Zhu et al. [437]	Board and drone				✓								✓	
	Cao et al [405]	Malicious object				✓								✓	
	Yan et al. [438]	Ultrasonic foaming				✓								✓	
	Nakka and Salzmann [439]	Patch on road				✓								✓	
	Nesti et al. [440]	Billboard				✓								✓	
	Wang et al. [423]	IR lights					✓							✓	
	Cao et al. [442]	Laser shooting to LiDAR					✓							✓	
	Sun et al. [443]	Laser shooting to LiDAR					✓							✓	
	Yang et al. [444]	Malicious object					✓							✓	
	Nassi et al. [421]	Projection and billboard					✓							✓	
	Sun et al. [445]	mmWave shooting					✓							✓	
	Ji et al. [441]	Ultrasound to inertial sensors			✓	✓								✓	
	Yan et al. [438]	Ultrasound shooting			✓	✓								✓	
	Jia et al. [446]	Patch on obstacles						✓						✓	
Jha et al. [447]	Malware							✓					✓		
Hong et al. [448]	Compromised ROS node							✓					✓		
Chen et al. [449]	Patch on obstacles							✓					✓		
Wang et al. [450]	Patch								✓				✓		
Yan et al. [438]	Laser shooting to camera								✓				✓		
Yan et al. [438]	mmWave jamming								✓				✓		
Yan et al. [438]	Ultrasonic jamming								✓				✓		
A3: Localization	Shen et al. [406]	GPS Spoofing							✓					✓	
	Kong et al. [451]	Billboard							✓		✓		✓		
	Wang et al. [423]	IR lights							✓		✓		✓		
	Sato et al. [452]	Road patch							✓		✓		✓		
	Jing et al. [453]	Road patch							✓		✓		✓		
	Yan et al. [438]	Laser shooting to camera							✓		✓		✓		

Chapter 16

Detecting Data Spoofing in Connected Vehicle based Intelligent Traffic Signal Control using Infrastructure-Side Sensors and Traffic Invariants

Connected Vehicle (CV) technologies are under rapid deployment across the globe and will soon reshape our transportation systems, bringing benefits to mobility, safety, environment, etc. Meanwhile, such technologies also attract attention from cyberattacks. Recent work shows that CV-based Intelligent Traffic Signal Control Systems are vulnerable to data spoofing attacks, which can cause severe congestion effects in intersections. In this chapter, we explore a general detection strategy for infrastructure-side CV applications by estimating the trustworthiness of CVs based on readily-available infrastructure-side sensors. We implement our detector for the CV-based traffic signal control and evaluate it against two representative congestion attacks. Our evaluation in the industrial-grade traffic simulator shows that the detector can detect attacks with at least 95% true positive rates while keeping false positive rate below 7% and is robust to sensor noises.

This activity was originally reported in [16].

16.1 Introduction

The Connected Vehicle (CV) technologies enable Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) and Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communications and can help the vehicles and infrastructure make more informed driving/control decisions. They can benefit our transportation system by improving mobility, reducing safety risks and greenhouse gas emissions, etc. As a result, government agencies across the globe are competing to push for CV deployments [459–461]. Particularly, the US is one of a few early adopters that has been testing the CV applications in US cities since 2016 [459]. In general, CV applications can be categorized into *vehicle-* and *infrastructure-side*. The vehicle-side applications aim to maximize fuel efficiency, enable better perception, etc. The infrastructure-side applications focus on improving the control decisions that will be executed in the infrastructure. The most representative infrastructure-side application is CV-based traffic signal control, which designs to improve traffic mobility by assigning signal timing plans that prioritize lanes with longer queues to reduce the total vehicle delays. Due to the enormous efforts for CV deployment, CV applications need to consider an inevitable transition period where CVs and Regular Vehicles (RVs)

coexist on the road [462]. It is projected to take over 20 years to reach 95% market penetration rate (i.e., 95% vehicles are CVs) [462].

The widespread deployment of CV applications has a significant impact on the traffic safety and operations, thus making them to be valuable targets of cyberattacks. Among them, the most representative attack targets *real-world* infrastructure-side CV application [463], where they discover that CV-based traffic signal control is vulnerable to data spoofing attacks. The authors assume that the attacker can compromise the On-Board Unit on a CV to send malicious vehicle states to the signal controller to cause traffic congestions in the intersection. To exploit the vulnerabilities, they design two congestion attacks that target the full deployment and transition periods respectively. The two attacks are demonstrated to be very effective on the USDOT Intelligent Traffic Signal System (I-SIG) [464], a system already under testing in real-world intersections in US cities.

To defeat such data spoofing attacks, we explore a general spoofing detection strategy that cross validates the cyber-layer vehicle states using the physical-layer ones to identify the spoofers. In our design, we use the readily available *infrastructure-side sensors* [465–467] to obtain the physical states of CVs. However, the infrastructure-side sensors suffer from a fundamental limitation in the detection range compared to the CV communication range. This leads to challenges when dealing with vehicles out of the sensor range. To address it, we leverage well-established *traffic models* in transportation systems, which empirically describe the normal vehicle driving behaviors. We take the traffic models as the *traffic invariants* to estimate the physical states of the vehicles out of sensor range and assign trust scores based on the difference between reported and estimated states. Finally, a threshold-based anomaly detector is applied to identify suspicious CVs that have large negative impacts on the signal plan.

We evaluate the detector in an industrial-grade traffic simulator, PTV Vissim [468]. In the offline detection setting, our detector can strike a good balance between True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR)—it can achieve at least 95% TPRs under all penetration rates while maintaining a low FPR of 7%. Specifically, when CVs are fully deployed, our detector shows a perfect detection with 100% TPR and 0% FPR. We also evaluate the robustness of our detector to the infrastructure-side sensor detection noises. The results indicate that our detector can tolerate even $3\times$ normal sensor detection noises. We then systematically explore the online detection capability of our detector. Results show that our detector remains effective even in online setting, where in the worst case, the FPR is only increased by 5% when the TPR maintains at 98.1% compared to offline detection. In summary, this work makes the following contributions:

- We explore a general spoofing defense for infrastructure-side CV applications based on the discrepancy between the cyber- and physical-layer vehicle states leveraging infrastructure-side sensors and traffic models.
- We implement the detector for CV-based intelligent traffic signal systems and evaluate the detection effectiveness against two congestion attacks. Results show that the detector can achieve $>95\%$ true positive rate when the false positive rate is $\leq 7\%$ and is robust to sensor noises.
- We explore detection timeliness and effectiveness when it is deployed as an online detector. Results show that online detection increases the false positive rate by only 5% when maintaining a high true positive rate in the worst case.

Figure 16.1: An 8-phase intersection.

Figure 16.2: Signal timing plan for 8-phase intersection. Circled numbers with solid background denote phase IDs.

16.2 Background and Threat Model

16.2.1 CV-based Traffic Signal Control

Traffic signal control is one of the important applications of CV technologies designed to improve transportation mobility by reducing vehicle delays in the intersection. It determines the signal timing plan based on the real-time vehicle states (including vehicle ID, location, speed, heading, etc.) periodically broadcast from the CVs in the intersection. Specifically, CVs send their vehicle states in a standard Basic Safety Message format, which is transmitted over the CV communication network, i.e., Dedicated Short-Range Communication (DSRC) [469] or Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) [470]. Among the open efforts in CV deployment in the US [459], the Intelligent Traffic Signal System (I-SIG) [464] is the only traffic signal system designed for the mobility of general urban intersections [471]. It has been tested in US cities and shown high effectiveness at reducing vehicle delays [472].

Fig. 16.1 shows the configuration of a common major arterial intersection. As shown in the figure, the traffic lanes are grouped by different *phases*, each with a dedicated traffic signal. As a major arterial intersection, it has two concurrent phase sequences (or *rings*) that do not interfere with each other and can be planned simultaneously. However, the phases in the same ring need to be planned sequentially due to the confliction. The 8 phases are separated into two *stages*, which are also conflicting with each other. The CV-based traffic signal controller is invoked at the end of each stage to calculate an *allocation of green lights* to the phases, which is called a *signal timing plan*. Fig. 16.2 shows a typical timing plan for 8-phase intersections. The green blocks indicate the allocated green light durations. The yellow and red blocks are two predefined durations for the yellow light and red clearance light (to accommodate for potential red light runners). The inputs to the signal controller are the latest CV states received at the end of each stage, which we refer them as a CV or traffic *snapshot* in this work.

16.2.2 Congestion Attacks on I-SIG

Recent work [463] discovered two vulnerabilities in the I-SIG system that can be exploited using data spoofing attacks. The first one is in queue length estimation, where the I-SIG system estimates the number of vehicles stopping in a queue based on the farthest stopped CV in the transition periods, i.e., when the Penetration Rate (PR) is smaller than 95%. They find that such a design can be exploited by the attacker to inject a fake long queue in the estimation, which we term *queue length attack*. The second vulnerability targets the arrival time estimation, where I-SIG estimates when will a vehicle arrive at the stop line or stop behind a queue. An attacker can exploit this by setting the CV with a slow speed to cause a late arrival time estimation, which we term *arrival time attack*. In both attacks, the I-SIG system allocates an *unnecessary* long green time for traffic lanes that are not busy and thus starve the other lanes that need prioritization. The attacks are evaluated in an industrial-grade traffic simulator PTV Vissim [468]. Results show that the two attacks can effectively cause severe congestion effects in full deployment and transition periods of CVs, respectively.

16.2.3 Traffic Modeling

Traffic models as the traffic invariants. Traffic modeling is a well-established topic in transportation engineering, which aims to precisely describe the relationships between vehicles and infrastructure with mathematical equations [473]. Due to the attractive property of describing normal traffic behaviors, we repurpose traffic models as the traffic invariants for security enforcement, e.g., benign vehicles will generally behave according to the traffic models. Specifically, we leverage *microscopic* traffic models as they describe individual vehicle behaviors when reacting to the actions of other vehicles.

Newell’s car-following model. Car-following models [474–476] are the most typical microscopic model type that describes how should a vehicle follow its leading vehicle. The Newell’s car-following model [475] is a simple but effective model, which is built upon the assumption that the follower vehicle’s trajectory looks similar to its leading vehicle’s trajectory, except with a time delay and a space translation. More formally, the model describes the following relationships:

$$\begin{aligned} s &= v_f \cdot \tau + d \\ x_{\text{follow}}(t + \tau) &= x_{\text{lead}}(t) - d, \end{aligned} \tag{16.1}$$

where s is the spacing the following vehicle keeps to the leading vehicle; x_{follow} and x_{lead} are the longitudinal position offsets of the following and leading vehicles; τ and d are two empirically determined parameters describing the reaction time and stopping distance of a normal driver, which are typically between 1.0–1.7 and 6.0–9.6, respectively [477, 478]; v_f is the free-flow speed, which is the speed limit of the road.

16.2.4 Threat Model

We assume same threat model as the congestion attacks proposed by Chen et al. [463], where the attacker is able to compromise the in-vehicle CV communication device, i.e., the On-Board Unit, in their own vehicle to send malicious BSM messages. We do not assume the attacker can spoof the vehicle identifier in the BSM messages, which are protected by the Security Credential Management System. Thus, the attacker needs to use the original certificate associated with the physical vehicle in order to get the messages correctly authenticated.

16.3 Related Work

Security analyses of CV applications. Previous works [479–481] have studied the security threats on the CV communication networks, such as DoS, spamming, masquerading, replay attacks, which greatly damage the availability, authenticity, and confidentiality of the network. On the other side, domain-specific attacks have been demonstrated in different CV application scenarios. Chen et al. [463] show that CV-based Intelligent Traffic Signal Systems are highly vulnerable to congestion attacks if the attacker can compromise the OBU device. Amoozadeh et al. [482] demonstrate that message falsification attack cause significant instability in the Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control (CACC) vehicle stream. Abdo et al. [483] perform a detailed analysis on CACC and present 4 different attack scenarios. Furthermore, Huang et al. [484] analyze the impact of falsified CV data and propose a black-box attack on the CV-based traffic signal control system.

Defenses against data spoofing. Sun et al. [485] propose a verification scheme approach that utilizes the angle-of-arrival and frequency-of-arrival to detect spoofing attacks. Such a defense requires extra hardware and the presence of enough number of reflectors in the driving environment. Guo et al. [486] propose a collaborative intrusion detection system, which leverages the sensor data from onboard sensors of neighboring CVs. Liu et al. [487] propose a blockchain-based framework to build trust and defeat spoofing attacks in CV applications. Both works assume specific hardware or software updates in the CVs, which may require enormous efforts due to a large number of CVs. In comparison, our detector does not impose such requirements on the CVs. Instead, we reuse the readily-available infrastructure-side sensors to establish the physical root-of-trust for the detection (§16.5.1). In this work, we approach from a novel angle by constructing and propagating trust based on infrastructure-side sensors and traffic invariants, which are complementary to existing defenses.

16.4 Challenges of Applying Infrastructure-side Sensors for Data Spoofing Detection

Data spoofing attacks are cyber-layer attacks, where attackers send dishonest information of their physical states over the communication channels. Thus, a natural strategy to detect such attacks is to cross validate with physical-layer information. One readily available physical-layer information source is the infrastructure-side sensors, e.g., cameras [465, 488] and LiDARs [467], which perceive vehicle positions and speeds in the physical world and can serve as the *physical root-of-trust*. Currently, the infrastructure-side sensors are already performing vehicle detection and tracking in red-light enforcement [489] and traffic monitoring [490]. Thus, we reuse them as a cost-effective solution for data spoofing detection.

16.4.1 Defense Challenges

Fundamental limitation of infrastructure-side sensors: detection range. Although infrastructure-side sensors can provide accurate detection of the CVs to validate their reported states, their detection ranges are often much more constrained than the CV communication ranges. As illustrated in Fig. 16.3, the effective detection ranges of traffic cameras are usually at ~ 100 meters [466, 491, 492], while CV communication channels (e.g., DSRC and C-V2X) can cover much larger ranges (typically >300 meters [493]). This thus leaves opportunities for the attackers since they can simply spoof CV locations beyond the sensor detection range to evade direct detection. For example, the spoofed CVs are usually located at the end of each intersection approaches with

Figure 16.3: CV communication range is often much larger than infrastructure-side sensor range.

a distance of ~ 300 meters to the center of the intersection in the congestion attacks [463]. In fact, this is a fundamental limitation of sensors compared to cyber-layer communication—extending the sensing range (e.g., installing and synchronizing with additional sensors) is often much more costly and difficult than extending cyber-layer communication ranges (e.g., using signal relay devices or opting to longer range communication protocols such as C-V2X). Because of this fundamental limitation, two defense challenges need to be addressed in order to leverage the infrastructure-side sensors for effective data spoofing detection in the CV context.

Challenge 1: How to systematically propagate the trust from the sensor range to the CV communication range? With the help of infrastructure-side sensors, it is straightforward to verify the reported states of the CVs within the sensor range and establish trust for the ones that match the detection results. But for the CVs outside the sensor range, there is no direct way to measure their states. Despite that, the trusted CVs within the sensor range can provide useful information to verify the positions of the farther CVs, and hence a systematic solution is required to facilitate such trust propagation.

Challenge 2: How to infer the RV states outside the sensor range? Since it is estimated that the deployment of CV technology needs more than 20 years to reach at least 95% market penetration rate [462], there will be an inevitable transition period where CVs and RVs co-exist on the road. During such period, the RVs that are outside of sensor range may disrupt the trust propagation and cause mis- or false detections since the detector is not aware of these RVs. Thus, gaining the knowledge of these RV states is important for accurate spoofing detection.

16.5 Defense Design

16.5.1 Design Overview

In our design, we define the *trust* of a CV based on its integrity, i.e., CVs that report a state far away from its ground truth state will be assigned with lower trust (or higher suspicion). Our detector measures the trust of each CV in a traffic snapshot (i.e., the received CV states that a CV application is used for decision-making) and pinpoint the ones that have the lowest trust and the

Figure 16.4: Defense design overview.

largest impact on the CV application performance. As shown in Fig. 16.4, the detector takes the CV snapshot and the corresponding sensor detection results as input and outputs the suspicious CVs that are likely to be spoofers for further handling. The detection process involves two major steps: *Trust Assignment* and *Remove-and-Rerun*.

Trust Assignment (TA). In this step, we start from our physical root-of-trust, i.e., sensor detection results, to assign *suspicious scores* to the CVs in the sensor range by comparing their reported states with the detection results. Next, we propagate the trust out to the CV range in the order of CVs’ reported distances to the sensor range. Since there is no direct way to measure the physical states of CVs out of the sensor range (Challenge 1), we estimate the CV states based on our *traffic invariants*, i.e., the traffic models, which are empirically derived mathematical equations describing the vehicle driving behaviors under various traffic conditions (§16.2.3). For example, the car-following models can be used to estimate a vehicle’s spacing and velocity based on its leading vehicle. We then use the estimated state as a proxy to the CV’s ground truth state to calculate the suspicious score.

Since traffic model’s accuracy depends on the availability of surrounding vehicle information, it is thus imperative to address Challenge 2 to infer their states in the current CV snapshot. To achieve that, we look into the “future” sensor frames when an RV first enters the sensor range to learn which vehicles are its neighbors. Based on the neighboring vehicles in a future time window, we can thus apply traffic models to infer an RV’s state in the current CV snapshot. When the detection process is deployed as an offline analysis, such “future” sensor frames are always available. However, when deployed as an online detection, we have to delay the detection for a certain duration to wait for more sensor frames to come. In this case, since the future time window is limited, the number of recoverable RVs will also be reduced. However, in practice, even a relatively short future time window (e.g., 6 seconds as shown in §16.8.1) is sufficient to cover the majority of RVs. Although the detection is delayed in the online analysis, this is not much a problem for traffic signal control since the attack effect often takes time to build up, e.g., the I-SIG congestion attacks take ~ 18 minutes to build up the congestion effects [463].

After the trust assignment, we rank the CVs based on their suspicious scores. As will be shown in §16.6.2, the spoofing CVs are always ranked with top suspicious scores. In practice, we can aggregate the suspicious score rankings from multiple CV snapshots to more accurately pinpoint the spoofing CVs. Nevertheless, in our design, we apply a Remove-and-Rerun step to further improve the detection accuracy.

Remove-and-Rerun (RnR). In RnR, we re-execute the CV application *with* and *without* a suspicious CV to confirm its impact on the attack objective. The intuition behind this is that the attacker’s goal is to disrupt the CV application to cause adverse effects on some CV application metrics, which can often be quantified in the application itself. For example, the congestion attacks on I-SIG are designed to increase the total delay of the vehicles in the intersection, which is exactly what I-SIG is optimized for. Such an attack objective driven approach can effectively distinguish attack CVs from benign ones among the most suspicious CVs.

16.5.2 Trust Assignment

The TA step essentially checks the cyber-layer CV states against their physical-layer states to locate dishonest CVs. It calculates a suspicious score s_i for each CV in the current snapshot as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} s_i &= \|x_i^c - x_i^p\| \\ x_i^c &\in X^c, x_i^p \in X^p, i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, \end{aligned} \quad (16.2)$$

where x_i^c and x_i^p represent CV’s reported and physical states (detailed later); n is the total number of CVs in the current snapshot; $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the absolute difference between two states, e.g., Euclidean distance. Based on the suspicious scores, we then rank the CVs to obtain the top- K suspicious ones X' :

$$X' = \arg \max_{X' \subset X^c, |X'|=K} \{s_i \mid i = 1, \dots, n\}. \quad (16.3)$$

We define the vehicle state as a vector $x = [t, l, r, v, h]$, where t is the timestamp; l is the traffic lane ID (e.g., as in Fig. 16.1); r is the distance to the intersection center; v is the vehicle speed; h is the vehicle heading. Since traffic signal controllers need to know the intersection geometry in order to plan for dynamic traffic situations, they often have a pre-built map that supports querying these state elements from vehicle BSMS. For example, I-SIG by default will convert the BSMS into such information before optimizing for the signal plan.

Among cyber- and physical-layer states, x_i^c is readily available from CVs’ continuous broadcasting. For x_i^p , we rely on the physical root-of-trust (i.e., sensor detection) and traffic invariants (i.e., traffic models) to obtain and infer the physical states of CVs in and out of the sensor range. The former is out of scope of this work since vehicle detection and tracking is a well-studied topic in computer vision [491, 492] and already has many commercial products on the market that can provide real-time detection [465, 488, 490, 494]. For the latter, it involves two sub-steps: *RV state inference* and *trust propagation*, and we will detail them in §16.5.2 and §16.5.2.

Car-following model as the traffic invariant. Since car-following models describe the inter-vehicle spacing that a vehicle will maintain given the leading vehicle’s speed, we use them as the traffic invariant to infer the *ideal* position that a vehicle will be located in the current lane based on its leading vehicle. Specifically, we apply the widely-used Newell’s car-following model (Eq. 16.1 in §16.2.3) in our design for its simplicity. Given a leading vehicle state $[t, l, r, v, h]$, we can estimate the following vehicle state at time t as follows:

$$\mathcal{M} : [t, l, r, v, h] \rightarrow [t, l, r + (v \cdot \tau + d), v, h]. \quad (16.4)$$

This conforms to the Newell’s model that (1) the follower drives at the same speed as the leader, and (2) the follower’s spacing is adjusted based on the speed.

RV State Inference

For RVs out of sensor range, we infer their states based on their *future* leading vehicles in the sensor range. More concretely, if an RV appears in the sensor detection in any of the future frames

between t_0 and $t_0 + T$, we can thus infer the RV's physical state at time t_0 as follows:

$$x_j^{t_0} = \begin{cases} \mathcal{M}(x_{\text{lead}}^{t_0}), & \text{if } \exists t \in \{t_0, \dots, t_0 + T\}, \|x_j^t - C\| < R \\ \emptyset, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (16.5)$$

$$j \in \{1, \dots, m\},$$

where x_j is the RV state at time; x_{lead} is the leading vehicle in the sensor frame; m is the total number of RVs; t_0 is the time of the CV snapshot to check for spoofing activity; $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$ denotes the state estimation function based on the car-following model; C and R are the geographic center and radius of the sensor range, respectively. Depending on the time window (or the delay) allowed in the detector, it is possible that an RV will not appear in the sensor range. In such case, our detector will simply not be aware of this RV.

Identifying leading vehicle. To find the leading vehicle for a target vehicle, we iterate over all available vehicle states at t and look for the one that 1) belongs to the same lane and 2) is in front of and closest to the target vehicle. In cases when the distance to the closest leading vehicle is greater than $v_f \cdot \tau + d$, we regard the target vehicle as in free-flow traffic and exclude the leading vehicle since it should have negligible impact on target vehicle's driving behavior.

Handling RVs without leading vehicles. When there is no leading vehicle or the leading vehicle is too far away, we then estimate the RV state at t_0 based on its kinematics, assuming that the RV maintains the same speed between t_0 and t .

Trust Propagation

With more RV states made available out of sensor range, we can now more accurately estimate the physical state of the CVs and propagate the trust from our physical root-of-trust. Similar to the RV state inference, we apply the traffic invariant, i.e., the Newell's car-following model, to estimate the physical state of the CV i based on its leading vehicle as follows:

$$x_i^p = \begin{cases} \mathcal{M}(x_{\text{lead}}), & \text{if } \exists x_{\text{lead}} \\ [t_i^c, l_i^c, d_i^c, v_f, h_i^c], & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (16.6)$$

Different from RV state inference, even when there is no leading vehicle, we are still aware of the existence of CV i . Thus, instead of ignoring it, we set its state the same as its reported cyber-layer state *except its speed as the free-flow speed of the lane* since we know for sure there is no leading vehicle and hence the CV should be driving at the free-flow speed in the normal case.

Suspicious score calculation. After obtaining the physical states from the sensor detection or inference, we then calculate a suspicious score for each CV, which is defined as the *distance* between the cyber- and physical-layer states (Eq. 16.7). More concretely, the suspicious score calculation depends on the availability of physical state elements as below:

$$s_i = \begin{cases} |d_i^c - d_i^p|, & \text{if } \exists d_i^p \\ |(v_i^c - v_i^p) \cdot \tau + d|, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (16.7)$$

When the CV's physical distance to the intersection is available, we calculate the suspicious score directly based on the difference to the one in the cyber-layer state. When only the speed element is available in the inferred physical speed, we plug the speed difference into Newell's model to obtain a spacing penalty such that the suspicious score is a distance measurement and hence comparable to the above case.

16.5.3 Remove and Rerun

We perform RnR on all top- K suspicious CVs (Eq. 16.3). For each CV k in X' , we exclude it from the current CV snapshot and re-execute the I-SIG application to obtain the new total delay. Since the attacker aims to increase the total delay and ultimately cause congestion in the intersection, removing a spoofing CV from the snapshot would likely to reduce the total delay. Formally, we perform the RnR as follows:

$$x_k^c = \begin{cases} \text{spoofed,} & \text{if } \frac{\mathcal{F}(X^c) - \mathcal{F}(X^c \setminus \{x_k^c\})}{\mathcal{F}(X^c)} \geq \epsilon \\ \text{benign,} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (16.8)$$

where $\mathcal{F}(\cdot)$ denotes the I-SIG application that calculates the total delay; x_k^c is one of the top- K CVs; ϵ is an empirically determined anomaly threshold for spoofing detection. Since total delay varies under different traffic demands, we calculate a total delay reduction percentage based on the one with all CVs rather than an absolute value.

16.6 Defense Effectiveness Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate our detector against the two congestion attacks [463] in an offline setting, where it is performed as a post-processing step on the saved traffic snapshots.

16.6.1 Evaluation Methodology

Real-world intersection configuration. In our evaluation, we use PTV Vissim to generate the traffic snapshots for the I-SIG system and execute the produced signal plans. To faithfully reproduce the simulation setup, we obtained the detailed Vissim configurations they used when evaluating the attack. Specifically, we simulate a real-world intersection as shown in Fig. 16.1. In addition, we also use the same traffic demand (i.e., vehicle arrival rate) and turning ratio (i.e., vehicle lane changing probability) in each lane that the authors collected from real-world intersection [463].

Infrastructure-side sensor detection assumption. In this section, we assume perfect camera detections, i.e., the vehicle positions and speeds can be accurately detected in the sensor range. We will relax this assumption later in §16.7 to evaluate the robustness against sensor noises. We set the sensor range to 91 meters (300 ft) in the evaluation since this is a common specification for traffic cameras [466, 494] and prior works also report similar capabilities [491, 492].

Evaluation metrics. To quantify the detection performance, we show the *True Positive Rates (TPRs)* and *False Positive Rates (FPRs)* under the attacked and benign CV snapshots, respectively. To generate such CV snapshots, we simulate each Vissim seed twice—with and without attack. Each simulation lasts for 4000 seconds, which consists of about 70–140 snapshots depending on the congestion level. In the attacked simulations, the attacker may choose not to spoof a snapshot if she cannot find any spoofing location to increase the total delay. We also plot the *Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves* to systematically show the TPR and FPR under different anomaly thresholds ϵ (§16.5.3). To validate the effectiveness of trust assignment, we report the *Top- K rate* to show the percentage of CV snapshots that rank the spoofing CV among the top- K most suspicious CVs.

16.6.2 Results

Accuracy of trust assignment. Table 16.1 shows the Top- K rates in the attacked snapshots. As shown, the TA step is quite effective at finding the attack CVs, where it *always ranks the attack*

Table 16.1: Suspicious score rankings of the attack CVs in Trust Assignment. The numbers in the parentheses are the CV snapshots that we rank the attack CV in Top- K and the total number of CV snapshots in the simulation, respectively.

PR	Attack	Top-1 Rate	Top 3 Rate	Top-5 Rate
100%	Arrival time attack	91.2% (93/102)	99.0% (101/102)	100.0% (102/102)
75%	Queue	89.3% (200/224)	99.1% (222/224)	100.0% (224/224)
50%	length	90.7% (194/214)	99.5% (213/214)	100.0% (214/214)
25%	attack	92.8% (180/194)	99.5% (193/194)	100.0% (194/194)

CV among the top-5 most suspicious CVs across all PR settings. Therefore, we set $K = 5$ in the following RnR step (thus denoted as RnR-5) as this empirically ensures that the attack CV, if any, is among the ones that will be validated. Moreover, over 89% of the total CV snapshots rank the attack CVs at Top-1. The reason that some attacked CVs are not ranked at the top is mainly that in these snapshots some benign CVs exhibit driving behaviors that are not considered in the car-following model (e.g., lane changing) such that the TA mistakenly assigns high suspicious scores to these benign CVs. This indicates that a simpler detector that purely relies on TA is unlikely to be effective. Yet, the TA is a crucial part of the detection process as it helps narrow down the detection scope for RnR to accurately pinpoint the attack CVs.

Effectiveness of the complete detector pipeline. We now evaluate the performance of our complete detection pipeline (TA and RnR). Since the benign CV snapshots are also involved in the evaluation, we need to select the anomaly threshold in RnR (§16.5.3) such that it would not incur many false positives while still maintaining a good detection accuracy. Table 16.2 shows the best TPRs that can be achieved under different FPR levels by varying the anomaly threshold. Our detector can achieve a *perfect detection with 100% TPR and 0% FPR* when the CVs are fully deployed (i.e., PR = 100%). Also, when the FPR is 7%, the detector can achieve at least 95% TPRs in all PR settings. Benefitting from the RnR-5, the complete detector pipeline further improves the detection accuracy on top of TA.

Nevertheless, the detection performance in the lower PR settings is generally worse, where the TPR drops to 85.6% when FPR is 5%. This is mostly caused by the congestion effects in the attacked snapshots, where a benign CV stops in the middle of an empty lane waiting to cut into a queue in the adjacent lane. This makes the I-SIG queue estimation mistakenly considers many RVs in the empty lane and thus allocates an unnecessary long green time for it. In such cases, removing this benign CV from the snapshot will actually reduce the total delay. In practice, such cases might not be much of a concern since one can use attack detection from multiple snapshots to reduce the false positives.

Detection effectiveness under different anomaly thresholds. To systematically evaluate the detection performance, we plot the detection ROC curves by varying the anomaly thresholds. To highlight the importance of RnR-5, we also plot the ROC curves of a simpler detector design *without* RnR-5. We use a threshold-based anomaly detection design to classify CVs as attackers if their suspicious scores are above the threshold. Fig. 16.5 shows the ROC curves of the detector with and without the RnR-5. As shown, incorporating the RnR-5 greatly improves the detection performance in all PR settings. Moreover, the ROC curves indicate that our detector can generally well-distinguish the attack and benign CVs.

Table 16.2: Attack detection effectiveness (TA + RnR-5).

PR	Attack	Detection effectiveness				
		TPR (FPR=7%)	TPR (FPR=5%)	TPR (FPR=3%)	TPR (FPR=1%)	TPR (FPR=0%)
100%	Arrival time attack	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
75%	Queue	100%	99.1%	96.0%	70.1%	61.6%
50%	length	99.5%	99.1%	98.1%	78.5%	0.5%
25%	attack	95.4%	85.6%	82.0%	69.6%	0%

16.7 Robustness to Sensor Noises

Experimental setup. In our TA design (§16.5.2), sensor detection noises in the position and velocity will directly affect the suspicious score calculation. Lu et al. [491] quantifies that the average position errors are only 0.8m and 1.7m within 50m and 120m distances from the camera, respectively. And the position errors are mostly longitudinal, i.e., in the direction of the lane. For the velocity error, they find that the estimated speed has an average error of 1.47 m/s to the actual speed. We model the camera detection noises based on their findings. More concretely, we inject random errors sampled from Gaussian distributions $e_{\text{pos}} \sim N(0, \sigma_{\text{pos}}^2)$ and $e_{\text{vel}} \sim N(0, \sigma_{\text{vel}}^2)$ to the detected position and velocity for all vehicles (CVs and RVs) in the sensor range. We select $\sigma_{\text{pos}} = 1.7$ m and $\sigma_{\text{vel}} = 1.47$ m/s in the evaluation. In addition, we also evaluate larger noise levels by scaling the error amounts to $2 \times \{\sigma_{\text{pos}}, \sigma_{\text{vel}}\}$ and $3 \times \{\sigma_{\text{pos}}, \sigma_{\text{vel}}\}$, respectively.

Results. Fig. 16.6 shows the ROC curves with/without camera detection noises. As shown, the detection performance is barely affected when PR is 100% or 75%, and is only slightly worse in the lower PR settings. This is mainly because the camera detection errors are relatively much smaller than the distance between the spoofed CV location and the location estimated from the traffic invariant. For example, even with $3 \times$ position errors, the error standard deviation merely equals to a common vehicle length (4–5m). In comparison, to induce a large total delay increment, the spoofed CV location is usually >18 m away from the estimated location.

16.8 Online Detection Exploration

Timing overhead. Our detector is assumed to run on the Road-Side Unit that hosts the CV applications. To ensure that we do not assume any unreasonable computation capability, we measure the timing overhead on a Raspberry Pi. The TA and RnR-5 steps take at maximum 9.05 sec and 6.13 sec, respectively. Therefore, we estimate the maximum required duration of the detection process as 15.58 sec.

Detection timeliness requirements. The I-SIG system runs at the end of each signal stage (§16.2.1) to plan for the next signal timing plan. Thus, the online attack detection needs to be finished within one stage in order to keep up with the pace of I-SIG. Specifically, we assume a minimum green light as 7 sec [495] for each phase. Each phase will also go through a yellow light (typically 3 sec) and red clearance period (to account for red light runners, typically 1 sec). Hence, one signal stage (i.e., two sequential phases) will take at least 22 sec. Excluding the computation delay, it leaves 6 sec for the future time window. Therefore, we set the future time window as 6 sec in the online detection evaluation.

Figure 16.5: Attack detection ROC curves of our detector with and without the RnR-5.

16.8.1 Online Detection Effectiveness

Fig. 16.7 shows the comparison of the offline and online detection ROC curves. Since the future time window only affects the RV state inference (§16.5.2), online detection has no impact in the full deployment period ($PR = 100\%$) and has little impact when PR is 75% where the number of RVs are limited. Interestingly, limiting the future time window has a larger impact on $PR = 50\%$ compared to $PR = 25\%$. This is because when $PR = 25\%$, although the number of RVs increases, the number of CVs decreases correspondingly. Therefore, the detector is less affected due to the smaller number of CVs that need to be validated. Nevertheless, even when $PR = 50\%$, the FPR only increases by 5% if we aim to keep the same TPR at 98.1% . Such a good online detection performance is likely because a future time window of 6 sec can already cover many RVs to enter the sensor range.

Figure 16.6: Attack detection ROC curves (zoom-in view) under different levels of camera detection noises ($\sigma = \{\sigma_{\text{pos}}, \sigma_{\text{vel}}\}$).

Figure 16.7: Attack detection ROC curves (zoom-in view) of the offline and online detection setups.

16.9 Conclusion

In this work, we explore a general defense solution against data spoofing attacks on infrastructure-side CV applications. Building upon the general principle that using physical-layer information to cross validate cyber-layer information, we leverage the readily-available infrastructure-side sensors, such as traffic cameras, to estimate the physical-layer CV states. However, such infrastructure-side sensors suffer from a fundamental limitation that the sensor range is generally much smaller than the CV communication range. To address this, we take traffic models as traffic invariants to infer the vehicle states that are out of sensor range. We implement and evaluate our detector against two representative data spoofing attacks that aim to cause congestion in the intersections by exploiting the CV-based traffic signal control. Our results show that the detector can effectively identify the spoofer with high detection accuracy and is robust to sensor noises. We also demonstrate that an online detection setting only slightly degrades the detection performance.

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Chapter 17

Risk Analysis for Vehicle-Pedestrian Interaction with Extended Sensing

In this chapter, we introduce the concept of Extended Sensing (ES) and provide a comparison tool that evaluates the risk for vehicle-pedestrian interaction (VPI) scenarios by performing statistical analysis of the number of hazardous situations encountered when there is occlusion (without communication) versus using a sensing technology that informs the vehicle of the presence of a potentially occluded pedestrian.

The Extended Sensor can be a camera on a pole or a pedestrian self sending a warning signal. We propose a collision-avoidance planner for the vehicle based on a finite state machine (FSM). The risk analysis is performed using the Backtracking Process Algorithm (BPA), which has been used in previous works, as a way to provide sufficient coverage of the Operational Design Domain (ODD). Qualitative and quantitative simulation results show the benefits of having ES (in this case, an external pedestrian alert system) to decrease the possibility of collision. The proposed method also proves to be useful to evaluate the risk for VPI scenarios in general.

This activity was originally reported in [17].

17.1 Introduction

Based on collision data from the Traffic Safety Facts Annual Report released by the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA), more than 40% of the crashes resulting in pedestrian injuries between 2017 and 2019 happened at intersections [496], making them a fundamental scenario for safety analysis. There are several factors and scenarios that make intersections particularly important for safety analysis, as exemplified in Fig. 17.1. Here, we see that in an intersection the ego vehicle may need to turn left, go straight and turn right. It turns out that in every occasion, the crossing pedestrian is being occluded by dynamic or static environmental factors. These environmental factors can include trees or buildings too close to the intersection, or large moving vehicles like trucks.

One may intuitively consider that challenges concerning occlusions can be solved by having perfect AV sensing and perception. However, as shown in [497], there are some scenarios where an AV cannot guarantee safety without the help of an external communication system (vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V), infrastructure-to-vehicle (I2V), vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I).) These scenarios include non-signalized intersections and T-junctions, where the vehicle has little to no knowledge about the other actors in the environment. This situation is even more severe when there are large buildings next to the corners or big trees that hinder visibility. Actually, view obstructions

Figure 17.1: In three different configurations, the ego vehicle cannot detect the occluded crossing pedestrian via its own sensors because of different static or dynamic obstacles.

constitute around 11% of all the crash cases, according to a 2018 NHTSA report [498].

Some companies have developed external alarm/perception systems to deal with the occlusion issues. For example, in order to reduce the risk of overtaking in a two-lane road when following a truck, Samsung developed an external detection system by attaching a camera to the front of a truck that is connected to a video wall (four exterior monitors) located on the back of the truck [499]. The monitors at the rear give drivers behind the truck a view of the current road condition ahead of the truck. Similarly, the Austin Transportation Department has implemented a pilot system to alert vehicles when there is a pedestrian near the crossing by using wireless networks or connected vehicle infrastructure [500].

Inspired by this latest technology, for this work we have focused on studying the functionality and effect of an external pedestrian alert system that we will call Extended Sensor for the rest of this document. The purpose of this system is to inform a vehicle about the presence of possibly occluded pedestrians near a crossing. Theoretically, the availability of this extra information will be helpful for the vehicle's decision making module, thus reducing the number of risky situations. The contribution of this work is twofold:

1. A general framework for risk analysis for scenarios containing VPI.
2. A tutorial case study for the general use of this framework. This case study contains three stages: system design, probabilistic cell-to-cell mapping, and risk validation for an ego-vehicle turning right in an occluded intersection. The risk analysis is performed as a comparison for the same scenario with and without the Extended Sensor for informing drivers of occluded pedestrians.

The rest of the chapter is structured as follows: We briefly review related work in Section 17.2. Section 17.3 introduces the proposed framework for risk analysis. Section 17.4 shows the case study where the vehicle needs to turn right and encounters an occluded crossing pedestrian. The pedestrian model, vehicle motion, the proposed collision avoidance planner for the specific case as well as the detection system are discussed in this section. Section 17.5 describes the simulation experiments and shows the qualitative and quantitative analysis. Section 17.5.3 presents the BPA results. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 17.6.

Figure 17.2: Framework for the proposed model-based risk analysis.

17.2 Related Work

Alert systems for both drivers and pedestrians have been studied and developed from different perspectives. Rahimian et al. [501] developed a cell phone app based on Vehicle-to-Pedestrian (V2P) communication to inform pedestrians by text messages about traffic conditions and about when it is safe for the pedestrian to cross. Their experiment was conducted in an immersive virtual environment. In [502], Kankaria et al. developed an improved object detection system based on deep learning to help prevent accidents and ensure the safety of vehicle drivers. Their proposed methodology could detect important traffic signs and traffic lights. The detection of pedestrians was also achieved with the desired accuracy. Koc et al. [503] also proposed a method to deal with possibly occluded jaywalking pedestrians, but focused on developing the vehicle’s controller for straight segments of the road.

The Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP) method is another popular method that researchers have used to solve AV driving through occluded intersections. Bouton et al. [504] proposed a POMDP planner that computed a common belief for all invisible road users. They combined the common belief and the optimal belief for each visible road user to compute the minimum belief action utility. Their approach also included a utility fusion to approximate the global problem of collision avoidance. In [505], Lin et al. used POMDP to predict the behavior of other road users and model the traffic situation. They set virtual vehicles at the boundary of occluded areas and considered them in the belief tree search process. Sequential decisions were obtained from the belief tree search.

To determine the safety assurance for automated driving vehicles, Rodionova et al. [506] proposed a method to explore the performance limits of automated vehicle safety models in a set of NHTSA scenarios, including intersections, using robustness as a metric of safety. Hejase et al. [507] implemented a backtracking process algorithm (BPA) to identify the significant risk scenarios for a case study in unmanned aerial systems (UAS). They partitioned the UAS state space into intervals and computed the probability of the system state transition as well as the system configuration transition. BPA allows one to identify the sequence of events that leads to scenarios that result in a top-level hazard. In this work, we use a similar approach to identify the undesired scenario with the highest probability.

Event). BPA starts from these states and traces the sequence backwards through $k\Delta t$ time-steps. In the end, a transition tree with probabilities showing the sequence with the highest possibility leading to the Top Event is obtained.

When the BPA process is complete, we can identify one or more key reasons that lead to the Top Event. The acquired information is used to correct parts of the system that lead to the top-level hazard (i.e. provide the safety argument.)

17.4 A Case Study

In this section we provide details about the simulation implementation (Fig. 17.3). We start by selecting the appropriate motion models for the pedestrian and the vehicle considering their interaction (VPI). Then, a finite-state machine (FSM)-based collision-avoidance planner is proposed to handle the braking maneuver to avoid potential collisions. Next, we validate the simulator characterization and the functionality of the Extended Sensor by conducting qualitative and quantitative risk analysis.

Algorithm 10 Backtracking Process Algorithm [508]

Require: # continuous states L and system configuration states M

Require: Non-overlapping intervals of continuous states $J = J_1 \cdots J_l \cdots J_L (l = 1, \dots, L)$

Require: System top event of interest at last simulation step

Require: Backtracking search depth k

Require: Probability $P_j^k = 1$ at time $t = k\Delta t$

Require: State-to-state transition probability g

Require: State System configuration transition probability h

```

1: while  $k > 1$  do
2:   Get cell to cell transition probability  $q$ :  $q = h \times g$ 
3:   Update probability  $P_i^{k-1} = P_j^k q$ 
4:   if  $P_i^{k-1} > \epsilon$  then
5:      $P_i^{k-1}(\epsilon) = P_i^{k-1}$ 
6:   else
7:     Prune out
8:   end if
9:    $P_j^k = P_i^{k-1}(\epsilon)$ 
10:   $k \rightarrow k - 1$ 
11: end while
12: return System paths with probability greater than  $\epsilon$ 
    
```

17.4.1 Pedestrian and Vehicle Motion Models

For the **pedestrian**, the social force model is applied [510]. It uses point-mass Newtonian dynamics for both the longitudinal and lateral directions

$$\ddot{X}_p = \frac{1}{m_p} f_{total}, \quad (17.1)$$

where $X_p \in \mathbb{R}^4$, $X_p := [s_{px}, s_{py}, v_x, v_y]^\top$ is the pedestrian state vector containing the position and velocity along the x and y axis, respectively, m_p is the pedestrian mass and f_{total} is the total applied force. We consider that the pedestrian is mainly influenced by the attractive force created by its

Figure 17.4: State transition of the collision-avoidance planner.

destination. Hence, let $f_{total} := f_{des} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, where the destination force is $f_{des} = k_{des}(v_p - v_d)$. Here, k_{des} is a parameter that scales the difference between v_p and v_d . The current pedestrian velocity vector is $v_p \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $v_d \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the desired velocity vector, defined by

$$v_d := v_0 \frac{s_{des} - s_p}{|s_{des} - s_p|^2 + \sigma_{des}^2} \quad (17.2)$$

where $s_{des} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the destination coordinates vector, $s_p \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the pedestrian current position, and σ_{des} is a scalar that adjusts v_d depending on the pedestrian's distance to the destination. The speed v_0 is a constant parameter that represents the most comfortable walking velocity for humans.

For the motion of the **ego vehicle** we use the kinematic bicycle model [178]. The vehicle state vector $X_{veh} = [x_{veh}, y_{veh}, \psi, v_{veh}]^T$ represents vehicle longitudinal position, lateral position, heading angle and velocity, respectively. The control input consists of acceleration a and steering angle δ_f . Other parameters include l_f , the distance from the front wheels to the center of gravity, and l_r , the distance from the rear wheels to the center of gravity.

For the longitudinal control, when there is no detection of obstacles the vehicle should keep its target speed, attained by a proportional control $a = K_p(v_{veh,0} - v_{veh})$ where K_p is the proportional gain and $v_{veh,0}$ is the desired vehicle speed. The deceleration action is a uniform deceleration motion. A constant deceleration $a_{veh,dec}$ is applied when the vehicle needs to brake.

Additionally, we use pure pursuit control to generate the steering angle δ_f for lateral control. The reference path is divided by multiple target points. At each time step, the lateral distance between the target point and the vehicle's center is l_d . The look forward gain is K , L_{fc} is the look-ahead distance and $L := l_r + l_f$ is the vehicle wheelbase. Then, considering $L_f = K v_{veh} + L_{fc}$, the steering angle is $\delta_f = \arctan((2L l_d / L_f) / L_f)$.

17.4.2 The Collision Avoidance Planner

We generate a collision-avoidance planner based on an FSM (Fig. 17.4). Here, we include the functionality of the proposed Extended Sensor to detect pedestrians. Initially, the vehicle follows a pre-planned reference path and decelerates to a predefined turning velocity when it is approaching the corner. Suppose the vehicle sensor's field of view can detect a crossing pedestrian and the vehicle has not passed the pedestrian. In that case, the vehicle implements a braking maneuver and yields to the pedestrian. Also, if the Extended Sensor detects the pedestrian and the connection between this device and the vehicle is good, the sensor will alert the driver or vehicle to brake. Otherwise, if the connection is lost, the vehicle driver or AV will not receive the warning and the vehicle will only brake when its internal sensors detect the pedestrian. After the pedestrian arrives

at the target location on the opposite sidewalk, the vehicle accelerates to reach its original turning speed and finishes the turning process.

17.4.3 The Detection System

It is assumed that the vehicle has a radar with a detection range of $R_{veh,det}$ and a detection angle of $\alpha_{veh,det}$. We use a lidar sensor model that incorporates a probabilistic rain model [511] whose detection range varies as follows:

$$R_{veh,det} = R_{veh,FOV} e^{\frac{-\rho_{rain}}{\rho_{rain,max}}} \quad (17.3)$$

where $R_{veh,det}$, $R_{veh,FOV}$ are the actual detection range and ideal detection range, respectively. The rainfall intensity is ρ_{rain} .

Furthermore, an **Extended Sensor System (ES)** is implemented to provide the vehicle with more information about the current environmental situation, which is useful in the case of occlusions. The system, placed in the corner of the intersection, sends alerts to turning vehicles via a wireless connection when it detects pedestrians crossing the street.

The ES combines the sensor module and the connection module. Ideally, if the ES detects a crossing pedestrian and the vehicle is within communications range, it should alert the vehicle. However, the stability of the connection might not be perfect, so we use a state transition matrix, Eq. (17.4), that represents the probability of maintaining or losing the connection to the ES given that at the previous timestep the connection existed (c) or there was no connection (nc).

$$\text{Connection state: } \begin{bmatrix} p(c|c, \Delta t) & p(nc|c, \Delta t) \\ p(c|nc, \Delta t) & p(nc|nc, \Delta t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9 & 0.1 \\ 0.9 & 0.1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17.4)$$

17.5 Simulation Experiments

A two-lane intersection was created for simulation experiments, with a single-lane width of $3.2m$. For each episode, the experimental turning velocity of the vehicle was set to be in the range of $0^+m/s$ to $16m/s$. The pedestrian was located one meter away from the right edge of the road, and its position along with the road was defined as $x_{ped,init}$. The destination was set at $4.2m$ from the left to the other edge of the road. When the simulation time reaches $t_{ped,cross}$, the pedestrian starts crossing the road at a constant speed v_{ped} . If the vehicle detects the crossing pedestrian via its own sensor or is alerted by the Extended Sensor System, it implements a braking maneuver and yields to the pedestrian. The environmental variables d_{obs} and ρ_{rain} represent the distance from the building block to the corner and the rainfall intensity, respectively. We consider a detection range $R_{veh,det} = 30m$ and a detection angle of $\alpha_{veh,det} = 90^\circ$. The detailed values of the variables used for the qualitative and quantitative simulation are shown in Table 17.1.

17.5.1 Qualitative Analysis

Initially, we set a predefined control experiment to test if the ES helps the vehicle avoid a potential collision with a crossing pedestrian. As is shown in Table 17.1, in the simulation the vehicle's desired turning velocity was $12m/s$ and the deceleration rate of the braking maneuver was $3m/s^2$. The vehicle detection range, detection angle, and the communication range of the Extended Sensor were $30m$, 90° , and $30m$, respectively. The rest of the variables remained unchanged.

Screenshots of two episodes are shown in Fig. 17.5, where we observe that the vehicle that had a connection to the ES detected the pedestrian earlier and thus had enough time to fully decelerate

Table 17.1: Variables for Qualitative and Quantitative simulation

Symbol	Qualitative	Quantitative		Units
	Value	Range/Value	Step size	
$v_{veh,turn}$	12.0	0.0 ⁺ - 16.0	0.5	m/s
$a_{veh,dec}$	3.0	1.5 - 6.0	1.5	m/s^2
R_{com}	30.0	30.0 - 50.0	10.0	m
$x_{ped,init}$	17.0	12.0 - 19.5	2.5	m
$t_{ped,cross}$	5.0	3.0 - 19.0	2.5	s
v_{ped}	0.5	0.5 - 1.5	0.5	m/s
d_{obs}	3.0	5.0 - 9.0	2.0	m
ρ_{rain}	0.0	0.0 - 100.0	50.0	mm/h

and yield to the pedestrian. On the other hand, without help from the ES, the vehicle could not fully stop in time and collided with the virtual pedestrian.

17.5.2 Quantitative Analysis

The objective of the quantitative simulation is to determine the difference between the scenario with and without the ES. The variables for these experiments are shown in Table 17.1, where instead of choosing fixed parameters we chose a range and a step size for each variable. We observe from the histogram in Fig. 17.6 that the car could entirely stop and avoid the collision with the pedestrian on its own if the turning velocity were under $4m/s$. However, when the velocity was beyond $4m/s$, the number of collisions in the scenarios with the ES was much less than in cases without the ES. We found that the variation of other parameters apart from speed did not greatly affect the obtained results.

Also, with the increase in the velocity range, the difference between the number of collisions for both cases grew. From Table 17.2 we can see that the collision rate with assistance from the ES consistently decreased as the speed of the vehicle was incremented. Interestingly enough, we found that even with the alert in place, the vehicle could not avoid all collisions, presumably because the braking maneuver is a constant deceleration.

Table 17.2: Collision Rates in Quantitative Simulations (46656 episodes)

Velocity range (m/s)	0-2	2-4	4-6	6-8	8-10	10-12	12-14	14-16
Collision % w/o ES	0.00	0.00	3.92	19.47	41.38	58.51	69.53	70.32
Collision % w/ ES	0.00	0.00	1.79	8.73	14.11	21.93	26.68	31.39
% col decrease w/ ES	0.00	0.00	2.13	10.74	27.27	36.58	42.85	38.93

Figure 17.5: Screenshots of the simulation without (above) and with (below) the ES. In the graphs of the first row, the ego vehicle (yellow box) approached the corner but did not detect the crossing pedestrian (red dot) until 8.7s. The vehicle failed to fully decelerate and collided with the pedestrian at 10.7s. The graphs in the second row show the scenario with the ES, The black star represented the position of the ES and the green circle was the visualization of the communication range. With the help of the ES, the vehicle noticed the pedestrian at 7.9s and successfully kept a safe distance from the crossing pedestrian and avoided a possible collision.

Figure 17.6: Simulation results for different ranges of desired vehicle turning speeds.

Figure 17.7: Sample BPA branch result for case study set up in Sec. 17.3.2. The top level hazard is shown at the bottom of the plot and the backtracking algorithm runs for three timesteps back in time. System state transitions with probability smaller than $\varepsilon = 0.00001$ have been pruned out.

17.5.3 Risk validation setup

The theoretical basis of the backtracking process follows [508]. First, we need to discretize and partition the continuous state-space of the VPI process into sets of magnitude intervals (cell). The system has 12 states in total which includes vehicle desired turning velocity $x_1 \in \{0^+, \dots, 16\}$, vehicle deceleration rate $x_2 \in \{1.5, \dots, 6.0\}$, vehicle detection angle $x_3 = 90^\circ$, vehicle detection range $x_4 = 30m$, pedestrian crossing velocity $x_5 \in \{0.5, \dots, 1.5\}$, pedestrian initial position along the street $x_6 \in \{12, \dots, 20\}$, pedestrian crossing time $x_7 \in \{3, \dots, 19\}$, the distance from the building block to the corner $x_8 \in \{5, \dots, 10\}$, rain intensity $x_9 \in \{0, \dots, 100\}$, communication range between the Extended Sensor and the vehicle $x_{10} = 50m$, the collision states $x_{11} \in \{Yes, No\}$, and the ES connection state $x_{12} \in \{Normal, Failure\}$. The system configuration state, also regarded as the ES connection state x_{12} , follows the probability transition matrix specified by the user as shown in Eq. 17.4.

Based on the simulation results from the previous section, vehicle turning velocity is the main attribute of interest. To avoid the curse of dimensionality, we consider three states for this analysis: the vehicle desired turning velocity x_1 , collision state x_{11} , and the ES connection state x_{12} . The combination of these states are represented as a cell $c_i := (a, b, c), i \in \{1, \dots, 32\}$, where the vehicle velocity is $a \in \{1, \dots, 8\}$, system collision state is $b \in \{1, 2\}$ and the ES connection state is $c \in \{1, 2\}$. Then, the transition probabilities among the 16 system states $c_{sys,i} := (a, b), i \in \{1, \dots, 16\}, a \in \{1, \dots, 8\}, b \in \{1, 2\}$ are calculated using a cell-to-cell mapping technique [508] where we use forward propagation from sample points within each cell to find the probability distribution of the whole system. The probability distribution of the entire 32 system states can be achieved by the process mentioned in Algorithm 10.

The top event for this analysis is collision with the pedestrian, i.e. $d(X_{ped}, X_{veh}) < \xi$, where X_{ped} is the vector position of the pedestrian, X_{veh} is the vector position of the vehicle, and ξ is a user-defined distance threshold. We find out which cells contain the selected Top Event and then we determine sequential paths “back in time” with a user-specified search depth, $k = 3$, along with their associated probabilities. To avoid a numerical explosion of paths, a user-specified truncation probability $\varepsilon = 0.00001$ is used.

17.5.4 Discussion

Fig. 17.7 shows that the branch $11 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 11 \rightarrow 9$, has the highest probability among seven top events in a total of 26880 simulation episodes, and represents that the system has gone from configuration in cell c_{11} to configuration in cell c_9 . In cell $c_{11} := (3, 2, 1)$ the vehicle had a velocity between 4 and 6 m/s , the ES connection existed, and no collision happened. One time step later, the vehicle velocity was still in the range of 4 to 6 m/s , and the ES kept working. Another time step later, the system state remained $c_{11} := (3, 2, 1)$. However, in the final time step, $c_9 := (3, 1, 1)$ represents the vehicle had collided with the pedestrian but the velocity range remained the same and the ES connection still existed.

From Table 17.2, we know that if the turning velocity is in the range of 4 to 6 m/s , the possibility of a collision between the vehicle and the crossing pedestrian is comparatively low. The collision speed obtained from the BPA results indicated that the vehicle's initial turning velocity was higher than 6 m/s . In other words, the vehicle performed a braking maneuver based on the developed FSM for the vehicle control but could not entirely stop and avoid the collision. We conclude that if the vehicle's turning velocity is relatively high, then the possibility of potential collision between the car and the pedestrian will increase regardless of whether or not the ES alerted the driver or autonomous vehicle.

17.6 Conclusions

This work introduced a general framework for risk analysis and used the concept of an Extended Sensor as a tool to reduce the risk associated with certain ODD configurations. The occluded VPI scenario that was specifically considered for the use case of this framework provided enough complexity and information to test our risk validation tool. By creating a hybrid state system to represent the scenario actors' states and a finite state machine to describe the scenario transitions, we obtain a fully interpretable model of the scenario that was validated by means of the qualitative and quantitative simulations. Then, we showed that our proposed framework for risk analysis provides a criterion to decide on the utility of the Extended Sensor by depicting the risk-significant sequence of events that result in undesirable collisions. We found that the ES played a crucial role in alerting the vehicle about the pedestrian's presence, especially when such pedestrian was occluded and invisible to the vehicle's internal sensors. The braking capability of the vehicle remained the same, but the preventive action to avoid a collision was taken much earlier in those cases, resulting in fewer collisions. For future work, we propose to improve the collision avoidance planner by adding more complex braking maneuvers and will select different combinations of scenarios with occlusions and other environmental factors (like rain) to analyze risk.

Chapter 18

Vision-Based Two-Factor Authentication & Localization Scheme for Autonomous Vehicles

In autonomous vehicle systems – whether ground or aerial – vehicles and infrastructure-level units communicate among each other continually to ensure safe and efficient autonomous operations. However, different attack scenarios might arise in such environments when a device in the network cannot physically pinpoint the actual transmitter of a certain message. For example, a compromised or a malicious vehicle could send a message with a fabricated location to appear as if it is in the location of another legitimate vehicle, or fabricate multiple messages with fake identities to alter the behavior of other vehicles/infrastructure units and cause traffic congestion or accidents.

In this chapter, we propose a Vision-Based Two-Factor Authentication and Localization Scheme for Autonomous Vehicles. The scheme leverages the vehicles' light sources and cameras to establish an “Optical Camera Communication (OCC)” channel providing an auxiliary channel between vehicles to visually authenticate and localize the transmitter of messages that are sent over Radio Frequency (RF) channels. Additionally, we identify possible attacks against the proposed scheme as well as mitigation strategies.

This activity was originally reported in [18].

18.1 Introduction

Autonomous vehicles such as self-operated drones and cars will soon enable new applications in different domains, such as autonomous transportation and drone delivery. However, safety-critical operations, such as object-detection and avoidance, are integral components of these applications and it would make them appealing targets for cybercriminals [188]. In the United States, various efforts from government agencies have been directed to set up the rules, regulations, and policies for managing the secure operations of future autonomous systems (i.e., vehicles and Roadside Units, or RSUs). For connected and self-driving cars, the U.S. Department of Transportation (USDOT) has adopted the Security Credential Management System (SCMS) [512] for handling secure vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communications. For Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) have jointly developed the Remote ID framework [513] which would set the foundation for the anticipated Unmanned Aircraft System (UAS) Traffic Management System (UTM) [514]. Unfortunately, these systems still lack effective security measures to defend

Figure 18.1: Scheme Overview: a vehicle sends an RF message and a visual nonce as optical Pulse-Width Modulated (PWM) symbols using its headlights

against existing attacks [515] [516].

In the academic community, several attacks have been demonstrated against autonomous systems such as GPS spoofing attacks [517], V2I attacks [518], and Sybil (vehicle ID duplication) attacks [519]. These attacks have different threat models and attack methodologies, and find different mitigation approaches. However, we contend that all these attacks stem from the same root: *the decoupling between the sender of a message and its transmitting location*. In other words, if receiver of a message cannot locate its transmitter, multiple threats are exposed.

In this work, we propose a Vision-Based Two-Factor Authentication & Localization Scheme for Autonomous Vehicles to pinpoint and authenticate the location of a message transmitter. In this scheme, we leverage the lighting source of the vehicle to create an Optical Camera Communication (OCC) channel to send a random *nonce* – a randomly generated number that to be used only once – encoded as flashing blinks from the light source, while at the same time the sending vehicle includes the same nonce into the message to be sent over the Radio Frequency (RF) channel (figure 18.1). In this scheme, the receiver is equipped with an RF interface and a camera, so that it can receive the message via the RF channel while simultaneously use its camera to record the sender’s blinks and decode the visually modulated nonce using computer-vision algorithms. The receiver then matches the nonces received on the two channels (RF and OCC). If the nonces match, then the vehicle is visually authenticated and localized and is indeed identified as the transmitter of the message. Note that our scheme can be used to authenticate each RF message as well as it can be used as a bootstrap to authenticate a vehicle’s location once then establish a secure channel with the localized vehicle.

We summarize our contributions as follows:

- We propose a vision-based authentication scheme that pinpoints (authenticates and localizes) the actual transmitter of a message sent over the RF channel by utilizing cameras and light sources to create an OCC channel.
- We identify a possible attack (named a Copycat Attack) with different variants against the

(a) C cannot tell if the message came from A or B
 (b) RSU cannot tell who actually sent the four messages
 (c) Control tower cannot tell which one is the legitimate UAV

Figure 18.2: Aerial view of three different attack scenarios

proposed scheme, where a malicious party mimics another legitimate transmitter’s visual blinks to spoof its identity or location.

- We present mitigation approaches that circumvent all variants of the copycat attack.

In the next section, we present our threat model with three different attack scenarios. In section 18.3, we give a brief background about wireless communications that utilize optical techniques. In section 18.4, we provide an overview of our proposed scheme. In section 18.5, we evaluate the attack scenarios discussed in section 18.2 against our scheme presented in section 18.4. Section 18.6 demonstrates a new adaptive attack (named Copycat Attack) under multiple scenarios as well as mitigation approaches for each scenario. Related work is discussed in section 18.7 and section 18.8 concludes the chapter.

18.2 Threat Model

In our threat model (figure 18.2), a malicious party exploits the decoupling of a sent message from the location of its transmitter. Therefore, our main objective in this threat model is to identify and authenticate the physical location of a message’s transmitter, whether the transmitter is an attacker or a legitimate vehicle. To illustrate further, three different attack scenarios are demonstrated as examples:

Location Spoofing: In this scenario, a compromised or a malicious vehicle fabricates fake GPS coordinates about its current location to cause accidents, alter a system’s behavior, or earn unlawful privileges. For example in figure 18.2a, a platoon of vehicles (cars \mathcal{B} , \mathcal{C} , and \mathcal{D}) is already formed and a malicious adversarial vehicle \mathcal{A} sends an emergency-braking message to vehicle \mathcal{C} while pretending to be in the location of vehicle \mathcal{B} . Or if vehicle \mathcal{A} is capable of compromising the identity of vehicle \mathcal{B} , \mathcal{A} can pretend to be \mathcal{B} itself without the need of fabricating any coordinates. Vehicle \mathcal{C} would react to \mathcal{A} ’s fabricated message and apply its brakes to avoid crashing into \mathcal{B} but also it would cause

\mathcal{D} to crash into \mathcal{C} if there are no implemented precautions against this scenario. In this scenario, the malicious vehicle does not need to wait for an opening to physically drive up in front of the targeted vehicle. Instead, the attack can be launched from faraway.

Identity Duplication: Identity Duplication attack, also known as Sybil Attack, is an attack carried out when a single malicious vehicle sends out multiple messages with multiple identities to give an impression of a congested road and alter the behavior of the infrastructure and/or other vehicles. For example, in figure 18.2b, the additional fake vehicles (ghost cars \mathcal{B} , \mathcal{C} , and \mathcal{D}) generated by \mathcal{A} would cause the traffic light to turn green sooner in the attacker's lane and longer for other lanes in order to clear the congested lane.

Identity Confusion: In this scenario (figure 18.2c), a swarm of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are flying in close-proximity of each other. A legitimate UAV is supplementing its credentials to the control tower for accessing the nearby restricted airspace. During that time, another intruding UAV enters the restricted airspace. Here the control tower cannot enforce the given access (e.g., take down the intruding UAV) since it cannot physically differentiate between the legitimate and the intruding UAV.

We can observe that each scenario represents different attacking capabilities. In the first scenario, the attacker has the ability to either *fabricate the content of its messages or use the identity of another legitimate vehicle*. In the second scenario, the attacker has the ability to *generate multiple identities of non-existing vehicles*. In the third scenario, the attacker is able to *passively listen to messages* in order to make an opportunistic attack (e.g. invasive access towards a restricted airspace). However, all three scenarios can be exploited due to the same reason; *the inability of the receiver to localize the transmitter of the messages*.

18.3 Background on Optical Wireless Communication

18.3.1 Overview

Optical Wireless Communication (OWC) is any communication channel that utilizes the terahertz band of the electromagnetic spectrum which includes the infrared and ultraviolet frequencies. Furthermore, an OWC channel utilizing the visible-light portion of the terahertz band is referred to as Visible Light Communication (VLC).

Optical communications require an imaging sensor for receiving the incoming light photons. That sensor is commonly known as a photodetector. A camera sensor such as Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS) consists of a matrix of photodetectors, each represents a pixel which gets its color by measuring the intensity and frequency of the recorded photon by its corresponding photodetector. The main objective of a camera sensor is to create an image out of the CMOS output as a grid of colored pixels, and the rate of images created by the sensor is known as frame per second (FPS). However, since cameras have become a commodity hardware, their sensors have been repurposed for various applications such as decoding messages that are digitally modulated into images. This type of optical communication technique is commonly known as Optical Camera Communication (OCC).

18.3.2 OCC Channel Model

Our channel model is based on two assumptions: **(i)** The modulation scheme used over the OCC channel is assumed to be optical On-Off Keying (OOK) since it only requires a single narrowband frequency (i.e., single color) which makes it applicable to any light sources. Note that visual symbols in figure 18.1 and 18.3 are pulse-width modulated (PWM) for ease of illustration only. **(ii)** We

assumes the use of cameras that are operated using the global shutter mode where all camera pixels are scanned simultaneously. The rolling shutter mode (its counterpart) scans rows of pixel independently one after another. However, the security intuitions in this work still holds true for both assumptions and should be applicable to different imaging techniques.

In OCC systems, a communication channel using OOK modulation can be modeled as a rectangular waveform. Let T_e denote to the camera exposure time which defines how long a camera shutter stays open to capture a single frame. Therefore, T_e is the inverse of the camera sampling rate FPS such that $T_e = \frac{1}{FPS}$. Let PW_s denote the symbol pulse-width which defines how long a light source stays on during the T_e time frame. Intuitively, we have $PW_s < T_e$. However, there is a minimum duty cycle $DC_{min} = \frac{PW_s}{T_e}$ for a given OCC system under certain conditions and SINR requirements. Furthermore, a guard width PW_g must be left unoccupied at the beginning and the end of the T_e time frame to prevent symbols from leaking into adjacent frames (similar to the guard bands that are added between RF channels to prevent inter-symbol interference). Finally, in our scheme, the OCC can be modeled as $PW_s + PW_g < T_e$ for $PW_s \geq DC_{min} \times T_e$. Note that the propagation delay is omitted from the channel model since it has a negligible effect especially for close-range communications such as in V2V and V2I. Furthermore, the guard band PW_g should mitigate the effects of propagation delay whenever it becomes critically high.

18.3.3 Challenges

There are several challenges when working with OCC systems such as: **(i)** unidirectional link - a lighting source can only be used for transmitting while a camera is only for receiving, **(ii)** highly directional communications - the camera and the lighting source need to face each other in a clear line-of-sight (LOS), and **(iii)** low bitrate - common camera sensors can sample up to 30 FPS (stand-alone photodetectors are capable of higher sampling rates with more complex modulation schemes, but cannot construct an image out of the received photons).

The requirements of our scheme are not affected by these shortcomings. For instance, the receiver in our scheme does not require a feedback channel for locating the sender, and whenever a feedback is required (e.g. loss in clock synchronization) the RF channel can be used. Also based on the threat model discussed in Section 18.2, the sender is expected to be in a clear view of the receiver which means that clear LOS is an inherent requirement for all the three attack scenarios explained in Section 18.2. Concerning the bitrate, the sender encodes only a short nonce into the OCC channel whereas the main message is sent over the RF channel. Therefore, a low OCC bitrate is sufficient to execute the authentication scheme. Furthermore, lower bitrates can be modulated using longer symbol periods which inherently make it cover larger distances in the optical domain.

18.4 Scheme Overview

As discussed in section 18.1, our scheme utilizes two different communication channels, an RF channel and an OCC channel. Both the sender and the receiver are equipped with an RF interface to implement an RF channel while the OCC channel requires the sender to be equipped with lighting source such as a light-emitting diode (LED), and the receiver to be equipped with a camera. We assume that these equipment are already available in most autonomous vehicles since we expect modern autonomous systems to have the minimum set of requirements to carry out safe and secure autonomous operations, which include: an RF interface (for wireless communications), a camera (for object detection and navigation), and a lighting source (for safety, illumination, and identification purposes) such as car's headlights/taillights and drone's anti-collision strobe lights.

Authentication & Localization Process: When a sender transmits a message over the RF channel, it includes a nonce in the message, while at the same time it encodes the same nonce as modulated blinks into the OCC channel using its light source. On the other hand, the receiver will continuously scan every captured camera frame for possible OOK modulated symbols. Here the receiver employs computer-vision algorithms and look at every two consecutive frames for a sudden change in pixel intensity. When a pixel intensity change is found, the algorithm locks on the object emitting the light source that caused the intensity change and extract the symbols encoded into each subsequent frame. The area of the locked object is called Region of Interest (ROI). Now whenever the receiver receives a message over the RF channel, it cross-references its nonce with the demodulated nonces emitted by the current ROI over the OCC channel at the time of message reception. To illustrate, to transmit $bit_i = "1"$ as an OOK modulated symbol, the sender sets its light source on high for PW_s seconds during the camera exposure time frame T_{e_i} . To transmit the next $bit_{i+1} = "0"$, the sender sets its light source to off-state during the next transmission window $T_{e_{i+1}}$. The receiver would detect a transition period from T_{e_i} to $T_{e_{i+1}}$ time frames as a change in pixel intensity caused by bit_i and bit_{i+1} respectively. As a result, the receiver will lock on the ROI region of the captured picture that has a pixel intensity change. This process will be triggered from the very first transmitted bit_1 where a timer T_{OCC} will be set starting from the beginning of T_{e_1} . When the receiver receives a message from the RF channel that has the same nonce which is received from the OCC channel, the time difference between the two messages must satisfy the following condition: $|T_{OCC} - T_{RF}| < \theta$ where T_{RF} denote to the time where the first bit of the message was received over the RF channel and θ denote to a minimum threshold that can be used as an attack window. More details on the aforementioned attack will be discussed in Section 18.6.1.

Technical Considerations: To prevent accidental ROI locks that are caused by pixel intensity change due to random environmental factors (such as a vehicle turning on its headlights or an object moving in front of a light source which would be interpreted as an OOK modulated symbol), OCC systems would use a preamble with an alternating 0s and 1s to synchronize the sender with the receiver before locking on the ROI and recording the nonce. Another point to consider is that during an OCC transmission, the nonce encoded by the sender might include long runs of 0s or 1s (continuous repetitions of 0s or 1s) which would cause multiple consecutive frames to not have any intensity change across their transitions which in turn cause a loss in clock synchronization on receiver side (cannot distinguish whether the transmission has ended or a long run is being transmitted). Therefore, the sender would use Run Length Limited (RLL) codes such as Manchester encoding where a "1" is represented as "01" and "0" is represented as "10". In this case, the receiver would have at most two consecutive frames with the same modulated symbol (maximum possible run is two frames). Finally, the change in OCC channel state (i.e. blinking) should be *faster than the perception of the human eye* to prevent causing confusions to surrounding human drivers/pedestrians and also physiological effects such as nausea. The IEEE 802.15.7 standard [520] for Short-Range Optical Wireless Communications recommends the use of at least 200 Hz in light flickering frequency.

18.5 Scheme Defense Analysis

In this section, we evaluate our scheme (section 18.4) against the threat model (section 18.2).

Scenario A: in figure 18.2a, the malicious vehicle \mathcal{A} attempts to deceive vehicle \mathcal{C} by pretending to be vehicle \mathcal{B} or by fabricating its location to appear as if \mathcal{A} is in front of \mathcal{C} . With our scheme, whenever \mathcal{C} receives a message pretending to be from \mathcal{B} , it checks the message's nonce with the visual nonce emitted by \mathcal{B} which is physically in front of \mathcal{C} . If the two nonces from the two channels

Figure 18.3: RF/OCC Channel Synchronization Problem

(RF and OCC) match, the message is indeed from \mathcal{B} . Otherwise, the message will be flagged as a spoofing attempt.

Scenario B: in figure 18.2b, the malicious vehicle attempts to deceive the traffic light into believing that the lane is crowded by broadcasting multiple messages with different IDs. Here the traffic light will use the OCC channel to match each message with its sender. Since the attacker is the sender of all the messages, all message IDs will be mapped to the same vehicle which will trigger a spoofing attempt.

Scenario C: in figure 18.2c, a malicious unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) attempts to access a restricted airspace by opportunistically waiting for a legitimate UAV to present its access credentials to the control tower. When the credentials are broadcasted, the malicious UAV flies to the restricted airspace knowing that the control tower cannot physically distinguish between the legitimate UAV from the malicious one. With our scheme, the legitimate UAV can physically present itself using OCC channel to distinguish itself from all other nearby UAVs.

18.6 Copycat Attack & Mitigation Methods

The threat model presented in section 18.2 represents three different attack scenarios that an attacker might attempt under different capabilities. However, we identified a possible attack against our authentication and localization scheme where the attacker adapts to our authentication strategy by recording visual nonces using its own camera then plays them back to mimic the legitimate sender (hence, the name Copycat), or fabricate new messages with someone else’s OCC nonce.

Copycat attack can be executed under different scenarios. To mitigate its impact, we present the scenarios where this vulnerability might exist and discuss how to overcome it.

18.6.1 RF/OCC Channel Synchronization

In this scenario, the attacker attempts to exploit the time difference between the transmission time over the RF channel and the transmission time over the OCC channel in order to inject a spoofed message/nonce. To illustrate, let us consider the scenario in figure 18.3a. The legitimate vehicle transmits a message over the RF channel then shortly later transmits the nonce over the OCC channel. Assuming the attacker is capable of reading the RF message, the attacker extracts the nonce from the message then reproduces it over the OCC channel using its own lighting source.

Now the receiver will believe that the RF message was actually sent by the attacker since the receiver correctly received the attacker's OCC nonce first.

Similarly, in the scenario demonstrated in figure 18.3b, the legitimate vehicle first transmits the nonce over the OCC channel then afterwards it transmits the message over the RF channel. By assuming the attacker is capable of fabricating the legitimate vehicle's identity, the attacker can read the legitimate vehicle's visual nonce and then fabricate an RF message using that nonce. Now any receiver would believe the attacker's message was actually transmitted by the legitimate vehicle since the two nonces match (attacker's RF nonce and legitimate vehicle's OCC nonce).

To understand how to mitigate this attack, we need first to define the notion of "attacker response time". Let $AttRes$ denote to the attacker response time which defines the minimum time the attacker needs to react to a message transmission. In other words, $AttRes$ is the elapsed time from the moment the attacker detects a transmitted message to the time the attacker reacts to that message by sending a spoofed message on the opposite channel. By knowing or estimating the $AttRes$ time, we can formulate a minimum acceptable RF/OCC transmission time difference such that: $|T_{OCC} - T_{RF}| < AttRes$. In other words, when one of the channels (either RF or OCC) starts transmitting, the other channel should start transmitting no later than $AttRes$ seconds. Note that since we omitted the propagation delay in section 18.3.2, we re-used T_{RF} and T_{OCC} from section 18.4 to denote to transmitting time instead of receiving time.

18.6.2 Sender/Receiver Channel Synchronization

In the previous scenario, the attacker either listen to the RF channel then transmit over the OCC channel, or listen to the OCC channel then transmit over the RF channel. In this scenario, the attacker listen to the OCC channel then transmit over the OCC channel as well to mimic the legitimate vehicle's visual nonce and cause confusion at the receiver side. In other words, the receiver would receive a single RF message from the legitimate vehicle but at the same time it will receive the same visual nonce from two different vehicles. Therefore, the receiver cannot distinguish who is the actual transmitter since there are two different vehicles emitting the same visual nonce.

To mitigate the impact of this attack scenario, the camera frame captured by the receiver must only include the OCC symbol produced by the sender. To achieve this property, the sender needs to delay its OCC transmission to the end of the receiver's frame exposure time window T_e . This would cause the attacker's symbol to appear in the subsequent/different frame at the receiver side. To accomplish this, the sender needs to know the sampling rate of the receiver's camera (i.e. its FPS) as well as the receiver's clock time at which the camera starts and ends its shutter exposure period for each frame. Let st_i and st_{i+1} denote to the the start time of $frame_i$ and $frame_{i+1}$ respectively. If the sender knows st_i , then it can synchronize its clock with the receiver for all subsequent frame start times such that $st_{i+1} = st_i + T_e$. Now for the sender to transmit an OCC $symbol_i$ to be captured during $frame_i$, the time to transmit $symbol_i$ is at time $T_i = st_{i+1} - (PW_s + PW_g)$. This would cause $symbol_i$ to be transmitted as close as possible to the end of $frame_i$ but not too close to risk an inter-symbol interference. Furthermore, in section 18.3.2 we discussed that the symbol pulse-width must satisfy $PW_s \geq DC_{min} \times T_e$. In this section after defining the Sender/Receiver Channel Synchronization problem, we set $PW_s = DC_{min} \times T_e$ to minimize the attack window as much as possible. Therefore, for the OCC symbol transmission to be safely and successfully captured, the transmission time for $symbol_i$ is $T_i = st_{i+1} - (PW_s + PW_g)$ and the total pulse-width is $AttRes > (PW_s + PW_g) < T_e$ for $PW_s = DC_{min} \times T_e$.

18.7 Related Work

Most previous efforts related to vehicle authentication are directed toward authenticating their identities (e.g. through the use of digital certificates) [512]. However, such conventional authentication cannot be directly applied to many threat models as we have seen in section 18.2 where authenticating the location (i.e. "where you are") factor is also required. Mainly there are two localization techniques in the literature, RF-based and optical-based. Note that since we are interested in locating transmitters, techniques for localizing passive devices/objects such as computer-vision object detection and radar will not be discussed.

RF-Based Localization has abundant number publications. It mainly relies on Time/Difference of Arrival (ToA/TDoA), Angle of Arrival (AoA) and RSSI measurements techniques. For example [519] proposed an RSSI-based localization algorithm that depends on vehicles or RSUs as observers to triangulate the target vehicle. However, the dependence on other trusted vehicles sets a limitation to the threat model. Furthermore, the location of a target vehicle is approximated as an area (a common limitation for most RF-based localization schemes). That means a group of vehicles in close-proximity with each other (a typical road scenario) would have very similar RF transmissions in terms of timing and angle which makes it a challenging task to localize one of the vehicles among the other group members. Even a single attacker can manipulate its transmission power and timing to deviate the observers. In general, RF-based localization schemes tend to be complex, require special antenna designs, and suffer from multipath and interference phenomena [521].

Vision-Based Localization is a well studied research field but mostly in the context of using visual cues as beacons for enabling devices to localize themselves. For example, [521] uses projectors and photodetectors while [522] uses LEDs and cameras as indoor localization solutions. However, such solutions cannot be repurposed to our threat model since it either require the cooperation of the localized device or require a map reconstruction phase (also found in RF-based techniques) prior to rolling out the localization system. In vehicle network, the use of VLC channels is gaining a great attention lately but mainly in the context of communication rather than localization which might make it inapplicable to our threat model. For example to increase the bitrate of the VLC channel, [523] sampled each row of a rolling shutter independently while [524] suggested the use of a standalone photodiode but both techniques make it impossible (or at least extremely difficult) to construct an image from the received VLC signal. [525] and [526] attempted to increase the VLC bitrate with a fully constructed image by utilizing visual-MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) where multiple light sources act as multiple output and the individual pixels of the receiver's camera are considered the multiple inputs. However, visual-MIMO via OCC requires additional hardware and its bit error rate drastically increases with increased distances [527]. In an alternative approach, [528] implemented a visual localization scheme for drone swarms where a locator commands the target drone that need to be localized to perform a short flight maneuver such as a quick turn which would act as a visual cue for the locator who is equipped with a camera to distinguish the target drone among the other swarm members. However, the maneuver command cannot be performed until a safe distance from all surrounding objects is established. Furthermore, it is difficult for stationary vehicles to perform maneuvers such as cars stopped at a red light. Finally, accepting maneuver requests from other devices adds an additional attack surface to the autonomous system.

18.8 Conclusion & Future Work

We proposed a vision-based authentication and localization scheme for autonomous vehicles that employ localization as a form of authentication where we use visual nonces as a proof of RF message transmission. We also introduced a Copycat Attack that exploits our scheme's synchronization vulnerabilities as well as mitigation approaches for each vulnerability. In future work, we will design testbed to **(i)** numerically define $AttRes$ and PW_g then evaluate if $AttRes > (DC_{min} \times T_e) + PW_g$ can be applied using commodity cameras with an acceptable SINR, **(ii)** implement an encoding scheme that utilizes a low frame rate (e.g. 30FPS) as a receiver and high flickering frequency (e.g. 200Hz) as a transmitter without introducing the sender/receiver sync problem, and **(iii)** demonstrate a dual-channel protocol that sync between the low bitrate of the OCC channel and high bitrate of the RF channel without introducing the OCC/RF sync problem.

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Chapter 19

Play the Imitation Game: Model Extraction Attack against Autonomous Driving Localization

The security of the Autonomous Driving (AD) system has been gaining researchers' and public's attention recently. Given that AD companies have invested a huge amount of resources in developing their AD models, e.g., localization models, these models, especially their parameters, are important intellectual property and deserve strong protection.

In this chapter, we examine whether the confidentiality of production-grade Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) models, in particular, Error-State Kalman Filter (ESKF), can be stolen from an outside adversary. We propose a new model extraction attack called TASKMASTER that can infer the secret ESKF parameters under black-box assumption. In essence, TASKMASTER trains a substitutional ESKF model to recover the parameters, by observing the input and output to the targeted AD system. To precisely recover the parameters, we combine a set of techniques, like gradient-based optimization, search-space reduction and multi-stage optimization. The evaluation result on real-world vehicle sensor dataset shows that TASKMASTER is practical. For example, with 25 seconds AD sensor data for training, the substitutional ESKF model reaches centimeter-level accuracy, comparing with the ground-truth model. The evaluation shows that TASKMASTER can recover the ESKF with high fidelity. The error rate of the recovered parameters can be below 1%.

This activity was originally reported in [19].

19.1 Introduction

In the recent decades, the advancement of technologies in machine learning, sensing, and control has elevated autonomous vehicles (AV) from ideation to reality. A growing number of AV companies have emerged and some have pushed their products to public roads. For instance, Google and Baidu have been operating self-driving taxis [529, 530] for years. Among all the components inside AV, the Autonomous Driving (AD) system is the most important piece, acting as the AV's "brain". The AD system commands the actuators according to the prediction of perception models.

One key component in the pipeline of AD is *localization*, which computes the real-time vehicle position. Ensuring the accuracy of localization is fundamental to the safety of AV, for which most of the AV companies use a complex Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF) model [78, 196] to fuse the readings of multiple sensors. Essentially, MSF takes input from sensors like GPS, IMU and LiDAR, and runs a state estimation model, e.g., Kalman Filter (KF), to predict AV's state, including position,

heading direction, velocity, etc. As a result, the prediction made by MSF is highly robust, even in bad weather conditions or when one sensor is under attack, like GPS spoofing [531]. Yet, Shen et al. [532] showed that the *integrity* of a MSF model can be violated, by demonstrating a successful attack on the production-grade AD system, *i.e.*, Baidu Apollo [72]. In the meantime, the *confidentiality* of a MSF has not been discussed, not to mention the demonstration of attacks and defense. Considering the importance of MSF, we study the MSF confidentiality issues.

Confidentiality of MSF models. By examining the production-grade MSF implementation, *e.g.*, the one from Baidu Apollo, we found confidentiality is indeed a great concern. Although Apollo is an open-sourced project, the source code of MSF module is not released and cannot be decompiled into a readable format. In fact, based on our discussion with industrial partners, the parameters of MSF are considered the project’s top intellectual property, since they devoted years of hard work to tune the parameters and localization became the deciding factor for their product to outperform their competitors.

On the other hand, previous works in ML security have demonstrated *model extraction attacks* [533–535], which queries a blackbox ML models on a remote server (*e.g.*, public cloud), can infer the secret parameters of ML models. Given that the input to and the output from an MSF model can be observed, a natural idea is to borrow such model extraction technique to attack MSF. Yet, a few challenges prevent the direct application of the existing model extraction attacks, including the physical-world constraints to attacker’s observations, the complexity of MSF models, and its interaction with other controller components (detailed in Section 19.3.3).

Our attack. To tackle these challenges in extracting MSF models, we leverage the two main insights of the AD system: 1) Though MSF models differ from ML models, their parameters can be approximated through gradient-based optimization, as their equations are *derivable*. 2) When the input or output is inaccessible, in particular, when the MSF’s output is only sent to AD controllers and the channel between them might not be interceptable, we can *emulate* derivable AD controllers and use their output for optimization. In fact, the emulated AD controllers do not need to be the exact same implementations, and the only requirement is that their performance is comparable to the ones in the target AD system.

Based on the above insights, we propose TASKMASTER¹, a new model extraction attack against MSF models, with a set of techniques, like training unrolling, search-space reduction, and multi-stage optimization. Though our approach can be classified as *system identification (SI)* [536], we found none of the existing approaches directly work in our setting due to the complexity of MSF in AV and the constraints on attacker’s data access. We examine TASKMASTER under three attack settings (intrusive in-AV attacker, non-intrusive in-AV attacker, and AV follower), and evaluate it on the real-world vehicle sensor traces (the KAIST Complex Urban sensor traces [252]). The evaluation shows that model extraction attack is a practical threat. As a highlight of our findings, by collecting data points within *25-second window* of a targeted AV, we can train an ESKF model (a variation of KF model used by AV companies) reaching *centimeter*-level accuracy to the ground-truth model. Starting from the extracted model, the cost of the adversary (*e.g.*, unethical competitors) can be greatly reduced.

Contributions. We summarize the contributions of this work as follows:

- We present the *first* study about the confidentiality of the AD localization models.
- To address the new challenges posed by the unique structure of MSF, we develop a new model extraction approach, TASKMASTER, comprising optimization techniques tailored to the control-theory models.

¹TASKMASTER is a fictional character in Marvel Comics who can mimic any fighting style of a superhero.

- We examine TASKMASTER under three attack settings with the real-world sensor traces, and our result indicates model extraction attack is feasible and could benefit unethical competitors.
- The implementation of TASKMASTER is published at [537].

Ethics and disclosure. We have disclosed our findings to the developers of the Baidu Apollo team.

19.2 Background

In this section, we first overview the architecture of Autonomous Driving (AD) system of an Autonomous Vehicle (AV), focusing on the localization module and its design based on Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF). Then, we describe the most popular MSF algorithm that is based on Kalman Filter. Another AD component that is investigated in this work, AD controller, is introduced in Appendix 19.9.1.

19.2.1 AD Localization

Generally, an AD system is composed of 3 main modules: sensor/information collector, on-board computer and actuator/command executor. Specifically, the sensor/information collector takes input from sensors like GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) receiver, LiDAR, IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit), camera, and communication devices like LTE/5G Antenna. The data is sent to the onboard computer to infer a model of the world. Based on the destination and route planning, the controller inside the computer generates the control vector to direct the vehicle, including three parameters: steering control, throttle control, and brake control. These 3 controlling parameters will be fed to the actuator/command executor to change the physical position of the vehicle and also affect the running state of the AD system.

In this work, we investigate the *localization* (or state estimation) component, which computes the real-time ego-vehicle position on the map. Localization is critical in ensuring driving safety and correctness, requiring *centimeter-level* accuracy [98], robustness under severe weather and road conditions, and high-fidelity under cyber-attacks. A trivial solution for localization is to directly use the input from GNSS. However, the GNSS signal significantly degrades due to atmosphere delays and multi-path effect [208]. Moreover, civilian GNSS lacks signal authentication and is vulnerable under spoofing attack [292], in which the attacker can override the authentic signal with stronger power. Using LiDAR, which measures the reflection of laser light, individually is also fragile for localization, especially under poor weather conditions like rain [531]. Hence, localization based on *Multi-Sensor Fusion (MSF)*, which fuses the input from multiple sensors like GPS, IMU, and LiDAR, has become the optimal solution so far, as it delivers much more accurate and robust result, by addressing the weakness of individual sensors [78, 196].

MSF algorithms. Among the existing MSF algorithms, Kalman Filter (KF)-based MSF [538] has gained much broader adoption, compared to the others (e.g., Particle Filter [539]). According to the survey by Shen et al. [532], out of the 18 top-tier robotics papers for 2018-2019, 14 papers adopted KF-based MSF. Baidu Apollo [72], an open-source AD system that has gained prominent buy-in from the AD industry [540] (e.g. being deployed in the self-driving taxi services in China [530]), also chooses KF-based MSF [78].

We focus on the confidentiality of the KF-based MSF model, and the ESKF (Error-State Kalman Filter) model used by AV (e.g., Baidu Apollo ESKF) is our primary target, mainly because it

reaches the highest localization accuracy [532] and its implementation has been considered as a secret (detailed in Section 19.3.1). It is worth mentioning that our approach can be generalized to other KF-based MSF models, e.g., Extended Kalman filter (EKF).

19.2.2 Kalman Filter based Multi-Sensor Fusion

Kalman Filter (KF) [541], also known as linear quadratic estimation (LQE), uses prior state measurements to produce estimates of the posterior states. Equation 19.1 and 19.2 show the how a state in time k is estimated from a state in time $k - 1$.

$$\begin{aligned} x_k &= Fx_{k-1} + Bu_{k-1} \\ P_k &= FP_{k-1}F^\top + Q \end{aligned} \quad (19.1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} K' &= P_k H_k^\top (H_k P_k H_k^\top + R)^{-1} \\ \hat{x}_k &= x_k + K'(z_k - H_k x_k) \\ \hat{P}_k &= P_k - K' H_k P_k \end{aligned} \quad (19.2)$$

In particular, KF iteratively executes two phases: Prediction and Update. For Prediction (Equation 19.1), x_k (the predicted state at k) and P_k (the predicted covariance matrix measuring the confidence of x_k) are computed based on x_{k-1} , P_{k-1} and u_{k-1} (the measurement of kinetics). For Update (Equation 19.2), the observations of the real-world environment (e.g., through sensors), denoted as z_k , are used to refine x_k and P_k to \hat{x}_k and \hat{P}_k , in order to reduce prediction errors. H_k is used to map the true state space (where x_k resides) into the observed space (where z_k resides). Q and R are the covariance matrix of the process noise and the covariance matrix of the observation noise. F and B represent the state-transition model and the control-input model.

Error-State Kalman Filter in AD system. We use the MSF implemented by Baidu Apollo to demonstrate how KF is applied for AD. Specifically, Baidu Apollo fuses the readings from IMU, LiDAR, and GNSS with Error-State Kalman Filter (ESKF), a variant of KF [78]. IMU measures the acceleration ($accel_{k-1}$) and angular velocity ($omega_{k-1}$) of the AV, which are used to construct the control vector $u_{k-1} = (accel_{k-1}, omega_{k-1})^\top$, for Prediction phase. The predicted state x_k is a vector consisting of 16 values. It is represented as $(pos_k, vel_k, quat_k, ba_k, bg_k)^\top$, where pos_k represents the AV's current location (3 elements), $quat_k$ represents the heading direction in form of quaternion (4 elements), vel_k represents velocity (3 elements), ba_k represents accelerometer bias (3 elements), and bg_k represents gyrometer bias (3 elements). P_k is a 15×15 matrix. For Update phase, the position measurements from GNSS and the position measurements and car heading measurements from LiDAR are considered as the observations z_k after data processing. When Update phase is finished, an Error-state Reset phase ($\hat{P}_k = G\hat{P}_kG^\top$) is introduced by ESKF to reset \hat{P}_k , to address the issue of observation drifting [78]. G is defined in Equation 19.11 of Appendix 19.9.2.

In addition, Baidu Apollo uses different R and H for GNSS and LiDAR. For GNSS, we assume R_G (noise distribution injected into GNSS data) and H_G are used to replace R and H in Equation 19.2, changing the Update phase to Equation 19.12 of Appendix 19.9.2. For LiDAR, the Update phase is separated into two sub-phases that use the position sensing data and pose (or yaw of the AD car) sensing data separately. The output of the first sub-phase is fed to the second sub-phase. The Update phase is changed to Equation 19.13 of Appendix 19.9.2. To notice, Prediction phase happens whenever IMU sends new input, and Update phase happens whenever LiDAR or GNSS sends new input. Hence, Prediction and Update do not necessarily happen in turns. Figure 19.1 illustrates the workflow.

Figure 19.1: Workflow of ESKF. The flows of GNSS and LiDAR both generate Update states, but the values could be different.

19.3 Attack Overview

In this section, we first describe the motivation of our adversary. Then, we describe the three scenarios that the attack could happen, differentiated by attackers’ capabilities. Finally, we overview the workflow of our attack, termed TASKMASTER.

19.3.1 Adversary Motivation

Though the procedure and equation of KF (including ESKF) are known and it is expected that every AD system follows them in implementation, the parameters of KF can be varied among AD systems, resulting in different localization performance. According to [78], the production-grade implementation by Baidu Apollo achieves 0.054 meters accuracy, which outperforms the academic KF implementations by a large margin (1.17 meters for JS-MSF [97] and 1.91 meters for ETH-MSF [542]). A lot of driving data from a human driver needs to be collected and different tuning approaches have to be experimented with by professional AV engineers [532]. In fact, we reached out to one author of Baidu Apollo ESKF [78] and learnt that it takes more than *6 months* for a specialized team to tune ESKF. As such, the parameters of KF are considered as “intellectual property”, and kept as a secret by the AV companies (e.g., Baidu’s leadership decides to keep the current and future versions of ESKF close-source, as we learnt from the author of [78]). We also tried to reverse-engineer the KF parameters from Apollo’s binary files but failed. The details are elaborated in Appendix 19.9.3.

This work focuses on the confidentiality of four covariance matrices Q , R_G , R_L^p and R_L^y (process noises, GNSS noises, position observation noises, and yaw observation noises) of an ESKF model, which are explained in Section 19.2.2. The generalizability of the extracted parameters is explained in Appendix 19.9.4.

Figure 19.2: Adversary model. δ is the function adding noises.

Hacking AV to extract KF parameters. Hacking into the AD system of the targeted AV and then stealing the KF model is another unethical approach for the same attacker's goal. A few recent works demonstrated it is feasible to exploit the vulnerabilities in Wi-Fi modules of Tesla, send messages through CAN (Controller Area Network) bus, and take control of the AD system remotely, e.g., by opening a Linux shell [543, 544]. However, due to the high investment into AV security by AV companies (e.g., Tesla puts US\$1 million for bug bounty [545]), such vulnerabilities are very rare and can be quickly patched. Moreover, even if the shell is obtained by an adversary who is interested in KF parameters, the files containing KF models are very likely to be protected.

19.3.2 Adversary Model

We assume the adversary wants to steal the KF model of a competitor's AV and integrate it into her own AV products to save the work for KF tuning. Instead of assuming "whitebox" access and directly extracting the model parameters (e.g., by reading the files/memory/registers containing the KF parameters), our adversary has "blackbox" access to a KF model, meaning she can observe the input and output, and use the information to *infer* the KF parameters of victim's AV². We assume 3 attack scenarios based on adversary's capabilities, which are also summarized in Figure 19.2.

AS1: Intrusive In-AV Attacker. We assume the attacker has exclusive physical access to the targeted AV, e.g., by purchasing, renting or borrowing the AV, and the attacker is able to sniff the data transmitted *within* the AD system, by inserting the sniffers directly onto the paths between ECUs (Electronic Control Units). As such, the attacker is able to observe the input to ESKF (u_{k-1} and z_k), and the output from ESKF (\hat{x}_k). With such information, the attacker attempts to extract a victim AV's ESKF model.

AS2: Non-intrusive In-AV Attacker. We assume the attackers cannot sniff the data within the AD system, but they can plug in a transceiver onto the AV's Universal Serial Bus (USB), and use the transceiver to read the messages, including the readings of sensors (IMU, LiDAR, and GNSS) [546] which are unencrypted. Alternatively, the attacker can bring her own sensors. For example, LiBackpack [547] integrates LiDAR and GNSS at the backpack size, and mobile devices usually have IMU sensors [548]. Observation noises could be encountered, including the measurement accuracy of LiBackpack and synchronization issues of IMU accuracy on the mobile devices, which would reduce the attack accuracy. The attacker cannot observe the data between ESKF and controller, therefore she has no direct visibility into \hat{x}_k . The output of the controller, termed y_k , including steering, throttling, and braking, can be observed, by sniffing the command issued to those actuators. To notice, we assume the attacker knows nothing about the controller and we do not consider controller parameters as a secret.

²Similar as blackbox model extraction attacks against DNN [533], the attacker needs to know the structure of KF ahead.

AS3: AV Follower. This scenario has the most stringent attack condition that the attacker has to be outside of the AV, e.g., by driving another car to follow the AV in close vicinity. With high-resolution sensors on her AV, including GNSS, LiDAR and camera, the attacker collects the motion traces of the victim AV, and infers the sensor readings of the victim AV (u_{k-1} and z_k) and the controller output (y_k), but the readings are inaccurate. We model the input to victim’s KF as the combination of the sensor readings of attacker’s AV and attacker’s measurement noises. Shen et al. [532] adopts a similar approach to model the inaccurate attacker’s readings when launching GPS spoofing against another AV on the move.

19.3.3 KF Model Extraction

At the high level, extracting KF model resembles *extracting machine-learning (ML) models*, of which the related works are surveyed in Section 19.7. In essence, model extraction against ML models also assumes blackbox access, though which the attacker uses the prediction APIs provided by the deployed model $O : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ to issue queries (e.g., requesting classification of images) $X \subset \mathcal{X}$, and obtains the responses, including the labels $Y \subset \mathcal{Y}$, and optionally confidence scores S_Y or logits L_Y . With X, Y (together with S_Y or L_Y if available), the attacker runs an extraction algorithm \mathcal{A} and obtains an extracted model \hat{O} . The extraction is considered successful, if \hat{O} matches one of the criteria [549]: 1) Functional equivalent: $\forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \hat{O}(x) = O(x)$; 2) High fidelity: for a target distribution $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}$ over \mathcal{X} , $Pr_{x \sim \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{F}}}[S(\hat{O}(x), O(x))]$ is maximized, where S is a similarity function; 3) High accuracy: given a true task distribution $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{A}}$ over $\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}$, $Pr_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{A}}}[\text{argmax}(\hat{O}(x)) = y]$ is maximized. \hat{O} with high fidelity tries to replicate the decisions of O , including mis-classifications, while \hat{O} with high accuracy aims to match or even exceed the accuracy of O .

Following the above terminology, we aim to recover a KF model, in particular Q, R_G, R_L^p and R_L^y , at *high accuracy* or *high fidelity*, and we focus on ESKF in this work. A variety of learning-based approaches have been developed towards this goal [533–535]. Though none of the related works investigated control-theory models, we found the learning-based approaches hold promise in addressing our problem. When considering ESKF in isolation, our task is similar to model extraction against *RNN* models, as both RNN and ESKF have a feedback loop between output and input. As such, we can try to find the best parameters that minimize the error between the predicted states outputted by the targeted ESKF O (ground-truth) and the attacker’s ESKF \hat{O} . Gradient-based optimization can be applied here because the ESKF functions are derivable.

A similar research direction is system identification [536], which aims to construct the mathematical models of dynamic systems from measured input-output data. Section 19.7 reviews the existing methods, but we found none of them are directly applicable to the complex MSF models, in particular ESKF used by AVs.

Challenges. Extracting the parameters from KF models encounters prominent challenges that cannot be addressed by the existing approaches. **1)** ESKF is complex, which takes the input generated by the heterogeneous sensors (GNSS, LiDAR, and IMU) at a vastly different pace. **2)** AV is not always controlled by the attacker (e.g., under AS3), and the number of traces about the targeted AV might be small. Given that the search space of the secret is not small (e.g., Q and R are 15x15, 3x3 matrices), the attacker’s search strategy has to be highly efficient. **3)** When the output of ESKF (i.e., \hat{x} and \hat{P}) is not directly observable, e.g., under scenario AS2 and AS3, the data available to the model extraction is incomplete.

To address these challenges, we proposed a novel method for learning-based KF model extraction, termed TASKMASTER, involving techniques like *multi-stage optimization*, *search-space reduction* and *controller simulation*. The details are described next.

19.4 Attack Implementation

The goal of the attacker is to learn an ESKF model \hat{O} that mimics the target model O . In this section, we first describe how we optimize the training procedure of ESKF to learning \hat{O} in an efficient way when the ESKF output is available. Then, we describe how to train \hat{O} without the ESKF output, by emulating controllers. We summarize the symbols in Appendix 19.9.5.

19.4.1 Extracting ESKF Alone

Under AS1, TASKMASTER uses u_{k-1}, z_k^p, z_k^y (ESKF input, position measurement and yaw measurement) and x_k (ESKF output) to train \hat{O} . The attacker can directly sniff IMU output to get u_{k-1} . By sniffing GNSS output, z_k^p is obtained. By sniffing LiDAR locator output, z_k^p and z_k^y are obtained. In the end, the attacker obtains a time sequence $T = [t_1, \dots, t_i, \dots]$ as input, where t_i is u_{k-1}, z_k^p or z_k^y . For output, \hat{x}_k can be intercepted from the wires between ECUs within AD system, which are produced after t_i is processed by the ESKF. We train \hat{O} in a recurrent way. Specifically, for each round i , \hat{O} uses t_i and the last state P_{i-1} as input, and predicts a new state x_i and its covariance P_i . The same input is sent to O to generate the predicted state x'_i and its covariance P'_i . Notably, O is treated as a blackbox here. The difference between the output of O and \hat{O} is leveraged to update \hat{O} .

We use an optimizer penalized by the logarithmic value of Mean Squared Error (MSE) (denoted as L) between x_i and x'_i , as shown in Equation 19.3. The difference between P_i and P'_i is not integrated because P'_i is an internal variable that cannot be obtained when O is considered blackbox. We compute the logarithmic MSE to make the convergence process faster.

$$L(x, x') = \log\left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|x_i - x'_i\|^2\right) \quad (19.3)$$

Training \hat{O} is similar as training an LSTM model at the high level, where unrolling [550] is performed on the ESKF model. Specifically, the feed-forward process calculates the series x'_k one by one (*i.e.*, unrolled) and then calculates the loss according to Equation 19.3. While in the back-propagation process, the parameters of the ESKF model are only updated once according to the gradient from the loss to each variable (as if not unrolled).

With the above strategy, we train a shadow ESKF model \hat{O} . Alternatively, we can train a shadow LSTM model to extract \hat{O} . However, we found this approach did not work well, because some operations like pose transformation are not modeled well under LSTM, and it is hard to make the training converge with unbalanced data (e.g., IMU, LiDAR and GNSS are 50:6.5:1 in data volume).

Search-space reduction of Q . Though Q is a 15x15 matrix, we found not every value has to be tuned. According to [97], Q can be described with Equation 19.4.

$$\begin{aligned} V_i &= \sigma_{a_n}^2 (\Delta t)^2 I \\ \Theta_i &= \sigma_{\omega_n}^2 (\Delta t)^2 I \\ A_i &= \sigma_{a_\omega}^2 \Delta t I \\ \Omega_i &= \sigma_{\omega_\omega}^2 \Delta t I \\ Q &= \text{diag}(V_i, \Theta_i, A_i, \Omega_i) \end{aligned} \quad (19.4)$$

where V_i , Θ_i , A_i and Ω_i represent velocity, quaternion/pose, accelerometer error state, and gyrometer error state. Δt is the difference between timestamps. σ_{a_n} , σ_{ω_n} , σ_{a_ω} and σ_{ω_ω} are the standard

deviation of velocity, pose, accelerometer and gyrometer, and they are the variables to be optimized. Each of them is a scalar variable and they are located at the diagonal of the Q matrix. Hence, we limit the optimization process on the 4 variables while avoiding touching the others (they can be set to 0), reducing the variables to be optimized from 225 (15x15) to 4. In Section 19.5.2, we assess how this strategy impacts the attack performance.

Search-space reduction of R_G , R_L^p and R_L^y . Similar to Q , the search space of R_G , R_L^p , and R_L^y can be reduced based on the constraints of the physical world and control theory. As described in Section 19.2.2, R_G , R_L^p and R_L^y are covariance matrices describing the deviation of Gaussian noise injected into the related sensor observations, all of them have two properties: 1) it is a diagonal matrix, 2) elements on the diagonal of are non-negative. These properties are based on the related mathematical equations that hold universally [551, 552]. According to previous works on both GNSS and LiDAR sensor development [78], the variance of each dimension in the measurements is independent of other elements. Hence, we can fix the values of the elements not on the diagonal and add a check to avoid updating the diagonal elements to negative values. The number of elements to be optimized is reduced from 27 (R_G , R_L^p and R_L^y are all 3×3 matrices) to 9 (the diagonal elements), and the search space of each element is cut to half.

Multi-stage optimization. Learning \hat{O} could be based on maximum likelihood estimation (MLE), which seeks a set of parameters that maximizes a likelihood function. However, MLE assumes that the output is solely dependent on the current input. When the output is also dependent on latent variables (i.e., unobserved or hidden variables), MLE does not work well [553]. Such a problem exists in ESKF: the input from sensors as well as the ESKF model states decide the prediction. In addition, the data generation frequencies of IMU, LiDAR, and GNSS are vastly different (roughly 50:6.5:1 on the KAIST dataset we use [252]), resulting in unstable input dimensions that cannot be easily handled by MLE.

To address the aforementioned issues, *expectation maximization (EM)* [553] can be performed which introduces an extra estimation step. EM has been particularly effective in learning Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM). The dataset used to train GMM consists of points generated from one or more Gaussian processes at different paces. The two steps of EM are:

- **E-Step.** Estimate the expected value for each latent variable.
- **M-Step.** Optimize the parameters using maximum likelihood.

Under EM, the initial estimation by E-step can assign random values to the latent variables. Along the iterations, the optimized model from M-step can estimate the latent parameters for existing and new data points. We adopt this idea and develop a multi-stage optimization technique for ESKF. Specifically, Q , R_G , R_L^p and R_L^y are partitioned into two groups, i.e., $G_1 = [Q]$ and $G_2 = [R_G, R_L^p, R_L^y]$. Since the two groups have different frequencies and dimensions, we can choose different learning rates and decay rates. For G_1 , parameters in R_G, R_L^p, R_L^y will be treated as constant and only Q will be optimized. For G_2 , Q will be constant and other parameters will be optimized. Notably, EM has been leveraged to tune KF, but it has to be adjusted under TASKMASTER because we use the input and output of *another blackbox KF model* for optimization. In Appendix 19.9.6, we summarize the whole training process.

19.4.2 Extracting ESKF from Controller Outputs

Under AS2 and AS3, the adversary has no visibility to the ground-truth output (x'_k) of O , so the loss L cannot be directly computed for training. On the other hand, x'_k is sent to the controller, who outputs y_k (including steering, throttling, and braking) as the control signal, which is nonetheless

Figure 19.3: Workflow of ESKF combined with controllers. Anomaly filter is an optional component included by some AD like Baidu Apollo.

observable. Hence, the attacker may regard the ESKF and the trailing controller as a whole, so she can train the series (ESKF + controller) with the observable ESKF input (u_{k-1}, z_k^p, z_k^y) and the observable controller output (y_k) . Then she can readily extract the ESKF O from the trained series. Noticeably, the attacker does not need to know what controllers are used by the victim AVs, and *we do not consider the controller as a secret*. In fact, the attacker can implement a trainable controller or even use an out-of-box, open-source implementation, which is quite different from the victim AVs.

Mechanisms of the AD controllers. As described in Appendix 19.9.1, Baidu Apollo uses PID controller for longitudinal control and LQR controller for lateral control (steering). When an AV receives a map and a destination point, it generates a planned trajectory consisting of a sequence of reference positions on the map (tp^*), and the AD controller generates corresponding control vectors to minimize the error between the current position and the reference positions. PID controller in AD generates the longitudinal control vector, based on the predicted position (pos_k) and velocity (vel_k) from the ESKF output x_k . The PID control vector contains the planned next position (p_k) and acceleration (a_k), which are used to derive control commands (throttle and brake). They can be computed as below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_k &= K_{pp} \times \text{MinDist}(tp^*, pos_k) + K_{ip} \times \sum_{m=k-M}^{k-1} (p_m) \\
 a_k &= K_{pa} \times (max_speed - vel_k) + K_{ia} \times \sum_{n=k-N}^{k-1} (a_n)
 \end{aligned} \tag{19.5}$$

where MinDist computes the minimum distance between the reference positions tp^* and the current position pos_k , max_speed represents the maximum speed allowed on the AV during navigation, M and N are the number of positions and accelerations from the controller output in the past, p_m and a_n are the corresponding positions and accelerations. K_{pp} , K_{ip} , K_{pa} and K_{ia} are the controller parameters. Notably, the above equation contains “Integral” (modeling the past) and “Proportional” (modeling the present), but does not contain “Derivative” (modeling the future), which is based on Apollo’s implementation.

Similar to PID controller, LQR controller generates the lateral control vector (yaw) to derive the control commands (steering), based on the planned trajectory, the past states, and the present state (from ESKF output). However, this process requires solving Discrete-time Arithmetic Riccati

Equation (DARE), which cannot be implemented compatibly with gradient descending. Specifically, iterative methods have been used to obtain a numerical solution of the equation, whose process is not derivable. As such, if we simulate LQR controller after ESKF, we will not be able to derive the gradients to optimize ESKF parameters. To address this issue, we implement *Stanley controller* [554] and use it replace LQR controller. Stanley controller was used for lateral control during the 2005 DARPA Grand Challenge of Autonomous Robotic Ground Vehicles [555] by the Stanford team, who won the first place. It is a perfect match for our goal because its equations related to yaw computation are derivable, as shown in Equation 19.6. Since TASKMASTER does not extract the controller parameters, using another controller of similar performance is acceptable.

$$\begin{aligned}
 front_axle_vec &= (\cos(yaw_k + \frac{\pi}{2}), -\sin(yaw_k + \frac{\pi}{2}))^\top \\
 error_front_axle &= (x_{min^*}, y_{min^*})^\top \cdot front_axle_vec \\
 \theta_e &= \text{normalize_angle}(cyaw_{min^*} - yaw_k) \\
 \theta_d &= \arctan 2(k \times error_front_axle, vel_k) \\
 d_k &= \theta_e + \theta_d
 \end{aligned} \tag{19.6}$$

where yaw_k is the yaw (or heading) derived from $quat_k$ of ESKF's output, $front_axle_vec$ is the estimated front axle velocity, x_{min^*} and y_{min^*} are the x and y coordinates of the nearest position on the planned trajectory to the current position, $error_front_axle$ represents the error to the reference states on the front axle, $cyaw_{min^*}$ is the yaw associated with the nearest position, normalize_angle normalizes the difference between $cyaw_{min^*}$ and yaw_k into $[-\pi, \pi]$, θ_d and θ_e are the cross track error and the heading error, and d_i is the resulted yaw control vector. k is the only tuning parameter and it can be optimized along with ESKF in our method.

Extracting \hat{O} . In Figure 19.3, we illustrate how ESKF, PID controller and Stanley controller are connected for AS2 and AS3. Compared to AS1, x_k is replaced by p_k , d_k and a_k (position, yaw, and acceleration). To accommodate this change, we modify the loss of Equation 19.3 to Equation 19.7.

$$\begin{aligned}
 L(p, d, a, p', d', a') &= \lambda_p \log\left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|p_i - p'_i\|^2\right) \\
 &+ \lambda_d \log\left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (d_i - d'_i)^2\right) \\
 &+ \lambda_a \log\left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (a_i - a'_i)^2\right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{19.7}$$

where $\langle p, d, a \rangle$ and $\langle p', d', a' \rangle$ are the controller outputs linked to \hat{O} and O . λ_p , λ_d and λ_a are the weights for each controller loss. After empirical analysis, we found the optimization process converges faster when λ_p is much higher than λ_a and λ_d , since values of position coordinates ($\sim 3e + 5$) are much larger than that of yaw ($\sim 1e + 2$) and acceleration ($\sim 1e + 1$).

Another difference to AS1 is that $\langle p, d, a \rangle$ will not be fed back to train \hat{O} , thereby training becomes non-recurrent. We make such change to avoid amplifying the error to ESKF caused by the inaccurate modeling of the controllers. Training ESKF under AS2 and AS3 follow the same workflow, except the input to ESKF and the output of controllers have noises.

Anomaly filter. We found some AD systems add another anomaly filter between MSF and controller, when the output of MSF is too noisy to direct the controller. For instance, Baidu Apollo takes the output of ESKF (x_k) and corrects it with other information, before feeding it to

the controllers, as shown in Figure 19.3. Since the source code of the anomaly filter is not released by Baidu Apollo, we introduce a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) model to replace it, which can be trained together with ESKF. We choose MLP because the input size is small (x_k is 16x1). Our MLP has 5 layers, and each layer has 16 neurons. The activation function is ReLU. The MLP model is initialized by identity matrices and all zero bias.

19.5 Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate how TASKMASTER recovers ESKF models with the real-world data. To evaluate TASKMASTER against different models, we re-implemented one ESKF model based on [97] (termed `Sola-ESKF`), and obtained the blackbox ESKF model of Baidu Apollo v2.5 (termed `Apollo-ESKF`), which is also the major evaluation platform for AD security research (e.g., [188, 556, 557]). For Stanley and PID controllers, we re-implemented them based on [558] and [559]. Our implementation of TASKMASTER includes 756 LoC (lines of code) for ESKF and data pre-processing, 213 LoC for controller and 348 LoC for the training process.

We first describe the experiment settings. Then, we elaborate the attack results on `Sola-ESKF` and `Apollo-ESKF` under the three attack settings. We leave the evaluation of different parameters in Appendix 19.9.7. We have also conducted experiments to compare TASKMASTER against the baseline system identification, and evaluate how TASKMASTER can help the spoofing attack proposed in [532], but due to the page limit, the results are not reported in this version.

19.5.1 Experiment Settings

Evaluation datasets. To evaluate TASKMASTER, we use the KAIST Complex Urban sensor traces [252] (termed `KAIST` hereinafter). The authors of [252] collected sensor data, including Image, LiDAR, GPS, IMU and Encoder, from the complex urban areas of four different cities, with a mapping vehicle. In total there are 31 *traces* (each trace corresponds to one trip of the vehicle), and 12 are in highway and 19 are in downtown. Same as [532], we selected 5 traces from them for evaluation, which are labeled as *local08*, *local31*, *local07*, *highway06* and *highway17* by KAIST, because `Sola-ESKF` and `Apollo-ESKF` cannot achieve reliable performance on the rest. According to Section 6.2 of [532], the 5 selected traces have the smallest average MSF state uncertainty in their categories (i.e., local and highway). According to the extended version of [532], these traces all have complete sensor data (e.g., some other traces do not have complete IMU data) and provide a complete motion history.

We use the `KAIST` sensor data as input and feed them to the two ESKF models to obtain two sets of ESKF states output as the ground-truth. We name the dataset consisting of the ESKF states output from `Sola-ESKF` as `Sola-Output`. The second dataset has the ESKF states output from `Apollo-ESKF`, and we name it `Apollo-Output`.

Evaluation metrics. We consider two metrics to evaluate TASKMASTER, focusing on *fidelity* and *accuracy*.

- **Difference between the parameters (PER).** Since `Sola-ESKF` is implemented by us, we have the ground-truth about the secret parameters. Therefore, we compute the difference between the parameter values learnt from the evaluation datasets and the ground-truth values, which we term *Parameter Error Rate (PER)* and show in the equation below:

$$PER = \frac{|\hat{\theta} - \theta|}{|\theta|} \quad (19.8)$$

where $\hat{\theta}$ represents the learnt parameter of the substitutional model and θ represents the ground truth. The matrix mean is computed on their difference. This metric evaluates the fidelity of TASKMASTER. In real-world settings, when the ESKF model parameters are proprietary, we cannot compute this metric. So we compute PER only for **Sola-ESKF**.

- **Distance between the predicted states (SER).** The ultimate goal of the adversary is to build an ESKF model of high prediction accuracy, and the parameters stolen by TASKMASTER should serve this purpose. Hence, for each trace, we use the inferred ESKF and the ground-truth ESKF to predict the vehicle states using the sensor inputs, and compute the Root Mean-Squared Error (RMSE) between the states, termed *State Error Rate (SER)*, with the equation below:

$$SER = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i - y'_i\|^2} \quad (19.9)$$

where N represents the number of positions, y'_i and y_i represent the predicted states (they are vectors) by the ground-truth ESKF O and the inferred ESKF \hat{O} . Since the states can be generated by a blackbox ESKF, we evaluate against both **Sola-ESKF** and **Apollo-ESKF**.

Experiment parameters. We choose Adam as the optimizer. We set the maximum number of epochs to 200 for the training process. For the learning rate, we adopt step decay [560]. For Q , the learning rate is set to $1e-3$ for the first 10 epochs and then changed to $1e-4$, $1e-5$ and finally $1e-6$ for the following 30, 70 and 100 epochs respectively. For R , the learning rate is set to $1e-5$ initially for first 10 epochs, and then $1e-6$, $1e-7$ and finally $1e-8$ after 30, 70 and 100 epochs respectively. When the anomaly filter is emulated, its replacement MLP also needs to be trained, and we set the learning rate to $1e-9$ initially and then decreased to $1e-10$ and $1e-11$ after 30 and 80 epochs respectively.

We select a subset of one trace (its positions and corresponding ESKF output) for training, because 1) using the whole trace is time-consuming (it contains hundreds of thousands of samples), and 2) the initialization stage (usually the first 40 seconds) of an MSF module yields unreliable output which should be removed. All the other traces are used for testing (the first 40 seconds' data are removed similarly). We term the number of selected positions for training as N , and set it to 1000 after empirical analysis. Other parameters for training, including the three loss weights of Equation 19.7 (λ_p, λ_a and λ_d) are set to 100, 1, and 0.1 respectively. The impact of different parameter values in training, initialization and controllers will be evaluated in Appendix 19.9.7.

Experiment environment. The training and testing processes are done on a workstation of one NVIDIA RTX 2080 Ti GPU and one AMD 5950x with 32 GB memory. The code runs on PyTorch 1.11.0 with Nvidia CUDA 11.5 support. All the data used in the experiments are in `float64` format.

19.5.2 Extracting Sola-ESKF

In this subsection, we evaluate the effectiveness of TASKMASTER when extracting the secret parameters from **Sola-ESKF**. Since we have white-box access to it, we assess both PER (it is averaged for Q , R_G , R_L^p and R_L^y) and SER. To show the impact of the training traces, we selected 2 different traces to train each model. The extracted models are tested on all 5 traces. Table 19.1 summarizes the results.

Result on AS1 (Intrusive In-AV Attacker). The 2 training traces are *local08* and *highway06*, which represents local (roads of downtown areas) and highway navigation respectively. As their

AS	Training	PER	Testing (SER)				
			<i>lo08</i>	<i>lo07</i>	<i>lo31</i>	<i>hi06</i>	<i>hi17</i>
AS1	<i>lo08</i>	0.01347	-	0.067	0.042	0.076	0.089
	<i>hi17</i>	0.01297	0.043	0.029	0.073	0.038	-
AS2	<i>lo08</i>	0.00978	-	0.018	0.028	0.026	0.036
	<i>hi17</i>	0.00206	0.024	0.013	0.018	0.036	-
AS3E	<i>lo08</i>	4.5431	-	1.76	1.24	1.33	3.15
	<i>hi17</i>	4.6247	1.43	2.88	2.28	4.19	-
AS3G	<i>lo08</i>	3.9916	-	1.53	1.89	2.57	1.21
	<i>hi17</i>	4.3111	1.51	0.58	1.43	5.67	-
AS3R	<i>lo08</i>	5.8869	-	4.24	2.10	1.11	1.33
	<i>hi17</i>	4.2485	2.12	1.87	4.11	0.88	-

Table 19.1: Evaluation result on *Sola-ESKF*. The result of each testing trace is represented as SER. PER is the same for each training trace. PER could be larger than 1 if the error between the extracted value and the ground truth is larger than the ground truth itself. AS3E, AS3G and AS3R are AS3 under Exponential, Gamma and Rayleigh noises. “lo” and “hi” are short for “local” and “highway”.

environments are vastly different, the sensor noises and the AV kinetics (positions, velocities and heading poses) also have big differences. In general, *local08* has a smaller value variation than *highway06*. For example, both x and y coordinate of *local08* traces vary in 100-meter level (between $3.511e + 5$ and $3.514e + 5$, $4.022e + 5$ and $4.023e + 5$, respectively), while x and y coordinate of *highway06* traces vary in 1000-meter level (between $3.49e + 5$ and $3.53e + 5$, $4.02e + 5$ and $4.03e + 5$, respectively). For trace length, *local08* has 30,704 recorded data points while *highway06* has 205,375 recorded data points.

For a training trace, we select N points (set to 1000) to construct the training dataset, following this rule: from the first 15000 points, we randomly select a starting point from the points indexed in $[1001, 10000]$, and consecutively collect the following 1000 points for training. We drop the first N points, as ESKF is in the “warm-up” stage in the beginning, and the ESKF output is less stable. The same strategy has been adopted by [532]. For each testing trace, we select the points indexed in $[1001, 15000]$ to construct the dataset. The secret parameters of \hat{O} are all set to random values before training.

As shown in Table 19.1, the extracted \hat{O} is quite similar as the ground-truth O : PER is 0.01347 and 0.01483 for the two traces. It indicates TASKMASTER is able to learn the secret parameters at very high fidelity. SER ranges from 0.042 to 0.089 (the unit is m). Given that L4-standard AV asks for centimeter-level (0.01) RMSE, this result is satisfactory: if the targeted ESKF has reached centimeter-level RMSE, tuning \hat{O} to the same level is deemed much easier comparing to tuning from the scratch.

We also found the impact of the training traces is fairly small. The average SER resulted from *local08* and *highway17* are 0.0685 and 0.0458 separately. Our result also suggests the cost of attack is quite low: by just collecting 1000 data points on one trace (about *25 seconds of AV driving*), the attacker can extract a high-fidelity and high-accuracy ESKF model. In Appendix 19.9.7, we show that increasing N from 1000 to 5000, a small performance gain can be obtained but the training

overhead also significantly increase.

Result on AS2 (Non-intrusive In-AV Attacker). Since the attacker cannot get the output of the ESKF model, but only the output of the followed controllers in this setting, the extracted \hat{O} is expected to be less accurate. We follow the same training and testing strategy as AS1 (N is also 1000 points).

Interestingly, the result shows AS2 can achieve even lower PER and SER compared to AS1, e.g., 0.013 vs 0.029 SER when training on *highway17* and testing on *local07*. We speculate controller outputs actually enhance the training performance, as controllers also handle noises.

Result on AS3 (AV Follower). In this setting, we injected noises into the sensor input and controller output. Though noises following normal distributions are usually used in academic studies about AV security (e.g., [532]), real-world noises are often more complex. As such, we select Exponential, Gamma, and Rayleigh noises based on a survey of noises [561]. These noise models are widely used in radiation-based systems, such as X-ray, LiDAR, and MRI systems. We define the model of the noise injection as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta(u_{k-1}) &= u_{k-1} + n_1 \\
 \delta(z_k^p) &= z_k^p + n_2 \\
 \delta(z_k^y) &= z_k^y + n_3 \\
 \delta(y_k) &= y_k + n_4
 \end{aligned} \tag{19.10}$$

where $\delta(u_{k-1})$, $\delta(z_k^p)$, $\delta(z_k^y)$ and $\delta(y_k)$ are measurements from u_{k-1} , z_k^p , z_k^y and y_k under the influence of noises n_1 , n_2 , n_3 and n_4 . We show the three noise models in Appendix 19.9.8.

For n_1 , n_2 and n_3 , we select $\lambda_1 = 10$ for Exponential noises, $\alpha_1 = 0.1$, $\beta_1 = 2$ for Gamma noises, and $\sigma_1 = 0.05$ for Rayleigh noises. For n_4 , we select $\lambda_2 = 1$ for Exponential noises, $\alpha_2 = 1$, $\beta_2 = 2$ for Gamma noises, and $\sigma_2 = 0.5$ for Rayleigh noises. These settings are considered reasonable given that the extracted ESKF can tolerate meter-level errors and sensors can tolerate decimeter-level errors. According to Table 19.1, we found PER is significantly higher, however, this is expected, as the KF parameters have to be changed to tolerate the noises. SER ranges from 1.26 to 3.07, showing the impact of noises cannot be neglected. Yet, given that the academic implementations of ESKF have meter-level RMSE (see Section 19.3.1), our RMSE is comparable.

The impact of search space reduction. In Section 19.4.1, we propose a strategy to reduce the search space of Q . Here we evaluate the impact of this strategy. Specifically, we implement another version of TASKMASTER that optimizes the covariances within the *same* sensors (position, velocity, quaternion/pose, accelerometer error state and gyrometer error state). In this setting, in total 45 (5x3x3) variables are to be optimized, which is much more than the 4 variables under search space reduction. Since more variables are involved, we optimize the model for 400 epochs.

In Figure 19.4, we demonstrate the training loss (measured by SER) of the two settings on *local08* on AS1. It turns out that, with search space reduction, the training loss reaches 0.026m after 200 epochs, while it takes 400 epochs to reach a similar level without reduction. Moreover, the training time is almost reduced to half (198.27s vs 399.93s, per epoch). This result suggests our reduction strategy significantly improves the efficiency of TASKMASTER.

19.5.3 Extracting Apollo-ESKF

In this subsection, we report our results of extracting Apollo-ESKF, which is blackbox and might have components not modeled by us. In Table 19.2, we show the SER of the 5 testing traces, paired to the two training traces (*local08* and *highway17*). We only measure SER, as we have no knowledge about the ground-truth parameters of Apollo-ESKF.

Figure 19.4: Training loss with and without search space reduction. The training trace is *local08*. The number of maximum training epochs is 400. We stop the training with space reduction after 200 epochs as the loss is sufficiently low.

It turns out for AS1 and AS2, the error rate significantly increased. There are 6 cases with SER more than 1 in testing, e.g., training on *local08* and testing on *highway17* (1.18) in AS1 / *local07* (1.26), *local31* (1.01) and *highway06* (1.03) in AS2. All the other SERs are in decimeter level. We speculate the rise of SER is caused by the additional procedures of Apollo-ESKF not implemented by us. We also show the error distribution in Appendix 19.9.9.

With noises injected in AS3, errors of attacker’s observation rise to meter-level: the average SER training on *local08* under Exponential, Gamma, and Rayleigh noises rise to 1.88, 2.67, and 1.87, respectively. Interestingly, the SERs between Sola-ESKF and Apollo-ESKF are much closer compared to AS1 and AS2.

To assess whether the extracted ESKF model is useful, we conduct another experiment and the result is shown in Appendix 19.9.7.

19.6 Discussion

Generalization to other KF models. AD may use variants of KF models in localization. For example, unscented Kalman filter and Extended Kalman filter (EKF) are good candidates as they work better with non-linear systems [562].

We believe TASKMASTER can also be used to extract these variants when the structure is approximately known by the attacker. As for the reasons, 1) these variants have a similar structure with ESKF (for instance, EKF differs from ESKF only in the equations deriving x_k , P_k and K' [538]), and 2) these models are derivable. With the above reasons, the attacker can adopt a similar methodology of TASKMASTER.

Limitations. 1) We did not deploy the extracted ESKF models on real AV and evaluate them on the real roads, given we have no access to the AV testing and manufacturing process. Yet, we

AS	Training	Testing (SER)				
		<i>lo08</i>	<i>lo07</i>	<i>lo31</i>	<i>hi06</i>	<i>hi17</i>
AS1	<i>lo08</i>	-	0.37	0.42	0.91	1.18
	<i>hi17</i>	0.95	0.72	0.68	0.89	-
AS2	<i>lo08</i>	-	1.26	1.01	1.03	0.62
	<i>hi17</i>	1.12	0.96	0.88	0.79	-
AS3E	<i>lo08</i>	-	1.72	1.82	2.03	1.96
	<i>hi17</i>	1.92	1.48	2.41	1.27	-
AS3G	<i>lo08</i>	-	1.45	1.63	2.11	3.07
	<i>hi17</i>	1.26	1.43	1.55	1.90	-
AS3R	<i>lo08</i>	-	1.78	2.08	2.13	1.49
	<i>hi17</i>	1.71	1.82	1.56	1.33	-

Table 19.2: Evaluation result on Apollo-ESKF. The result in each cell is represented as SER, as Apollo-ESKF is blackbox.

use the real-world traces (KAIST) and target ESKF models (Apollo-ESKF), and the result shows TASKMASTER is effective. We are discussing with the AV vendors to obtain their feedback on our study, as an indicator of the attack’s practicality. 2) When the AD of the attacker uses a set of sensors with *very different* settings as the targeted AD, the stolen parameters cannot be directly used. However, as described in Section 19.3.1, industry-grade models like Apollo-ESKF is able to achieve good performance on different AVs even without re-tuning. Hence, we believe stealing such models should be useful to attackers in most cases. 3) TASKMASTER is less effective against Apollo-ESKF comparing to Sola-ESKF. We believe the main reason is that Apollo-ESKF is more complex than Sola-ESKF, and we are unable to emulate all components surrounding Apollo-ESKF. 4) Except Baidu Apollo, we have not found another AD system to verify if obfuscation is applied on the localization module. Though Autoware [563] is another popular open-source AD system, we found it only uses LiDAR for localization by default. Though extracting binaries from an AV can help us get another ground-truth MSF, it is impossible without vulnerability exploitation. In the meantime, we will keep inquiring the AD community. We evaluated TASKMASTER against Baidu Apollo v2.5 while the latest version is v6.0. The ESKF version is upgraded from v1.0.3 to v1.0.4. We plan to test the latest version, but we expect the changes to be small.

Defense. Though there are a number of extraction attacks against ML models, recent works show defenses are possible. An example is PRADA [564], which analyses the distribution of clients’ queries and detects the ones that deviate from the normal ones. However, these works assume MLaaS (Machine-learning as a Service) settings, where the queries can be audited. This is very difficult in our setting, as the attacker’s observation cannot be blocked under AS3, and there is no need to actively query ESKF under AS1 and AS2. A partial solution, which is practical under AS1 and AS2, could be mediating the access to ECUs. Specifically, AV vendors may add “self-destruction” modules to ECUs. Once an attacker tries to break the ECU to get the output of ESKF, the ECUs can wipe out the parameters of ESKF. Additionally, AV vendors can encrypt all internal messages.

19.7 Related Work

Security of AD. The research into the security of modern vehicles has been started a decade ago [171, 565–567], and the attack surface on wireless protocols, CAN bus, etc. were explored. The security of AD has attracted attention from the research community only recently. One direction is to study the sensors leveraged by AD, including LiDAR, IMU, perception, etc. [83, 187, 188, 280, 557, 568–573], and defense based on physical invariants was proposed [574]. Attacks against the traditional computing architecture, like cache side-channel attacks [575] and malware attacks [576], were examined and found feasible against the software stack of AD. Regarding the security of MSF, only Shen et al. [532] demonstrated its integrity can be tampered with, while TASKMASTER looks into the confidentiality issues of MSF models.

Model Extraction. Similar to KF models, the parameters of machine-learning models, including the classic models like logistic regression, and DNN, can be considered secret. Tramer et al. proposed an equation-solving attack and a path-finding attack [533] to guess the model parameters. Wang et al. studied how the model hyper-parameters used to balance between the loss function and the regularization terms can be stolen [577]. Juuti et al. improved on the existing attacks by generating synthetic queries and proposed defenses [564]. The attack precision is further improved with semi-supervised learning [534] and active learning [535]. While prior works focused on CNN when attacking DNN, recently, the attack against RNN was demonstrated feasible [578]. But as described in Section 19.3.3, successful model extraction against KF has to overcome new challenges, which are addressed by the new design of TASKMASTER.

System Identification. System identification (SI) [536] builds a mathematical model for a dynamic system with statistical analysis. The related methods can be divided into 4 categories [579], but we found directly using SI to steal ESKF parameters does yield satisfactory results. 1) The Bayesian Method treats parameter update as a Bayesian update [580], but a Bayesian optimal estimation might be unrealizable [581]. 2) Maximum Likelihood carries out non-linear, gradient-based optimization to minimize the difference between model prediction and measurement [580, 582, 583], and Expectation Maximization [584, 585] attempts to avoid the non-linear optimization. However, the optimization process is time-consuming. 3) Covariance Matching runs Monte Carlo simulation and checks if the sampled statistics are internally consistent [585–588]. Though faster, Covariance Matching leads to sub-optimal results. 4) Correlation Techniques assume the sequence of prediction error is zero-mean white Gaussian noise when the model is optimal, and tune the control parameters towards this criteria [589–591]. However, this assumption does not always hold. Some works have applied SI on simple KF models [592–594], but none of them are applicable to the MSF models adopted by AVs, especially ESKF. In fact, ESKF is an LTV (linear time-variant) system while KF is an LTI (linear time-invariant) system, and many properties from LTI systems do not hold in LTV systems. Recently, deep-learning models have been used for SI [595, 596] but again none of them work on ESKF.

19.8 Conclusion

In this work, we systematically studied the confidentiality issues underlying the AD control models, in particular the ESKF model used for localization, which has been considered intellectual property by AD companies. We designed TASKMASTER, a novel optimization-based framework to infer the secret parameters by observing the input and output of an AD. Under 3 practical adversarial settings, we found TASKMASTER can achieve very high accuracy for `Sola-ESKF` and comparable accuracy for a complex, industry-grade model `Apollo-ESKF`. As the first study on

the AD model confidentiality, we hope our findings can attract attention from AD industries and security community in addressing this new threat.

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19.9 Appendix

19.9.1 AD Controller

After localization, the estimated vehicle status is combined with the output of path planning, collision avoidance, etc. in the navigation stack, and sent to the controller module to guide actuators/command executors. We briefly overview this module here, since it has to be emulated for the attack scenarios when the output to ESKF is not directly observable to the adversary (see Section 19.3.2).

An AD controller is normally divided into 2 sub-components: lateral controller and longitudinal controller. The lateral controller makes decisions on the angular velocity change (i.e. steering) while the longitudinal controller makes decisions on the acceleration (i.e. throttle and brake). Both the lateral controller and the longitudinal controller share the same input data, and their output, including steering, throttle and brake, forms a complete control vector.

The AD controller solves the optimal control problem in a dynamic system. As such, it uses the existing classic control algorithms. For Baidu Apollo [559], the LQR (linear-quadratic regulator) algorithm [259] is used for lateral control while the PID (proportional-integral-derivative) algorithm [597] is used for longitudinal control. LQR controller uses a cost function defined by human, in the form of a sum of the deviations of key measurements, and finds the controller settings that minimizes the cost. PID controller calculates proportional, integral, and derivative responses after reading the sensors, and sums them to compute the actuator output. LQR controller produces better response compared to PID controller, as it aims to achieve optimal control states, though at the cost of higher complexity.

19.9.2 More Details of ESKF

G is the matrix to reset the \hat{P}_k , defined as follows:

$$G = \begin{pmatrix} I_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_3 - [\frac{1}{2}\hat{\delta}\theta] & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I_9 \end{pmatrix} \quad (19.11)$$

where I_n represents an $n \times n$ identity matrix and $\hat{\delta}\theta$ represents the error state of the AD car heading (in euler angles).

The Update phase is changed from Equation 19.2 to the equation below in ESKF.

$$\begin{aligned} K' &= P_k H_G^T (H_G P_k H_G^T + R_G)^{-1} \\ \hat{x}_k &= x_k + K' (z_k - H_G x_k) \\ \hat{P}_k &= P_k - K' H_G P_k \end{aligned} \quad (19.12)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 K' &= P_k(H_L^p)^\top(H_L^p P_k(H_L^p)^\top + R_L^p)^{-1} \\
 x'_k &= x_k + K'(z_k^p - H_L^p x_k) \\
 P'_k &= P_k - K' H_L^p P_k \\
 K'' &= P_k(H_L^y)^\top(H_L^y P_k(H_L^y)^\top + R_L^y)^{-1} \\
 \hat{x}_k &= x'_k + K''(z_k^y - H_L^y x_k) \\
 \hat{P}_k &= P'_k - K'' H_L^y P_k
 \end{aligned} \tag{19.13}$$

where R_L^p, H_L^p, z_k^p and R_L^y, H_L^y, z_k^y are related to position and yaw observations separately.

19.9.3 Reverse-engineering KF Parameters

The GitHub repo [72] of Baidu Apollo embeds ESKF in a binary file `liblocalization_msf.so`, though other parts have source code. We have attempted to reverse engineer this binary file for 5 weeks but were unable to extract its ESKF parameters. First, we try to decompile this binary, and found SIMD vectorization [598] is heavily used, which makes the decompiled code (including the pre- and post-processing) less readable. We have used reverse-engineer tools including IDA Pro [599], Snowman [600], and McSema [601] (an LLVM IR lifting tool), and all failed. Though McSema claims that AVX instructions can be handled, SIMD Instructions still cannot be decompiled. Second, we also tried binary analysis tools like Intel Pin [602] and Frida [603] to recover the secret values at the runtime, but were also unsuccessful. Regarding the information learnt from the 5 weeks' efforts, we roughly know the execution steps of ESKF, such as IMU prediction, measurement update, outlier detection, after reading the disassembled code. We also discovered that the ESKF prediction and updates occurred asynchronously with multi-threading, which increases the difficulty for reverse engineering.

19.9.4 Generalizability of the extracted model

Here we explain how the extracted KF parameters can be used in AVs different from the target. R (including R_G , R_L^p and R_L^y) depends on the sensors (e.g., GNSS and LiDAR). For two AVs, if their sensors are similar, their R can be similar. As a supporting evidence, we collected a trace (*local08*) from KAIST Complex Urban [252] (described in Section 19.5.1), which contains the sensor input and localization results when the tested AV is driven by a human. We consider its localization results as the ground truth, and compare to the localization results generated by Baidu Apollo's ESKF (using the sensor input from *local08*), in order to assess how well the ESKF can adapt to different vehicles (the default vehicle supported by Baidu Apollo is different from the KAIST vehicle) with similar sensors (e.g., their LiDAR sensors are the same). We found that the root mean squared error (RMSE) between the ground truth and Apollo's output is only 0.074m, reaching cm-level error, suggesting the industry-grade MSF has good adaptability.

When the sensors are quite different, directly using the stolen R parameters for attacker's ESKF model might yield sub-optimal result. We consider the re-tuning of R in certain circumstances as limitation (also described in Section 19.6), but we expect heavy re-tuning is unnecessary in most case. In fact, a few sensor providers are very popular among the car manufacturers. For instance, (1) the default LiDAR sensors supported by Baidu Apollo were manufactured by Velodyne [604], which were also integrated by AVs from Google/Alphabet [605], Ford [606–608], Toyota [609], Mercedes-Benz [610], Hyundai Mobis [611], ThroDrive [612], etc; (2) most car manufacturers purchase GNSS/IMU sensors from Novatel [613].

Aside from R and Q , the other matrices, including F , B , H_G , H_L^p and H_L^y , are determined by the vehicle kinematics and sensor measurement models, which can be obtained from textbook or tutorials [97]. Since sensors do not have lots of measurement variations – they typically measure vehicle positions in global coordinate systems such as longitude/latitude/altitude, these matrices usually will not change for different sensors.

19.9.5 Symbol Notations

The symbols used by Section 19.4 is shown in Table 19.3.

Symbol	Description	Dim
u_{k-1}	IMU measurement	2×1
z_k^p	Position measurement	3×1
z_k^y	Yaw measurement	4×1
x_k	Predicted state	16×1
P_k	Predicted cov	15×15
y_k	Controller output	4×1
p_k	Position control	2×1
a_i	Acceleration control	1×1
d_i	Yaw control	1×1
$*Q$	Observation noise cov	15×15
$*R_G$	GNSS noise cov	3×3
$*R_L^p$	LiDAR position noise cov	3×3
$*R_L^y$	LiDAR yaw noise cov	3×3
O	Ground-truth model	-
\hat{O}	Extracted model	-

Table 19.3: Symbols used in Section 19.4. “Dim” is for Dimension. “cov” is for covariance matrix. “*” marks the secret to be inferred by TASKMASTER.

19.9.6 Algorithm of AS1 Attack Flow

The algorithm is shown in Algorithm 11.

Algorithm 11 Attack workflow under ASI

Input: N measurement $T = [t_1, \dots, t_N]$, the output of O *refStates*, MaxEpoch

Output: Inferred Q, R_G, R_L^p, R_L^y

Initialize $x_0, P_0, Q, R_G, R_L^p, R_L^y, myStates$;

$x_{k-1} \leftarrow x_0; P_{k-1} \leftarrow P_0; cnt \leftarrow 1$;

for $i \leftarrow 1$ to MaxEpoch **do**

while $cnt \leq N$ **do**

$t_k \leftarrow get(T, cnt)$;

if t_k is from IMU **then**

$x_k, P_k \leftarrow predictIMU(x_{k-1}, P_{k-1}, t_k)$;

end if

if t_k is from GNSS **then**

$x_k, P_k \leftarrow updateGNSS(x_{k-1}, P_{k-1}, t_k)$;

end if

if t_k is from LiDAR **then**

$x_k, P_k \leftarrow updateLiDAR(x_{k-1}, P_{k-1}, t_k)$;

end if

 add x_k into *myStates*;

$x_{k-1} \leftarrow x_k; P_{k-1} \leftarrow P_k; cnt \leftarrow cnt + 1$;

end while

$Loss \leftarrow log(MSE(myStates, refStates))$;

 optimize($Q, Loss$);

 optimize($R_G, R_L^p, R_L^y, Loss$);

end for

return Q, R_G, R_L^p, R_L^y ;

	100	500	1000	2000	3000	4000	5000
PER	0.4377	0.1274	0.01347	0.01562	0.01285	0.02014	0.009974
SER (m)	0.59	0.27	0.03	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.04
Training Time (s)	11762.11	13270.62	13878.90	14957.63	15724.83	16765.74	17833.91
Time per Iteration (s)	168.03	189.58	198.27	213.68	224.64	239.51	254.77

Table 19.4: The impact of N on AS1. The targeted model is **Sola-ESKF**. *local08* and *highway17* are for training and testing.

		Q			R		
AS	Original	$[1e-3, 1e-2]$	$[1e-2, 1e-1]$	$[1e-1, 1e0]$	$[1e-6, 1e-5]$	$[1e-5, 1e-4]$	$[1e-4, 1e-3]$
AS1	0.01347	0.01220	0.01265	0.14031	0.03868	0.10514	0.92062
AS2	0.00978	0.09540	0.12428	0.17274	0.12237	0.16641	0.50272

Table 19.5: Comparison of PER under different parameter initialization ranges in **Sola-ESKF**. The training trace is *local08*. “Original” are the values (matrices) used in previous evaluation.

		Q			R		
Original		$[1e-3, 1e-2]$	$[1e-2, 1e-1]$	$[1e-1, 1e0]$	$[1e-6, 1e-5]$	$[1e-5, 1e-4]$	$[1e-4, 1e-3]$
0.85	0.97	1.03	1.73	0.88	2.43	5.64	

Table 19.6: Comparison of SER under different parameter initialization ranges in **Apollo-ESKF** in AS2. The training trace is *local08* and the testing trace is *highway17*.

19.9.7 Impact of Parameters

The number of points for training (N). We set N to 1000 as the default setting. Here, we evaluate how TASKMASTER is influenced by different N . Intuitively, a small N will introduce more errors to each state, as ESKF might not be stabilized yet. Though a large N can overcome this issue, the training process will be longer, and more storage will be consumed to store the prior states.

We vary N from 100 to 5000 and evaluate **Sola-ESKF**. It turns out PER and SER are significantly decreased (from 0.4377 to 0.01347 and from 0.59 to 0.03) when N is increased from 100 to 1000, as shown in Table 19.4. When $N > 1000$, PER and SER remain the same level. However, the time overhead increases greatly (from 198.27s to 254.77s per iteration) with increasing N from 1000 to 5000. The benefit brought by a larger N is diminished by the overhead it incurs, and therefore we use $N = 1000$ as default.

Initialization and controller parameters. We initialize the values of Q and R based on the results of existing works [97]. Here we assess the effectiveness of TASKMASTER when different initial values are chosen.

We first assess the impact on **Sola-ESKF**, where the ground-truth of Q and R are known. We tested with 3 different ranges: $[1e-3, 1e-2]$, $[1e-2, 1e-1]$ and $[1e-1, 1e0]$ for Q , and $[1e-6, 1e-5]$, $[1e-5, 1e-4]$ and $[1e-4, 1e-3]$ for R . In each range, we draw 50 random values in uniform distribution, and run the experiment 50 times with the same setting as Section 19.5.2. Table 19.5 compares the average PER in AS1 and AS2. As we can see, the impact is relatively small for both settings, except when Q falls in $[1e-1, 1e0]$ and R falls in $[1e-4, 1e-3]$. The impact by R is larger,

and we speculate this is because the ground-truth R are in smaller range ($1e - 5$ level) compared with Q ($1e - 2$ level).

We then assess Apollo-ESKF in AS2. As the initial values of Q and R are not far away from the values of Sola-ESKF, we can learn whether starting from another ESKF model is important to get closer to an industry-grade ESKF. The answer seems to be negative. For Q and R , the same ranges are tested as the previous experiment. The result is summarized in Table 19.6.

Testing (SER)				
<i>local08</i>	<i>local07</i>	<i>local31</i>	<i>highway06</i>	<i>highway17</i>
12.60	8.15	9.18	7.90	5.31

Table 19.7: Comparison between Sola-ESKF and Apollo-ESKF on the same KAIST dataset.

Comparison between Sola-ESKF and Apollo-ESKF on the same KAIST dataset. Here we assess how useful the extracted ESKF model would be to the attacker. In particular, we run Sola-ESKF and Apollo-ESKF on KAIST and derive SER on their output (Sola-Output and Apollo-Output), under AS2. Table 19.7 shows the SER of all 5 traces. The best case has 5.31 SER while the worst case has as high as 12.60 SER, and the average is 8.63. In the meantime, our extracted \hat{O} trained on *local08* has 0.98 SER in average. Hence, starting from the extracted model, parameter tuning is expected to be much easier for an adversary.

Other evaluations. We have also evaluated the impacts of the weights in loss function (λ_p , λ_d and λ_a) and compared PID and Stanley controllers. The results are omitted due to page limit.

19.9.8 Noise Models

We adapt three noise models for noise injection in AS3 based on a survey [561]. λ , α , β and σ are model parameters.

Exponential noise. Exponential noise follows a distribution whose probability density function (PDF) is:

$$f(x; \lambda) = \lambda e^{-\lambda x} \quad (19.14)$$

where $\lambda > 0$. Mean of Exponential noise is $\frac{1}{\lambda}$, and standard deviation is also $\frac{1}{\lambda}$.

Gamma noise. Gamma noise follows a distribution whose PDF is:

$$f(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} x^{\alpha-1} e^{-\beta x} \quad (19.15)$$

where $\alpha > 0$, $\beta > 0$, and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is gamma function [614]. Mean of Gamma noise is $\frac{\alpha}{\beta}$, and standard deviation is $\frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{\beta}$.

Rayleigh noise. Rayleigh noise follows a distribution whose PDF is:

$$f(x; \sigma) = \frac{x}{\sigma^2} e^{-x^2/2\sigma^2} \quad (19.16)$$

where $\sigma > 0$. Mean of Rayleigh noise is $\sigma\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}$, and standard deviation is $\sigma\sqrt{\frac{4-\pi}{2}}$.

Figure 19.5: Distribution of RMSE on 2D locations in AS1 on Apollo-ESKF. The training trace is *highway17* and the testing trace is *local08*.

19.9.9 Error Distribution by Trace Locations

In addition to inspecting SER on a whole trace, we also take a closer look at the error distribution on different trace locations. In Figure 19.5, we show the distribution of RMSE on 2D locations of *local08* under AS1, and it turns out 60% locations have less than 0.95 SER, and only a small fraction (around 5%) of locations have high SER (more than 2).

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